

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

Ref. Ares(2025)4775795 - 16/06/2025

WP4 Country report: Introduction

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Pınar Uyan-Semerçi (Istanbul Bilgi University)

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
European Election Results and Party Affiliations.....	5
# Differences Observed Over Time	8
Developing the feed	9
Thematic Content.....	10
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	11
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	13
# Content Related to Defence, War and International Conflicts	15
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	15
# AI Generated Content	16
# Video Typologies.....	17
Conclusions.....	18
Bibliography	19

Introduction

These country reports have been made as part of the CO3 project, where they formed the basis of WP4. The 2024 European Elections were seen as an important way to analyse contemporary political processes, which also included the social contract. WP4 embarked on an ambitious collaboration. The dataset itself lends itself to different types of analysis, from the post-pandemic politics in Europe as from the perspective of the ENDURE project funded in the Trans-Atlantic Platform consortium, or the site of grievance politics in Europe as for the PLEDGE and MORES Horizon projects funded in call [HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01-04](#). Resources from all these projects enabled the coverage of ten countries, for which we in CO3 process eight country reports, three different synthetic political profiles for each country and a larger set of questions – as well as the generation of a dataset that can also be used in the other projects in the future. The Country Reports are written in a way that they would constitute, on the one hand, an analysis of the European Elections and, on the other hand, metadata for a large dataset that can in the future be used in a diversity of ways.

What you have at hand are the country reports that the CO3 consortium researchers were collaborating with, Croatia, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Portugal and Sweden. We are also processing Poland and Spain with colleagues from PLEDGE, and for one profile in Poland, MORES. The overall dataset includes data from all the ten countries and will be finalised in autumn. We sought to have two countries from the South-East, South-West, North-East Europe, Western and Eastern parts of Central Europe. Unfortunately, we did not have the scope for North-West Europe in this project. The UK was no longer part of the European Union, and we did not have teams in the Netherlands and Ireland, unlike for the previous elections in 2019 (Herkman & Palonen 2024).

From the previous literature we know that the European Elections are typically second-order elections where the discussion is over some themes that can be national – or in the cases of combining local elections with the European ones, even local. Nevertheless, for us they still offered a basis for exploring argumentation for Europe and had value in exploring contemporary construction of the European (and sometimes national, local or even global) social contract. After all, in the elections, the target of political communication is to generate a bond between the potential voter and the political party, candidate or other communicating body that they would go and vote in the elections, therefore lending legitimacy for the European community, or potentially not, for the Eurosceptics.

In the previous study, we had found out that there are, besides the Eurosceptic and Europhilic parties, also something we called the Critical Europeans (Herkman & Palonen 2024). These categories did not seem to hold when we started our data gathering, and this is why we did not apply these headings here or categorise parties from the start. Instead, we used profiles that were supposed to get their feeds to follow content from what we considered as far-right, centre-right and red-green parties and actors. There can be a selection bias in terms of what was included under these headings from the start, but as part of the data gathering protocol, we had an excel sheet for the type of content where country experts had discussed parties in these orientations. The feed-generation was successful, as our data shows. We used organic – not predefined as politically oriented – feeds as the backup and the control for the study.

For the CO3 consortium, the writing of these country reports was an important activity in terms of the collective effort that enabled the senior researchers (of whom the data gatherers mainly were composed) to experience the contemporary social media platforms that are used in political communication and what kinds of content is produced across the EU and beyond for the citizens of the

European Union. Limitations of the large dataset and team is that there may be inconsistencies due to inter-coder reliability, despite the extensive support network and guidance with iterative research process and planning we generated. We gave and enabled peer support to the researchers.

There were risks involved with access to data and the data processing. We had ethical approval before the start of the project. We had a technical struggle because the changes introduced by the operating system we had successfully used in the two pilots (2024 Finnish presidential elections and 2024 Portuguese parliamentary elections). Each data gatherer made it to the very end. The data from ten countries (8 of which are presented here) is a valuable source also in the future. We are transforming the dataset to something that can have as public access as possible.

We did not pilot the research notes, which were originally supposed to be a source of metadata for the feeds, but in the end were seen as a valuable comparable dataset. In these digital field notes, people, after having scrolled through one profile (synthetic or organic) on both TikTok and Instagram, added their field notes. Epistemologically, we found it important to ask what people thought they had seen after the scrolling experience, even if sometimes people were very meticulous with their notes and other times, they were more indicative of the content of the feed. Hence, the data indicates the perception of what people saw. We consider this an equally valuable research finding as what the feeds contained. For us, it was crucial that the feed was curated by a country expert familiar with the political context.

Going through the dataset and the country reports, we can see, however, that some of the data still needs to be cleaned or recategorised before we can release the dataset. We trusted we would get the feed also. (Which we have but this is slightly inaccurately OCR-described from the split video files. This data was not used in this study: we relied on the researcher's notes.)

The process has also enabled us to reflect philosophically and epistemologically on large datasets of social media data and the combination of country experts with artificial intelligence. These research notes have been used practically through human perception, but the data that has been collected by humans has also been processed through an LLM pipeline. These country reports we based on the human observations.

Choosing the order in which the different data is presented was of course one of the challenges in the design of the study. Here in the Introduction, we deviate a bit from the order in the country reports. Perhaps some of this could be pursued in the future. The numbering of graphs follows that of the country reports themselves. We are also aware that for future publications the number of visuals could be different. All visuals are made by Vaibhav Agarwal who was working in collaborating PLEDGE and the UH projects as a research assistant but also kindly wanted to contribute to the processing of this data aside from his Social Data Science studies. Huge thanks to Vaibhav.

In the following sections, we will introduce the overall results around Europe with our summarised data. we are aware that this WP has already produced a pile of pages, so we wanted to keep these to a minimum. The contribution to the contemporary social contract lies in the way in which the different themes are discussed, and we look forward to developing analysis based on this EP2024 study also in the other WPs of the CO3 project (WP3, WP5, and WP6 in particular) and disseminating the results in the WP7 also discussing the perceptions with the audiences, political parties and policy-makers in Europe.

European Election Results and Party Affiliations

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

The 2024 European elections were tipped to be won by the far right. They did get stronger particularly in larger member states, but the largest groups have still remained the centre-right European People's Party (EPP) and the centre-left Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D), receiving 188 and 136 Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) respectively. The combined share of the MEPs parties we did consider in this study as far-right, now grouped under the names of Patriots of Europe (formerly Identity and Democracy) and the European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR), is 162, and with the Europe of Sovereign Nations, it is 187. This indicates a strong presence of the far right in the parliament. The liberal Renew (77), the Greens/EFA (53), and the Left (46) are also large groups in the parliament. The balance has been kept with the pro-European integration side, and this is how it was interpreted in the post-election politics. Running far-right accounts as one third of the feeds may raise the presence of some of these actors, but our synthetic profiles match also the election results (Figure 1).

We used the group affiliations from the previous parliament (EP2019–2024) to generate comparable Europe-wide data. Mostly, the researchers knew that they were supposed to match the parties and politicians they had seen with the Eurogroup for “party”. We have also corrected some of this data, but potentially, there are still some inconsistencies.

We asked the researchers to indicate whom did they think they saw in their feeds. From Week 2 onwards we extended this point with a separate question whose accounts did they think they saw to separate the presence of political actors from the production of content. This was important to make a distinction between the content where some politicians or parties could be openly criticised and the content which was produced by the group.

This method enabled us to see in the synthetic feeds, which were far-right, centre-right and red-green, the presence of the parties at the European scale. The results revealed the dominance of the largest groups, EPP, S&D and the ECR. We also saw a strong presence of the Greens and the Left (GUE-NGL) on Instagram, while the Left and ID were more dominant on TikTok. This indicates that the algorithm was slightly favouring the content produced by accounts connected to those parties, but there is no huge difference between the platforms in terms of visibility of people. Also Renew has a presence in the data, but they were less visible than the share of the MEPs they received.

While Figure 2a indicates the visibility of actors, Figure 2b indicates the visibility of the accounts. We left out the figure 2b from the reports. Here there is not a huge difference between the two neither in the Europewide nor in the national level.

The Non-Inscrits are parties that did not belong to any of these groups at the time of the 2024 European elections, including important players that lost their European group affiliations, such as Fidesz (HU) or Alternative for Germany (DE). New movements such as Reconquest! (FR) or Sahra Wagenknecht Alliance (DE) were also coded as Non-Inscrits.

European Parliament 2024-2029

Constitutive session

Political groups in the European Parliament	Number of seats	% of seats
EPP – Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)	188 ●	26.11%
S&D – Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament	136 ●	18.89%
PfE – Patriots for Europe	84 ●	11.67%
ECR – European Conservatives and Reformists Group	78 ●	10.83%
Renew Europe – Renew Europe Group	77 ●	10.69%
Greens/EFA – Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance	53 ●	7.36%
The Left – The Left group in the European Parliament – GUE/NGL	46 ●	6.39%
ESN – Europe of Sovereign Nations	25 ●	3.47%
NI – Non-attached Members	33 ●	4.58%

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Figure 1. Results Europewide

6

Figure 2a: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 2b: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Differences Observed Over Time

This set of graphs is in Section 3 of the country reports. It addresses the changes in visibility of different political actors distributed by EP groups (Figure 23) and of accounts affiliated with the EP groups (Figure 22) across Europe and over time. We started collecting this data on Day 9 of the data-gathering period.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 3: Visibility of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram over time

Figure 22 allows for tracking changes in visibility of accounts affiliated with different EP groups over time on both platforms under consideration, TikTok and Instagram. The data demonstrates that at the beginning of the data-gathering exercise, accounts that can be clearly identified with an EP group were comparatively less visible on TikTok than on Instagram. Yet by the election day, 9 June 2024 (Day 21 in the Figure), the differences between the two platforms had become largely negligible: all the key EP groups present in the ten countries part of the data-gathering effort were visible in the researchers' synthetic, politically oriented profiles. It is also worth mentioning that accounts connected to both centre-right and radical right EP groups turned out to be comparatively more visible on TikTok than on Instagram, especially in the run-up to the election. From this standpoint, Instagram offered a wider choice of politicised content in its feeds than TikTok.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 4: Visibility of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram over time

Along similar lines, Figure 23 offers insights into the visibility of politicians affiliated with EP groups on TikTok and Instagram over time. The Figure shows that over the course of the data-gathering exercise, the researchers across Europe managed to build politically oriented synthetic profiles on both platforms: while in Week 1, the share of the option “None of the above” reached up to 50 per cent of the responses (see Day 1), by the start of Week 2, both platforms started consistently showing political content in the feeds. The graph also shows that TikTok turned out to be slightly more political than Instagram, a claim that is supported by observations of many country teams involved in this exercise. It is also worth mentioning that politicians whose political forces were affiliated with centre-right and radical right EP groups turned out to be comparatively more visible on TikTok than on Instagram. From this standpoint, Instagram offered a wider choice of politicised content in its feeds than TikTok, another claim widely shared by the researchers involved in the study.

Developing the feed

In the third section we explored the development of the feed for different profiles. Following the protocol we sought to direct the political synthetic profiles to a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or

far-right orientation. As control the organic feed was more explorative to find out what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The section discusses also differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. In the country reports figures indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

The heat-maps in this section provide insights to the amounts of political content the researchers were getting – according to the fieldnotes. These amounts could also vary depending on the feed, but also the amount of time spent online. The data gathering was supposed to be done on a daily basis, but this was difficult in some personal situations and due to labour legislation in some countries. Also often data-gathering was done as the last thing of the day, sometimes after midnight. Hence we used a system of corresponding dates for getting the content in the right days.

All profiles indicated that TikTok was faster to form a political feed. In the pilot research we also had had long periods of Indian dance videos and other non-political content that frustrates the researcher as they do not get a proper feed. Rather than assuming that there are filter-bubbles that hinder political communication as existing research has unveiled, we sought to simulate someone who would want to get political content of their choice. The researchers were told to search and follow political actors and at times like their posts to get the feed aligned with their profile. Going through the data we see that it did develop relatively fast in both platforms but TikTok clearly faster than Instagram.

In spring 2024 Instagram also had sought to restrict the content from political actors, whom the account users would not follow, requiring a confirmation from the users they allow for other political content. This was seen as a measure by the platform to protect the users. Many political actors and NGOs also saw this as a harmful measure for democracy as the dissemination of political content before the election is seen as important for multi-voiced democratic process. In so far as the organic accounts sought for a wider selection of political information (we did not require this in our research protocol but some did) and also received it, we could see some functioning of the Habermasian public sphere. However, our politically leaning synthetic profiles did not receive a full range of content. There were some videos coming from other orientations in the feed, but the researchers were told to largely ignore them not to impede the feed development.

Thematic Content

In section of the reports we draw on the contents of the feeds from the themes and topics that were present to the reflections researchers wrote for their accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. The themes for the questionnaire of the field notes, where the data is drawn selected topics and thematics that are important for the collaborating research consortia. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 5: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

The researchers were asked to daily mark key themes appearing in the content they were watching. As every country team was responsible for three synthetic accounts — a radical right one, a centre-right one, and a green-left one — **the content seen and recorded in the feeds of the synthetic accounts was skewed to the right.**

Hence, unsurprisingly, immigration-related content was seen considerably more frequently than any other topic on the list. At the same time, discussions on TikTok and Instagram also addressed a range of topics brought up by political forces across ideological lines: Social Europe (including education, healthcare, the welfare state), the Economy (including taxation, labour market, unemployment), and Environmentalism (including the Green Deal). These were followed by such topics as Gender and Defence and considerably less prominent topics like Media, Agriculture, and Religion.

Yet, the ranking orders of the topics varied widely across our sample depending on the political preferences of the synthetic profiles. If the Economy and Social Europe appeared in the feeds of the synthetic accounts regardless of their political leanings, centre-right and radical right synthetic profiles recorded significantly more videos connected to Immigration and Defence. In other words, the centre-right engaged with the core topics of the radical right. Meanwhile, the researchers responsible for red-green profiles recorded that in addition to the Economy and Social Europe, many videos in the feeds touched upon such topics as the Green Deal and Gender.

It is important to note here that the coders identified these themes as discourse topics regardless of sentiments attached to them. For example, a video was marked as related to the Green Deal both when it was critical of the Green Deal and when it was favourable to it.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 6: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

From a chronological perspective, all the most important themes—Immigration, Social Europe, the Economy, the Green Deal, Gender, Defence, Media, Agriculture, and Religion—were consistently visible on TikTok and Instagram throughout the data-gathering exercise. Importantly, the share of the option “None of the above” (meaning that the researchers could not record any content related to these common theme) never exceeded ten per cent: a vast majority of the synthetic profiles across Europe allowed for recording politicised content connected to key societal issues.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

Figure 7: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

While the feeds of synthetic profiles across Europe were primarily filled with content related to national and even local politics, European discussions also prominently featured in the feed of some (types of) synthetic accounts. This is particularly true for red-green profiles, as many Green parties in the EU capitalised on their strong European representation. Key European actors such as Ursula von der Leyen, Emmanuel Macron, and Georgia Meloni appeared in the feeds of many political accounts regardless of the political leanings of the synthetic profiles.

External, non-EU players—not only the US and the UK but also Russia and China—were also very visible in the feeds of political accounts across the political spectrum. The international dimension turned out to be very important as ongoing military conflicts—in Ukraine and Gaza in particular—served as a backdrop for (national) political debates online.

Figure 8. The most visible political actors seen internationally (in a context different from their home country)

Figure 8 shows the most visible political actors recorded in an international context – a context different from their own home country. We chose to indicate the presence of different politicians in the feed by choosing the overview of the international actors, as the data of the presence of the domestic actors would distort the numbers globally, highlighting those individuals who have been extremely prominent across all the domestic feeds. The international actors are of course also European actors, and some of them are European leaders in their national contexts. The figure indicates the prominence of these different actors.

The prominence of Vladimir Putin of Russia (often impersonating a threat to Europe), as well as Joe Biden and Donald Trump of the USA (including in the context of the 2024 US presidential elections) demonstrates the importance of the international political dimension in the European debate. At the same time, the visibility of key European leaders such as Ursula von der Leyen, Emmanuel Macron, and Georgia Meloni, but also Viktor Orbán and Marine Le Pen indicates a high degree of Europeanisation of politics in individual EU member states even if this Europeanisation may be driven by Eurosceptic political actors. In some videos Meloni, Orbán, and Le Pen also were presented as a threat to European democracy. The far-right MEP from Ireland Claire Daly was visible across Europe in practically all feeds, and often on the theme of Gaza.

The recorded presence of Javier Milei of Argentina in the feeds shows that the national discussive fields in some EU countries (like Spain and Portugal) have also visible transatlantic dimensions underpinned strong historical and cultural ties with Latin American countries.

Finally, the visibility of such politicians as Manfred Weber (EPP) and Terry Reintke (EFA/Greens) indicates a strong European effort undertaken by (some of the key) European parties.

Content Related to Defence, War and International Conflicts

Content related to Defence was unevenly distributed across the feeds of synthetic accounts, being much more visible in centre-right and radical right synthetic feeds. At the same time, War-related content, including ongoing military conflicts in Ukraine and Gaza, was visible across the board. The content related to Gaza and Ukraine was, however, very unevenly distributed over different types of political profiles: videos on the conflict in Gaza featured prominently in the feeds of red-green synthetic profiles, while the war in Ukraine (and the threat of Russia looming over Europe) appeared in synthetic profiles across the board.

Threats to Equality and Diversity

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Various types of content threatening equality and diversity were not equally distributed across the feeds of the political profiles. First, some types of synthetic profiles – especially radical right and, in many cases, centre-right profiles – recorded these types of content much more frequently than red-green ones. Second, there were discrepancies between countries, with Central and Eastern European synthetic profiles recording content threatening equality and diversity more frequently than profiles from Western Europe, with notable exceptions of such countries as France and Germany.

Still, in about a third of all data-gathering instances, the synthetic profiles did not record any content threatening equality and diversity. Interestingly, whenever such types of content were actually recorded, this was primarily anti-migrant content, with racist and anti-Muslim content lagging far behind. While anti-democratic content and content related to religious activism were consistently present in the feeds of some synthetic profiles throughout the data-gathering exercise, anti-LGBTQ+ and anti-feminist/misogynist content appeared regularly, yet not daily. Interestingly, AI-generated content started appearing in the feeds only in Week 2 of the data-gathering exercise and antisemitic content appeared only sporadically in the feeds.

Figure 10: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content was not much visible in the feeds of the synthetic accounts across Europe. Yet, when AI-generated content was present, it was mostly featured in entertainment-related and satirical videos mocking specific politicians.

Still, many researchers noted that they might have overlooked AI-generated content, as they had not received sufficient training to be able to identify it. We consider that AI-generated is content just as any in the feeds: we did code the AI contents just as we did for the obviously human produced.

Video Typologies

Some of the most frequently seen types of videos noted by the researchers across the synthetic political profiles include:

- Campaign videos: videos produced by parties' campaigns, containing key political messaging, usually professionally shot and edited.
- Campaign ads: professionally produced short videos, usually consisting of a montage and voiceover, sometimes combined with direct addresses by candidates. Likely to have also aired elsewhere as a political advertisement, for example, on TV, YouTube, etc. These videos showcase core campaign messages, candidates, and slogans.
- Personal addresses: an individual or a group of politicians addressing the viewer directly can be professionally shot and edited or can just be a selfie video. Depending on the candidate, it can just be sticking to regular campaign messaging or directed at some topics that a particular candidate finds important. It can sometimes also be more personalised, e.g. a meet-the-candidate type video.
- Politicians in non-political situations: for example, playing sports, gardening, etc.
- TV clippings: short clips from TV news reports or talk shows featuring political themes, including politicians, journalists, pundits or citizens.
- Parliamentary clips: videos of politicians' speeches in various parliaments (EP or national). Often used to show a politician's highlight statements, jokes, or insults towards other politicians. The format often presents the politician in a positive light (smart, witty, being right), while the recipient of the statement (often unknown) is indirectly shown as incompetent and being taught a lesson.
- Public event speeches: different politicians or officials giving speeches at various events or assemblies.
- Explainer videos: short educational content with professional graphics.
- Selfie videos: amateur, personal videos, usually in a casual setting, in which interested citizens discuss a specific political topic.
- Podcast clips: short clips from video podcasts.

These and other typologies were commented by the research across Europe. Quite typical attractive posts were talking heads. Many of the videos also were in a political setting: clips were used from the parliamentary speeches or video interviews from other media. Some videos are made for the horizontal format, and these do not work as well as those in the vertical one. On the other hand, the horizontal format videos can be used with captions, commentary and emojis or other visual markers. The videos are accompanied by contextualising images or images or clips are added for further debate, ridiculing or issue-based argumentation. Sometimes a very short clip or video indicated the presence of the parties or issues. This is recorded in these country reports. But in the LLM-read video database we focused on the longer videos to explore the arguments through the narrative structure.

We sought and received ethical clearance and promised that we would be attentive to minors and laypeople in the content. There were very rare instances of this kind of content. The content of the

videos clearly indicate that this is a form of media content creation rather than an interactive social media engagement with laypeople. The authors of the posts in our feed are fully aware of the public visibility of the content they produce. Indeed, it appears to be their aim to get the message to as wide circulation as possible on the platform.

Conclusions

In the final section we discuss the basis of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. We discuss about us-building mobilisation and antagonism through the formula and populism. The country reports also include a conclusion of the whole study for the country case.

We consider that the social media offers a “hashtag landscape”, space for publicly voicing concerns, which then researchers and others would be able to follow to explore how the general public think in the open (Koljonen & Palonen 2021). On the other hand, these platforms offer a possibility for politicians to connect with their voters. On the widely available platforms such as Twitter, it is the objective of the people posting online to get heard, and to contribute to a public conversation. This data has been gathered by practitioners. In Finland, the health authority THL was following closely Twitter conversations in the beginning of the pandemic, and in the analysis that we conducted, it was also revealed that when a hype emerged in the public sphere regarding pandemic measures, the governments readily responded and the wave of criticism toned down (Koljonen & Palonen 2021). We turned to the short videos as a way of exploring the continuous construction of the social contract in the present. Also thinking about the social contract as a heuristic to understand political struggles, and the bases of the argumentation for Europe. The results show that social media is used throughout the case countries and that the two platforms also provided political content that could be used to reflect on the social contract. Of the political parties the centre-right EPP had the strongest presence in our feeds across Europe.

As we saw from the above, the key themes we coded as we chose to follow particular categories, arguments for Europe (why vote in Europe, integration, social Europe etc.), grievance politics (making political demands and raising concerns, immigration), and war (Gaza and Ukraine) were present quite evenly. Doing deeper analysis how these were framed and what is now discussed around Europe was related. As for the combined analysis of the country reports we see some contestation of the social contract in the emergence of the Eurosceptic parties and in the issue of immigration. The gender issues were also discussed, but anti-migrant rhetoric was dominating the feeds (Figure 9).

We also did ask people to reflect on the populist mobilisation following the formula of populism (expanded further in Vulovic & Palonen 2023):

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

At the same time, the climate issues are also put in question on which basis is the contract done. The further dataset to be released in September 2025, there is also an LLM reading of the video data that uses this to recognise the articulations of the people and their others and the ways in which they are affectively loaded. Further research will be done to this data as well: we use it in the CO3 for studying

the social contract, in PLEDGE it serves for the analysis of the grievance politics in Europe and MORES for moral political arguments. In this dataset we included videos of 10 seconds or more, even if it lost the shortest videos, but this way we could focus on those which had a more narrative structure.

The formula was to enable the inclusion and exclusion dimension in the research. Political campaigning from the Laclau-Mouffean perspective is about the performance of points of political identification where what we are standing for and what we are against are the key pointers. In the usual conceptualisations of populism there is always an other-to-be-opposed, but in the formula of populism we also wanted to work on social contract, we stress with the notion of the frontier “what” is opposed over antagonism to another group “who”. Here rather than consensus-seeking Habermasian public sphere we talk about a Mouffean one: marked by the political, where disagreement is part of democracy.

Our reading of the social media space for analysing the continuously constructed social contract in its contemporary articulations is further premised on the Masseyan idea that space and the public are co-constitutive (Massey 2005): the common themes that we discuss in the shared environment co-constitute space of what is the common (bases of the social contract) and the public as a collective us as the contracting parties in the social contract.

Our research revealed that it is vital to be researching these platforms both the algorithmic feed and the content of political communication that increasingly takes place in the short video format and platforms like TikTok, Instagram and YouTube. We witnessed the presence of all parliamentary groups from the European parliament. The platforms were used across the ten countries (eight in the CO3 deliverable) we studied. New parties and movements mobilised on the platforms visible in the amounts of non-inscripts: many of them affiliated later with a parliamentary group accounting. The platforms offer a relatively easy way for reaching audiences but there are also typologies of videos that worked better than others.

Bibliography

- Herkman, J., & Palonen, E. (Eds.). (2024).** *Populism, Twitter and the European Public Sphere: Social Media Communication in the EP Elections 2019*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-41737-5>
- Koljonen, J., & Palonen, E. (2021).** Performing COVID-19 Control in Finland: Interpretative Topic Modelling and Discourse Theoretical Reading of the Government Communication and Hashtag Landscape. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2021.689614>
- Massey, D. (2005)** *For Space*, London: Sage.
- Mouffe, C. (2005)** *On the Political*, London: Verso.
- Vulović, M., & Palonen, E. (2022).** Nationalism, populism or peopleism? Clarifying the distinction through a two-dimensional lens. *Nations and Nationalism*, 28(4), 1203–1217.

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Bulgaria

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Ruzha Smilova, Kaloyan Velchev and Daniel Smilov, CLS and Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" (all authors)
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, University of Helsinki; Szilvia Horváth, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Pinar Uyan Semerci (İstanbul Bilgi University)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Bulgaria: EP Election Results	4
National Election Results and Party Affiliations	6
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	7
Section 2: Bulgaria: Political profiles	10
# Centre-Right Feed	12
# Far-Right Feed	16
# Red-Green feed	19
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	23
Section 3: Bulgaria: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	25
# Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	25
# Notes on the organic profiles	26
# Differences Observed Over Time	29
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok	32
# Audience Appeal	33
Section 4: Bulgaria: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	34
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	34
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram	35
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	36
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	37
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	39
# AI Generated Content	39
Section 5: Bulgaria: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	40
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time	40
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate	40
# Emotional Mechanisms	40
# Video Typologies	41
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	42
# Discussion on the most interesting videos	43
Concluding section	44
# What was Europe about and why vote? (Social Contract)	44
# Populist mobilisation	45
# Conclusions	46
Bibliography	47

Bulgaria: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

Run together with the national parliament elections, European Parliament (EP) elections in Bulgaria were overshadowed by the former. While the turnout for the EP elections slightly increased compared to 2019, fatigue dominated the political landscape. Six national parliament elections, held within just 3 years, failed to produce a stable government, contributing to the growing sense of frustration among political elites and the public alike. The fragmentation of the national parliament was replicated in the party affiliations of the Bulgarian MEPs, who are now part of 5 (including 3 MEPs in the newly formed far-right “Europe of Sovereign Nations”) rather than 4 groups in the EP.

The campaign was very negative, especially on TikTok and Instagram, with a starkly negative portrayal of parties and politicians standing for pro-EU and liberal values. Social media – particularly TikTok – gave birth to a new party *Velichie* (Greatness), which made it to the National Assembly despite being altogether missed by pollsters.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Проведени заедно с изборите за Народно събрание, изборите за ЕП в България останаха в сянката на националните. Макар че избирателната активност на изборите за ЕП беше повишена в сравнение с 2019 г., умората доминираше политическия пейзаж. Шестте избори за национален парламент, проведени в рамките само на 3 години, не успяха да излъчат стабилно правителство, което допринесе за нарастващото чувство на неудовлетвореност както сред политическия елит, така и сред широката общественост. Фрагментацията на националния парламент беше възпроизведена в партийната принадлежност на българските евродепутати - които сега са част от 5 (включително 3 евродепутати в новосформираната крайнодясна „Европа на суверенните нации“), а не от 4 групи в ЕП.

Кампанията беше много негативна – особено в TikTok и Instagram – с рязко отрицателно представяне на партиите и политиците, отстояващи проевропейски и либерални ценности. Социалните медии – особено TikTok – роди новата партия в Величие, която влезе в Народното събрание, въпреки че беше напълно пропусната от социолозите.

Section 1: Bulgaria: EP Election Results

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

The 2024 European Parliament elections in Bulgaria were held on June 9th and were run together with the pre-term national parliament elections. The turnout for the EP elections was 33.78% – a point higher than in 2019. The turnout for the national parliament elections was 34.41% - the lowest for national elections since 1989. This low turnout is likely the result of holding 6 (one regular and 5 pre-term) national elections within the span of just 3 years. Both EP and national elections were won by the electoral alliance *Citizens for European Development of Bulgaria party – Union of Democratic Forces* (GERB–UDF).

Six parties and coalitions sent MEPs: GERB–UDF with 23.55% of the vote will have 5 (being centre-right parties, both coalition partners are members of the EPP group). This is down 1 MEP compared to 2019. Second is the *Movement for Rights and Freedoms* (DPS) – the party representing mostly the ethnic Turks in Bulgaria. With 14.66% of the vote, it will send 3 MEPs (the same as in 2019), who will remain part of the Renew group. The coalition *We Continue the Change – Democratic Bulgaria* (PP–DB) came third and with 14.45% of the vote is sending 3 MEPs, of whom 1 will remain in EPP (Radan Kanev from DSB, part of DB was re-elected), and two – Nikola Minchev and Hristo Petrov (both from PP) will join the Renew group. The far right nationalist *Vazrazhdane* (Revival) party came fourth with 13.98% and is sending 3 MEPs. They are joining the newly formed far-right “Europe of Sovereign Nations” group. *Vazrazhdane* did not have MEPs in 2019. Fifth came the *Bulgarian Socialist Party* (BSP), and with 7.01% it will have only 2 MEPs (down from 5 in 2019), who will remain in S&D. BSP was the big loser of the EP elections, only matched by PP–DB at the national elections – where both shrank considerably their respective support. Lastly, the populist *There Is Such a People* (ITN) will have one MEP (with just over 6%), who is joining ECR (the party did not exist in 2019 and did not have MEPs). The nationalist VMRO (*Internal Macedonian Revolutionary Organization*, successor party of the historic IMRO), which had two MEPs in the ECR group after 2019, will not have MEPs in the current EP.

The national elections, in their turn, produced an even more fragmented parliament, with 7 parties and party alliances clearing the 4% electoral threshold. As no government was formed, new elections were called, which will be held on October 27th, 2024. They produced an even further fragmented parliament, with 8 parties and party alliances making it there after elections that were deemed not fair. [Petitions to the Constitutional Court were filed, demanding the partial or full annulment of the elections](#) (Todorov, 2024).

Results by national party – 2024-2029

Bulgaria – Official results

Figure 1. Results by national party

Percentage of votes

National Parties

GERB - SDS/ГЕРБ - СДС – Coalition Grazhdani za evropeysko razvitiye na Bulgariya – Sayuz na demokratichnite sili/Граждани за европейско развитие на България – Съюз на демократичните сили

DPS/ДПС – Dvizhenie za prava i svobodi/ Движение за права и свободи

PP - DB/ПП - ДБ – Coalition Prodalzhavame promyanata – Demokraticzna Bulgariya/

Продължаваме промяната – Демократична България

Vazrazhdane/Възраждане – Vazrazhdane/ Възраждане

BSP/БСП – Bulgarska sotsialisticheska partiy/ Българска социалистическа партия

ITN/ИТН – Ima takav narod/Има такъв народ

Other parties – Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

National Election Results and Party Affiliations

As a result of the EP elections, Bulgarian voters sent MEPs from six parties and coalitions: GERB-UDF (5), DPS (3), PP-DB (3), *Vazrazhdane* (2), BSP (2) and ITN (1)

The affiliation of the MEPs summarized and compared to 2019:

- EPP: 6 (down 1)
- Renew: 5 (up 2)
- ESN: 3 (new)
- S&D: 2 (down 3)
- ECR: 1 (down 1)

The turnout for the pre-term national elections was the lowest on record and produced an even more fragmented parliament – with 7 instead of 6 parties and coalitions making it into the national Parliament.

Even though GERB–UDF came first with 24.71% and has 68 seats in the current Bulgarian parliament, the coalition lost almost 150,000 votes and got 1 seat less. The second place, somewhat surprisingly, went to DPS, which won 17.06% and 47 seats – it was considered the biggest winner from these elections as for the first time in this party's history it came second in national elections and also increased its absolute votes by 20,000. This latter is considered an impressive achievement as this happened under conditions of extremely low turnout – a fact that the co-leader of DPS Delyan Peevski often points out. Despite these considerable advances at the start of the current Bulgarian Parliament, DPS surprisingly split and as of July 18 has a group of just 22 MPs. DPS' parliamentary group will likely continue to shrink because of the current acute conflicts in the leadership of the party – between the current co-leaders Delyan Peevski and Dzhevdet Chakarov, and between Peevski and Ahmed Dogan – the dissident, founder and honorary chair of DPS.

The biggest losers of the national elections were the coalition PP-DB, which not only came third (14.33% and won 39 seats), but also lost over 300,000 of its voters.

Despite the expectation that the far-right nationalist party *Vazrazhdane* (Revival) will be among the big winners in these elections, it came only 4th with 13.78% and has 38 seats.

The second biggest loser of these elections was the Bulgarian Socialist Party – the successor of the communist party which ruled the country between 1945 and 1989. Even though it survived the transition as one of the two principal parties in the country, after 2014 it rapidly lost support and at 7.06% it currently has 19 seats in the 240-seat National Assembly. *There Is Such a People* – which won the pre-term parliamentary elections in mid-2021, and rapidly lost support after failing to form a government, again managed to clear the 4% threshold and with 5.96% now has 16 seats.

The biggest surprise in these elections came from social media – especially YouTube and TikTok, where the newly formed nationalist populist party *Velichie* (*Величие*, Greatness) was gaining momentum while being entirely unnoticed by pollsters. Against the low turnout, it garnered just below 100,000 votes, which proved just enough to clear the 4% threshold and send 13 MPs. However, this party lost its parliamentary group after it expelled some of its members, including the party leader, as it fell below 10 MPs – the minimum number for a parliamentary group. As a result, the Bulgarian parliament had 6 groups and a growing number of 'independent' MPs, who have been expelled from their respective groups. This further increases the fragmentation and lowers the legitimacy of the current Bulgarian Parliament. After the failed attempts to form a government, new elections were held on

October 27, which produced an even more fragmented parliament (with 8 parties and coalition, and a 9 challenging the results and possibly also making it there).

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Bulgaria

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

The EP elections campaign was dominated by national themes as it was run together with the campaign for national parliament elections – and the latter was deemed the more important ones. The same applies to the leading political figures – dominant were the leaders of the lists for the national parliament, and only secondary attention was given to candidates for MEPs. As the Bulgarian electoral system is proportional and with preferential voting, prominent were some very active former MEPs as well as popular national politicians.

Moreover, some parties had top national politicians running on both MEP and MP candidate lists. For example, the top politician from GERB Rossen Zhelyazkov (ex-speaker of Parliament) led the MEP list and the party list in Blagoevgrad and chose to serve as MP. DPS co-leader Dzhevdet Chakarov led MEP list but also gave up his seat to become a member of the Bulgarian parliament. The same did the long-standing MEP from DPS Iskra Mihaylova – who served as vice-chair of the Renew group in the last EP, yet chose to serve in the Bulgarian parliament instead, even though she was second on the DPS list for the 2024 EP elections.

Another prominent politician from DPS – Ilhan Kuychuk – is an MEP since 2014 and since 2015 has been Vice-President of the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe (ALDE). DPS's campaigns are one of the least publicly observable – be it on mainstream or social media. Its top candidates rarely participate in pre-election debates or other media formats, as they prefer direct, in-person contact with their electorate.

As these and many other candidates were effectively running 2-in-1 campaigns and were obviously considering the national parliamentary elections much more important, the national issues dominated the agenda during their campaigns.

7

The MEP campaign of PP-DB candidate Hristo Petrov (better known under his rapper nickname *Ico Hazarta*), which he mostly ran on social media, was so successful, that even though he was placed 7th on the list for MEPs of PP-DB, he garnered over 30,000 personal preferential votes and made it to the EP. Again, based on preferential voting, the leading politician from DSB (currently part of Democratic Bulgaria) Radan Kanev secured his election in 2019 and re-election in 2024. The use of preferential voting has long characterized the vote for PP-DB, where the separate parties within the coalition try to increase their respective vote share by encouraging their own voters to use it. This party strategy within PP-DB has led to campaigns that lack organizational coherence and clear messages.

The far-right nationalist *Vazrazhdane* (Revival) was probably the party that spent most of its resources, airtime, etc. to promote its candidates for EP elections, running on an extreme Eurosceptic agenda. Particularly notable was the media – including social media - presence of Petar Volgin – a controversial journalist at the public Bulgarian national radio, who had for a long time advanced Eurosceptic and pro-Putinist positions. During his campaign for MEP, his voice was clear and loud, and he managed to 'mainstream' several Eurosceptic positions – on limiting military support for Ukraine to promote 'the peace cause' there, renegotiating the 'Green deal', holding a referendum on joining the Eurozone, and so on. *Vazrazhdane* became the second largest party in the newly established "Europe of sovereign nations" EP group, where Petar Volgin will serve as its speaker and the leader of its MEP candidates list – Stanislav Stoyanov will be its deputy floor leader (Todorov, 2024).

Breakdown of national parties and political groups – 2024-2029

Bulgaria – Constitutive session

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PfE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
GERB - SDS/ГЕРБ - СДС	23.55%	5									5
DPS/ДПС	14.66%					3					3
PP - ДВ/ПП - ДБ	14.45%	1				2					3
Vazrazhdane/Възраждане	13.98%								3		3
BSP/БСП	7.01%		2								2
ITN/ИТН	6.04%				1						1
Other parties	20.31%										0
	100.00%	6	2	0	1	5	0	0	3	0	17

GERB/ГЕРБ > EPP: ANDREY KOVATCHEV, EVA MAYDELL, ANDREY NOVAKOV, EMIL RADEV

Vazrazhdane/Възраждане > ESN: RADA LAYKOVA, STANISLAV STOYANOV, PETAR VOLGIN

DPS/ДПС > Renew Europe: TANER KABILOV, ILHAN KYUCHYUK, ELENA YONCHEVA

BSP/БСП > S&D: TSVETELINA PENKOVA, KRISTIAN VIGENIN

PP/ПП > Renew Europe: NIKOLA MINCHEV, HRISTO PETROV

ITN/ИТН > ECR: IVAYLO VALCHEV

DSB/ДСБ > EPP: RADAN KANEV

SDS/СДС > EPP: ILIA LAZAROV

National Parties

GERB - SDS/ГЕРБ - СДС – Coalition Grazhdani za evropeysko razvitiе na Balgariya – Sayuz na demokratichnite sili/Граждани за европейско развитие на България – Съюз на демократичните сили

DPS/ДПС – Dvizhenie za prava i svobodi/Движение за права и свободи

PP - ДВ/ПП - ДБ – Coalition Prodolzhdavame promyanata – Demokratichna Balgariya/Продължаваме промяната – Демократична България

Vazrazhdane/Възраждане – Vazrazhdane/Възраждане

BSP/БСП – Bulgarska sotsialisticheska partiya/Българска социалистическа партия

ITN/ИТН – Ima takav narod/Има такъв народ

Other parties – Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

● EPP - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)

● S&D - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament

● PfE - Patriots for Europe

● ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group

● Renew Europe - Renew Europe Group

● Greens/EFA - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance

● The Left - The Left group in the European Parliament – GUE/NGL

● ESN - Europe of Sovereign Nations

● NI - Non-attached Members

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Section 2: Bulgaria: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

During the study, the Bulgarian team, which maintained the far-right, centre-right and centre-left profiles, found three trends common to all profiles:

- Lower levels of political content on Instagram compared to TikTok. While TikTok actively offers political content, on Instagram the user must actively seek out and engage with political content for the algorithm to begin offering it. Even when actively searching for political content, Instagram's algorithm is slower to respond to user preferences.
- Dominance of radical content on TikTok. Over the course of the study, the content that the three different profiles receive becomes increasingly diverse, but common political videos and themes emerge for all three profiles, coming from profiles of users supporting far-right and populist formations.
- Low levels of overlap between Instagram and TikTok content. In general, Instagram offers more traditional and formal political content (meetings with voters, political debates), while TikTok offers more diverse, more casual content (online conversations with voters, more informal language of communication, more informal clothing of the politicians).

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Country codes are two-letter ISO

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Country codes are two-letter ISO

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

Analysing Figures 4a and 4b, the high level of visibility of the liberal coalition We Continue the Change–Democratic Bulgaria (PP–DB) seems evident across all profile types in both platforms studied. The main reason is not, however, a good campaign by this coalition, which has managed to reach different types of voters across a diverse set of platforms. The main reason lies elsewhere – in the strong negative campaign against PP–DB launched by virtually all political actors. PP–DB became an easy target for criticism because (1) they created an unpopular governing coalition based on a complex political compromise, as a result of which (2) a large part of their electorate turned away from them and a competition started on which party would win over these voters and (3) as the most prominent pro-European political force, PP–DB became the logical target of the Eurosceptic attacks by populist and far-right parties.

The centre-right party GERB is most prominent in the centre-right user’s profiles both on TikTok and Instagram and the far-right *Vazrazhdane* is most prominent in the far-right profiles on both platforms. The data demonstrates the algorithm’s ability to navigate the user’s political preferences and suggest similar content to her/him. The centre-left formation Solidary Bulgaria is dominating only the Instagram content of the centre-left user thus demonstrating the bigger amount of political and radical content on TikTok, where the most prominent parties for the centre-left user are PP–DB (mostly negatively illustrated) and *Vazrazhdane* in third place.

It is also very telling that in the radical right profile there is a large section of “other” Bulgarian political actors. There were at least three small parties acting in this field (*Vazrazhdane*, Greatness, and MECH (Sword)), as well as other smaller groups. This indicates the proliferation of radical right and Eurosceptic actors and considerable demand for such content on TikTok and to a lesser extent on Instagram.

Centre-Right Feed

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Over the course of the study, the amount of political content increased dramatically. On the first day, the centre-right political account received no political content. TikTok was very quickly trained and within a week or so, political content was already dominating both the synthetic and the organic profiles there. On Instagram, political content increased in the last days before the election. Before that, one had to search for political content. Data in figures 5 and 6 demonstrate, however, that this subjective evaluation of the relative paucity of political content on Instagram compared to TikTok is not entirely warranted – in fact, more accounts of politicians and better visibility of candidates from the assigned party profile were achieved on Instagram over the whole period. What is confirmed, however, is the observation that political content on Instagram and TikTok was not identical – on the contrary, hardly any overlaps were seen.

The videos on Instagram were more repetitive and gave the impression that this platform as a whole is not a major field of political clash, and there is not much political content. The observation of the centre-right profile produced the impression from TikTok's content that the algorithm respects one's political leanings to a certain extent (the researcher's synthetic profile had more GERB content), but it also generates political videos that seem to have been viral at the moment of viewing, thus integrating the researcher into the subcultural community that has formed and opening a space to become part of its specific code of communication.

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Thus, the feed was divided equally between the centre-right GERB party and conservative, nationalist and populist content that seemed like mainstream political content for the Bulgarian TikTok. IMRO (ECR) was the second most visible political player on TikTok after GERB, and is responsible for producing the most anti-immigrant, anti-LGBTQ, and anti-Green-deal content there. GERB's interest in the topics of defence and the economy explains their prominence.

Observing TikTok and Instagram left the impression that for a systemic party like the centre-right GERB, social media was not a top priority during the campaign. On the contrary, emerging parties that present themselves as an alternative to the status quo are promoted very actively and successfully on Instagram, but especially on TikTok and YouTube (the latter platform was not part of the observation). As evidence of the above observations, one can offer the surprising entry into parliament of the TikTok party *Velichie* (Greatness), whose social media campaign was very noticeable.

Far-Right Feed

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

The synthetic profile of the far-right sympathizer was quite dense throughout the campaign. Compared to the organic profile, it contained more information, as the difference was especially visible on Instagram.

The key influencers in the videos were the leaders of *Vazrazhdane* Kostadin Kostadinov as well as several other MPs or candidates for the EP of this party. The prominent Bulgarian National Radio journalist Petar Volgin was featured quite a lot with his strong anti-European and pro-Russian rhetoric. The feed also contained a lot of content from smaller and newly founded nationalistic and populist parties. Especially prominent was *MECH* (Sword) – the party of Radostin Vassilev, which got around 3% in the vote and almost made it into the national parliament. Another example is the party *Velichie* (Greatness), which was also featured through important representatives such as “Colonel Markov” and Ivelin Mihaylov.

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The content of the feed was heavy on Eurosceptic and anti-European messages of different sorts, as well as nationalistic themes. Especially on TikTok, there were quite a lot of war videos, as the message was openly pro-Russian and against Ukraine. This is confirmed by the data – war was a top theme, as was the topic of defence.

Mocking European leaders, as well as Joe Biden was quite widespread. There were also a lot of videos with Donald Trump, Viktor Orbán and some other voices, critical of the EU and Ukraine. Even more was the content about Putin and the war in Ukraine, where the pro-Russian position was prevalent. Another prominent feature of the feed were the open and rather harsh attacks on liberal, pro-European parties such as PP-DB (We continue the change and Democratic Bulgaria).

Interestingly, this party had its campaign exclusively on TikTok, Instagram and YouTube. Surprisingly, this party cleared the 4% threshold for the national parliament. Because of that in the days after the elections the feed was dominated by content generated by *Velichie* – apparently a lot of people were interested in who these people were. Last, but not least, there were “independent” influencers producing content for this feed – some of them journalists or intellectuals like Martin Karbovsky and Ivo Hristov, others – YouTubers, bloggers, vloggers such as *Nakata.bg*, *Otvetna reaktsia* (Отвѣтна реакция).

We conclude with three key points from the far-right feeds in Bulgaria:

- The content in Russian increased during the campaign – at the end, there were quite a lot of videos in Russian directly.
- The content from the synthetic profile was more often seen in the organic profile than *vice versa* – in fact the opposite almost never occurred.
- To a great extent, the content on TikTok and Instagram was identical – in stark contrast to the centre-right synthetic profile discussed above.

Red-Green feed

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

The content of the feed on the red-green profile, which focused on the candidates of the coalition “Solidary Bulgaria”, did not fit well the assumed ideological-political profile of left-environmentalists. In Bulgaria, this type of political identification – and the corresponding ideological content – is not politically represented by a notable party or coalition currently. *Solidary Bulgaria* probably comes closest to it, yet the positions of its candidates on most EU-relevant issues are often scarce. This is well demonstrated by the data summarized in figure 18, where the environmental issues come only third – after the issues of the economy and defence.

Furthermore, one cannot infer from them any strong support for the EU Green Deal, for example. Just to the contrary, the expressed commitment to defending workers’ interests – and particularly the workers in the mining industry – naturally renders the two leaders of Solidary Bulgaria – the former Ombudsman of the Republic Maya Manolova and the syndicalist leader Vanya Grigorova, herself is a vocal supporter of the rights of miners (Safe News, 2023).

Probably because their main interest in these elections was to make it to the Bulgarian parliament (with its lower, 4 % threshold) their messages were entirely focused on national political issues. Forming a coalition just days before registering to run, their main policy agenda was for keeping utility–gas, water, electricity, and so on–payments low, as well as fighting against the monopolistic behaviours by telecoms, banks and private bailiffs. In general, their trademark is ‘catering for the interests of the working people’. From her activism as the Ombudsman of the republic and supporter of social causes, Maya Manolova kept her commitment to the cause of the social rights of mothers of children with disabilities, single mothers and similar issues – which is well reflected in the left ideological profile of this coalition. From her background as a syndicalist, Vanya Grigorova kept her strong commitment to workers’ rights.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The content of the feed on this profile was very poor – especially on Instagram, where one had to specifically look for political content by searching and following politicians and activists of Solidary Bulgaria. Even then, there was very little original content as very few of the key figures had profiles on Instagram, and there was no new content posted every day. During the first days of the campaign, both Maya Manolova and Vanya Grigorova were using older content—from previous campaigns—to populate their respective pages, but with the advancement of the campaign, some new content appeared. However, their campaign was marred by scandals. Mihail Mikov – the former political partner of Maya Manolova within the coalition *Levitsata* (The Left) – accused her of stealing the password of the *Levitsata* TikTok account and using without authorization content from her previous campaign in her new political project. The accusation was largely fair. The second scandal came at the end of the campaign and was provoked by a very popular video of Vanya Grigorova playing chess and winning with the pawns – which video seems to plagiarize its main idea and message from a campaign video by a visually impaired candidate (Glasove News, 2024).

The feed on TikTok was much richer in political content, but there Solidary Bulgaria started to disappear shortly after the start of the monitoring period. Instead, content from pro-Putinist sites started flooding in. This content came at times directly in the Russian language – which is understood by the older generation in Bulgaria and is unlikely to have been produced in the country. Rather, it is well known that such content is produced and sponsored by Putin's regime. Content from competing nationalist-populist political projects such as that of Radostin Vassilev and his newly found party *MECH*, of party *Vazrazhdane* (Revival), of the older *IMRO*, *Ataka*, etc. was also prevalent, accounting for the prominence of anti-migrant, anti-LGBTQ and anti-democratic political content (fig. 19).

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Bulgaria

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Bulgaria

As Figures 20a and 20b clearly demonstrate, TikTok is the platform that offers much more political content compared to Instagram. Boyko Borissov – the leader of the centre-right party GERB is the most prominent politician for the centre-right profile on both platforms and Kostadin Kostadinov- the leader of the far-right *Vazrazhdane* is the most visible politician for the far-right profile on both platforms. The data demonstrates the algorithm's ability to navigate the user's political preferences and suggest similar content to her/him. The case with the centre-left profile is different. Due to the lack of a prominent centre-left party in Bulgaria this space is being taken over by populist political actors who use the social inequality as a narrative to oppose the “people” to the “elite” but are also highly critical of the EU and use the migration issue to run a campaign of fear. Therefore, the anti-establishment politician Radostin Vassilev (the leader of MECH) has dominated the TikTok content of the centre-left profile and Solidary Bulgaria represented by Maya Manolova and Vanya Grigorova dominated the Instagram content, demonstrating that TikTok is the platform which promotes more radical content. Figures 20a and 20b also show the prominence of the far-right politicians in general. Kostadinov is strongly present in the content of all three synthetic profiles. The same is true for anti-establishment actors such as Nikolay Markov and Radostin Vassilev, who are particularly visible on TikTok, and this can be traced if one examines the content of the organic profiles. In general, it is Vassilev and Markov who are the “gateway” to entering the far-right bubble of content that TikTok offers.

Section 3: Bulgaria: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

Some of us noticed a larger difference between different social media platforms (Instagram and TikTok) than between the synthetic and the organic profiles. Others, however, noted the greater density of political content on their synthetic compared to their organic profiles. Generally, the political content on TikTok was much more abundant, and the political messages – much more extreme. The use of life streams and content produced in informal settings contributed to the feeling of authenticity, which may have contributed to the viral spread of political messages. This was particularly true of new political actors and parties, covered under the category of *non-inscrits* in EP groups – which is the dominant 'group' in our data, only occasionally matched by the EPP. Without access to mainstream media and other traditional channels of political influence, these new political actors aptly used these social media platforms, amplifying the spread of their messages often to groups that do not use traditional media – such as members of minority groups and the young.

Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

During the research and engagement process with different social media platforms, the researcher, following the *centre-right* political profile, noticed that the most significant contrasts were not between the synthetic and organic accounts but between the platforms themselves. There was a lot of radical content on the TikTok organic account because the algorithm offered it, whereas in the synthetic account, there was a process of sifting the content so that the profile would target centre-right content. TikTok offered much more extreme content than Instagram. The former platform offered much more space for non-mainstream politicians to express themselves, thus creating a subcultural space that generates its own language and narratives. This happened unnoticed to people who are not on TikTok (or YouTube, since Bulgarian radicals have very successfully entered YouTube, too). Instagram offered a much smaller amount of political content, but politicians were present there as influencers, as stars, and hate speech was much less prominent. Conspiracy theories were also gaining momentum, mostly via TikTok, and were much less visible on Instagram.

The *radical-right* synthetic profiles were much denser than the organic profiles: the organic profiles did not feature a lot of political videos, especially on Instagram. This may be because the researcher did not use Instagram for professional or politics-related activities. The TikTok profiles were generally denser than those on Instagram. The TikTok feed created the impression of a lack of distance between the speaker and the audience – talks from couches, kitchen tables, and ordinary-looking apartments,

25

Funded by
the European Union

life streaming or videos from streets or symbolic venues also contribute to this feeling of immediacy, even intimacy of the message. The more unprofessional the video is, the more “authentic” and trustworthy it may claim to be – or at least there is a probability that the viewer may reach (unconsciously) such a conclusion.

The political content received on the *left-green* organic profile (compared to the synthetic one) was much richer and much more varied. The organic profile enabled the user to engage freely with content without deliberate curation (which was needed when working with the synthetic account). Thus, the organic profile tended to receive a broader range of political narratives, especially on TikTok, though this trend was also observable on Instagram. In contrast, Instagram's algorithm initially delivered a substantial volume of non-political content primarily centred on food, beauty routines, and tourism, indicating the platform's emphasis on lifestyle-related media. Over time, TikTok distinguished itself as a space where content produced by ethnic minorities, notably Roma users, surfaced more frequently than on any other social platform. A possible explanation for such a phenomenon is that other social media implement hidden censorship – they contain more text and written communication, while the content on TikTok is based entirely on video sharing, which reduces the linguistic distance and allows the production of content that becomes more easily accessible to a wide range of social groups. One striking feature of TikTok is the immediacy of communication – the widespread practice of life streaming on these platforms significantly contributes to a sense of immediacy and personal connection, reinforcing the platform's role not just as a content distribution system but as a space for real-time dialogue.

The big surprise of the national election – the breakthrough of party *Velichie* (Greatness), it transpired, was due to the very effective campaign of its leaders on YouTube, TikTok and Instagram. During the campaign, they engaged directly with users, bypassing traditional media channels. Live videos of Nikolay Markov and Ivelin Mihaylov from *Velichie* were shared broadly on social media and could be spotted on both synthetic and organic accounts creating a momentum that mainstream sociology failed to track.

Notes on the organic profiles

Whereas the synthetic profiles attempted to emulate specific voter profiles, the organic ones had no restrictions regarding viewed political content.

Starting with no political content, over the course of the study, it increased considerably on both platforms, with content appearing much faster on TikTok than on Instagram – the latter only got more such content in the last days before the elections yet was not comparable in volumes to that available on TikTok. In general, the content on Instagram was more repetitive, giving the impression that political clashes were not happening there – especially compared to TikTok, which provided a much more dynamic feed filled with diverse political content.

Somewhat surprisingly, and in contrast to our subjective evaluations, the data on the visibility of political actors demonstrate that in fact Instagram was more saturated with political actors from the largest party in the country (GERB-SDS, from the EPP group) compared to TikTok. The feed on both TikTok and Instagram was dominated by political content coming from accounts of parties and candidates belonging to the two systemic party groups in the European Parliament – the European People's Party (EPP) and Renew. Reflecting the much lesser influence of the Bulgarian socialist party (Socialists and Democrats, S&D) in the country – which got only 6-8% in recent national elections, content from S&D was also much less visible on both platforms. This lesser visibility can be accounted for by the choices

made by the researchers on what to follow and watch on their organic accounts – with all of them having much more interest in the main competitors in the elections GERB-SDS, PP-DB and DPS.

Given the constant supply of new political parties in recent Bulgarian politics (with two parliamentary elections in the last three years being won by newcomers), it is not surprising that political content from *non-inscrits* came second or third in the organic accounts – as some of them have been just established and had not yet made their EP group choice. Some of the parties that were *non-inscrits* are anti-systemic, with nationalist-populist and far right ideology, and are often also with strong pro-Russia sympathies on the war in Ukraine – this is the case with parties *Vazrazhdane* (*Revival*), *Velichie* (*Greatness*), *Centar* (Center) and MECH (МЕЧ in Bulgarian means “sword”, yet here it is an acronym from *Морал, Единство, Чест* or ‘Morality, Unity, Honour’). Their considerable presence in the feed of the organic accounts explains why anti-migrant, anti-democratic, anti-LGBTQ content was also abundant.

Many of these political players – and their supporters produce and spread content filled with conspiracy theories and disinformation, including Russia-produced propaganda, mocking the West and Western politicians (Biden, Macron, von der Leyen) and positively portraying Russia, Putin and other non-Western leaders (for example, Erdogan). Central issues that reappeared in the feed were the war in Ukraine (with the Russian aggressor often portrayed quite favourably), while the conflict in Gaza was marginally covered as was the presidential campaign in the US.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Negative campaigning was prevalent – with almost all attacking the politicians from PP-DB from all directions. This explains their constant presence in 'mocking' videos produced and aired by their political opponents.

The national campaign dominated over the European one, similarly to the national leaders and candidates. This was not due only to the fact that EP and national parliament elections were run together but is a general feature of all EP election campaigns in Bulgaria, which have been dominated by national issues and national political struggles.

Differences Observed Over Time

Over the study, the amount of political content increased dramatically in the centre-right accounts. On the first day, there was no political content. TikTok was very quickly trained and within a week or so, political content was already dominating the feed on TikTok. On Instagram, political content increased in the last days before the election. Before that, we had to search for political content. The videos on Instagram were more repetitive and gave the impression that this platform was not a major field of political clash and there was not much political content. TikTok's algorithm seemed better aligned with

29

one's ideological political leanings, with the synthetic profile receiving more GERB content. At the same time, it fed political videos that were viral, drawing the viewer into a virtual community that does not necessarily share his/her ideological positions.

The red-green synthetic profile—especially on Instagram—was very poor in terms of political content – even though the researcher purposefully looked for political content there. It remained so to the last moment. The account on TikTok was more diverse and was getting some content—mostly nationalistic, often pro-Russian—not directly related to the campaign of Solidary Bulgaria. The researcher even received some content in Russian; mostly related to Russia's war against Ukraine (with a pro-Russian message). During the last week—after the June 9th general and EP elections—the synthetic TikTok account started getting a lot of content related to the big surprise of the parliamentary elections – the breakthrough of party *Velichie*. The nationalist propaganda—with a very negative portrayal of mainstream Europhile political players, especially the incumbents from PP–DB—dominated the feed for the greater part of the campaign period. In the last week, however, it quickly gave way to content focusing almost exclusively on *Velichie* – who they are, what they stand for, who their leaders are, and so on.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Bulgaria over time

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Bulgaria over time

Similarly to the red-green profile, the radical right profile received content in Russian—containing official pro-Putin videos, as well as bloggers and vloggers on the Russian side in the war—and this content increased significantly during the campaign. Ukraine and the war were generally a major theme in the radical-right profile (though it also featured in the red-green one): threats of war expansion, mocking of Western leaders, glorifying non-Western political leaders, and so on flooded the feed. Curiously, “European” content from sources like Orbán, Meloni, and Le Pen was more likely to appear in the synthetic far-right profile, rather than pro-European leaders to appear in the organic profiles.

The amount of political content that both platforms offer peaked in the week before the elections, as can be seen in figures 24a and 24b.

Finally, it must be noted that formations that had their campaigns predominantly or exclusively in the social networks did very well in these elections (especially the national ones). One of the parties *Velichie* got into the National Assembly, another – *MECH* – got 3%, and Vassil Bozhkov’s party also got over 1% of the vote in national elections. Although those parties failed to gain representation in the EP, their performance was totally surprising both for pollsters (none of whom had predicted such a result) and the public at large.

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

The war was a central topic both in the national parliament and the EP elections. The focus was exclusively on the Ukraine-Russia war, with the Israel-Gaza conflict completely marginalized. NATO-related discussion and the question of the defence strategy of the EU often featured – both in pro-EU and Eurosceptic political content on both platforms, though clearly the nationalist and far right parties (such as *Vazrazhdane*, *MECH*, *Velichie*, *IMRO* and others) who were very active on these platforms, used them to spread conspiracies and disinformation – about the imminent sending of Bulgarian troops on the front in Ukraine. War and defence were the top issues on both platforms. The economy – especially the speedy introduction of the Euro, strongly opposed both by radical right nationalists and the socialists, – and immigration – similarly strongly opposed by the same political camps – were also prominent there. This trend characterized our feeds on both platforms, even though the concrete content - the videos - was more often altogether different, with only some occasional overlaps. Opposition to the Green Deal also featured prominently on both platforms in both the (supposedly) red-green and the radical right accounts.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Audience Appeal

TikTok felt more intense and more extreme than Instagram. The TikTok videos had a more direct effect on the audience – they were much less of the traditional electoral propaganda type. Normally, a TikTok video features a person walking and sharing ideas, or people sitting on their sofa, or around a table and having an informal conversation. The informality and directness create an immediate connection with the audience and some sense of authenticity. This effect is less pronounced on Instagram, which featured a more traditional type of political propaganda – leaders giving speeches at party gatherings and rallies, for instance. The observations made are valid for both the organic and synthetic profiles, and also for the entire ideological spectrum covered within the study.

Section 4: Bulgaria: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section, we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process, simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI-produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 25: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

In the red-green profile there was mostly content related to the war in Ukraine and the Green Deal. There wasn't a politician or video that supported the Green Deal from the content that reached us. The Green Deal is used as a convenient topic to criticize the EU while at the same time not openly declaring yourself as anti-EU. In relation to the war in Ukraine it is also probably the most unpleasant content that has reached us because Ukraine is being insulted in a very ugly way. However, in relation to the war in Ukraine, we have also received content in defence of Ukraine, not just pro-Russian positions.

In the radical right profile on both platforms the most important theme was the war in Ukraine. There were reports from the war stressing the dangers of all-out conflict between Russia and NATO. Political leaders like Putin, Orbán and Meloni were featured. Mocking videos of Biden, Macron and other

European leaders were quite common. Generally, the idea was to portray the EU as weak and incompetent, lacking leadership.

The centre-right feed was divided equally between the centre-right GERB party and conservative, nationalist and populist content that seemed like mainstream political content for the Bulgarian TikTok. Observing TikTok and Instagram left us with the impression that for a systemic party like the centre-right GERB, social media was not a top priority during the campaign. On the contrary, emerging parties that present themselves as an alternative to the status quo were promoted very actively and successfully on Instagram, but especially on TikTok and YouTube (the latter platform was not part of the observation).

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

There was quite a lot of anti-immigrant content—migrants are generally presented as a major threat for Europe. We could not notice AI-generated content and bots—maybe some of the content in Russian language was of this nature. Religion does not play a major role in Bulgarian politics, although the far-right attempts to use some of the religious symbols for its purposes. There was no open misogynistic or anti-LGBTQ language, but a general theme of the far right is that they need to preserve the Bulgarian traditional culture and protect it from the detrimental influence of “European values”.

35

It is understood that in their usage “traditional culture” excludes tolerance of LGBTQ and promotion of traditional family values. The promotion of such values was not the exclusive preserve of the radical right, however. On the contrary, the red-green profile featured its leaders attending Easter service in an Orthodox church and explicitly stressing the importance of tradition and family values. The same applies to the centre-right profile; party GERB self-describes as a “conservative” party. There was occasional reference to the alleged ‘gender ideology’ and a commitment to not allow the spread of this supposed ideology was often reiterated by leaders of *Velichie*, the socialist party, but also by smaller newcomer parties, eager to enter the right-conservative niche.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

As mentioned above, there was a lot of content on Russia and Ukraine. Videos of Putin—from official and unofficial sites—were rather common, especially on TikTok. Occasionally leaders like Orbán were also featured. Mocking European leaders—especially French and German ones—was also present. Joe Biden and his age were further instrumentalized; the purported fragility and weakness of the West were often alleged with such videos. The data gatherers saw increasing Russian-language content as the elections were coming nearer.

There were some official campaigning materials from EU institutions, mostly encouraging the people to vote in the elections.

The outlined trends are valid for all synthetic accounts.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

The war in Ukraine was featured in a lot of videos. There were reports on Russian successes or updates of developments. The dangers of all-out nuclear conflict were also brought out. The necessity for peaceful solutions—mostly implying the surrender of Ukraine—was a major theme of far-right parties (and the Bulgarian Socialist Party, an outlier in European terms, followed by the red-green sympathizer). The weakness of the leadership of the West was also implied in the context of the war; Putin as a strong leader was given as a contrast. The idea that the aid for Ukraine prolongs the war was a major theme of the far-right campaign (and the campaign of the BSP). The war in Gaza generated much less interest in Bulgaria; there were occasional references, which hardly played any role in the EP elections.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

38

Threats to Equality and Diversity

The overtone of the far-right campaign was the preservation of the traditional culture and identity of Bulgaria. It is implied that these are rather homogenous and prevent diversity, especially when it involves LGBTQ matters. Curiously, traditionally Bulgaria is a diverse society – having one of the largest Muslim (10%) and Roma minorities in Europe. In none of the profiles was this brought up as a positive element or as a politically relevant fact. The radical right profiles—and to a degree the red-green profiles—featured more non-diversity or anti-diversity content than the centre-right.

Quite surprisingly, Radostin Vassilev and his newly formed party *MECH* explicitly appealed in their campaign to the Roma community, placing the Romani pop-folk diva Roxana as a leader of his party's list in two districts. In his speech at a rally in a Roma neighbourhood, where Roxana had a concert, Vassilev urged the members of this minority to vote for parties—such as *MECH*—that put Romani candidates on their lists; rather than sell their votes to parties that do not respect them and never send Roma representatives in Parliament. This is to an extent a surprising development, as the nationalist overtones—and often open anti-Roma speech—dominate the rhetoric of protest parties such as *MECH*.

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content was not prominent and may have been present in videos in Russian – part of the official Kremlin propaganda. In videos created specifically for the Bulgarian public by politicians and vloggers it was difficult to detect AI-generated content, but maybe this lack of sufficient sensitivity is due to the lack of specific expertise in this field among the researchers.

Section 5: Bulgaria: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In the section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

Due to the training of the profiles - after an initial phase in which the political content was scarce - there was a constant flow of such content on all accounts. The synthetic accounts had more political content than the organic profiles throughout the campaign. TikTok was a much faster learner than Instagram and generated much more (multiple times more) political content than Instagram. Immediately after the election, the accounts started featuring almost exclusively material from *Velichie* – the party that surprisingly entered the Bulgarian Parliament. This was so because hardly anyone was familiar with this party (apart from its social media followers) and the general interest in it was enormous.

With the progression of the campaign, content in Russian (may be AI-generated but we cannot be sure) started to appear regularly in the radical-right—but also occasionally on the red-green—profiles. Generally, there was more political content with the progression of the campaign, but this was true mostly of TikTok. In the organic profiles on Instagram the political content was often minimal.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

In Bulgaria there was clear evidence of the political influence of TikTok. Two parties, which had their campaigns almost exclusively in social media and especially on TikTok and YouTube, were very successful; one of them, *Velichie*, entered the Bulgarian Parliament and the other, *MECH*, almost did it. Due to the higher electoral threshold, they were not represented in the EP, but still the effect of TikTok cannot be dismissed as trivial. Actually, those two parties and especially *Velichie* did not have any existence outside social media. Most people—who get their information from TV and traditional media outlets, but even the political analysts, media commentators and the polling agencies—were totally surprised by the electoral results. In the aftermath of the elections, there was a dramatic increase in the interest in knowing who the politicians from *Velichie* are; and this content flooded social media, including TikTok and Instagram.

Memes and videos (sometimes even cartoons, some possibly with AI-generated content), mocking politicians—the liberal pro-EU PP–DB were a constant target—were also quite prominent on TikTok and Instagram. The effect of this is to discredit liberal, pro-EU positions. The negative portrayal of EU and US leaders as “weak” and old, representatives of a decadent “occidental” global culture - and their comparison with “manly”, virulent, younger looking, nationalist leaders such as Orbán and Putin – may contribute to the mainstreaming of anti-EU and far-right views, especially among the young males.

#Emotional Mechanisms

TikTok was felt as disturbing media by our team. It was stressful, direct, immediate – people were immediately involved in an emotional connection with the protagonists, which was very often negative. Instagram was different from this perspective – it seemed to provide a bit more distance. TikTok seemed to have substantively more extreme content as well. Arguments did not come in the form of text – they

40

Funded by
the European Union

were always narrated by someone and, as a rule, they were strongly emotionally charged. So, the content often was about anger, frustration, denigration of politicians, mocking them and so on. This could be both entertaining and emotionally stressful, no matter what side of the political divide a person is on. Because of the entertainment element, radical-right content was more likely to migrate to organic centrist profiles than vice versa. Actually, there was almost no penetration of centrist content into radical-right accounts.

Video Typologies

The main type of videos of the centre-right party, *GERB* were from party meetings in different cities of the country, where the leader Borissov gave speeches. The short videos usually concerned moments from his speeches in which he attacked or mocked his political opponents, *We Continue Change-Democratic Bulgaria*. The videos sought to project the charisma of the GERB leader. Short videos from the GERB rally, held in the ancient theatre in Plovdiv a week before the election day, which featured Ursula von der Leyen and Manfred Weber, were the main content GERB spread on all media channels – including in the platforms covered here. The intended message was that GERB is the only real pro-EU political force in the country, which can guarantee the EU future of the country.

The main type of videos of the far right were live videos of the leader spreading fear on a specific topic. The dominant topic for the far-right from *Vazrazhdane* was the war in Ukraine. The format of the video boils down to the following plot: the party's leader Kostadin Kostadinov in a long monologue in front of a camera explains how Bulgaria has joined the war against Russia, how military equipment is being sent to the Ukrainian front and how Bulgarian soldiers are expected to be sent to fight on the side of Ukraine. A similar format of the videos was followed by other representatives of nationalist formations - *VMRO* and *Velichie* - as for them the leading topic was rather the Green Deal and how harmful it is for Bulgaria. *Vazrazhdane* and *VMRO* have paid a lot of attention to the migration as well.

A lot of political players – especially from smaller newcomer parties, but not only - used the format of debate highlights from televised debates – often aired by the national TV, which assigns free airtime to all candidates. They used it to stress their public visibility but also to share their ideas and to mark their superiority vis-à-vis their competitors, who often share the same agenda (the radical right conservative political space is overpopulated in Bulgaria).

Most of the video content on the red-green accounts came from the official profiles of the co-leaders of the coalition *Solidary Bulgaria*: Maya Manolova and Vanya Grigorova. As the coalition was hastily formed just ahead of the elections, most of the video content was recycled videos from previous campaigns with a focus on social themes such as the social problems single mothers face, the high social cost of monopolistic services in the utilities, the banking and the telecom sectors. Only in the last days of the campaign some new video content was produced, but it was focused on the national rather than the EP elections. Though the same trend of predominance of national over EP elections-related content was observed in the other two ideological profiles, it was much more pronounced in the case of the red-green profile, which almost entirely was saturated with national-elections-focused content. Strikingly, there was hardly any pro-green content on either of the three profiles, including the red-green one. On the contrary, due to the long-standing social commitments of the co-leaders of Solidary Bulgaria – one was an Ombudsman of the Republic, and the other was a leader of an influential trade union – at no point did they express any positive sentiment towards environmental causes.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Image 1. Text from the screenshot: The Bulgarian border (in red, on top); INVASION (in green). BG1:07.06.2024 ORGANIC PROFILE 1ST PART TIKTOK: 9:40-10:49.

In the video, the leader of *Vazrazhdane* Kostadin Kostadinov speaks against the background of a bare meadow with clothes unorderly heaped on the grass. Kostadinov claims he is at the border with Turkey, and the viewers see clothes left by migrants who crossed the border illegally. Kostadinov seeks to demonstrate not only that foreigners enter the country illegally, but that they are filthy and dangerous. “Mainly men with nothing to lose,” the *Vazrazhdane* leader says. “This is an invasion that will kill us if we do not deal with it”, Kostadinov believes. He says that when *Vazrazhdane* comes to power, it will increase the presence of the army along the border and give soldiers the right to shoot at any intruder, as was the case before 1989. That is clearly a radical anti-migrant narrative.

Image 2. Text from the screenshot: “They wan WAR!) BG1 :04.06.2024 SYNTHETIC PROFILE 1ST PART TIKTOK: 6:00-06:55

The video is an excerpt from a debate between Peter Volgin (*Vazrazhdane* (BG) - *Europe of Sovereign Nations Group* (ESN)) and Stephan Tafrov from *We Continue the Change- Democratic Bulgaria* (the formation that supports Ukraine to the greatest extent). Volgin, a former journalist at Bulgaria’s Public broadcaster BNR, asks Tafrov if he will volunteer for the Ukrainian army after defending the war so passionately or if he will sit in Bulgaria and comment from a safe distance. Tafrov is unprepared for such a question and answers unconvincingly. The host asks Volgin if he will enlist in the Russian army since he believes Ukraine has no right to defend itself. Volgin replies that he does not pretend to be a brave man like his opponent, and he is against war in general. That’s why he doesn’t plan to enlist in anyone’s army. The short video is a vivid demonstration of the popular anti-war narrative that serves the pro-Russian position in Bulgaria. All those who support Ukraine are presented as cowardly elites who want war but have no courage to participate in it. Anyone who sits on the side of the aggressor Russia is presented as the authentic representative of the wise Bulgarian people, who are peaceful by nature and do not want there to be a war between two brotherly nations.

42

Image 3. Text from the screenshot: Third World War (in red)
 If Vazrazhdane wins (in green)
 Immediate exit from NATO (in red)
 Bulgaria is threatened with involvement in a third world war (in green)
 Nuclear weapons in Bulgaria (in green)
 BG1 :01.06.2024 ORGANIC PROFILE 1ST PART TIKTOK:
 04:30-07:35

The video represents highlights from a press conference of the leader of *Vazrazhdane* Kostadin Kostadinov. During the press conference Kostadinov developed a series of radical positions. The video starts with the words, “If *Vazrazhdane* wins these elections, tomorrow we will leave NATO”. The argument is elaborated that NATO is the biggest threat to Bulgaria’s national security. It continues with the suspicion that America has deployed nuclear weapons on Bulgarian territory without asking the Bulgarian people. The servile Bulgarian politicians have allowed such a thing to happen. “Make no mistake, there will be a Third World War soon”, Kostadinov says. And when that happens, the Americans will use the nuclear weapons they have deployed on Bulgarian territory, which will not only get us into the war, but it will lead to the destruction of Bulgaria because it has become a target. This is the most radical anti-NATO narrative articulated during the campaign. In general, the anti-NATO narrative becomes more and more popular even though the public opinion is still on pro-NATO positions.

Discussion on the most interesting videos

All team members were surprised by the amount of radical content and the sense of proximity between the content user and the content creator on TikTok which the platform produces. The intersection in the content observed by the far-right, centre-left, and centre-right accounts was precisely the appearance of videos on the feed that spread radical narratives, though the amount of radical content varied between account types. The same observation can be made when comparing synthetic and organic accounts on TikTok.

The more radical the content, the more memorable it is, the more emotions it generates for the user. The emotions that radical political content generates are mostly those of fear and frustration. In this way, a new type of voter is constructed who does not see traditional parties and politicians as an option to support in elections. The TikTok content successfully constructs traditional politicians, media and experts as enemies. They become the object of the frustration engendered in the user and their political mobilisation henceforth is to punish the elite so narrated, by voting for the marginal political players who use social media effectively.

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion to the bases of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was Europe about and why vote? (Social Contract)

The national parliament elections overshadowed the EP elections in Bulgaria. So, there was not much content strictly related to EP elections, and when there was such content, it was often very much mixed with messages addressing strictly national issues.

The general tenor of the campaign was determined by massive negative campaigning against candidates from competitor parties, and in the nationalist-populist camp, a lot of anti-green rhetoric, rhetoric against EU supporting Ukraine as this allegedly would prolong the war, and so on. Negative campaigning was dominant even among mainstream parties that try to portray themselves as different. Thus, the campaign of the lead parties GERB–SDS (centre-right) and DPS (ethnic party of the Turkish minority with liberal affiliation), but also of the smaller parties such as *There is such a people (Conservatives)*, BSP (Socialists) and others, was built on tarnishing the liberal coalition *We continue the change–Democratic Bulgaria* (PP–DB). But even politicians from the electoral alliance PP–DB were not immune to using negative campaigning. Their arguments for why it is important to vote are revealing here. It is that by voting in big numbers, the influence of the *Movement of Rights and Freedoms* – the political party led by Delyan Peevski, who is sanctioned under the global Magnitsky Act for high-level corruption – will be diminished.

To the extent there was a positive EP elections campaign by the leading mainstream Europhile parties, it was very general, with mostly ‘declarative’ rather than policy-related messages – declaring commitment to the EU values and loyalty to the geo-political path chosen some 20-25 years ago when decisions to join the EU and NATO were taken. Examples of such declarative messages were the campaign of Boyko Borissov and, even more so, that of Rossen Zhelyazkov. The leader of the MEP candidate list of GERB in a much-circulated speech proclaimed GERB's commitment to EU values. This speech was delivered at the rally attended by Ursula von der Leyen, Manfred Weber and other EPP leaders and became the main staple of the last week of GERB's campaign before elections.

Vazrazhdane (Revival) was probably the party that not only spent most of its resources, airtime, etc. to promote its candidates for the EP elections, but also proposed an extreme Eurosceptic agenda with concrete policy proposals such as voting against any military support for Ukraine and promoting “the peace cause” by negotiating a peace deal with Putin, renegotiating the *Green Deal*, renegotiating the EU's *Migration Pact*, holding a referendum in Bulgaria on joining the Eurozone, holding a referendum on leaving NATO, and so on. The overarching theme in their campaign rhetoric was “sovereignty” – not only any decisions to privilege the interests of Bulgaria alone over all other EU nation-states, but all decisions affecting Bulgaria were to be taken in Bulgaria - by Bulgarians alone. When asked why they would like to send MEPs instead of focusing only on national politics, their answer was revealing; they kept saying they need to fight in Brussels – in the heart of the EU, where currently the site of decision-making is. Their main declared objective was the right of sovereign nations to take their sovereign decisions – which right has been presumably challenged by Bulgaria's EU membership.

There was a considerable supply of EP-sponsored content both on TikTok and Instagram, which aimed to convince young Bulgarians to vote in the EP elections. The campaign often used influencers to target

these younger audiences. There were some well-targeted messages that may have proven successful, as voting turnout among the young exceeded that of older age cohorts.

The fact that due to his very apt – and entirely positive - campaign on TikTok and Instagram the politician from PP-DB, Hristo Petrov (Ico Hazarta)¹ managed to get one of the 3 MEP seats for PP-DB demonstrates the potential of using those platforms effectively. Using songs and visuals, he was able to explain the EU in simple language – sending a strong positive message.

This positive example demonstrates that the platforms themselves are just a medium, which can be used to fuel support for buffoon projects such as that of party *Velichie* (Greatness) but can also convey powerful and motivating messages in support of democratic values, which can reinvigorate citizen commitment to the European project.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

Populist discourse is mainly used by the far-right formations in Bulgaria (*Vazrazhdane*, VMRO) as well as among newly emerging formations (*Velichie*, MECH). There are some similarities but also serious differences in the way the parties listed above construct “us” and “them”. Sometimes, populist discourse appears in the messages of the centre-right. GERB, for example, target their main competitors from the Europhile centre-right coalition PP-DB. PP, in particular, are often portrayed by GERB as “them”, not truly belonging to the right-wing “us”, while DB are presented as temporarily lost, yet ultimately genuinely belonging to “us”.

Focusing on the far right, politicians from *Vazrazhdane* claim that they represent the true Bulgarians. However, their concept of a “true Bulgarian” is very exclusive. The real Bulgarians are not the political elite, they are not the minorities, they are not the people who support Bulgaria’s membership in NATO and joining the Eurozone. Anyone who does not support Kostadin Kostadinov’s positions is not a real Bulgarian. Thus, for *Vazrazhdane*, the category “us” refers to a limited group of active citizens, who are easily mobilized for political demonstrations, which acts in an organized way to provoke violence and aggression, both on social media and on the street. The high degree of mobilization and the massive presence on social media give the impression that this group is much larger and more influential than it is. *Vazrazhdane* positions itself as a harsh critic of the EU in its political communication. Using terms like bureaucrats, servants, colonial administration, the representatives of *Vazrazhdane* are the biggest Eurosceptics in Bulgaria at the moment.

VMRO uses a classic ethnic construct to define the political community. Bulgaria belongs to the ethnic Bulgarians. The Roma, the Turkish minority in Bulgaria, migrants and sexual minorities have no place on the territory of Bulgaria (*Vazrazhdane* also attacks the LGBTQI+ community and migrants, but Roma and Turks are less often the target of Kostadinov’s hate speech). They position themselves as Eurosceptic, but do not want to leave the EU. They support the concept of a “Europe of Nations”. This is the plural “us”.

With *Velichie*, it is more difficult to identify a coherent narrative. Ivelin Mihaylov and Nikolay Markov are highly critical of the political elite and the EU (especially regarding migration and the Green Deal), but at the same time they recognize the benefits of European integration. They refer to Bulgarian history

¹ He was placed 7th in the EP elections party list of PP-DB.

and want to make Bulgaria great again, but at the same time they criticize the country's most mythologized national heroes. The narratives through which they build political community are not exclusive. Their main focus is Bulgarians abroad. The large diaspora living outside the country often appears in the narratives that political parties offer to citizens. Bulgarians abroad have voting rights and targeting them is not a new practice in Bulgarian politics. Such a narrative is also very effective in targeting the rest of the electorate. The basic idea is that the preconditions will be created for all Bulgarians to return to their homeland, which will solve practically all our problems.

Party MECH of Radostin Vassilev's uses the most the classic opposition that populist leaders resort to. He positions himself as a representative of the 'pure people' and as the only alternative to the 'corrupt elite'. Vassilev is also highly critical of the EU and gets fully into the narrative of *Vazrazhdane* when he criticizes the European Union. The most interesting thing in Vassilev's communication tactics is the inclusion of Roma in the political community he narrates. Considering that the Roma minority is very active on TikTok, Vassilev targeted a large part of his campaign messages to the Roma by narrating their problems as having nationwide relevance - poverty, social inequalities affect not just the Roma, but the ethnic Bulgarians, too. Furthermore, it is not the Roma who are external to the community, but the migrants who are stealing jobs, raiding and committing crimes on the territory of Bulgaria. Bulgarians and Roma have a common interest in stopping the migrant wave and expelling this common enemy. Vassilev tries to turn the marginal Roma minority into mainstream Bulgarian nationalists.

Conclusions

The monitoring of the social platforms TikTok and Instagram during the European parliament elections campaign for Bulgaria clearly demonstrates that social networks play an increasingly important role in shaping the political preferences of citizens. The extent to which political preferences formed through social media are lasting is a question that requires further research, which seems urgent given the influence of social media not only on citizens' political preferences, but also on the formation of political agenda, political mobilizations and the formation of increasingly emotional reactions to political events and actors (increasing frustrations, fanhood, and so on).

Run together with the national parliament elections, EP elections in Bulgaria were overshadowed by the former. It is the results of the national elections that clearly demonstrate the influence of social media. The entry of the party *Velichie* into the Bulgarian parliament was a surprise for the mainstream media and happened mainly thanks to their active and successful campaign on the YouTube and TikTok platforms (to a lesser extent Instagram). The negative campaign dominated the landscape, creating favourable conditions for a good performance of far-right and populist formations. Negative content was prevalent in all organic and synthetic profiles that were created for the purpose of the study.

The increased levels of frustration and dissatisfaction that social media produces among citizens have deeper effects than support for one party or another. The democratic system and its institutions are being delegitimised and are proving unprepared to respond to the increased desires and expectations of citizens. It is reasonable to assume that this process will continue to develop and deepen. Democracies are faced with the dilemma of whether to introduce regulations on the use of social networks or to adapt to the growing role of social media on real life and thus on democratic politics. On the one hand, the virtual reality exposes citizens to a number of risks – cybercrime, online violence, and so on. Such risks should be legally addressed. On the other hand, Internet freedom has become a natural value for users, and any attempt to introduce regulations will meet with serious resistance. The introduction of any measures needs public support. It is possible to start with regulations with a more limited effect, such as restricting the use of mobile phones in class, a measure that more and more European countries are introducing and which is meeting with support from citizens.

46

Funded by
the European Union

Although the topics that are discussed in social media are broadly in line with the debates in the mainstream media, TikTok and to a degree Instagram are turning into an alternative forum in which the issues are approached in a much more unrestrained manner. The main difference between the mainstream and these social networks is in the degree of exercised self-restraint by the speakers: in the latter it is much, much lower, especially when it comes to radical right actors. The lack of self-restraint creates an atmosphere of authenticity and even some intimacy, which apparently is attractive to many users. Generally, the decreasing levels of self-restraint in major elements of the public sphere is a problem for liberal democracy, because this regime is based on the understanding that even powerful majorities are constrained by (self-imposed) constitutional, legal and conventional rules.

Bibliography

- Anonymous author** (2023). *“The Left: Matt with the pawn! You’ve all seen this clip, right?”*. Glasove: <https://glasove.com/novini/levitsata-mat-s-peshkata-vsichki-ste-gledali-tozi-klip-nali> (last checked on 15th May 2025)
- Anonymous author** (2024). *Vanya Grigorova: I support the mining blockade*. Safe News: <https://safenews.bg/vanya-grigorova-podkrepyam-blokadata-na-minorite/> (last checked on 15th May 2025)
- Todorov, M.** (2024). *Velichie Petitions Constitutional Court Demanding Total or Partial Annulment of Elections*. BTA: <https://www.bta.bg/en/news/bulgaria/777754-velichie-petitions-constitutional-court-demanding-total-or-partial-annulment-of-> (last checked on 15th May 2025)
- Todorov, M.** (2024). *Vazrazhdane Boast Own Role in Formation of New EP Group*. BTA: <https://www.bta.bg/en/news/bulgaria/706463-vazrazhdane-boast-own-role-in-formation-of-new-ep-group> (last checked on 15th May 2025)

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Croatia

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	Final draft
Author(s):	Ana Matan, University of Zagreb; Leon Cvrtila, University of Ljubljana; Matej Mikašinović-Komšo, University of Zagreb
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, Szilvia Horváth, and Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Emre Erdoğan (Istanbul Bilgi University)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Croatia: EP Election Results	5
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	7
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	7
Section 2: Croatia: Political profiles	10
# Centre-Right feed	12
# Far Right feed	15
# Red-Green feed	18
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	22
Section 3: Croatia: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	24
# Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	24
# Notes on the organic profiles	25
# Differences Observed Over Time	28
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok.....	31
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	32
Section 4: Croatia: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	33
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	33
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram.....	34
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	35
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	36
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	37
# AI Generated Content	39
Section 5: Croatia: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	40
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time.....	40
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate.....	40
#Emotional mechanisms	41
#Video Typologies.....	41
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	42
# Discussion on most interesting videos.....	48
Concluding section.....	50
# What was Europe about and why vote? (Social Contract)	50
# Populist mobilisation	51
# Conclusions.....	51

Bibliography 52

Croatia: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

The 2024 European Parliament (EP) elections in Croatia were marked by “electoral fatigue”, taking place not even two months after the 17 April national parliamentary elections. There was a historically low voter turnout (21,35%), making Croatia the member state with the lowest turnout. The results mostly followed the national parliament election results, with the centre-right ruling party Hrvatska demokratska zajednica (HDZ, Croatian Democratic Union) reinforcing its position as the party with the most MEPs. Additionally, the far-right party Domovinski pokret (DP, Homeland Movement) rode on its surprise electoral success and entrance into the government, receiving one MEP mandate. Key insights from the monitoring are: 1) the centre-right and far-right campaigns were mostly a continuation of the same style, content, and topics which dominated the national parliamentary elections, focusing more on national issues; 2) the red-green campaigns shifted gears between elections, focusing more on EU policy and the dangers coming from the far-right; and 3) despite the content similarity between TikTok and Instagram, the former proved to have a more agile algorithm, catching quickly on user preferences and providing political content more aggressively.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Izbori za Europski parlament (EP) u Hrvatskoj održani su u atmosferi “političkog umora”, ni dva mjeseca nakon državnih parlamentarnih izbora 17. travnja. Birački odabir je bio povijesno nizak - samo 21,35% - što je Hrvatsku svrstalo u državu članicu EU s najmanjim odazivom birača. Rezultati europskih izbora su više-manje pratili rezultate parlamentarnih izbora. Vladajuća stranka Hrvatska demokratska zajednica (HDZ) učvrstila je svoju poziciju stranke s najviše zastupnika u Europskom parlamentu. Dodatno, krajnje desna stranka Domovinski pokret (DP) zajahala je na iznenađujućem izbornom uspjehu i ulasku u Vladu, dobivši jedan europarlamentarski mandat. Ključni uvidi iz praćenja kampanje su: 1) kampanje desnog centra i krajnje desnice uglavnom su bile nastavak istog stila, sadržaja i tema koje su dominirale nacionalnim parlamentarnim izborima, više se fokusirajući na nacionalna pitanja; 2) lijeve i zelene kampanje mijenjale između izbora, fokusirajući se više na politiku EU i opasnosti koje dolaze od krajnje desnice; i 3) unatoč sličnosti sadržaja između TikToka i Instagrama, prvi je pokazao agilniji algoritam koji je brzo reflektirao korisničke preferencije te je češće nudio politički sadržaj.

Section 1: Croatia: EP Election Results

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

Croatia has 12 seats in the European Parliament, and the election results closely follow the 17 April 2024 national parliamentary election results. The longstanding ruling party, the centre-right *Hrvatska demokratska zajednica* (HDZ, Croatian Democratic Union), received 35,13% of the vote (an increase of 12,41% from 2019), increasing their EP seat count from 4 to 6, mostly at the expense of single candidates from smaller parties. The main opposition party, *Socijaldemokratska partija* (SDP, the Social Democratic Party), obtained 25,62% of the vote (6,91% more than in 2019), retaining their EP seat count of 4. The other two seats were filled by the Green Party *Možemo!* (We Can!), which got 5,93% of the vote, and the nationalist, far-right party *Domovinski pokret* (DP, Homeland Movement), which received 8,84% of the vote. The biggest electoral losers include the populist party *Živi Zid* (ŽZ, Living Wall), and the independent populist candidate Mislav Kolakušić, who formed the *Pravo i pravda* (PiP, Law and Justice) party. Despite receiving 13,55% of the vote in 2019 (5,66% for *Živi zid*, and 7,89% for Mislav Kolakušić), they now gained only 2,98% votes altogether, which is a decrease of 10,57%. *Istarski demokratski sabor* (Istrian Democratic Assembly, IDS), a centre-liberal regionalist party, held one seat in the previous EP session but lost it this time with 5,65% of the vote. *Most* (The Bridge), a prominent parliamentary right-wing party, was hopeful to win a seat finally but fell short of this goal with 4,02% of the vote. Finally, a particular case to point out is Nina Skočak, a prominent Croatian TikTok influencer working for the European Union. Participating for the first time in an election, her independent list "Gen Z", which targeted youthful voters, won 4,06% of the total vote, failing to win a seat. Several candidates won their seats via Croatia's preferential vote system (which allows voters to single out a preferred candidate, no matter their position on the list), these being Tonino Picula (SDP), Ivana Kekin (Možemo), who gave her seat to Gordan Bosanac, and Stephen Nikola Bartulica (DP). In summary, there was little surprise with the results, and the MEP seat distribution now generally reflects the seat distribution of the Croatian parliament, which was not the case during the previous EP session.

Results by national party – 2024-2029

Croatia – Official results

Figure 1. Results by national party

Percentage of votes

National Parties

HDZ – Hrvatska demokratska zajednica

Koalicija 'SDP' – Koalicija 'SDP' (Socijaldemokratska partija Hrvatske, Centar, Dalija Orešković I Ljudi S Imenom I Prezimenom, Građansko-Liberalni Savez, Hrvatska seljačka stranka)

DP – Domovinski pokret

Možemo! – Možemo! – Politička platforma

IDS-DDI – Coalition Istarski demokratski sabor – Dieta democratica Istriana (Demokrati, Hrvatska Narodna Stranka – Liberalni Demokrati, Hrvatska

socijalno-liberalna stranka, Istarski demokratski sabor – Dieta democratica Istriana, Istarska Stranka Umirovljenika – Partito Istriano Dei Pensionati, Nezavisna Platforma Sjevera, Narodna stranka – Reformisti, Primorsko Goranski Savez, Lista Za Rijeku, Socijaldemokrati, Samostalna demokratska srpska stranka, Unija Kvarnera)

Other parties – Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

National Election Results and Party Affiliations

The crucial takeaways from the EP election results are: 1) the reinforcement of the ruling party HDZ; 2) the disappearance of several smaller parties; and 3) the entrance of Croatia's far-right party DP into the EP. The results show that the dominant Croatian political and ideological direction remains tethered to the pro-EU centre-right, spearheaded by HDZ. Notably, HDZ increased its seat count from 4 to 6, capitalizing on showcasing how Croatia developed under HDZ and the EU. Meanwhile, SDP, its primary political opponent, remained at 4 seats. As HDZ was previously tied with SDP in MEP seats, this change confirms HDZ's position as Croatia's strongest political party, holding power since 2016. Additionally, this consolidation of power resulted in a relative loss of seats filled by smaller parties; previously 4, now only 2 – the Green party *Možemo* and the far-right party DP. HDZ continued its campaign from the parliamentary elections, focusing on its own successes and projecting an image of stability, while SDP focused on EU policy and values. *Možemo* also campaigned on various policy issues, as well as a hard stance against the far-right's influence and impact on the EU. DP focused its campaign on national issues, elaborating on its supposed role as the only authentic Croatian option that endorses Croatian national interests in the EU.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Croatia

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

Given that the EP elections followed shortly after the national parliament elections, they served as additional evidence of shifts in political trends that had already been detected and strengthened existing relations. Notably, all smaller party MEPs lost their seats – Mislav Kolakušić and Ivan Vilibor Sinčić represented PiP, Ladislav Ilčić came from the far-right conservative party *Hrvatski suverenisti* (HS, the Croatian Sovereignists), and Valter Flego represented IDS.

The most prominent HDZ candidate was, by far, current Prime Minister Andrej Plenković, appearing in almost all the campaign content despite never intending to sit as MEP. The second most prominent MEP candidates (at the time also sitting) were Sunčana Glavak and Željana Zovko. Other HDZ candidates who were elected (Tomislav Sokol, Karlo Ressler, Davor Ivo Stier, Nikolina Brnjac) were not as prominent in social media campaigns.

On the red-green side of the spectrum, the most prominent candidate on TikTok and Instagram was Biljana Borzan, an incumbent MEP from SDP, a member of the *Socialists & Democrats* group in the EP. Besides Biljana Borzan, other prominent candidates from SDP were Fred Matić and Tonino Picula, but they were not as present on TikTok and Instagram. Tonino Picula was elected as MEP despite holding last place on the SDP list (won via preferential votes) and being publicly critical of his party during the campaign. The Green party *Možemo* was mainly promoting the candidates who were first and second on the list for the EP – Gordan Bosanac and Jelena Miloš. Ivana Kekin, as a popular national MP from *Možemo*, participated actively in the campaign, even though she was last on the list. In the end, Ivana Kekin got the most preferential votes but did not consume her mandate, which instead went to Gordan Bosanac.

The remaining seat went to DP, which rose in prominence in the national parliamentary elections, receiving enough mandates to enter the government coalition with HDZ. Still, they retained a separate EP election campaign (while sharply scaling back criticism of HDZ compared to their recent campaign in the national elections). Riding on the wave of national electoral success, DP pushed several politicians as their EP election candidates, including Ivan Penava, Stipo Mlinarić, and Stephen Bartulica. Of the three, Stephen Bartulica became the most relevant candidate, winning a seat through preferential votes. This win was achieved despite a series of pre-election controversies and scandals surrounding Bartulica, which forced DP to take a more defensive campaign. Notably, major internal developments did not occur during the EP elections but several months later, on 31 August. After several months of internal conflicts, internal party elections were held, resulting in several members of the party resigning their party affiliations, including Stephen Bartulica, now no longer a member of DP. Additionally, this divide also resulted in the official TikTok profile of DP being deleted. What remained of the DP continued to support the HDZ government.

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

Croatia - Constitutive session

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PfE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
HDZ	34.60%	6									6
Koalicija 'SDP'	25.96%		4								4
DP	8.82%				1						1
Možemo!	5.92%						1				1
IDS-DDI	5.61%										0
Other parties	19.09%										0
	100.00%	6	4	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	12

HDZ > EPP: NIKOLINA BRNJAC, SUNČANA GLAVAK, KARLO RESSLER, TOMISLAV SOKOL, DAVOR IVO STIER, ŽELJANA ZOVKO

SDP > S&D: BILJANA BORZAN, ROMANA JERKOVIĆ, PREDRAG FRED MATIĆ, TONINO PICULA

Možemo! > Greens/EFA: GORDAN BOSANAC

DP > ECR: STEPHEN NIKOLA BARTULICA

National Parties

HDZ - Hrvatska demokratska zajednica

Koalicija 'SDP' - Koalicija 'SDP' (Socijaldemokratska partija Hrvatske, Centar, Dalija Orešković I Ljudi S Imenom I Prezimenom, Građansko-Liberalni Savez, Hrvatska seljačka stranka)

DP - Domovinski pokret

Možemo! - Možemo! - Politička platforma

IDS-DDI - Coalition Istarski demokratski sabor - Dieta democratica Istriana (Demokrati, Hrvatska Narodna Stranka - Liberalni Demokrati, Hrvatska socijalno-liberalna stranka, Istarski demokratski sabor - Dieta democratica Istriana, Istarska Stranka Umirovljenika - Partito Istriano Dei Pensionati, Nezavisna Platforma Sjevera, Narodna stranka - Reformisti, Primorsko Goranski Savez, Lista Za Rijeku, Socijaldemokrati, Samostalna demokratska srpska stranka, Unija Kvarnera)

Other parties - Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

● EPP - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)

● S&D - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament

● PfE - Patriots for Europe

● ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group

● Renew Europe - Renew Europe Group

● Greens/EFA - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance

● The Left - The Left group in the European Parliament - GUE/NGL

● ESN - Europe of Sovereign Nations

● NI - Non-attached Members

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

9

Section 2: Croatia: Political profiles

This section discusses the differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

Political content on the three synthetic profiles confirmed that the far-right had a strong presence in EP election campaigns. Far-right content commonly appeared on centre-right and far-right feeds, especially in the case of the far-right synthetic profile, containing negative portrayals of the LGBTIQ+ community, migrants, and globalist influences. The red-green profiles did not see many occurrences of right-wing content. However, the red-green campaign commonly referred to the far-right, insisting they pose a danger to the EU, democracy, and various vulnerable groups. The centre-right campaign portrayed the EU in a positive light, but only as a factor of prosperity for Croatia, while being mostly uninterested in its democratic values. Lastly, the red-green profile received content on defending the Green Deal, democracy, women's and minority rights in the EU, as well as policy advocacy for housing, small farmers, railway infrastructure and youth participation in EU politics.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

Figure 4: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

The centre-right profile's feed was highly diversified regarding party appearances on TikTok. Naturally, HDZ took up most of the attention, but the left-wing *Rivers of Justice* coalition took up second place, with far-right DP in fourth place and left-green *Možemo* in fifth. While some of these appeared through campaign videos for the EP election, a large part of their presence was as 'leftovers' from Croatia's parliamentary election. Notably, TikTok also featured a large presence of *Fidesz*, mostly with the appearance of Viktor Orban. The German CDU was also very prominent, though mostly through its connections with the EPP group. Other than that, most other international parties appeared as part of the general news content. The Instagram feed was somewhat different, with less emphasis on far-right parties and more of a focus on HDZ and its EPP campaign allies. Diverse Croatian parties also appeared, but again, mostly as 'leftovers' from the parliamentary election.

This was not the case with the far-right profile, which revealed a more condensed and stable number of political parties. Despite both dominantly showing the *Homeland Movement Party (Domovinski Pokret)*, there was a notable difference between TikTok and Instagram feeds. The Instagram feed included non-far-right political parties as some of the more frequent accounts, such as *The Bridge (Most)*, the *Croatian Democratic Union (HDZ)*, as well as *Možemo! (We Can!)*. On the other hand, TikTok's feed dominantly showed DP, with other parties' content appearing much more infrequently.

As for the red-green account, both TikTok and Instagram were expectedly focused on *Možemo*, followed by a selection of other European left-wing and green parties. This is notably more pronounced on Instagram, as TikTok also features a variety of centrist, right-wing and even far-right parties, though of course in lesser amounts than left-wing parties. Other than a focus on the few main left-green parties (*Možemo*, *Greens-EFA*), there is a notable variation of parties appearing between TikTok and Instagram, although the ideological profile still tends left with a slight right-wing tendency on TikTok

Centre-Right feed

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The centre-right synthetic profile initially faced an influx of content related to national issues, largely focused on the recently held national parliamentary elections. However, this content soon vanished, giving space for a noticeable uptick in EU and EP-related content, which would eventually overrun the feed as the elections closed in, only to fade in presence after the elections concluded. The feed is filled with campaign videos from Croatian actors (mostly HDZ and its political candidates) and EU actors, such as EPP’s Ursula von der Leyen and Manfred Weber. In the latter’s case, the observed content revolved around inciting users to vote, giving reasons such as: “If you won’t vote, someone else will vote for you”, and “Stem the tide of populism and fascism”. Croatian content was, in turn, dominated mainly by the HDZ campaign with the slogan “Hrvatska snažna i važna” (“Croatia, strong and important”), which did not share EPP’s campaign direction of emphasizing the democratic importance of the EU. Instead, it focused on Croatia and the direct benefits that it enjoys due to the prosperity brought by EU membership. These benefits would then be commonly framed as the direct result of the successful work of HDZ, equating EU benefits with HDZ benefits. Additionally, HDZ often presented its rule as a major contributor to Croatia’s alleged respect and influence within the EU.

As most HDZ political candidates have not opened a TikTok account, its campaign was largely dominated by Andrej Plenković’s profile, which he opened just three months before the EP elections. Nevertheless, the account swiftly rose in popularity, becoming one of the most followed and viewed accounts among all political options. Interestingly, HDZ’s content featured a split between moderate and stronger right-wing views, depending on the candidate. While Andrej Plenković and Sunčana Glavak attempted to present themselves as moderate candidates, Željana Zovko and Tomislav Sokol would often insist on the importance of religion for society or espouse anti-LGBTIQ+ opinions. Personal addresses and walkabouts were the most common formats and a couple of professionally produced

campaign videos. HDZ's campaign was mostly a continuation of the Croatian parliamentary elections campaign, with similar topics.

Despite focusing on centre-right content, there was a noticeable influx of far-right content, especially in the second half of the data-gathering period. For instance, Mislav Kolakušić and Marin Miletić (*The Bridge*) suddenly became very prominent on the TikTok feed the week before the elections. Also, a significant amount of political content was not directly related to EP elections, which mostly focused on the conflicts in Ukraine and Gaza. Campaigns for other national elections appeared, e.g. the US and UK. Outside of political candidates and campaigns, various pro-Russian propaganda efforts and conspiracy theories started to pop up in the feed, mostly related to the war in Ukraine, e.g. the narrative that NATO is preparing a ground operation in Ukraine or painting the whole conflict as a U.S. imperialist proxy war. The content relating to Gaza was largely pro-Palestinian, with an interesting influx of Irish politicians weighing in on the matter, resulting in general Irish politics being present in the feeds for the rest of the data-gathering period (likely stimulated by Ireland's local elections held on 7 June). Content on Ukraine was mostly pro-Ukrainian, though pro-Russian content was also present, along with some clear attempts at disinformation and propaganda, such as the claim that Turkey recently exited NATO. Overall disinformation cases started to appear more frequently on TikTok and Instagram after the elections, which may be attributed to the platforms dropping election-safeguarding efforts the moment they concluded.

Far-Right feed

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

While the centre-right synthetic profile took some time before showing political content, the far-right synthetic profile highlighted the alarming ease with which a user's feed can become dominated by far-right content. Mere four days after the start of monitoring, the feed was filled with such rhetoric. The content primarily came from official politician's accounts, such as DP and their politicians Ivan Penava, Stipo Mlinarić, Stephen Bartulica, Mislav Kolakušić (independent, but shared a list with DP), Karolina Vidović Krišto (*Determination and Justice*)

Their content frequently contained anti-migrant and anti-LGBTIQ+ topics, encapsulated within a narrative that emphasized the importance of Croatia, its values, and its people. Another common topic related to anti-globalism, notably through criticism of the EU and HDZ, including Prime Minister Andrej Plenković. DP also sometimes participated in this criticism despite being in a government coalition with HDZ. While the EU was criticized for forcing its agenda and needs upon the Croatian people, the Prime Minister was accused of not representing national Croatian interests nor Croatian citizens, but rather the interests of the aforementioned international organizations. Such accusations would be juxtaposed with an emphasis on Croatia's and Croatian citizens' positive aspects, with special attention being given to the fact that only far-right politicians represent authentic political options. Other topics, present in smaller quantities, referred to misogynistic and anti-Muslim content.

Outside of these, some politicians posted content that was often suffused with disinformation and conspiracies. Of note is Mislav Kolakušić (and to some extent DP and their politicians), whose content frequently referred to the COVID-19 pandemic, vaccines, the war in Ukraine and the Israel-Palestine conflict. Regarding conspiracy theories, he often referred to the Great Reset, the Great Replacement, and the establishment of a digital dictatorship. All three conspiracies have in common that they accuse globalist political elites and the EU of deliberately destroying national politics and societies, in order to

establish a single globalist state and introduce a dictatorship in which personal civil liberties would be completely abolished.

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

These findings reveal the overall strong presence of both the nationalist and far right on TikTok and Instagram. Despite the smaller number of unique political parties, their content dominated the far-right Instagram and TikTok feed. However, there was a notable difference between TikTok and Instagram feeds, where the Instagram feed included non-far-right political parties as some of the more frequent accounts. On the other hand, TikTok’s feed dominantly showed DP, with other parties’ content appearing rarely. Additionally, it demonstrates that these political options take digital avenues of political communication and dissemination seriously since they bypass traditional media gatekeepers, allowing for direct contact with potential voters.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Red-Green feed

The synthetic red-green profile's content consisted mostly of campaign videos or speeches from red-green parties and candidates. They were very slow to pick up political or any other content relevant to the EU before intensifying as the campaign picked up and died again after the elections.

18

The videos most similar to typical TikTok influencer videos were those made by Nina Skočak, a MEP candidate who is herself an influencer. The profile received not only her MEP campaign videos but also old non-political videos about her everyday activities, especially her apartment renovation in Brussels, a series of videos showing each step of the renovation process. The European Greens also had their attempts to make influencer-type videos where young women spoke about EP issues, but those were far less successful. The red-green profile followed two political content creators in English, *Barely Informed* and *RoteRote* that were interesting and informative, but their reach was also very modest compared to that of Nina Skočak’s whose video of young men trying a menstrual pain simulator has more than 2 million views.

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

The European level and foreign content received by the synthetic red-green profile were focused on two main points: the threat of the far right and policy issues such as the Green Deal, inequality and Palestine. The European Greens and their Spitzenkandidat Terry Reintke connected the far right to Putin, offering evidence that the far right has been financed by Russia and presented this combined threat as the biggest threat both to the EU and the Green Deal. Although some criticism against the present Commission’s president did surface in the European Greens videos, the main line of the EU political battle was against the far right, and the Greens’ support for Ursula von der Leyen came as no surprise at all. Spanish Sumar and Irish MEP Clare Daly represented the Left in the EP. Both had a lot of pro-Palestine videos, but Clare Daly was by far the most critical of the present EU policy and its leadership. Sumar and the official Left in the EP videos also had a lot of anti-far right (anti-fascist videos), as well as pro-workers, pro-women’s rights and pro-immigrants videos from Spain. The synthetic profile was getting very few videos from the Socialists and Democrats, and those were mainly about protecting social and women’s rights.

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Regarding strictly Croatian content, along with Nina Skočak’s very successful TikTok videos, the *Možemo* campaign videos were also compatible with the short video format. They were showing candidates in real-life situations, but with a political message. The candidates travelled on a night train, eating sandwiches, wearing pyjamas to make a point about the need for modernisation of the railways

21

as environmentally friendly public transport. The videos showed candidates visiting small farms to make a point about the need for the EU to support small food producers and conversations between them at a Pride parade in Zagreb about the evolution of LGBTIQ+ rights in Croatia. There were also sketches and other filmed content about the danger of the far right for women's rights and minority rights and a bit of a negative campaign against the populist and conservative MEPs Kolakušić, Sinčić and Ilčić (who lost their seats in the end). SDP and their lead candidate Biljana Borzan had a campaign centred on her achievements in the EP regarding consumer rights and was not so anti-far right oriented.

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

The most prominent politician for the centre-right profile was Andrej Plenković on both TikTok and Instagram, though far more relatively prominent on TikTok. Plenković's campaign colleagues from HDZ, Željana Zovko, Sunčana Glavak, Tomislav Sokol, and Karlo Ressler were also prominent, though more so on Instagram than TikTok (as some of them did not have official TikTok accounts). Plenković's EPP colleague, Ursula von der Leyen, was also highly prominent on both feeds. Zoran Milanović also retains a high position among visible politicians on both feeds, but mainly as a presence in general news broadcasts and as Plenković's regular (hostile) interlocutor. A number of far-right politicians, such as DP's Stjepo Bartulica, Josip Dabro, Stipo Mlinarić Čipe, and Ivan Penava, were noticeably present on the TikTok feed, though less so in campaign videos as just in general news broadcasts. Notably, Viktor Orbán and his foreign minister, Peter Szijjarto were present in campaign videos on TikTok. Vladimir Putin took second place on TikTok, though largely as part of general news broadcasts and content related to the war in Ukraine. Some left-wing politicians were also prominent on TikTok, such as Tomislav Tomašević and Gordan Bosanac from *Možemo*. Instagram featured a lesser diversity of politicians. Aside from HDZ's campaign candidates, the feed was mostly populated by foreign politicians appearing in general news content. Notably, Nina Škočak was highly prominent on Instagram.

Comparing TikTok and Instagram feeds when it comes to far-right politicians' presence, similar conclusions can be given as when it comes to political parties. On TikTok, dominant politicians were all connected to DP, with little appearance from centre-right (Andrej Plenković, Prime Minister) and centre-left politicians (Gordan Bosanac, *Možemo!*). On Instagram, however, politicians who did not belong to far-right actors appeared more frequently, such as Marin Miletić (The Bridge), Andrej Plenković (HDZ, Prime Minister) and Nina Škočak (Independent). Therefore, TikTok's feed better attuned itself with Croatian far-right options, showing political content that rarely entered centre-right and centre-left content and political or international narratives. Instagram, despite also dominantly showing Croatian far-right content, often provided content from other Croatian political options.

Lastly, regarding the red-green profile, *Možemo*'s Gordan Bosanac is the overall most prominent politician, even though he takes second place on TikTok, the first place taken over by independent Nina Škočak, who takes third place on Instagram. Clare Daly takes third place on TikTok while also being highly prominent on Instagram. Other *Možemo* politicians prominently appear on both TikTok and Instagram, including Sandra Benčić, Ivana Kekić, Jelena Miloš and Tomislav Tomašević. Other European left-wing politicians are quite prominent on both feeds (e.g. Terry Reintke), though TikTok features a stronger presence of particular right-wing politicians, e.g. Mislav Kolakušić.

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Croatia

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Croatia

Section 3: Croatia: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content and mention the activity of the organic profiles.

The common experience is that there is a difference between TikTok's and Instagram's feed algorithms. Notably, TikTok's algorithm was quicker and more efficient in providing political content, as opposed to Instagram's, which took some time to train, and even after four weeks, it showed political content in limited amounts. However, when political content did appear on Instagram, it was clear that it matched the one seen on TikTok, showing that there is limited platform difference when it comes to the type of content. The frequency of the political content also changed over time, becoming more apparent in the week right before the elections.

Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

There was a commonly observed difference between TikTok and Instagram when it came to political content availability. Namely, all three researchers faced some initial resistance while training the profiles' algorithms, before they started to show the appropriate type of political content. This proved to be harder for Instagram than it was for TikTok. Based on the monitoring experience, it appears that TikTok's algorithms are much more aggressive and more susceptible to directing the user towards political content if they detect user interest. On the other hand, Instagram's algorithm is much "weaker", and training it to display political content was demanding.

The centre-right profile was decently focused on its designated political orientation. It took some time to train the algorithms towards political content in general, but the feeds performed exactly as expected when it was done. However, this required extra effort as the researcher had to continuously mark content as (un)desirable, using additional controls afforded by the platforms.

As for the far-right profile, it became clear that far-right political content is available on both TikTok and Instagram, with limited content made for a specific social media platform. However, there were fundamental differences between the platforms in terms of quantity and ease of access. Of the two platforms, TikTok proved far more relevant as a social media platform for far-right content, providing it after just four days of searching for appropriate profiles, such as DP, and liking their posts. Upon doing so, for the remainder of the monitoring period, the far-right profile had its TikTok feed filled with DP's content and those of other related politicians and parties. On the other hand, Instagram required work to provide appropriate content, including manually marking content as undesirable or desirable.

For the red-green profile, Instagram also proved to be more difficult to force into providing appropriate content than TikTok. However, once Instagram started to show the profile's preferred content, there was slight difference between it and TikTok, especially towards the climax of the EP campaign. Also, the red-green profiles were receiving very little right-wing content. The TikTok algorithm especially was quick to show similar green and left ideological content from other countries and other languages (UK, France, Spain, Germany, Austria, and the US) unrelated to the EP elections rather than different ideological content related to the EP elections.

Notes on the organic profiles

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Whereas the synthetic profiles attempted to emulate specific voter profiles, the organic ones had no restrictions about viewed political content. As a result, the feed consisted of incoherent combinations of political content, coming from political candidates ranging from the far left, all the way to the far right. Some of the observed content came from politicians of various ideological backgrounds, such as Andrej Plenković (HDZ, Prime Minister), Zoran Milanović (President of Croatia, nominally independent though strongly tied to SDP), Ivan Pernar (Ivan Pernar’s party), Ričard (independent joke candidate), Marin Miletić (The Bridge), Mislav Kolakušić (Law and Justice), Karolina Vidović Krišto (far-right Determination and Justice), Ivica Todorčić (Pametno), Gordan Bosanac (Možemo), Ivana Kekin (Možemo), etc. Additionally, two GUE/NGL MEP’s, Clare Daly, and to a slightly lesser extent Mick Wallace, were a disproportionately common occurrence.

The increased focus on political content of all types meant that the organic profile was swift on the uptake, but as a consequence, it was not stable. Notably, centre-right content was limited in TikTok and Instagram organic feeds, generally tending towards the political fringes, including occurrences of far-right disinformation and conspiracy theories. In general, the breadth of organic profile topics was very wide, perhaps even a bit chaotic. Particularly, we can point out the quite common occurrence of content

related to the Ukraine and Gaza conflicts. However, the center-right content remained dominant throughout the monitoring period, increasing in frequency as the election date approached and continuing to prevail even after the elections.

The red-green organic profiles were remarkably similar to the synthetic ones, receiving predominantly political content from *Možemo*, the European Greens, and the UK Green Party. This type of content appeared evenly throughout the monitoring period, showing similar trends to the center-right content. It slowly increased in prevalence as the election date approached and continued to remain relevant and dominant after the election date had passed.

More than half of the content was in English and other foreign languages (German, French) from accounts of the EU party families or other countries. In Croatian content, videos from *Možemo* and the independent Nina Skočak were dominant.

In addition, the feeds were also filled with a variety of meme videos, which were made by non-political citizen accounts. What is interesting is the fact that these meme videos frequently refer to politics and politicians. These meme videos always made fun of and criticized politicians, but sometimes, they would positively portray a specific politician in opposition to others. An example is a video shared by the official account of Ivan Pernar, in which his face is digitally edited onto Heath Ledger's Joker from the movie *Batman: The Dark Knight*, as he is blowing up the hospital.

This was not the experience of the organic profile of the researcher who dealt with the synthetic radical-right account. The political content of the organic accounts remained limited and infrequent throughout the entire monitoring period, peaking a week before the election date before returning to its usual lower content amount.

Between the two social media platforms, TikTok proved to be much more sensitive, changing its content more quickly. On the other hand, Instagram proved to be fairly difficult for one researcher to train. After searching for political content for four weeks, the feed continued to be filled with entertainment and popular content.

Differences Observed Over Time

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Croatia

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Croatia over time

At first, the profiles provided no political content on their own. However, once the researchers trained them to “understand” the simulated user preferences, the frequency of political content started to rise, eventually dwarfing all other forms of content. For all the researchers, this was especially noticeable on Instagram. Throughout the first week of data collection, the political content was sparse despite all the efforts to steer the algorithm towards such content. The second week saw a slight increase in political content, and only in the third week did it rise to an appropriate level. On the other hand, TikTok also took some time to start showing political content but started performing decently by the end of the first week.

Regarding more specific insight into content change over time, for the centre-right profile, both TikTok and Instagram experienced a noticeable uptick of political and EP campaign content during the third week and a sharp downturn of EP campaign content in the final week. This was attended by a diversification in the appearance of individual actors and parties, as shown in Figure 21, driven in part by the new appearance of far-right content on TikTok and Instagram. The centre-right profile is distinct in experiencing such a boost, which did not appear for far-right and left-green profiles; for these two accounts, the frequency and appearance of political accounts remained stable, with minor changes

over time. In general, the centre-right profile was prone to display actors that veer to either side of the political spectrum, which was not the case for the other two profiles that tended to stay within their own spheres. This was the case, again, for both TikTok and Instagram. The centre-right profile also experienced a notable dip in unique parties starting on day 20, the very day of the elections, most noticeably on TikTok. This is likely due to campaign content being deprioritized as soon as the election ended. The diversity recovered in the coming week as generalized political content resumed. As for political content, despite dropping in frequency in the final week, it remained decently present. Notably, disinformation and misinformation were more noticeable during the final week, primarily related to immigration and the war in Ukraine. As previously stated, this could be attributed to platforms immediately dropping their election-safeguarding efforts upon the end of the EP elections.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Similar trends were noticed on the red-green profiles. After some time spent training the algorithms, appropriate political content appeared, mainly from official political party and candidate profiles. The presence of official political content related to the EP elections lasted up until the elections concluded. After, EP campaign content slowly faded, being replaced by particular national politics videos (such as France, UK, Germany, and the USA).

As for the far-right accounts, the frequency of EP election content remained low (mostly revolving around MEP candidate promotion), even after a noticeable uptick during the second and third week. Instead, the content mostly focused on national politics and issues, alongside criticism and negative portrayal of vulnerable groups. Additionally, disinformation and conspiracy theories were abundant throughout the monitoring period, with no clear sign of frequency change.

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

Across all profiles, content remained overwhelmingly similar between TikTok and Instagram, showing that politicians and parties do not adjust their content to different age groups and communities. Content-wise, clear differences were detected between the profiles. Both the centre-right and green-red profiles received content promoting the EU's positive role in Croatia (social for centre-right, and democratic for

Funded by
the European Union

green-red). However, the far-right profile saw content that emphasized the importance of asserting Croatia's national will and interests in the EU. Anti-migrant and anti-LGBTIQ+ content were also present, though as minor occurrences in the case of red-green and centre-right profiles, and as more prominent on far-right profiles. Additionally, the far-right profile mostly saw content focused on Croatian topics, while the centre-right and green-red profiles saw a lot of international content related to the Ukraine-Russia and Israel-Gaza conflicts. Lastly, all researchers noted AI-generated content, but it was not a significant phenomenon.

Regarding the frequency of specific political parties appearing, some differences were noted between the platforms. When comparing TikTok and Instagram feeds, TikTok's provided far-right content more frequently and stably, maintaining consistent content throughout the monitoring period. However, as stated previously, these numbers, while stable, never reached significant mention numbers, as was the case with the center-left and center-right content.

As for the red-green content, the differences between TikTok and Instagram were in the time frame in which they appeared. While the content appeared consistently throughout the monitored period (albeit in smaller quantities), on TikTok it was contained within the first half of the monitoring, dropping off in frequency in the second half. On Instagram, however, the red-green content remained stable and appeared in similar amounts during the monitoring period.

Lastly, the center-right content appeared the most on the organic accounts throughout the monitoring period and showed similar trends on both platforms. The only difference is that it reached higher mention peaks on Instagram than TikTok.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

The main difference between TikTok and Instagram is the sensitivity of their algorithms. TikTok is quicker and likelier in delivering users' ideologically preferred content, no matter where it comes from – national politics, EU politics, US politics, etc. TikTok appears to have more influencers and political commentators who are not present on Instagram. This is irrespective of whether it was a centre-right, red-green, or far-right profile. The content was, in general, similar across both platforms. Some researchers often saw the same videos between platforms, while others saw different videos on different platforms (although the themes and topics stayed the same).

Section 4: Croatia: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section we go through the themes and topics in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts simultaneously in the data gathering process for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

As previously stated, the frequency, direction, and nature of the observed topics greatly depended on the political background of the profile. Notably, the centre-right and red-green profiles had feeds with a positive outlook on the EU, while the far-right one contained a more critical, negative perception. However, most content framed their perception of the EU through domestic issues. For instance, the HDZ campaign extolled their own successes when talking about the prosperity granted by the EU, claiming they made Croatia better for all. However, HDZ's colleagues in the EPP took a different approach, with campaign videos focused on specific EU issues, such as the Green Deal, Social Europe, economy, defense, etc. What they did share with HDZ, however, was an attempt to project stability and continuity. HDZ's campaign mostly inspired boredom and slight annoyance as the campaign felt uninspired, pompous, and cliché, insisting on the same old.

Croatian content makers mostly disregarded making content on defense issues, NATO, and the Ukraine-Russia and Israel-Gaza conflict. However, centre-right and red-green profiles did see a decent amount of international content focused on these topics. As for the far-right profile, when such topics did appear on the feed, they were dominantly presented in a negative light, as conflicts which do not concern Croatia, and which are being pushed by globalist interests. This included criticizing the EU's supposed clandestine influence against Croatian authenticity, negative and aggressive disregard of "woke ideology", spreading conspiracy theories about migrants and EU politics, etc. The content would certainly evoke anxiety and fear in left-wing users, and anger amongst the right-wing ones, but for the researcher, it did not invoke any particular feelings as they are used to monitoring such topics.

The Croatian content in the red-green accounts' feed rarely included international topics besides the advocacy of Palestine's recognition. The Croatian content was more about advocacy for youth participation, consumer rights and women's and minority rights. The Green Deal and Social Europe were represented by videos in support of small farmers instead of support for big corporations, investment in railway infrastructure and EU investment in affordable housing. International topics were prominent in the content of EU and foreign origin appearing in the red-green profile account. The Green Deal here appeared often together with the threat of the far right and the war in Ukraine. International topics were also represented by the Israel-Gaza conflict. They included speeches made by the Irish PM and members of the *France Unbowed* party in the French Parliament, as well as testimonies and appeals of Jews who were against the war policies of Israel's government. The researcher found the content against Palestinian suffering to be most inspiring.

33

Funded by
the European Union

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

Content targeting vulnerable communities, including LGBTIQ+ and migrants, appeared only rarely for the centre-right and red-green profiles. It would only appear when far-right content found its way into their feeds (especially on the centre-right profile), or when particular centre-right politicians would occasionally espouse anti-LGBTIQ+ sentiments in the form of anti-woke discourse (e.g. Tomislav Sokol of HDZ). This aligns with their overall pro-EU positions and is seen as the clearest in the red-green profile. Rather than attacking vulnerable groups, *Možemo's* content frequently contained anti-racist, pro-migrant, pro-women's rights, and pro-LGBTIQ+ topics. Additionally, their content frequently criticized and confronted anti-migrant, misogynistic, and religious content, which promoted conservative social values, gender roles, and abortion restrictions.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 25: Distribution of common themes that appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

On the other hand, the far-right profile saw content that, while focusing dominantly on Croatia and domestic issues, revealed a political narrative deeply rooted in anti-globalist and national sovereign identities. Notably, discussions on gender were connected with anti-LGBTIQ+ themes, while talk of migrants usually portrayed them negatively, especially if they were of Muslim background. For anti-migrant content, the topic of the rapidly growing number of foreign workers from Nepal in Croatia was frequently discussed. These migrants were always portrayed negatively as a danger which would change and ruin Croatia. The far-right politicians and parties often called voters to action because they need to support the DP so that these groups can be stopped. As for anti-LGBTIQ+ content, this topic was commonly focused on the critique and dismissal of “woke ideology”. It was always presented as a socially dangerous idea, pushed onto Croatian society by foreign, globalist actors. As such, it is portrayed as something alien and unnatural to Croatia and needs to be suppressed as such so that the sanctity of traditional family structure and the safety of children can be preserved.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the distribution of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Content Related to Foreign Countries

Foreign content frequently appeared on the feed of the centre-right and red-green profiles, while being virtually non-existent in the far-right profile. Israel-Palestine and Russia-Ukraine conflicts were a very common topic, as well as NATO discussions (with both pro-NATO and anti-NATO content). This type of content did not just come from politicians and parties and other sources such as news channels, accounts, influencers, podcasts, and common users. When it came to the far-right profile, the very limited appearances of foreign content would always discuss current international wars and conflicts.

Other countries also often appeared in the observed content of the centre-right and red-green profiles. Frequently mentioned countries included the UK, France, Germany, Austria, USA, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Spain, Germany, etc. Their national politics were a common topic, such as the UK general elections, the Irish local elections, and the US presidential elections. Bosnian Herzegovinian as well as Serbian politics were prominent during the first two weeks of monitoring, likely due to the UN General Assembly's adoption of the Resolution on Srebrenica Genocide which was passed at the same time. Content related to Russia and China was not common, but when it appeared, they were usually presented as a threat in Western sources. There was also a notable amount of pro-Russian and pro-Chinese content (some labeled and state-controlled media), especially on the centre-right profile.

Foreign content, especially when it dealt with other countries, was often seen as interesting, since it provided a chance to distance oneself from the meticulous following of Croatian politics.

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

Current global conflicts were rarely mentioned by Croatian political actors, across all profiles. Despite this, the Ukraine-Russia and Israel-Gaza conflicts were prominent in the centre-right and red-green profiles, mostly through international content. The centre-right profiles had the highest frequency of such content, usually coming from various European politicians, journalists, activists, but also influencers. Interestingly, while content relating to the Israel-Gaza conflict remained dominantly pro-Palestinian, the content related to the Ukraine-Russia conflict contained a mixture of pro-Ukrainian and pro-Russian content, especially after the EP elections concluded.

Similarly to the centre-right profile, the red-green profile also received content related to these two conflicts. However, the Ukraine-Russia conflict had far less dedicated content when compared to the Israel-Palestine conflict. It appeared mostly in Clare Daly's speeches and *Renew's* campaign videos, several videos revealing connections between the European far-right and Russia/Putin, and a video of a panel discussion among candidates in Croatia. On the other hand, the Palestinian situation was very present, both in the appearances of the candidates and parties, but even more in the content related to other actors (e.g. recognition of Palestine by Ireland and Spain). Interestingly, defense and security were not only a prominent topic through Ursula von der Leyen and *Renew's* videos, but also as a way of perceiving European values, which were seen as something which needed to be defended against the far-right.

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024, Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

The exception to these trends was the far-right profile, which, again, had little content related to foreign affairs, countries, and conflicts. However, when these topics would appear, they would commonly be discussed from the Croatian perspective, and the danger posed by getting tangled up in the conflicts. Notably, a common point made by far-right politicians was that Croatia has no concerns in such conflicts, and that it should remain neutral in order to dodge any potential repercussions. This type of argumentation seems to belong to the principles of anti-globalist, national sovereignty, commonly associated with far-right political parties. Although seemingly pacifistic, this sentiment espouses inaction against Russian aggression, potentially playing into their geopolitical and international goals.

Threats to Equality and Diversity

As was previously touched upon, content related to threats to equality and diversity varied greatly, depending on the nature of the profile. These topics, both in their negative and positive portrayal, were minor for the centre-right profile, rarely appearing when far-right content (commonly anti-migrant) intruded into the feed. Some centre-right politicians would espouse anti-LGBTIQ+ opinions (e.g. Tomislav Sokol), but they were a minority amongst their centre-right peers, who would usually not even broach the topic.

Figure 29: Distribution of the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

More relevant to these topics were the red-green profile and the far-right profile, each approaching them differently. The red-green profile, for instance, had threats to equality and diversity as a constant theme in the feed’s content, which touched upon threats to women’s rights, LGBTIQ+ rights, and migrant rights. This mounted defense was not based on defending diversity as a European value, but rather on expressing anxiety in the face of the far-right threat, combined with the determination to fight for their continued existence. The researcher saw the sentiment expressed in this type of content as positive. On the flipside, far-right content frequently contained threats to equality and diversity. Anti-migrant and anti-LGBTIQ+ themes portrayed them as something foreign to traditional Croatian values and interests. Noteworthy was the fact that anti-LGBTIQ+ sentiment was focused on the critique and dismissal of “woke ideology”. The researcher did not emotionally respond, as the monitored content was approached in a professional and impartial manner. However, such content raised concerns over the future spread of anti-globalist and anti-EU political narratives, which could endanger European integration and democracy.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

AI content occasionally appeared across all three profiles, but it was of limited political significance as it was usually made for entertainment purposes. Its frequency also varied between the profiles, with the centre-right and far-right profiles rarely seeing AI content. Even when it was present, its nature would be entertaining and amusing, with no clear political goal. Examples include impersonations of various politicians (Andrej Plenković and Zoran Milanović in Croatia, Joe Biden, Vladimir Putin, and Xi Jinping internationally). The Croatian politicians would often be audio-visually edited into music videos where they would perform songs together. Additionally, their debates and public speeches would be edited into discussions of the best strategies to deploy while playing a popular mobile video game called *Brawl Stars*. An interesting exception to this trend occurred for the red-green profile, which not only saw a good deal of AI-generated content (such as AI-generated dancing cats), but also saw it being put into use for political purposes by the green party *Možemo*. They created an official AI-generated persona named Nitkolina (a pun on the common Croatian name Nikolina, with “*nitko*” meaning nobody), which was used to raise awareness on AI political manipulation. They also released AI-generated campaign songs. The uncertainty generated by not knowing whether the content they watched was AI or not caused some unease among the researchers.

Section 5: Croatia: Data Gathering –

Influence and appeal

This section is exploring the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. We use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process in the section.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

When it comes to the speed at which individual algorithms started filling the feed with political content, TikTok proved to be far quicker at identifying user preferences and providing appropriate content. The first few days provided no political content in the feed for both the red-green and far-right profiles. However, after just a few days of manually searching politics, their individual feeds started showing political content, which also aligns with the simulated political preferences. It is important to emphasize that the initial content was related to the national parliamentary elections, and not the EP elections.

On the other hand, Instagram proved to be much slower in showing political content and identifying user preferences for political content. All three researchers noticed that it showed less political content, even after a week and a half, and that training it to show appropriate political content was harder. However, when it finally started to show political content, it behaved similarly to TikTok, with one exception. Notably, it experienced less ideological diversity of political party and politician accounts regarding the center-left and center-right accounts. The far-right account, however, had the opposite case, with TikTok experiencing less diverse political content than on Instagram.

Timewise, as the profiles started to “understand” the simulated user preferences, the frequency of political content started to dominate all other forms of content. At first almost no political content was found during the initial days. Then it became more prevalent and noticeable around the second and third week. Even more importantly, this was the period in which EP election campaign content started to appear for all three profiles (with the small exception being the far-right profile, which still had a lower frequency of EP campaign content). This peaked at the end of the third week, and slowly reduced in frequency upon the EP elections finishing. After the EP elections, political content related mostly to post-election reporting, or more pertinent political events, such as the situation in France, upcoming UK elections, and US elections, with EP election campaign videos mostly disappearing from the feed.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

We believe that this type of content can certainly influence political debate. It enables immersion in attention-grabbing political narratives and interpretations which can also be passed on off-platform. The affordances of sharing and algorithmic distribution means that the information spreads rapidly. It is also clear that the platforms enable the spreading of all kinds of mis-and-disinformation and don't put enough effort to combat them, as they are clearly still very prevalent and readily available. We believe that all populations can be influenced by this type of content, whether directly or indirectly. But we are not sure that the short video format is suitable for policy debates or putting policy proposals on the political agenda. The short-video format is currently immensely popular among both political actors and

40

Funded by
the European Union

consumers of political messages. Thus, political narratives everywhere are starting to reflect the affordances of the short-video formats, privileging a particular style of messaging which is not very conducive to deliberation as envisioned by standard democratic models. It remains to be seen what the long-term consequences for the public sphere will be.

#Emotional mechanisms

For the centre-right profile, the most common emotion felt by the researcher was boredom and annoyance. The reason lies in the centre-right's party's (HDZ) EP elections campaign, which was mostly a rehash of their parliamentary election campaign where they mostly talked about the reasons why they are the best party and why Croatia is prospering under them. The researcher's verdict was that this campaign style failed to elicit any strong emotions – it was bland, uninspired, and repetitive. The most commonly detected emotion portrayed by the campaign was confidence. HDZ was trying to convey that everything was just fine, and that there is no need for any significant political change. Or, put differently, they tried to evoke a sense of normalcy and stability. Other, non-HDZ, content did elicit some emotion, namely the plethora of Gaza-related content fostered indignation and anger over the violence and destruction in Gaza.

Regarding the red-green profile, the researcher found the official campaign videos of the green/left parties to not be very interesting or engaging. In fact, they proved to be rather boring, but with a few exceptions. These exceptions, which were more emotionally engaging, were good speeches delivered by the Irish Prime Minister on Palestine, a member of the French parliament from the France Unbowed Party, and Yolanda Diaz in the Spanish Parliament. Outside of these cases, the Green UK campaign also left the researcher feeling good and optimistic. The emotions deployed in the videos varied. The main emotions in the videos by the left and green parties (The Left in the EP and the European Greens) were anxiety, worry, and even fear. The Socialists and Democrats videos featured less worrisome tones, while Claire Daly's videos were angry. Other actors, such as Ursula von der Leyen, mostly attempted to show a feeling of confidence.

For the far-right profile, the researcher didn't feel any particular emotions, as the monitored content was approached in a professional and impartial manner. However, placing oneself in the shoes of an average user, the observed far-right content would surely invoke a feeling of fear that irrevocable negative changes are coming for Croatia, threatening its very existence as we know it. This is clear from the commonly expressed and used emotions in the content: fear and anger. Fear was used when referring to dangerous groups for Croatian politics and society, such as foreign workers, migrants, LGBTIQ+ community, and EU. It acted as a method to convince voters that something has to be done about these changes, or else they would engulf Croatia. Conversely, anger was dominantly deployed when talking about the corrupt government and mainstream Croatian politics. It seems to have been used strategically to motivate and mobilize voters to support DP.

#Video Typologies

Amongst all the content seen across the three profiles, it became clear that politicians and parties favor certain types of content more. We list the commonly seen ones:

1. Campaign videos: videos produced by parties' campaigns, containing key political messaging, usually professionally shot and edited. Subtypes include:

41

Funded by
the European Union

- a) Campaign adverts: professionally produced short videos, usually consisting of a montage and voiceover, sometimes combined with direct addresses by candidates. Likely to have also aired elsewhere as a political advertisement, for example, on television, YouTube ads, and so on. Showcases core campaign messages, candidates, and slogans. They're also produced to convey specific emotions the campaigns focused on, for example, a sense of triumph and optimism in HDZ's campaign, pride in Croatia and fear over its future in DP's campaign, and fear of the far-right in red-green campaigns.
 - b) Personal addresses: an individual or a group of politicians addressing the viewer directly can be professionally shot and edited or just a selfie video. Depending on the candidate, it can just be sticking to regular campaign messaging or directed at some topics that a particular candidate finds important. It can sometimes also be more personalized, e.g. a meet-the-candidate type video.
 - c) Politicians in non-political situations: for example, playing sports, gardening, and so on.
2. TV clippings: short clips from television news reports or talk programmes featuring political themes, including politicians, journalists, pundits or citizens.
 3. Parliamentary clips: videos of politicians' speeches in various parliaments (EP or national). Often used to show a politician's highlight statements, jokes, or insults towards other politicians. The format often presents the politician in a positive light (smart, witty, being right), while the recipient of the statement (often unknown) is indirectly shown as incompetent, and being taught a lesson.
 4. Public event speeches: different politicians or officials giving speeches at various events or assemblies.
 5. Explainer videos: short educational content with professional graphics; rare in Croatian.
 6. Selfie videos: amateur, personal videos, usually in a casual setting, in which interested citizens discuss a specific political topic. Rarely appeared in the feeds.
 7. Podcast clips: short clips from video podcasts. Notably, they frequently featured far-right and alternative political candidates, such as Mislav Kolakušić (Pravo i pravda), Karolina Vidović Krišto (Odlučnost i pravednost (Determination and Justice)), and Stephen Bartulica (Domovinski pokret). The discussion would often include harsh criticism of the EU, attacks on vulnerable groups, and conspiracy theories regarding social engineering (Great Reset, Digital dictatorship, and Great Replacement).

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Narrative 1. "Croatia – strong and important" (*Hrvatska, snažna i važna*)

This was the slogan of center-right HDZ's EP election campaign. It tried to emphasize how the EU contributes to Croatia's empowerment and improvement, while Croatia became respected and influential in EU affairs. However, the content mostly focused on various ways Croatia developed in the past few years (i.e. during Andrej Plenković's rule since 2016). It mostly amounts to economic growth and various social, infrastructural, and security improvements. The narrative essentially claimed that

42

Funded by
the European Union

everything is good and right with Croatia, that it is on a stable path of development and growth, and that nothing needs to (politically) change (although it needs to be noted that any negative indicators and trends were conveniently ignored). It associates HDZ with political stability and normality, while occasionally castigating the opposition as trying to halt development and bring about chaos. It should be noted that this narrative was also central to HDZ's campaign for Croatian parliamentary elections in April; that is, HDZ mostly recycled its campaign. However, as for the audio-visual aspect, nothing in particular can be pointed out as interesting. The videos mostly focused on the speaking politicians themselves, with occasional montages of political gatherings and panoramic views of Croatia's landscapes, all to the background of uplifting music. The production was nothing special and did not differ from anything that might be seen on e.g. Croatian TV channels (in fact some campaign videos might've appeared both on TV and on Instagram/TikTok). In short, the researcher did not find it very convincing. In conclusion, when considering other Croatian videos and comparing them with non-Croatian ones, it appears that Croatia's short-form video culture is a bit underdeveloped, especially among the political class. Audio-visual forms still are not very well adapted to the format; for example, the video material doesn't adhere to the vertical aspect ratio but is still horizontal, the videos are too long, they deploy no attention-grabbing techniques, and so on.

Narrative 2. "Croatia First" (*Hrvatska na prvome mjestu*)

Despite not being the slogan of DP's EP electoral campaign, this slogan was present in posts made by their MEP candidate Stephen Nikola Bartulica (as part of the visual and as a hashtag). While not officially used in all DP content, this statement best encapsulates the overall political narrative espoused by the Croatian far-right political candidates.

This narrative presents all contemporary issues and challenges through a lens of Croatian national interests and ethnic population, which must be prioritized against globalist agenda. A good example of this narrative is a political commercial from Stephen Nikola Bartulica on TikTok, which contains the following quote: "*Fertile fields for Croatia, Croatia without gender ideology; safe borders, happy family, and a Christian identity...for a Europe of sovereign national states, with Croatia first!*" (in Croatian language, the word fertile, *rodno*, is the same for gender, *rod*). Common talking points of this narrative

44

include stating that fences need to be placed across Croatia's national borders, in order to prevent illegal immigrants from entering the country, criticism of foreigners who purchase real estate, mass arrival of foreign workers (usually Nepalese) instead of taking care of domestic workers, and criticism of the EU.

EU criticism acts as one of the most important aspects of this political narrative, and it may as well represent the crucial element in the far-right EP election campaign. Inside this narrative, the EU is presented as a malignant political entity towards national states and their interests, because it pushes a globalist agenda. This agenda is portrayed as not only unacceptable for Croatian interests, but also dangerous and destructive, since it aims to control all aspects of human lives (including diet practices). Often, far-right politicians (such as DP's Stephen Bartulica) would state that they will not *"sacrifice the Croatian truth, nor interests, at the altar of so-called European values."*, and that *"foreign ideologies and religions"* must be rejected. They would also name European influences as a form of *"ideological colonization of Croatia"* and promote conspiracy theories in which EU politics are actually a form of deliberate ethnic population replacement. It is important to note that this negative attitude and narrative against the EU is not passive, in the sense that they simply criticize it as a rhetorical tool to gain votes. DP's content actively states that it is important to *"jumpstart national, especially sovereignist, politics at the EU level."*, and put a stop to globalist influence.

domovinskipokret.hr
Hrvatska

Prati

Spremljeno Spremi u zbirku

Svidi mi se: 321

domovinskipokret.hr Hrvatice i Hrvati, izađite na EU izbore i podržite Domovinski pokret – nama su na prvome mjestu hrvatski nacionalni interesi, a ne interesi Bruxellesa!

Drage građanke i građani Republike Hrvatske! U Europskome parlamentu donose se zakoni koji određuju i kroje način života svih nas u Hrvatskoj. Pozitivne procese i promjene već smo započeli na razini državne politike, a sada je vrijeme da te nacionalne, prije svega suverenističke, politike pokrenemo i na razini Europske unije.

Bruxelles nastoji provesti mnoge globalističke agende koje su neprihvatljive i štetne za Hrvatsku. Stoga je važno ograničiti širenje ovlasti Bruxellesa i oduprijeti se agendama koje nisu u duhu hrvatske tradicije i hrvatskih vrijednosti

Other politicians are presented as EU servants who do not think about national interests and citizens. Instead, they simply follow the globalist agenda, enacting politics which do not help Croatia. Amusingly, Croatia is prioritized to such a level that even Ursula von der Leyen is presented as being a “female version of Croatian Prime Minister Andrej Plenković”, and not the other way around. These portrayals of other politicians are then always juxtaposed with narratives on the authenticity of far-right political candidates, which only serve the Croatian citizens, and their interests.

BARTULICA (DP): Rodna ideologija u školstvu će nestati!

PLENKOVIĆ (HDZ): Ta priča je apsolvirana. Poslali smo poruku partnerima ako su mislili da ima neki problem, da problema nema.

Jelena B.

Domovinski pokret tražio je da se Istanbulska konvencija, čiji je s... See more

See translation

From an audio-visual standpoint, this type of content commonly shows scenic and idyllic Croatian situations, such as (white) families, large agricultural fields, and national flags. The colors are bright and warm colors, and uplifting music is commonly played. Additionally, patriotic power ballads are played, accompanied by screeching eagles. But these videos are edited and presented as pure TV spots, which have simply been fitted for social media resolutions. They last long and have no clear

attention-grabbing strategies. More often than not, they only include politicians talking in different situations (on the street, in an office, at a press conference, during a public event), and they do not take advantage of the format. The conclusion that can be drawn from far-right content is that these politicians are still not fully aware of how to frame their messages on social media, opting to simply reproduce the content that they made for TV audiences.

Narrative 3. "Europe is in danger."

The predominant feeling expressed in the content of the green left profile was fear and discomfort. The causes for being fearful, threatened and worried were all interconnected and included fear from the far right related to Russia and Putin, fear for the future of the planet, fear for Europe, its industry and competitiveness, fear for women's rights and minority rights, fear for democracy. The videos that transpired these feelings were in dark colors, threatening music and dramatic voices and were coming from the European accounts of all parties on the left: the Greens, the Social Democrats, the Left in the EU, but also from the Liberals. To the extent that an action to counter the presented danger was proposed, it was often related to past struggles on the left - struggles for workers' rights, women's rights, LGBTIQ+ rights, against fascism, anti-communist struggles and past action for the climate. It is notable in the left green narrative that both the threats and the struggle against them are portrayed as analogous to past struggles. This is illustrated in the video that was going around in its Croatian version.

Narrative 4. "Europe is basically good but needs new/different policies."

This is a narrative of the Croatian green party Možemo! (We can!), the Social Democratic Party and the independent MEP candidate Nina Skočak. Besides continuation of the Green transition, Možemo! was promoting three main policies or policy changes: financial support for small agricultural producers, modernisation of railways and European housing policy. Nina Skočak was promoting more young people and women in politics, while the Social Democratic Party was also advocating for better consumer protection and housing. This narrative is accompanied by more enthusiastic messages and videos that show the candidates in action. One of the videos was telling a story of a night-train ride to Split, and how the trains could be much improved and more would be opting for a car. The feed also included videos of the European Left for taxing the rich.

Discussion on most interesting videos

The far-right campaign presented all contemporary issues and challenges through a lens of Croatian national interests and ethnic population, which must be prioritized against globalist agenda. Therefore, we consider the previously mentioned political commercial from Stephen Nikola Bartulica (DP MEP candidate) on TikTok to be interesting, as it captures the overall contemporary far-right worldview. About

48

one minute long, the commercial contains the following quote: “*Fertile fields for Croatia, Croatia without gender ideology; safe borders, happy family, and a Christian identity... for a Europe of sovereign national states, with Croatia first!*” (In Croatian language, the word fertile, *rodno*, is the same for gender, *rod*). This video perfectly encapsulates all the main points of the far-right narrative, including veiled references to placing fences across Croatia’s national borders in order to prevent illegal immigrants from entering the country, criticism of foreigners who purchase real estate, mass arrival of foreign workers (usually Nepali) instead of taking care of domestic workers, and criticism of the EU. All of these elements individually work towards fostering and spreading an anti-globalist, national sovereign, and anti-liberal sentiment, which seeks to challenge the EU and its influence.

Among many pieces of content related to the war in Ukraine, there was a very interesting video on TikTok that claims that NATO is amassing troops on the Ukrainian border with the implication that they’re preparing for a ground assault. The video is about two minutes long, with a superimposed text stating, “Russia Left Stunned: Massive NATO Deployment of 31 Allies and 10,000 Vehicles Converges on Ukrainian Border” at the top. The video shows various footage of military training and logistics (some forces shown are indeed identifiable as belonging to NATO members), likely shot during some NATO military exercise. The video is uploaded by a profile called “us Miritaly” (misspelling included). It is a very clear attempt at disinformation - no such troop amassing ever happened. At first glance, the military footage lends credibility while being decontextualized enough that an unassuming viewer will not question its veracity. There are clear signs that something is off, but piecing them together and questioning the truth of the video requires an active effort on the part of the viewer. It is exemplary of many encountered pieces of mis-and-dis-information about the war in Ukraine (mainly the centre-right profile).

Regarding the format, the most interesting videos were those by the independent candidate Nina Skočak. Since Skočak was an influencer before becoming a candidate, her videos had most or all of the elements of an influencers’ video: tone of voice, short video cuts, illustrations in the background, personal stories, etc. She did not have an elaborate political program, but she effectively communicated her messages that young people and women deserve to be at the decision table. An example video is the one where she explains the national structure of the EU parliament, the EP election rules in Croatia and her statement that 70% of Croatian laws come from the EU. The video has a background message from her comments and background illustrations, which she points to while speaking. The video is fast, edited in small cuts, and more informative than any official EP videos, both Croatian and European, that were made to boost voter turnout.

As an influencer, Nina Skočak has been making videos that are not explicitly political but are still projecting women’s power, especially in the videos where she explains buying and renovating her apartment in Brussels. An exemplary video of turning everyday life into a political campaign is where she shows what her campaign days look like. We see her having coffee, eating pizza, riding a tram, handling the renovation of her department in Brussels, shopping for office supplies for collecting signatures, her broken nails, her cat, collecting signatures for her candidacy, preparing for a TV appearance, and much more in less than 1,5 minutes.

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion to the bases of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was Europe about and why vote? (Social Contract)

By monitoring the content of centre-right, red-green, and far-right political parties and candidates, we uncovered widely different visions of what Europe means for Croatia and why Croatian citizens should vote. Regarding the centre-right party HDZ, it may seem at first glance that they did not reflect much on the nature of Europe and the European Union (its messages largely focused on Croatia). However, within these messages lies a vision of the EU as a source of prosperity for Croatia. This narrative is not unlike EPP's, to which HDZ belongs. However, the EPP presented the prosperity brought by the EU more widely, focusing its messages more on preserving democracy and exercising the right to vote and stemming the tide of both left-wing and right-wing radical parties. These two topics were, on the other hand, very sparse in the HDZ campaign. Instead, it focused more on the party's successes, including their successful navigation of EU politics, which resulted in great economic benefits and international prestige for Croatia.

Similarly to the centre-right content, the monitored far-right profiles also did not focus much on Europe, the EU, or the EP elections. Instead, they turned their content inwards, talking about Croatian history, emphasizing the importance of Croatia and its people. However, when Europe and the European Union were brought up, it was frequently presented as an external entity which pushes its political narratives and agenda onto the Croatian people. Notable examples include “woke ideology” and immigrants, both of which are seen as alien to Croatian society. Therefore, the EP campaign for the far-right political parties, such as DP, commonly espoused their candidates as the authentic Croatian options, which will, unlike the current government and MEPs, represent solely Croatian national interests in the EU. These messages also included a strong incitement to vote. Therefore, despite never bringing Europe and the EU into question, the far-right party politically criticized European integration, bringing to the forefront the notion that there are alternative political directions to EU goals and politics, such as national sovereignty.

Lastly, the observed content from the red-green profile, notably the party Možemo and SDP, had the overall strongest, positive, and explicit vision of Europe, the EU, and the need to vote. Although Možemo and SDP (through Biljana Borzan) joined HDZ in expressing the benefits of EU policies for Croatia (e.g. the Nature Restoration Plan or consumer rights protection), they presented it more as achieved by successful parties, rather than the EU itself. The overall message of the red-green content was about defending the EU from the far-right and proposing policies for a better EU. Možemo! was most prominent in presenting the fight for the EU as a collective endeavor of the European Greens. A stronger line of EU criticism was coming from the Left on the EU level that presented not only the far-right threat, but also the dangers of corporate capture, inequality and the compromise of European values in the stance towards the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. So, a vote in the EP elections, from the standpoint of the red-green profile, is a vote for EU policies that will improve consumer rights, housing, railway infrastructure and the lot of small agricultural producers, but primarily it is a vote to defend democracy, women's and minority rights and the Green Deal from the far-right.

50

Funded by
the European Union

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

All political parties attempted to build an “us” through their political communication, to use the constructed collective identity to improve their election results. The “us” identity can be clearly divided into two political narratives: the “European Us”, and the “National Us”. These two collective identities created a gap between globalist and national sovereign political parties and politicians, profoundly shaping their rhetoric, highlighting societal and political issues, and emphasised voter needs.

The “European Us” camp consisted of mainstream, liberal democratic parties from the center-left to the center-right, which included HDZ, SDP, *Možemo!* (and their politicians) as the dominantly visible political actors. These actors could be defined as Europhilic because they highlight the importance of European integrity and the economic, societal, and political benefits the EU brings to Croatia. For these actors, the “us” was constructed as Croatia leaving the Balkan geopolitical space and becoming a Western/Central European member. By doing so, Croatia would cleanse itself of backwards societal and political trends and, in turn, develop as a liberal democratic political system. Therefore, the political “us” in these narratives is defined as Croats being equal members of an international union, with all the benefits of such a union.

The “Croatian Us” camp was defined by more radical voices coming from DP, *Pravo i Pravda* (Law and Justice), *Odlučnost i pravедnost* (Determination and Justice), and *Most* (the Bridge). These actors are best defined as being a cross between Eurosceptic and critical Europeans. For them, the European Union is seen as a foreign influence and force, suppressing Croatian national sentiment and pushing for policies and societal changes which Croats do not desire. Therefore, the “us” is seen as the true voice of Croats, which, if these actors become MEPs, will be finally heard in the European Parliament. In turn, these actors' political “us” is defined as Croats firmly protecting their traditional identity and needs, refusing changes that come with becoming members of an international globalist union. Despite this, no political actor from this group advocated for Croatia to leave the EU.

Conclusions

To sum up, the European Parliament elections in Croatia were overshadowed by national parliamentary elections, which were held less than two months prior. Three arguments can be given for this conclusion: 1) the electoral turnout was historically low at 21,35%, which was also the lowest of all other EP elections held in other member states; 2) the results of the EP elections mostly reflected the results of the parliamentary elections; and 3) many parties simply recycled their campaigns between elections. Yet despite being overshadowed by national parliament elections, these EP elections were nevertheless important, as they were the first elections in Croatia (alongside the national parliamentary elections), where political parties significantly used TikTok, Instagram, and short-form videos. Every major candidate had a profile on either of the two.

Notably, the political candidates and parties' campaign approaches differed. HDZ, the centre-right party, mostly focused on itself by projecting an image of a successful party bringing about prosperity and stability for Croatia, the EU being spoken of almost as a resource for Croatia to extract value from, something that only HDZ is able to do well. DP, the far-right party, focused on the need to preserve

Croatian identity against destabilizing Western foreign influences, often being critical of the EU. Both parties spoke primarily of Croatia and did not substantially refer to EU politics. On the other hand, the green and left-wing parties, Možemo and SDP, actively spoke of EU policy and values and the emerging threat of the far-right endangering all of Europe. Political and EP election content was notably rare in the first week of data collection. It saw some uptick in the second week, was quite prominent in the third week (in the runup to the election), and then sharply dropped immediately after the elections concluded.

Regarding political content, the observed content was quite diverse between the three researcher profiles. Centre-right and red-green profiles saw a lot of pro-EU and various international content, while the far-right profile mostly saw content focused on Croatia and content critical of the EU. Anti-migrant and anti-LGBTIQ+ content were rare on centre-right and red-green profiles, while being common on the far-right profile. Content related to Israel-Gaza and Ukraine-Russia conflicts was very common on centre-right and red-green profiles, mostly pro-Ukrainian and pro-Gaza, but with a notable amount of pro-Russian content and even disinformation. All researchers noted AI content, but it was not a significant phenomenon. It should also be noted that far-right content would occasionally appear in the centre-right feed.

Regarding the monitoring experience, the social media profiles took some time to align with researchers' designated preferences. Notably, no political content was present at the outset - it only appeared after some "training" of the algorithm, and even then further training was required to align the ideological profiles. The experience was different between TikTok and Instagram. TikTok's algorithm appears to be much more agile and efficient, quickly delivering content as soon as it detects patterns in user preferences. Comparatively, Instagram's algorithm was very slow with one researcher never getting it to show political content properly.

To conclude, the 2024 EP elections revealed the increased importance politicians and political parties give to social media such as TikTok and Instagram. They were frequently used to reach potential voters, and political content was strongly present during the monitoring period. Yet despite their increased political relevance in Croatia, TikTok and Instagram are still not major channels of political communication in Croatia. Its reach among Croatian voters is relatively limited and campaigns, with some exceptions, such as Nina Skočak's, don't put as much effort in producing content appropriate for the platforms.

Bibliography

Mikašinić-Komšo, M. (2024). *Analysis of political narratives on TikTok during the 2024 election campaign*. Gong: Zagreb. <https://gong.hr/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Analysis-of-Political-Narratives-on-TikTok-during-the-2024-Election-Campaign.pdf>

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Finland

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1,0
Author(s):	Emilia Palonen and Henry Jokinen, University of Helsinki; Anna Björk, Demos Helsinki
Editors:	Alexander Alekseev, Szilvia Horváth, and Emilia Palonen University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Tuğçe Erçetin (Bilg)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Finland: EP Election Results.....	4
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	5
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	5
Section 2: Finland: Political profiles	7
# Centre Right feed	8
# Far-Right feed	12
# Red-Green feed	16
# Visibility of Political actors	19
Section 3: Finland: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles.....	22
# Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	22
# Notes on Organic Profiles	23
# Differences Observed Over Time	25
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok.....	26
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	28
Section 4: Finland: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	29
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	29
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram.....	30
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	32
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	34
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	34
# AI Generated Content	36
Section 5: Finland: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	37
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time.....	37
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate.....	37
# Emotional mechanisms	37
# Video Typologies.....	38
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	41
# Discussion on most interesting videos	43
Concluding section.....	45
# What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?	45
# Populist mobilisation	46
# Conclusions.....	47
Bibliography	48

Finland: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

Watching the pre-election campaign videos for the European Parliament, in Finland, we witnessed the strong presence of the centre-right and red-green profiles, while the native far-right content was less present in the feeds. The election results were a victory for the centre-right National Coalition party and the Left Alliance, whose leader became the most popular politician in the elections, pulling a historic result for the party. They and the Green candidates were strongly present on the red-green and organic profiles. The far-right had a narrower profile as fewer people seemed to be making content for them, and the election results were a disappointment for the party who had been tipped to gain even three seats in the trans-European pre-election hype for the far right. The far-right content was less communal, yet we saw several politicians for the centre-right and greens as well as the left parties communicating in together with several candidates. The debates often focused on national politics, where the austerity government versus the opposition discourse was prevalent. Security was an important theme, too. The far-right threat was also in the agenda. Ukraine and Gaza were important topics. In a candidate-centred political culture, we saw a strong presence of those who eventually also became MEPs.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Section 1: Finland: EP Election Results

Many themes, videos, and candidates in the EP elections were recycled from the presidential elections in January 2024. Finland is a candidate-based system in elections: parties are competing on an open party list, and this means that candidates' political communication is particularly pertinent. They compete not only for votes across parties but also within parties. The election results reflect security concerns: the most successful party in the elections was the centre-right. The presidential elections contributed to piling votes to a new MEP, Li Andersson, former party leader of the Left Alliance, who

had 13.5 per cent personal votes and pulled three seats for her mid-size party left of the Social Democrats. Centre-left, Greens and centre-right parties gained each two seats. The populist radical right got only one MEP, as a surprise compared to the pre-election polls and media attention. The Swedish People's Party also retained their one seat. The turnout was low.

16/07/2024 - 09:44

All times are GMT+2

Results by national party - 2024-2029

Finland - Official results

Percentage of votes

Figure 1. Results by national party

National Parties

KOK - Kansallinen Kokoomus/Samlingspartiet
VAS - Vasemmistoliitto/Vänsterförbundet
SDP - Suomen Sosialidemokraattinen Puolue/Finlands Socialdemokratiska Parti
KESK - Suomen Keskusta/Centern i Finland
VIHR - Vihreä liitto/Gröna Förbundet

PS - Perussuomalaiset/Sannfinländarna
SFP/RKP - Svenska folkpartiet i Finland/Suomen ruotsalainen kansanpuolue
KD - LIIK - Suomen Kristillisdemokraatit - Liike Nyt/Finlands Kristdemokrater - Rörelse.nu
Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

National Election Results and Party Affiliations

All of the parties that had won seats in the European parliament in the 2019 elections managed to maintain their presence though some seats were gained and lost. The elections were won by the pro-EU *Kokoomus* (centre-right, National Coalition Party, KOK), who ran visible candidates and European security focus. The surprise was the success of *Vasemmistoliitto* (left-green, Left Alliance, VAS), who reached the second place thanks to the nationwide popularity of their candidate Li Andersson, won them 3 seats out of the 15 Finland has in the European Parliament. Conversely, the speculated far-right success did not materialize, *Perussuomalaiset* (Finns Party, PS) won only one seat with the MP Sebastian Tynkkynen, whose voice is well-known from social media, originally from YouTube. The ‘victory for the left’ in Finland’s EP election is worth mentioning due to how it contrasts to the Finnish parliamentary elections from the previous year, after which the National Coalition and the Finns Party (moved from the ID to ECR in May 2023) had formed a right-wing government coalition in Finland. Domestic issues, such as criticism of the government, were visible in the campaign, alongside calls for security in Europe. The most visible parties were the Finns Party – often also in the counter discourse, and the Greens who made a lot of content, but also the EPP – mainly the National Coalition, who with the Left Alliance, won the elections. Of the left-wing parties Social Democrats came second also in this data set.

Figure 2. Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Finland

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

The list of 16 MEPs includes six former party leaders, and four of them from the previous all-female-led government of Sanna Marin. Top MEP candidates for each of the winning parties followed the trends observed in social media. Mika Aaltola for National Coalition, Sebastian Tynkkynen for Finns Party, and Li Andersson for Left Alliance were all visible figures. Aaltola and Andersson were candidates in the presidential elections earlier in the spring, but Aaltola was then running as an independent candidate. His profile as the director of the Finnish Institute for Foreign Affairs was marked by the questions of security and Ukraine. Similarly, the second most popular for the National Coalition, Pekka Toveri has a 5

long military career which includes international work, he is comparatively newcomer to the national politics, joining the National Coalition party in 2023 for the Finnish parliamentary elections. Toveri had very limited presence in the (especially centre-right profile) data gathering feed. Of the other National Coalition MEPs Henna Virkkunen became the commissioner for Finland and the newcomer Aura Salla was joined by a long-term MEP Sirpa Pietikäinen. Li Andersson's popularity managed to pull in and win seats for other candidates from

15/07/2024 - 17:47

All times are GMT+2

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

Finland - Constitutive session

National Parties	Votes	Political groups									Seats
		EPP	S&D	PIE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	
KOK	24.80%	4									4
VAS	17.30%							3			3
SDP	14.90%		2								2
KESK	11.80%					2					2
VIHR	11.30%						2				2
PS	7.60%				1						1
SFP/RKP	6.10%					1					1
KD - LIIK	4.60%										0
Other parties	1.60%										0
	100.00%	4	2	0	1	3	2	3	0	0	15

KOK > EPP: MIKA AALTOLA, AURA SALLA, PEKKA TOVERI, HENNA VIRKKUNEN

VAS > The Left: LI ANDERSSON, MERJA KYLLÖNEN, JUSSI SARAMO

VIHR > Greens/EFA: VILLE NIINISTÖ, MARIA OHISALO

SDP > S&D: MARIA GUZENINA, EERO HEINÄLUOMA

KESK > Renew Europe: ELSI KATAINEN, KATRI KULMUNI

PS > ECR: SEBASTIAN TYNKKYNNEN

SFP/RKP > Renew Europe: ANNA-MAJA HENRIKSSON

National Parties

KOK - Kansallinen Kokoomus/Samlingspartiet

VAS - Vasemmistoliitto/Vänsterförbundet

SDP - Suomen Sosialidemokraattinen Puolue/Finlands Socialdemokratiska Parti

KESK - Suomen Keskusta/Center i Finland

VIHR - Vihreä liitto/Gröna Förbundet

PS - Perussuomalaiset/Sannfinländarna

SFP/RKP - Svenska folkpartiet i Finland/Suomen ruotsalainen kansanpuolue

KD - LIIK - Suomen Kristillisdemokraatit - Liike Nyt/Finlands Kristdemokrater - Rörelse.nu

Other parties - Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

● EPP - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)

● S&D - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament

● PIE - Patriots for Europe

● ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group

● Renew Europe - Renew Europe Group

● Greens/EFA - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance

● The Left - The Left group in the European Parliament - GUE/NGL

● ESN - Europe of Sovereign Nations

● NI - Non-attached Members

seats for other candidates from Left Alliance who received comparatively less votes from other winning candidates; these included sitting Left Alliance MEP Merja Kyllönen and Jussi Saramo, who had been tipped to take the Left Alliance leadership after Andersson. While the three of them and the two Social Democratic MEPs Heinäluoma and Guzenina had low profile in the audiovisual social media, the Greens were prolific on the social media feeds. Their two seats match the results from 2019. However, since the Greens gained a seat in the aftermath of Brexit and the redistribution of MEP seats, in effect the result in 2024 meant a loss for the party. At the national level, the support for the Greens has been declining. MEP Ville Niinistö renewed his seat, also a former party chair Maria Ohisalo beat him in the polls. Also, the two Centre Party MEPs representing particular parts of Finland and gaining a large share of the votes from there, were present but not very visible on social media. The Swedish People's Party's party leader Anna-Maja Henriksson renewed the seat at Renew.

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Section 2: Finland: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

Looking into the notes made by the researchers, the centre-right profile was yielding a wider range while the red-green and particularly far-right profiles had a much narrower selection of political parties. This may be based on the data-gathering practice, but also probably indicates the focus of the feed and its tendency to generate an echo chamber.

Especially on TikTok, the content tended to curve towards a specific type of videos fast, if the researcher was opting to watch the video in length. Overtime, it was also possible to see how the content developed across the platforms depending on whether the actors were active on both. The feed then became rather depended on the type of videos that the most prominent actors were providing.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

Centre Right feed

Synthetic profile feed for both TikTok and Instagram showed much more political content than the organic counterparts. Additionally, TikTok feed provided political content far more consistently than Instagram feed. In synthetic feed for both TikTok and Instagram the feed was of a wide variety of different parties and ideologies, significant emphasis was on the National Coalition, Centre Party, *Svenska Folkpartiet* and Finns Party. The feed also showed a significant number of left-wing and centre-left political advertisements from both candidates and organisations. By far the most visible left-wing candidates in this feed were Li Andersson and Lauri Lindén, both from Left Alliance. Andersson being the most popular candidate of the elections and Lauri Lindén a young candidate who is very visible on TikTok, though he did not get elected. From the Greens, the most visible candidate was Maria Ohisalo, now MEP. Candidates and MEPs from the Social Democratic Party were least visible for this profile, though videos from the SDP's youth, women, and student organisations were recurring.

Various right-wing MPs such as Riikka Purra (PS) and Petteri Orpo (NC) were consistently present in the feed across the entire data collection period, although their presence was not from their own accounts but rather than third-party content creators focusing either on news or parody. Of the major EP election candidates, videos from Sebastian Tynkkynen (PS) were recurring almost daily and often multiple videos per data gathering session. Despite being outside the centre-right data gathering profile, the leading candidate of the Left Alliance, Li Andersson, was seen often through both first-party and third-party videos. All the centre-right candidates from National Coalition, *Keskusta* and RKP who won the election did have a significant presence in the feed apart from Pekka Toveri. Additionally, there were consistent new videos from National Coalition candidates who did not make the cut, such as Johan Träskbäck from the National Coalition or Joel Taskila from the Centre Party.

Feed about European politics showed a lot of content about EPP centring especially around Ursula von der Leyen. A significant uptick in the EPP content was seen a few days before the election, involving Ursula von der Leyen visiting Sweden in support of *Moderaterna* and Finland in support of National Coalition. Greens-EFA and Renew Europe were also both very regular presence in the feed, contrasting the style of videos by being more musical and youthful to the 'professional' or 'official' of EPP. Volt Europa was also seen in the feed often.

Outside of the EP elections feed also showed a lot of international and American political and public figures regularly, such as Donald Trump, Trump Jr., and Joe Biden. From Europe, recurring people were Czech President Petr Pavel and Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán. Sometimes, also Clare Daly, an Irish, now former, far-left MP in the European Parliament, was a surprising but recurring person.

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Interestingly, there was a spike in content relating to the Blue & Black movement (a far-right neofascist movement) in the centre-right feed midway through the data gathering, seemingly related to their attempts to participate in the elections and collecting of supporter cards.

10

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Far-Right feed

For the far-right synthetic account, the most striking thing was what kind of content the algorithm assumed to be of interest especially on TikTok. The key impression was that on TikTok, the complementary material to the Finnish debates was readily provided for by related content from both EU-level far-right politics and the US (anti-gender, Trumpist). On Instagram, the content was more narrowly focused on Sebastian Tynkkynen mainly, and some content shared by the Finns Party. Overall, TikTok seemed to be much more quickly adopting to a more versatile selection of topics in a more “imaginative” way than Instagram, but it is not possible to rule out how much of this is due to the adopted algorithmic training procedure in the sense that Instagram seemed to require more nudging than TikTok. While the option for training the algorithm was described in the procedures in a detailed manner, still, the observation here is that, all in all, the spectrum and broadness of content in Instagram was quite narrow apart from the work done by Sebastian Tynkkynen.

On TikTok, at first the content was heavily leaning on military aesthetics and content clips on e.g. national defence and the defence of the Baltic Sea countries and regions from Russia’s aggression, and the war in Ukraine. Another prominent feature, even if these videos were not chosen to be watched, were training videos and videos with cars. Also, ironic or humorous content on relationships and the differences between men and women were pushing at first. For EP2024 specifically, the Finns Party’s Sebastian Tynkkynen and also the assistant to Wille Rydman, Tuulia Alanko ended up being the most prominent figures in Finland. As the data shows, the content was heavily leaning towards the US politics and the Trump campaign. The content from EU politics was mainly from Hungarians. While the assignment was to see what kind of European social contract issues would rise up in the content, the US driven content seemed to fit the agendas so well and also link so much with the Orbánist approaches, that it felt like the bubble – and the US link as a strong link – made sense. Therefore, steering away from this content decisively did not seem like a legitimate choice.

12

Figure 10: Visibility of Accounts in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

As with all the other accounts, both Instagram and especially TikTok showed much more political content than the organic profile, at least originally. This was evened out slightly as the data gathering went on. TikTok content got quite fast from dancing videos to war, especially war in Ukraine, military analyses of how the Nordics should be defended and of the Finnish armed forces and their excellence. Sebastian Tynkkynen was prominent on TikTok eventually, but the feed was getting more and more towards content from Trump commentators (supporters), criticism of any woke sentiments and celebration of how Trump silences people who criticise him. Especially prominent were comments where Trump explains how he is not against women. Quite quickly, also, the TikTok feed showed much for Orbán and other Hungarian politics, especially Orbán’s anti-EU and anti-immigration content. Furthermore, Wille Rydman’s (PS) assistant, Tuulia Alanko, started to appear very frequently on TikTok towards the election day and beyond.

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

For Instagram, much of the content any other than Sebastian Tynkkynen (for example, Mauri Peltokangas) presented, did not resonate as much as a lot of the videos were quite general and without the same effortless flow as Tynkkynen’s communications. Content-wise, the most important observation was that any message that the Finns Party or even these two politicians shared did not include any clear visions about what kind of future or state of affairs should we strive for – other than saying no to things. Also, even if Riikka Purra was not running for the elections, she was still one of the core persons of all content shared by the party – which kept the focus tightly on Finland.

Notably, the Finns Party – even Tynkkynen – seemed to put most emphasis on what to say no to and how to say it rather than providing alternatives on what then should be the course of action for the EP. This differed from both the Left Alliance and Greens, who spoke more of what should and could be

done and provided alternative ways forward. Perhaps this was also because Tynkkynen clearly was not much leaning on the reputation of the existing Finns Party MEPs, but the home front (= the top politicians in Finland). In turn, the candidates from the Greens, for example, used a lot of their top candidates from the seated MEPs, other green politicians from the MP and linked them with their domestic politics.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

On Instagram, it was difficult to have anyone else from PS than Sebastian Tynkkynen, whose content slightly overlapped with that from TikTok. Even when following the protocol, the Instagram content from PS was mostly about Riikka Purra, Mari Rantanen and Jussi Halla-Aho – so Finnish politicians not even running for the elections and posted by others. Some content from Mauri Peltokangas appeared every now and then, but really TikTok was more prominent in this regard. It was the same with the organic profiles at first.

What was striking on TikTok was how fast the algorithm was reacting in such a way that it connected things together. To begin with, the military-related content got first so prominent that some mild steering away from that needed to take place, also because the content started to be less political and more just about videos of e.g., individual Ukrainian soldiers from the front. Once the feed got the US elections in the loop, the topic was endlessly appearing, leaving very little room for anything else (just Orbán mainly).

Red-Green feed

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

There were several prominent figures generating content in the Greens, and also some active accounts for the SDP and Left Alliance. The party-generated content was also appearing, particularly from the SDP, but also on occasion the European Greens. The Greens were sovereign in the feeds because of the width of the content, perhaps. Figures 15 and 16 show how the Left was more visible than the Social Democrats, which also reflects the results of the elections, where the Left gained a historic victory, becoming the second largest Euro-party for Finland. This content was not anti-European or Eurosceptic but pro-European and also seeking to solve common challenges. Left-green accounts communicated climate but also strong dimensions of Social Europe, economy and security. They were strongly critical of the far-right. Most viral were, however, internal politics issues and grievance politics where the Orpo government was contested. For most of these accounts, the main object of criticism for all of the feed was the sitting government of PM Petteri Orpo who was collaborating with the finance minister Riikka Purra and other ministers of the Finns Party.

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Considering that the confrontation was between the austerity government and the opposition, it is obvious that in the themes, grievance politics and economy were trending. Many of the videos accounted for challenges with government policy or featured speeches in the parliament or election

debates that were discussing relevant issues. The feed also included protests in Gaza, extinction rebellion and lobby organisations for animal rights and trade unions. Pride activities were also quite visible in the feeds, and anti-misogyny content was trending, visible in the high levels for the top themes (Figure 18) but not ticked in the negative side (Figure 19). Lay people had no small role in the feed as there was a diversity of accounts taking issue with the government policies.

Visibility of Political actors

In Finland, due to the electoral system, which has an open list where the electorate decides who eventually makes it to Brussels, the individual candidates and politicians are the most visible actors of election campaigns. Across the feeds, there were differences between the types of videos (see the section on typology) and the way in which the candidates were engaging with other candidates or politicians during their campaign. Furthermore, there were differences in emphasis of candidates beyond Finland, even though, for example, Donald Trump was appearing in both the centre-right and far-right feeds.

In the centre-right feed on TikTok, Finnish EP candidate politicians matching the profile were female candidates Anna-Maja Henriksson (SFP) and Henna Virkkunen (NC), and male candidates Mika Lintilä (Centre Party), Jocka Träskbäck (NC), Joel Taskila (Centre). Only Anna-Maja Henriksson and Henna Virkkunen were elected for the European Parliament. Of the people seen on TikTok, only Virkkunen reached the top 15 in visibility on Instagram as well. In addition to Virkkunen, the following centre-right personalities were visible: Male candidates Mika Aaltola (NC) and Ted Apter (NC), and female candidates Aura Salla (NC), Sirpa Pietikäinen (NC) Henriina Rantala (NC). Mika Aaltola and Aura Salla both were selected for the European Parliament.

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Finland

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Finland

Beyond the centre-right candidates that were visible and selected for Parliament were Sebastian Tynkkynen (FP) and Li Andersson (Left Alliance), Ville Niinistö (Green) and Maria Ohisalo (Green). On TikTok, there were slightly more centre-right male than female candidates despite those female candidates tended to be more successful than male candidates in being selected as MEPs. As for Instagram, female candidates had much greater presence in the feed in addition to being more successful in being selected as MEPs.

Greens were dominating the red-green feeds, because they were much more active in the platforms than the social democrats. The most prominent accounts from the red-green side were the prolific Green politicians Maria Ohisalo and Atte Harjanne and a newcomer Perttu Jussila, who all did well in the elections, topping the list with Ville Niinistö, the sitting MEP, who also appeared in the feed. Also, the party chair Sofia Virta was present a lot. From the gender perspective it is interesting how in the red-green profiles the most visible people were Green male candidates Perttu Jussila on TikTok and Atte Harjanne on Instagram. Maria Ohisalo was elected to the parliament, and she was third also in TikTok, but there Li Andersson (sixth in Instagram) was the second most visible. Green Party leader Sofia Virta also appeared particularly discussing oppositional national politics. The list included also social democrats Julia Sangervo and Aleksanteri Gustafsson, Ville Merinen, Joonas Räsänen and Antti Lindtman. The SDP-related accounts included the party leader Antti Lindtman and the official party account – but the prominently, the feeds included Aleksanteri Gustafsson, as a talking head and main critic of the far right. Also, Julia Sangervo as a candidate featured in the feed, but “Terapeutti Ville”, the MP who was against TikTok and worried about the social media use of the youth, was disappearing from the feed when moving onto more minimalistic text on image videos.

On the left, there were a lot of appreciative accounts for Li Andersson, who became the queen of the elections with a historic 13 percent vote share nationwide. Among the most visible Left Alliance

accounts were Lauri Lindén, who moved to text on image style – and in very long explain to the camera videos Jesse Jokelainen, who made it to the Finnish Parliament on a reserve seat as Merja Kyllönen renewed her seat at the European Parliament after a term. Other than that, the feed included EPP-related accounts, particularly the *Spitzenkandidat* Ursula von der Leyen, and sometimes the European Greens. There were some Macron and some Swedish politicians, too. Claire Daly also appeared irregularly in the red-green feed. As did, of course, Trump, Sanders, and other US politicians, sometimes even UK and South African politicians.

In the feed of the far-right profile, Sebastian Tynkkynen (Finns Party) was the most visible MEP candidate, especially through his own accounts on both platforms. In addition to Tynkkynen, the Instagram feed featured also Finns Party MEP candidates Nanna Väätäinen, Ari Koponen, and the Green party MEP candidate Atte Harjanne. The TikTok feed included also Tynkkynen. Out of political not running for EP, the Instagram feed featured MPs (not candidates) Riikka Purra, Mari Rantanen, Jussi Halla-aho, Teemu Keskisarja, Miko Bergbom (who was also the campaign lead for Sebastian Tynkkynen), and Laura Huhtasaari (ex-MEP). TikTok included also Jenna Simula (Finns Party) but emphasised non-Finnish actors including Donald Trump (US Republican party presidential candidate), Vladimir Putin (the president of Russia), Viktor Orbán (the prime minister of Hungary, Fidesz), and Péter Szijjártó (the foreign secretary of Hungary, Fidesz).

The featured political actors in the far-right feed on TikTok were predominantly outside Finland. The TikTok algorithm favoured both US and European far-right featuring content and accounts, which can be seen partly as a result of the online behaviour of the researcher, but also an indication of the associated content and themes with the very visible and prominent actors. These included themes such as immigration and gender politics in the sense of criticism of “woke ideology” and their resonance with the Trump campaign, for example. Some of the Finns Party’s content was rather repetitive. Most videos only include the individual candidate or actor without others, with few exceptions. The assistant to Wille Rydman (the Finns Pparty, non-candidate), Tuulia Alanko, appeared in the feed after the elections on TikTok.

Section 3: Finland: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

The three types of synthetic profiles developed both in similarities and differences over time. Some of the political actors were fairly recurring across the profiles (such as Li Andersson, Maria Ohisalo, Petteri Orpo and Sebastian Tynkkynen), while others were more profile specific. The organic profiles also showed differences in how frequently the political content was appearing in the feed, in terms of high level of appearance of political content in the beginning of the data collection period vs political content being emphasised towards the end of the period.

Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

Political content on the synthetic profiles had a much larger variety and frequency. Within both Instagram and TikTok on the synthetic account, there was a much larger variety of political themes from parody and humour to more serious content, including both local EP campaigns as well as campaign videos by EP parties. The organic profile seemed to follow a trend of showing very little political content outside the week before the campaign. Organic profile tended to be biased towards more entertaining rather than informative even with nudging it towards showing some political content. Additionally, right after the election and the following week, there was a significant drop in the organic profile's political content dropping to almost zero. A similar drop was not observed in the synthetic profile content feed.

The organic profile included much more parody, irony, and hope than the synthetic profile feeds. On both, Instagram was less versatile, though with the organic one, it got a broader scope of commentators. The synthetic (far-right) had a much more aggressive tone and content, and it seemed to get faster into steeper curves of edgier argumentation, while at the same time, the organic profile accounts maintained a steadier level of argumentation. Clare Daly became a prominent, more far-left figure on the organic feeds, and the Israel-Gaza conflict was dominating somewhat TikTok at some point on those accounts. With TikTok also, the timing of the data gathering seemed to affect the content: towards the evening in the earlier phases of data collection, the synthetic profile attracted more casual (usually including young women or prank content), while political content was emphasised in the afternoon sessions, but this is a tentative observation.

The synthetic account was always more political than the organic one, but even if all the organic and synthetic profiles were a bit in the same direction. We could see that the synthetic account was keeping to a particular set of parties rather focused, while the organic one would include more variation.

Notes on Organic Profiles

Videos on some of the organic profiles tended to be more related to political themes and global rather than being focused on Finnish politics or EP elections. While the most popular figures such as Tynkkynen, Andersson, and Ohisalo of the Finnish EP Elections were present the feed was much more geared towards people more relevant to the international context such as Putin, Zelensky, Biden, Trump, or even Orbán. Videos relevant to the EP elections were visible for most of the data gathering period for the organic account, but their occurrence was infrequent and non-existent on some days. An exception to this was the week before the election day during which EP election campaign videos were extremely common, showing videos from candidates of all parties. The organic account provided a variety of commentators and topics, ranging from the social security policy in Finland to environmental policy in the EU and beyond. On TikTok, the content was more relevant for the EP2024 than on Instagram, but even there especially Li Andersson, Ville Niinistö and Perttu Jussila were frequently appearing figures. On the organic profile, the tone of voice that the videos generated was concerned and serious, but not alarmist.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

As the Figure 21a shows, the first profile’s organic feed was not getting much political content, until the election week for the persons. When one of the researchers sought to run a profile that is more or less similar (red-green, but curious of the far-right and moderate right), the range of political actors was much wider on the organic account. The feed remained rather heterogeneous and ended up receiving content from a ruralist anti-elitist political influencer from the north of Finland. The synthetic and organic red-green profiles gathered a political feed rather swiftly, faster on TikTok and the content was largely similar. The researcher felt that they managed to streamline one for the Greens-SDP direction and the other remained more eclectic with anti-elitist voices and the Greens, Left Alliance and SDP. While the politically curious researcher got a lot of content for the whole period, surpassing the scale. The third organic profile gained political content from the beginning, continuing towards the end. The range of actors started to get a bit narrowed down (or rather, the same actors were performing strongly from the start), and the role of parody content in the feed was notable. The actors in the videos were similar with the exception of beyond Finland actors, who were more prominent on TikTok than on Instagram.

Differences Observed Over Time

Initially, data gathering, following and observing were difficult due to the algorithm training, during which both political content and non-political content shown were occasionally even months old on both platforms. There had been presidential elections in January 2024 and some significant political debates. Over the course of data gathering period, one could start to see more recent videos related to the election and the political process overall. The feeds showed various campaign appearances, world events, and other news.

One could also observe a significant ramp up in the political content frequency closer to the elections, especially around the time less than week before the election day. In some feeds, one could also see an observable drop in political content after the election day and the weekend. Although synthetic profiles continued to provide political content, it did show mixed post- and pre-election videos from MPs and candidates.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Finland over time

Instagram was initially very difficult to train towards political content with the synthetic profile, whereas the organic one was more flexible towards it, even if it was set up only for this task and had no previous existence or training. Since the synthetic and organic profiles differed in their preferences, they also got really differentiated over time. With the organic profile, the content remained more versatile, especially

on Instagram, where there were also posts from e.g. Left-green parties as well as National Coalition politicians. Instagram’s videos got really old after the elections especially with the synthetic far-right profile, most likely because the far right lost the elections in Finland. The only one providing any content was Tynkkynen who was elected.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Finland over time

Centre right profiles corroborate on the differences between TikTok and Instagram. TikTok became much more focused on national content though some European parliamentary groups also became visible closer to election. Instagram had much more variety in presence of national parties but especially European parliamentary groups were much more visible on Instagram including Greens-EFA, Renew Europe and EPP. While EPP was also visible on TikTok around elections, it was very focused on Ursula von der Leyen.

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

Although many of the candidates did use both platforms for their campaign videos, there were some differences in the type of content shown on TikTok and on Instagram. TikTok seemed to have much more focused content based on the individual personalities and their accounts, as well as showing specifically the Finnish politics and EP elections. Instagram account had more activity with various

organizational accounts belonging to the Finnish political parties, but also much more prominent presence of the European political groups such as Greens-EFA, Renew Europe, or EPP.

Most candidates used both platforms. Instagram was more prone to show content with candidates talking about a specific theme, with opposition parties especially criticising the Finnish government and their decisions and campaigning with them for the EP elections. These included questions on social security and environmental policy especially. The platforms also included similarities and some of the candidates used both of them.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

The Ukraine-Russia war was especially visible in the beginning of the data collection period. Also, videos for boosting the performance and readiness level of the Finnish military were appearing in the beginning. The Israel-Gaza conflict (from a perspective sympathetic to the humanitarian crisis in Gaza and critical against the continuing military activities of Israel) appeared throughout the data collection, but to a lesser extent.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

Videos shown on TikTok and Instagram were usually different. In the centre-right feed, we had a lot more personal and local content on TikTok while Instagram tended to show much more information about Europe and European parliamentary groups. The widest gap in content seemed to be between synthetic and organic profiles. For example, the centre-right synthetic profile showed consistently political content across the entire data gathering period, but the organic profile's political content was centred around the week before elections, showing almost no content at the start and after the elections. TikTok was considerably more intense especially on the far-right content and the type of content was more aggressive (including quite a bit of military content). TikTok did not display so much green party content and the way the Israel-Gaza conflict was discussed was more through commentaries, which demanded peace-building than in the case of Ukraine. In contrast for the red-green profiles TikTok did provide green content, too. The anti-capitalist content on TikTok seemed to be a particular feature to the platform: foreign American content and national Finnish content were connected in the feed. The better curated feed on TikTok was a significant part of the watching experience, and contrasted with Instagram, whose flow of videos seemed a bit haphazard. Talking heads were a winning formula in the audience appeal. Often, images and text were used to capture the attention or to form a point of reference. Simple rant also worked well; in any length, it seemed.

Section 4: Finland: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section, we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process, simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI-produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

A variety of topics were popular and recurring. Each of the conflicts and military-related topics were very recurring. Ukraine-Russia war through various war-focused videos as well within the context of political content. The Israel-Gaza conflict mostly through local protests. Immigration was a popular topic in campaign videos and surprisingly occasionally echoed in videos of NC candidates in addition to the PS. Economy was a common topic across a variety of parties, the Green Deal came up often especially with left-wing candidates, as well as discussions about education and the welfare state.

Social security and border security were prominent topics among the far-right feeds on both platforms. The shortcomings in the Finnish government's environmental policy and the rather hostile attitude of the current government towards climate action were a recurring topic of the left-green politicians. The single clip of Prime minister Orpo being criticised in the EP of his government's constellation and having the Finns Party in it, was a recurring clip throughout the period for several feeds

The red-green feed often focused on opposing the national government, whereby the social Europe was trending. Among the interesting things that occurred on was that TikTok started featuring anti-capitalist content on the red-green accounts. The political content of the feed solidified quite fast on TikTok, and it started to be more systematic with the accounts and themes present, as the algorithm curated the content in a more coherent way than Instagram. An example would be criticism of the austerity policies and capitalism in Finland were matched with the Rathbone or other anti-capitalist accounts from the US.

With the far-right synthetic profile, Instagram got quite monotonous towards the end since Tynkkynen was the only really prominent figure there. His content was skilfully framed but really if it had not been for TikTok's right-wing content beyond Finland, the picture would have gotten truly narrow. Green Deal, Social Europe and NATO-related discussions were recurring especially on TikTok.

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 25: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

A significant amount of the video feed showed a wide variety of different types of AI-generated content. Mostly through AI-synthesised speech of public figures, parodying them. Additionally, videos tended to use AI-generated imagery as an image collage being spoken over, context for these videos tended to be propagandistic. Outright racist, misogynistic, and anti-LGBTQ videos were seen though they were not very common. Anti-migrant sentiment was an occasional theme from the candidates of the Finns Party. While religious content was not particularly common, especially in the context of political content, videos about promoting religious values and lifestyles (both Christian and Muslim) were seen.

Anti-migrant and Misogynistic content were mostly prominent among Trump and the Finns Party supporters. Many videos included either a candidate speaking or a candidate speaking in an event or for example, in the parliament (national or EP), with some text commenting on them, sometimes also a person commenting.

For example, the red-green accounts had pro-queer and anti-racist content, but this is not visible in the answers here as we sought for the negative sentiments. This was a trend across the period.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

On the far-right account, anti-immigration content was a prominent feature. This was especially represented by Sebastian Tynkkynen’s campaign as well as the account of the Finns Party on Instagram, where immigration was referred to frequently. Debates for and against the renewal of the Finnish border legislation was ongoing, and the Finnish government had one of the Finns Party ministries (the Ministry of the Interior, Mari Rantanen) responsible for this. In addition to this theme, the feeds included content which criticised the National Coalition Party and prime minister Orpo for forming a governmental coalition with the Finns Party. The themes for which he was especially criticised for were the perceived racism of some of the Finns party members and the alignment between the parties as governmental allies.

The EU as a strong actor in environmental policy showed up within both positive and negative frames. For example, the recent directive for the plastic caps in bottles was ridiculed in the Finns Party posts on Instagram as an overkill of political steering, while the Green Party candidates especially highlighted the potential of the EU to do more to protect the environment .

On gender, the content for the far-right account in TikTok was strongly proposing non-political masculine-coded content in the beginning, such as workout videos, cars and driving, and pro-military and patriotic content before turning towards more explicit campaign feed.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

US politics and the upcoming US Presidential elections were extremely common topics in the feed with Trump being either seen or mentioned often. Putin was also seen regularly although more in the beginning.

For the centre-right feed but also the red-green, in European politics one could often see content from France and Germany. French content usually revolved around Emmanuel Macron, while German content had a bit more variety but often related to AfD or European parliamentary groups or parties, such as EPP or Volt Germany. Hungarian government content appeared on the centre-right feed in the beginning of the data gathering period.

For the far-right, in European politics, the content was a lot about Hungarian politics and Orbán’s addresses. Trump and US politics were a bit hard to avoid, but reappeared. The war in Ukraine and Gaza was present in a diversity of ways. It was perhaps a bit surprising that, on the far-right content, German politics were not prominent, but the emphasis was on the US politics. Clips from the war in Ukraine continued to show for a long period. Once the far-right TikTok feed started leaning towards the US elections, the feed frequently showed anti-woke content, where Donald Trump for example responded to a critical question on his stance on women’s rights and gender.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

For the left-green, it was mostly Clare Daly and Ville Niinistö appearing, and a random AfD-related content in relation to Germany. The European Greens and the EPP were quite much present for the red-green accounts. Sometimes there were mentions of Orbán and Marine Le Pen in the anti-far-right commentary. Also, Russia and Putin featured recurrently, mostly from a critical perspective. Some cultural actors hyped Europe: “The first video with FC Bayern promoting the EU described the basis of the EU and why to vote Europhilic. Prime material and a challenge to others.” (26 May F11 Organic, Instagram)

As to what kind of content the foreign content shown in Finland was: “Hungarian foreign minister Péter Szijjártó talking about how EU countries are not living up to the sanctions against Russia that they say they are – that is, accusing them of being misleading in their rhetoric. Interesting because Hungary now keeps appearing in my [far-right] feed. Also, the Polish former prime minister said they should bring Trump back because he wouldn’t have allowed the Ukrainian war to happen.” (27 May 2024, F13, Synthetic TikTok)

The appearance of Claire Daly across Europe has been a puzzle, as the researcher with the red-green feed commented: “The far-left Claire Daly had two videos in my feed that are mostly green and Social Democratic. I wonder if this is financed (by whom) or brought through the algorithm. One of them was

about Gaza and the other about the European Citizen initiative, which matches my feed that has a lot of stuff against violence against women.” (6 June 2024, F11 synthetic IG) They noted: “Claire Daly (IR GUE-NGL) speech in the parliament on European colonialism. Changed my feed to Gaza. (27 May 2025, F11 synthetic) They also noted that her organic feed does not get Claire Daly even if the content has been more left-wing. (29 May 2025, FI odd things to note).

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

Security was an important theme in the elections. Support for Ukraine was a permanent feature in the feeds, particularly for the centre-right candidates in Finland, but also for others. More generally, war related themes came in some varieties. War-related content in the centre-right synthetic feed was often tied to the campaigning or informative videos. Conversely, the organic profiles had a larger number of either AI-generated, or fearmongering videos related to conflict with Russia.

Pro-Palestine protest videos were a common theme across the platforms in both organic and synthetic, although the protest videos were much more common in the earlier half of the gathering period. Examples include: “The Chair of the Finnish Communist Party gave a report after the debate of small parties. She had her red Palestina scarf on, and this had been noticed. She also had mentioned that most Finns are against Israel's attacks on Gaza, which the journalist thought was daring, but in fact the same media, Finnish National Broadcasters YLE had just published a survey study indicating this.” (FI Organic, TikTok, 6 June).

In the synthetic profiles (far-right), war-related content was mostly about Russia-Ukraine and included combat training, footage of individual soldiers in the Ukrainian front, gun videos, NATO strategies, defence in the Nordics and glory for the Finnish troops in different ways. In the organic profiles, Israel-Gaza was commented on through peace process claims, showing Gaza footage on the destruction after Israeli strikes, or Clare Daly. Putin was rather randomly, featuring on both types every now and then, mostly through ironic framing.

Threats to Equality and Diversity

Most of the videos related to threats to equality and diversity were accounts that were not at least overtly connected to political profiles and campaigns. A lot of the anti-equality and anti-diversity videos were not natively Finnish, rather being either about US politics or the content otherwise was English. Anti-migrant sentiment was seen from candidates of the Finns Party and on occasion from some candidates of the National Coalition party. Anti-equality content rose in frequency only towards the end of the collection period through Trump and the US elections especially. Anti-immigration content was published by the Finns Party and Orbán connected contents mostly, Tynkkynen also making a point of challenging the anti-immigrant brand of the Finns Party by introducing his spouse in one of the Finnish TV shows. On the far-right profile, there was an expectation of getting more anti-Muslim content ,but this was not prominent (an early racist, anti-Muslim video indicated something like this, but this did not materialise).

Migrant voices were also present on these platforms in Finnish or in other languages. Many were election candidates, others, particularly on the organic feeds, explained life in Finland. Some even gave advice on how to survive in Finland. Examples include “Paco Diop video on systemic racism in Finland and how he has been working on a better world for black and brown children” (5 May 2024, F11 Organic TikTok).

There was quite a lot of Pride-related and other pro-queer content in the red-green feeds: “these were on the other hand upset about the ways in which these issues were dealt with or celebrating diversity. Pride week was well present by male and female content creators. One account HumanistiViikinki explained men’s misogyny, while there were two videos by Perttu Jussila on Pride and homophobia” (5 May 2024, F11 Synthetic TikTok).

The openly gay politician Sebastian Tynkkynen from the Finns Party, who became an MEP, was blaming the far left of being aggressive when he went to a bar. Also, after the election, there was a knife attack in Oulu, and this was covered in the feeds. These were angry and ridiculed Riikka Purra, who first took the position that this was another attack by a migrant person, while it was actually someone with far-right leanings. It was a shock to many content creators.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content was a recurring although irregular theme in the feed. As seen in the centre-right and red-green synthetic profiles' feeds, there was a theme of political humor and parody through the use of AI, in the form of synthesized speech of Finnish politicians having imagined conversations or songs. Some fully AI-generated videos were also seen in the centre-right feed, mostly anti-governmental videos, for example PM Petteri Orpo dancing about public sector cuts. AI features also included quizzes such as preferred chocolate bars or other consumables by the candidates, making their personas show. The use of AI was rather limited to harmless things, rather than deep fakes or hate speech. Most of the parody content showing up in the far-right profile were embedded in clips of TV shows. This behavioural emphasis in watching the videos probably resulted in not otherwise having so much AI-generated content on either profile. One of the most entertaining contents were the *Pressat Pelaa* videos popular on the centre-right and red-green synthetic and organic accounts, where top politicians, including former and current presidents (*Pressat*) were playing Minecraft. These popular videos featured AI-generated commenting contemporary or futuristic politics. Parody opened up a tool for voicing criticism and projecting to futures. We explain more about this in the section on typology. The parody script was commenting on politics and making fun of politicians across the board. But they were also somewhat critical of the far-right.

Section 5: Finland: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In this section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

Political content frequency ramped up over time. Content was very mixed and infrequent at the start of data gathering, especially in the organic profile feed. Political content shown was at its peak around the week before the election until the election. After the election and the subsequent week, the political content shown dropped significantly, some feeds showing almost none to none at all political content.

On both platforms, the frequency of political content increased over time until the elections. Afterwards, Instagram slowed down and showed mostly old materials in Reels, if even that. TikTok was more prominent probably since the content was also more beyond Finland and the elections in the US for example of course went on.

The feeds were filled with political content quite unevenly (see Figures 24a and 24b), with the red-green feed being the most populated one.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

Based on the data collection experience, it is fair to say that the type of audio-visual content can influence political debates to a degree. This argument draws on especially the way in which the TikTok feed got very quickly started elaborating on associated content, regardless of the political leaning of the profile. Therefore, the feeling of having one's preferred messages reaffirmed on different sides was strong, and introducing new actors and characters into the mix, creating a sense of expanding the community, was visible. At the same time, there is an element of randomness of how this influence can be achieved: based on this experience, it feels like creating a systematic message across national and political contexts and demographic groups to broad influence, probably requires also a systematic and coordinated effort. In a sense, contents like environmentalism or anti-immigration can have a universal appeal, but most likely, even this influence requires investment of actors who are close to the local content and able to translate nuances.

Emotional mechanisms

The far-right feed was tough for the data gatherer who remarked that watching and collecting data on a profile not matching their own values at all quite burdening, especially since TikTok got so intense with the content towards the elections. One got a feeling of being dragged into a closed yet very public community of like-minded, inward-looking group. However, as an observation this is very problematic since they were able to detect some of the same logic with the political content more matched with their own values while this still did not feel as intense – probably because it was something they felt mostly aligned with.

Another data gatherer remarked that the far-right comments on most topics made them feel quite depressed and anxious, while more left-green mostly made them feel angry towards the far-right and conservative-right politics in Finland and the US.

The reaction to most of the far-right content was, as mentioned above, anxiety or incredulous feelings about what type of untrue claims were made about, for example, immigrants or women. And in turn, the left-green content got a reaction of anger quite often as the struggle against racism, misogyny, and environmental destruction seems so slow and frustrating considering the far-right content. One of the data gatherers remarked that reactions and feelings to these were a growing sense of aggression (synthetic), confusion and anger (both profiles), but also numbness in the face of all that content.

On the other hand, some of the watching was pleasurable. Getting insights from politicians and ordinary people on how they view politics was interesting. Often there were old videos in the feed, but at current affairs also did feature. One of the irritating things about the feed-based media following was that one never knew what one got. At the same time, there were surprises. "I did also laugh", one of the data gatherers remarked.

Video Typologies

The most powerful formats were the *talking heads* who engaged directly with the speaker. Then the algorithm changed, talking heads on similar topics, but not the same videos were featured several times. The topics were lighter on Instagram, which could be more every day or recreational, than on TikTok, which was a platform for political rants.

Many of the political videos *explained* political issues to the general public or followers: taking up a thematic that had been in the news and engaging with this in a citizen journalist or political activist perspective. There was also more *election advert style*. When it came to showing Finnish candidates for EP Elections, or other Finnish politicians, the feeds emphasised *debate highlights* and *explainer videos*. Some *public event speeches* were available, as well as other types, but these two stood out. The debate highlights included clips from the Finnish parliament *Eduskunta* or from legacy media's election debates. These were cut into a vertical format or commented on top or bottom in the original horizontal format.

Finnish centre-right and red-green candidates mostly focused on the *explainer type* with some elements of *selfie types*. This was to gain a closeness to the viewer. Candidates from the National Coalition and Greens, in particular, often presented themselves in front of the camera explaining some policy or topic in front of camera in casual manner.

Centre party tended to focus on casual *selfie type* content that did not entirely focus on politics, often involving casual topics in casual settings such as a car ride for example by Mika Lintilä (Centre) but also by Atte Harjanne (Greens), or cottage outdoors. Maria Ohisalo, the former leader of the Greens showed her collections of bicycles or old Nintendos. These were of course generating more closeness to the viewer.

Sometimes emotional mechanisms of the videos were different. More aggressive commentary from for example Perttu Jussila (Greens) or Aleksanteri Gustafsson (Social Democrats) was commenting on contemporary discussions, with screenshots of press clipping or images that were prevalent. Anti-far-right content was typically in this format.

In the case of the beyond-Europe content, the videos were less about the explainer type. We found the explainer videos actually quite effective regardless of our alignment or misalignment with the values it expressed, if the candidate seemed at home with the platform format.

Some videos for example by the Centre Party were old-school horizontal videos with beautiful scenery from the countryside, indicating that TV or YouTube content was circulated to the short-video platforms by the candidates or their parties.

Car ride Selfie typology was common among some candidates such as Lintilä (Centre party, left picture) and Harjanne (Greens, right picture).

Some are at home in front of the camera. Sebastian Tynkkynen (Finns Party) often had a talk show or podcast-type of setting. As an experienced YouTuber in the Finnish political landscape Tynkkynen has been producing far-right content to the internet for a long time. In the caption, he asks if “all whites are grown into racism?”

The length of the videos varied. Some were just some clips with a moving image or slogan. Some of the young candidates for the Left Alliance Lauri Linden, could just stand with a statement where his claim was posted, or Julia Sangervo or Ville Meriläinen (*Terapeutti Ville – Ville the Therapist*) would have a statement in their feed. But there were full 10-minute length rants by some politicians, notably Jesse Jokelainen who was explaining the logic of capitalism to the audience while walking the streets of the northern Finnish city Oulu, of course in the local accent.

Network and peer promotion is strongly identified with National Coalition candidates. In picture Finnish PM Orpo (NC) promoting EU values and membership through National Coalition TikTok channel. There were also some differences between candidates in their choice of companions to the videos. “Pekka Toveri’s election video started with Elina Valtonen and featured many National Coalition people, it was on his expertise in the field of security. Contrast to Markku Rentto (first video) who only casts men discussing his economic policy.” (7 June 2024, F11 Organic, TikTok)

Aleksanteri Gustafsson (SDP) was recurring figure in left-green and centre right feeds. His political commentary used

political humour and sarcasm heavily. In the pictured video he was *in search of the political animal ‘sivistysporvari’ (liberal bourgeois idealist)*, which had become a rare animal after National Coalition joined forces with far-right Finns Party to form the current government.

Sociability of the platform came from the way in which multiple people were present in the videos. The non-candidate members of National Coalition promoted candidates from their party on their own or on the candidate’s videos. For example, the prime minister Petteri Orpo would be showing up in some of the candidate’s video calling for votes for the candidate. Often this would be of the bromance style male bonding, but in some of the videos this would be a different dynamic. The former Green Party chair Maria Ohisalo turned up in a video of her very prolific former aid Perttu Jussila, for a joined event. Sometimes candidates’ video was about giving positive feedback to others.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Maria Ohisalo (Green League) sharing her collection of old game consoles on Instagram, in picture showing the first Nintendo console made.

Something that was interesting was the way in which in a candidate based electoral system, the candidates made their personas present in the campaign. An example of this kind of content was the former Green League Chair who then became an MEP Maria Ohisalo, who on Instagram had series where she presented her own collections to share some of her personal life. In the picture is older video game consoles. She also featured her collection of bicycles.

Supporter video (Yama) for Li Andersson with stylised editing involving various screen transitions and visual effects.

Pressat Pelaa (Presidents Play): AI / synthesised speech video channel on TikTok using placing notable Finnish politicians playing videogames with each other. The videos synthesise speech and use the politicians' voices to 'talk' with each other interweaving political commentary with gameplay commentary to make humorous parody on various political topics. The gameplay in the video is often generic, usually Minecraft but other games are used in occasion. This political satire channel's content came up in the centre-right and red-green feeds and was among the most interesting and entertaining ones in the whole feed.

41

Funded by
the European Union

A lot of the content was also by traditional media outlets. There election debates and interviews were the most popular format. We list as an example the commercial TV channel “MTV Uutiset” (News) election debate clip on Lindtman SDP challenging Purra on the ID group and Orbán. Orpo was (present) not much appearing in this feed. Purra argued jubilantly and bright-eyed immigration is the key issue after Ukraine. And still did not comment anything on the potential collaboration with Orbán. She got the last word in her summer dress. (F11 Organic, TikTok, 30 May 2024)

Discussion on the most interesting videos

The most interesting political videos were typically TikTok, while Instagram faired better with lifestyle genre.

Perttu Jussila, produced content to both to the Instagram and TikTok. In contrast to the stereotypes of male short video producers, he was a young progressive male, liberal, very good at explaining things. “Perttu Jussila is still a prominent figure and the reason his material is interesting is that he comments on different issues and political questions, emphasising also other than environmental politics and also aiming at clear argumentation. The problem with the Green Party in Finland being that they’re a bit lost and locked with their original agenda, there might be some return to a wider portfolio of issues with this one.” (16 June 2024, FI3, Organic, Instagram)

In both centre-right and far right feeds there was a video by Wille Rydman’s (Finns Party) parliamentary assistant Tuulia Alanko commenting and criticising both *Yleisradio* and the political scientist [and one of the authors of this piece] Emilia Palonen on how YLE has an agenda of choosing “left-wing activist researchers” (referring to Emilia Palonen) to give commentary and analysis. Particularly angered by Palonen’s commentary on how Riikka Purra (Leader of Finns Party) should resign as party leader due to the EP election results. Palonen had expressed that at the moment when there is a significant electoral loss, the seat of the leader is usually put in question. The Finns Party, rather than gaining seats from two to three, halved their vote and only gained one seat with Tynkkynen.

We saw only some extreme right content. Neofascist Blue and Black movement video about that they were allowed to campaign in the EP elections while the Ministry of Justice wants to remove them from party registry. The Party had been added to the registry, despite some doubts about the content of their party programme. On the Finnish far-right they are quite different for their audiovisual communication from the Finns Party (Salojärvi et al. 2023). Imagery is used to paint the Ministry and ‘suva-kit’ (pejorative for anyone on the left) as powerless and crying.

Henna Virkkunen (National Coalition) who was selected as MEP taking care of her horses after the election. Personal video of the key candidate and eventually the Commissioner for Finland, but video does not discuss EP elections and politics at all. Relatability and authenticity are the rhetorical-performative tools that are evoked in these videos (Szebeni & Salojärvi 2022).

Concluding section

What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?

Urging people to vote was a popular theme in the elections. Besides the candidates there were Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and Civil Society Organisations (CSO), even football clubs encouraging people to vote. But our question was to explore why they were to do that to uncover whether there's a social contract in Europe and what is it based on, was the object of study here. The social contract was of course argued on the basis of shared themes and sentiments. Campaign videos and political content in the feed showed significant amount of general pro-European sentiment and arguments as well as favouring democratic institutions and unity. These were often referenced in the context of war, specifically the Russia-Ukraine conflict. In Finland, security and social Europe, even the green deal, were strongly present.

For far-right Finns Party, with Tynkkynen as their top candidate, the EU was presented as a necessary evil which should become more "owned" by MEPs and parties aligned with critical agendas against the influence of the EU on for example, immigration and environmental policy. In effect, by voting for such candidates, it would be possible to generate joint influence at the EU level. The main figure in the argumentation was precisely the EU, not "Europe" as such, that is, the most important reference point was the political and economic union with established institutions and a(n imagined) ruling elite. If anything, Europe was, as presented above, referenced in the context of Russia-Ukraine conflict. The main message was that the EU was something which influences the lives of everyday Finns in a harmful way (through, for example, steering of environmental policy), and which should be stopped from meddling with the Finnish social contract. In this case, the social contract was not an explicitly used concept but constructed through the claims for, for example, maintaining the national-level sovereignty in decision-making in environmental and immigration policies.

Several researchers saw the cork video of the Finns Party that was criticising the EU. "Finns party campaign video that featured for the first time in my feed - it's based on the new caps that the EU regulation brought to cans and bottles (the ones that don't fall off). A couple of workers (male) are in trouble and need to cut one off there, followed by the slogan 'let's decide for ourselves'. not super clever but interesting since it continues the series of campaign videos where the Finns party ridicules the EU for over-regulation. We now know this didn't work, which is also interesting." (11 June 2024, F13, Synthetic, Instagram)

In the red-green profiles Europe is discussed a lot as the place for shared policies on climate and security. The social Europe also emerges a lot – this is particularly in response to the Finnish government's austerity measures. Much of the attention is about the contestation with the government and the threat of the far right is also argued in terms drawing from this experience. Far right is a threat to Europe and would come as a challenge to the existing social contract.

In the centre-right profiles, the Centre Party profiles were very much focused on agriculture, forestry and the possibilities of defending Finland's interests there in Europe. The more prolific profiles in our sample were male candidates, who did not get seats. The National Coalition candidates, who appeared a lot, were discussing economy but did also not gain seats. Therefore, we could deduct that Europe was strongly about security, in terms of conflict, particularly in Ukraine, which from the geographical location of Finland sharing 1300 km border with Russia makes sense.

National Coalition cooperated in their campaign visibly a lot with EPP, involving the promotion of European Union values. While individual candidates focused on national topics, National Coalition

accounts worked together to promote the general EPP campaign centred around Ursula von der Leyen and EPP leadership in the European Union.

The European Greens and Social democrats were also visible in the feeds. Emmanuel Macron and Ursula von der Leyen were popping in several feeds, but it appears to us that the far-right feed was really international and European with Fidesz and even PiS politicians making entries.

Finnish national politics dominated the centre-right and red-green feeds, where the contestation between the austerity government and the opposition was quite palpable in the campaign. While in 2015 the previous austerity government's Prime Minister Juha Sipilä (Centre) had proposed a new social contract after the elections and in the midst of the cuts to public funding, in 2024 the Petteri Orpo (National Coalition) had not proposed them explicitly but had addressed funding of public and civil society institutions and introduced new labour legislation. Much of the videos coming from the opposition parties and contesting the government also implicitly on the basis that this is not in the Finnish Social Contract, where a model of negotiations of labour relations is a different one.

The Finns Party ended up in the centre of the austerity policy under Riikka Purra's leadership – even if their background is in the defence of the poorest in the society as far as the Finnish Rural Party's heritage goes. An example from the video notes, however, argues that Purra thinks that the SDP is secretly in agreement.

“Finns party sharing a video where Riikka Purra criticises Social Democrats for not having the courage to do the cuts that the Finns party is now doing in the government, with a banner 'this is what the social democrats secretly want'. This refers to Purra's statement that the social democrats want the structural reforms that the government is now doing but not they don't want to do it themselves. Purra has a very dramatic exit from the podium which makes a nice effect to the speech.” (13 June 2024, FI3, Synthetic, TikTok).

The fact that the election victory went for Orpo's government on the basis of security judging by choice of the MEPs from the open list of candidates, and the austerity policy of Purra in government backfired with the party gaining only one MEP when three was speculated, and that Left Alliance's leader Li Andersson got a landslide of personal votes and three MEPs to Brussels (Lahti and Palonen 2025), indicates that there are some issues with social contract and the acceptance of the government policies.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

Indeed, to follow from the previous account, the main confrontation was the one between the opposition and Petteri Orpo's government, as a lot of the criticism was on their policies in Finland. Also, many on the left and green side criticised the far-right Finns Party (in government with minister Purra). The left was criticised mainly by the Finns Party.

In the discourses that highlighted security Europe, EU with Ukraine was the “Us”, and Russia presents the threat (also affectively coded) to the unity of Europe and European security. In Finland this was quite palpable. Also, Gaza was seen as part of “Us” in the pro-Palestine videos. Social media offered a platform for pro-Palestine sentiment where those who did not think it is important were also rejected as other.

Us-building was part of the pride videos, too. Where the Pride discourses opened the us into a heterogeneous category, they also contested their critics. There was also anti-queer content in the far-right, and almost exclusively in the far-right feeds. Many male content producers were also posting anti-misogynist content.

In Eurosceptic discourses, mainly by some of the Finns Party posts, national autonomy was emphasised: Finns were the “Us” and EU criticised as the frontier. As the example from above indicated from the perspective of the plastic caps on bottles ridiculing provided the affective pinning on the EU and Us the Finns were seen as the clever ones.

Conclusions

The European elections in Finland were a victory to the pro-EU, trans-Atlanticist National Coalition party (EPP), who gained four seats, and the Left Alliance (The Left, GUE) got three surprisingly overtaking the usual large parties SDP (Progressives) and Centre Party (Renew) and the he Green League (Greens) who got two seats each, followed by the far-right Finns Party (ECR) and the liberal Swedish People’s Party (Renew) got two. The country has a nation-wide vote and an open list, which emphasizes the need for prominent candidates. We saw the profiling in short videos and the presence of the parties in the feed. TikTok and Instagram supported the candidate-centred politics in Finland, making it easier to communicate the policies and persona of the candidate.

The themes were relatively evenly distributed, with both arguments for Europe (economic, social, and climate as well as defence) and grievance politics dominating. The main division seemed to form between the government and opposition parties, but also between the right-wing conservative and the progressive left-greens. There were differences of campaign strategies, especially in the way in which the existing links to previously selected MEPs were utilised, and how the EU was positioned in the content. Common to most content was that EU politics were strongly linked with the domestic, internal Finnish politics and the debates there, for example, on social security and welfare politics, environmental politics, and immigration.

As in Finland the elections to the European Parliament are very much focused on the open party lists, it is a competition between candidates for the few seats the small member state has. The candidates across the spectrum were present in our feeds. Out of the profiles, the centre-right profile had the most distributed feed when it comes to parties and persons, rendering a broad scope in terms of both actors and content. The Finnish electoral system is based on individual candidates, even if these individuals are prominently candidates for political parties. For the Finns Party and the Left Party, strong individuals such as Sebastian Tynkkynen and Li Andersson dominated the feeds. Our red-green account was focused on the Greens and SDP, so it did not see a hype of the Left Alliance candidate Li Andersson, who nevertheless was the queen of the elections, gathering 14 percent of the total votes as her personal votes.

For the Greens, however, there were quite a few individual candidates appearing, such as Maria Ohisalo, Ville Niinistö, Perttu Jussila and the party leader Sofia Virta. From SFP only Anna-Maja Henriksson stood out in the feed. The Christian democrats had some promotional videos of their main candidate Eija-Riitta Korhola. National Coalition had a few prominent candidates from which Mika Aaltola stood out by his individually driven campaign, other candidates such as Henna Virkkunen and Aura Salla, Jocka Träsckbäck had recurring presence. From Centre Party Mika Lintilä, who was not elected, had much greater presence in the feed than the elected candidates Elsi Katainen and Katri

Kulmuni. A lot of middle-aged males were seen in the feeds of these platforms that until recently were seen as more for the youth.

The research team reflected their data collection practices further when drafting the report, and they have been taken into account in the analysis. As usual for an interpretative approach, the practices most likely affected the results from different feeds. The radical right was turning into inward-looking and with few major content producers other than Tynkkynen who became the only MEP for the party. In contrast, the centre-right and red-green feeds were collegial and active in producing content also in joined videos and appearances. In this sense, we could see that the following of the feeds, combined with the knowledge of the context, particularly the presidential elections that had been held months before, could help in anticipating the results to some degree at least. The short-video format worked for political communication of the social contract – joined themes – and grievance politics in Finland.

Bibliography

- Lahti, Y. & Palonen, E.** (2025). "Populism and EP Elections – Case Finland: Populism Gone Mad from Scissors and Chopping-board to Firing Guns and Latino Rush." *Populism & Politics (P&P)*. European Center for Populism Studies (ECPS). April 28, 2025. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.55271/pp0049>
- Salojärvi, V., Palonen, E., Horsmanheimo, L., & Kylli, R. M.** (2023). Protecting the future 'Us': a rhetoric-performative multimodal analysis of the polarising far-right YouTube campaign videos in Finland. *Visual Studies*, 38(5), 851–866. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1472586X.2023.2249430>
- Szebeni, Z., & Salojärvi, V.** (2022). "Authentically" Maintaining Populism in Hungary – Visual Analysis of Prime Minister Viktor Orbán's Instagram. *Mass Communication and Society*, 25(6), 812–837. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2022.2111265>

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results France

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Stephen Sawyer, Roman Zinigrad, Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, The American University of Paris; Alina Mozolevska, Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, Szilvia Horváth, and Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Pinar Uyan-Semerci (Istanbul Bilgi University)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: France: EP Election Results	4
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	4
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	6
Section 2: France: Political profiles	8
# Centre-Right feed	9
# Far Right feed	12
# Red-Green feed	15
# Visibility of Political actors	18
Section 3: France: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	20
# Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	20
# Notes on Organic Profiles	21
# Differences Observed Over Time	23
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok	27
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	28
Section 4: France: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	29
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	29
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram	31
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	31
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	32
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	33
# AI Generated Content	34
Section 5: France: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	35
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time	35
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate	35
# Emotional mechanisms	36
# Video Typologies	36
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	37
# Discussion on the most interesting videos	40
Concluding section	41
# What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?	41
# Populist mobilisation	42
# Conclusion	42
Bibliography	43

France: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

The 2024 European Elections in France were as important nationally as for the European Union. Following the 2019 elections, they reinforced the emergence of a new political landscape marked by the rise of the far-right as the main political force (Brack and Startin, 2020). Since 2022, French politics has been characterized as being constituted of three poles, which are very much represented in the results: the left block, the center block and the far-right block. The 2024 European Elections underscore trends in this regard, with a clear dynamic in favor of right-wing populism (CEVIPOF, 2024; Kahil, 2025).

The elections an important success for the far-right, which gathered more than 40% of the voting shares, driven by the 31.5 per cent of the Rassemblement National (National Rally) and their leader, Jordan Bardella. They also displayed the defeat of the Presidential party, Renew Europe, with only 13.8 per cent of the votes. At the same time, the combined score of the political left attained 34 per cent, especially driven by the good results of Raphaël Glucksmann, the candidate of the Parti socialiste (Socialist Party), with 15 per cent of the votes. Following the results, the President, Emmanuel Macron, decided to dissolve the National Assembly and called for Legislative elections.

Our data gathering, with three profiles – far-right, centre-right, and red-green profiles – revealed the powerful presence of the far-right on social media: even the left-wing accounts positioned themselves in response to the far-right, who imposed their themes on the campaign (immigration, security, Islam). We believe that social media, particularly TikTok, has significantly amplified the reach of far-right content, potentially influencing both the media and voters during elections.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Les élections européennes de 2024 en France ont été aussi importantes au niveau national que pour l'Union européenne. Non seulement les élections ont été un succès important pour l'extrême droite, qui a recueilli plus de 40% des voix, tirée par les 31,5% du Rassemblement national et de son leader, Jordan Bardella, mais elles ont également affiché la défaite du parti présidentiel, Renew Europe, avec seulement 13,8% des voix. Dans le même temps, le score cumulé de la gauche atteint 34%, notamment grâce aux bons résultats de Raphaël Glucksmann, le candidat du Parti Socialiste, avec 15% des voix. Suite à ces résultats, le Président Emmanuel Macron a décidé de dissoudre l'Assemblée nationale et a convoqué des élections législatives.

Notre collecte de données, avec trois profils - extrême droite, droite traditionnelle et profils de gauche - a révélé la très forte présence de l'extrême droite sur les médias sociaux : même les comptes de gauche se sont positionnés en réponse à l'extrême droite, qui a clairement imposé ses thèmes dans la campagne (immigration, sécurité, islam). Dans l'ensemble, nous pensons que les médias sociaux, en particulier TikTok, ont amplifié la portée des contenus d'extrême droite, ce qui a peut-être exercé une influence sur les jeunes électeurs lors des élections.

Section 1: France: EP Election Results

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

The general French turnout in the EP elections was 51.5%, a slight increase from 2019. The elections were marked by an astounding increase in the margin of votes for the far-right party of Marine Le Pen, the *Rassemblement National* (RN), whose candidate for the EP was Jordan Bardella. The RN garnered 31.5% of the votes, an increase of 8% from the previous EP elections. The new radical-right party, *Reconquête!* (Reconquest), led by the former presidential candidate Eric Zemmour and appointing Marion Maréchal Le Pen (Marine Le Pen's niece) as the EP representative, scored 5.5%. Macron's centrist party, represented by Valérie Hayer, Renew Europe, received only 13.83%, a drop of about 9% from 2019. This loss of popularity was used by Bardella and the RN to claim that the EP elections were an anti-Macron referendum. The *Place Publique* (Public Square), represented in the EP by Raphaël Glucksmann, the center-left socialist party received 14.6%, an increase of 6% as compared with the previous EP elections. The radical-left *La France Insoumise* (France Unbowed) party, represented in the EP by Manon Aubry, gained 9.9% of the general vote, increasing its popularity by 3%, and *Les écologistes* (The Ecologists), whose top MP in the EP is Marie Toussaint lost about 8% in popularity, receiving only 5.5% in 2024. To sum up, the main trends in the elections were a sharp rise in the popularity of the far-right, loss of support to the ruling party, and a slight increase in popularity of the left-wing parties – mostly built on the demise of the green party.

Compared with the general trends in the EU where the far-right surge was relatively modest, the French electorate showed a significant and alarming shift to the far-right at the expense of the centre-right ruling party.

National Election Results and Party Affiliations

While the polls and political analyses indicated a rise in popularity of the far-right prior to the elections, the extent of the success of the *RN*, *Reconquête!* came as a surprise, as they garnered about 40% of the general vote, at the expense of the traditional right-wing party *Les Républicains* (The Republicans), represented by François-Xavier Bellamy, who scored 7.25%.

Other parties that managed to secure representation in the European Parliament included *La République En Marche* (The Republic on the Move), which, despite a decline in popularity, maintained a significant share of the vote, underscoring its role as a centrist force. *Les écologistes* achieved notable success as well, reflecting a growing concern among voters regarding environmental and climate issues. The left-wing *La France Insoumise* also secured seats, although their performance remained modest compared to the far-right surge. Traditional socialist parties, though diminished, managed to retain a minimal presence, indicating an enduring albeit weakened base of support.

Results by national party - 2024-2029

France - Official results

Figure 1.
Results by national party

Percentage of votes

National Parties

RN - Rassemblement national

Besoin d'Europe - Coalition Besoin d'Europe (Renaissance, Modem, Horizons, Parti Radical, Union des démocrates et indépendants)

Réveiller l'Europe - Coalition Réveiller l'Europe (Parti socialiste, Place publique)

LFI - La France Insoumise

LR - Les Républicains

LE - EELV - Les Écologistes - Europe Écologie Les Verts

La France fière - Coalition La France fière (Reconquête!, Centre national des indépendants

et paysans)

Gauche Unie - Coalition Gauche Unie (Parti communiste français, Gauche républicaine et socialiste)

AR - Alliance Rurale

PA - Parti Animaliste

UPR - Union Populaire Républicaine

L'Europe ça suffit - Coalition L'Europe ça suffit (Les Patriotes, Via, la voie du peuple)

NPA - Nouveau Parti Anticapitaliste

Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

The main highlight and unexpected result of the EP election in France – at least for national politics – is its outcome: the dissolution of the parliament by President Macron on 9 June 2024, the night of the results. This acknowledged Bardella’s demand to dissolve the parliament, as the elections displayed a major defeat for the Presidential party.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in France

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

The most visible and prominent MEPs in our data gathering exercise were representatives of the extremes: the far-right and far-left parties. The most ubiquitous political candidate on social media was Jordan Bardella, the top MP of the *Rassemblement National*, whose age and charisma played a significant role in the sharp rise in support of the far-right among French youth, notwithstanding his lack of political experience. Bardella currently has close to 1.5 million followers on TikTok. Marion Maréchal was closely following Bardella in popularity on social media and expressing more blatant Islamophobic and anti-migrant views. While attracting the support of radical-right voters, the support for Maréchal's party, *Reconquête!*, did not come at the expense of *RN*. Other fringe far-right parties included the Rural Alliance, led by Jean Lassalle, and *Les patriotes* (The Patriots), chaired by François Philippot.

The France Insoumise, the far-left party, maintained an important presence on social media as well, especially Manon Aubry, the top MP of the list, and Rima Hassan (a rising star due to her vocal support for Palestine) supported with numerous other national representatives (such as Louis Boyard, Manuel Bompard, and others). This translated modestly in the results, since the polls predicted LFI at 6%.

Raphaël Glucksmann’s campaign was a success for *Place Publique* party marking the resurgence of centre-left socialist party. In the EP 2024, Glucksmann led the list Réveiller l'Europe, an alliance of *Place Publique* with *Parti socialiste*. He secured 13.83% of the national vote, a significant increase from

6

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

France - Constitutive session

the 6.19% obtained in 2019. This strong result made *Réveiller l'Europe* the third-largest list in France, solidifying Raphaël Glucksmann' political leadership and underscoring the emergence of *Place Publique* as a political force. *Place Publique's* success probably explains the downfall of the Greens, who usually particularly succeed in EP elections. This probably reflects the fact that this EP elections in France showed the importance of geopolitics (Ukraine-Russia and Israel-Palestine) at the expense of ecology.

Curiously, Valérie Hayer, who has been serving as a MEP since 2019 and was leader of the *Renew Europe* party during the 2024 European election, did not manage to attract much attention on social media. Despite holding a prominent position within her party and participating actively in campaign events, her online presence lacked the visibility and engagement seen with other high-profile candidates. Her statements and interviews on national television were most often used by her opponents for the purpose of ridicule and attack of Macron and her party.

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PIE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
RN	31.37%			30							30
Besoin d'Europe	14.60%					13					13
Réveiller l'Europe	13.83%		13								13
LFI	9.89%							9			9
LR	7.25%	6									6
LE - EELV	5.50%						5				5
La France fière	5.47%				4				1		5
Gauche Unie	2.36%										0
AR	2.35%										0
PA	2.00%										0
UPR	1.02%										0
L'Europe ça suffit	0.93%										0
NPA	0.15%										0
Other parties	3.28%										0
	100.00%	6	13	30	4	13	5	9	1	0	81

RN > PIE: MATHILDE ANDROUET, JORDAN BARDELLA, MARIE-LUCE BRASIER-CLAIN, MARIE DAUCHY, VALÉRIE DELOGE, MÉLANIE DISDIER, GAËTAN DUSSAUSAYE, ANNE-SOPHIE FRIGOUT, ANGÉLINE FURET, JEAN-PAUL GARRAUD, CATHERINE GRISET, FRANCE JAMET, VIRGINIE JORON, SYLVIE JOSSEAND, FABRICE LEGGERI, JULIEN LEONARDELLI, THIERRY MARIANI, ALEKSANDAR NIKOLIC, PHILIPPE OLIVIER, GILLES PENNELLE, PASCALE PIERA, PIERRE PIMPIÉ, JULIE RECHAGNEUX, ANDRÉ ROUGÉ, JULIEN SANCHEZ, MALIKA SOREL, RODY TOLASSY, MATTHIEU VALET, ALEXANDRE VARAUT

PS > S&D: CHRISTOPHE CLERGEAU, CLAIRE FITA, JEAN-MARC GERMAIN, PIERRE JOUVET, FRANÇOIS KALFON, MURIELLE LAURENT, NORA MEBAREK, EMMA RAFOVICZ, CHLOÉ RIDEL, ERIC SARGIACOMO

LFI > The Left: MANON AUBRY, DAMIEN CARÈME, LEILA CHAIBI, EMMA FOURREAU, RIMA HASSAN, MARINA MESURE, YOUNOUS OMARJEE, ARASH SAËDI, ANTHONY SMITH

LR > EPP: FRANÇOIS-XAVIER BELLAMY, LAURENT CASTILLO, CHRISTOPHE GOMART, CÉLINE IMART, ISABELLE LE CALLENNEC, NADINE MORANO

Renaissance > Renew Europe: GRÉGORY ALLIGNE, PASCAL CANFIN, VALÉRIE HAYER, FABIENNE KELLER, STÉPHANIE YON-COURTIN

LE - EELV > Greens/EFA: MÉLISSA CAMARA, DAVID CORMAND, MOUNIR SATOURI, MAJDOULINE SBAI, MARIE TOUSSAINT

MoDem > Renew Europe: LAURENCE FARRANG, SANDRO GOZI, CHRISTOPHE GRUDLER, MARIE-PIERRE VEDRENNE

Place publique > S&D: RAPHAËL GLUCKSMANN, AURORE LALUCQ, THOMAS PELLERIN-CARLIN

DVD > ECR: NICOLAS BAY, GUILLAUME PELTIER

Horizons > Renew Europe: GILLES BOYER, NATHALIE LOISEAU

UDI > Renew Europe: VALÉRIE DEVAUX

Indépendant > ECR: MARION MARÉCHAL

Mouvement conservateur > ECR: LAURENCE TROCHU

Reconquête! > ESN: SARAH KNAFO

Ind. > Renew Europe: BERNARD GUETTA

National Parties

RN - Rassemblement national

Besoin d'Europe - Coalition Besoin d'Europe (Renaissance, MoDem, Horizons, Parti Radical, Union des démocrates et indépendants)

Réveiller l'Europe - Coalition Réveiller l'Europe (Parti socialiste, Place publique)

LFI - La France insoumise

LR - Les Républicains

LE - EELV - Les Écologistes - Europe Ecologie Les Verts

La France fière - Coalition La France fière (Reconquête!, Centre national des indépendants et paysans)

Gauche Unie - Coalition Gauche Unie (Parti communiste français, Gauche républicaine et socialiste)

AR - Alliance Rurale

PA - Parti Animaliste

UPR - Union Populaire Républicaine

L'Europe ça suffit - Coalition L'Europe ça suffit (Les Patriotes, Via, la voie du peuple)

NPA - Nouveau Parti Anticapitaliste

Other parties - Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

● **EPP** - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)

● **S&D** - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament

● **PIE** - Patriots for Europe

● **ECR** - European Conservatives and Reformists Group

● **Renew Europe** - Renew Europe Group

● **Greens/EFA** - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance

● **The Left** - The Left group in the European Parliament - GUE/NGL

● **ESN** - Europe of Sovereign Nations

● **NI** - Non-attached Members

Section 2: France: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

We noticed that the political content on TikTok and Instagram, although very present, was also very poor in terms of content: the videos were mostly about clashes, focusing on the personal charisma of the candidates and focusing a lot on emotions (mostly fear, anger, anxiety, or indignation). Negative campaigning dominated, with many posts aiming to discredit opponents rather than proposing actionable solutions or coherent platforms. Edited videos and meme-like attacks illustrated the negative campaigns of the various parties. Only after the elections could one see a turn to socio-economic topics and more informed policy discussions.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

On TikTok, the far-right has the most visibility, especially the RN. This result aligns with our observation that TikTok is efficient in amplifying far-right narratives. Curiously, the left-green profile viewed the populist left *France Unbowed* more than any other party – which could be explained by the decision of Marie Toussaint, the list leader of *Les écologistes*, of not campaigning actively on social medias – whereas the far-right RN and *Reconquête!* featured in the third and fourth places with *Les écologistes* not appearing at all on the TikTok feed. Instagram paints a more diversified picture. Although *Reconquête!* and RN are still highly visible within the far-right, LFI and Ensemble received more mentions in the left-green and centre-right feeds, respectively. This aligns with the report’s observation that Instagram was less precise than TikTok in detecting political preferences. The far-right’s

commanding presence on TikTok, even within ideologically opposing profiles, underscores the platform’s role in amplifying polarizing content. Instagram, while also favoring the far-right in raw mentions, offers a slightly more balanced representation. These visualizations reaffirm that TikTok is a potent tool for ideological amplification – especially for the far-right – within the French digital political landscape.

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

Centre-Right feed

The centre-right profile was a *Les Républicains* follower. At the beginning, the algorithms of both TikTok and Instagram struggled to find specific content for *Les Républicains* and for the first week the profiles were only getting far-right content. The key influencer was at first Jordan Bardella, a real heavyweight on social media. The researcher responsible for the profile had to look specifically for *Les Républicains*’ leaders, such as François-Xavier Bellamy, Eric Ciotti and others, and to engage systematically with their posts, to have traditional right-wing content.

Once TikTok understood that the synthetic persona was a *Les Républicains*’ supporter, the feed almost only got François-Xavier Bellamy’s posts, with far-right content still appearing from time to time. The feed was therefore pretty robust, especially on TikTok (less so on Instagram).

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

10

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

A lot of the content was from public debates with other candidates, or from interviews in important TV media or online media. This was mostly debating content, with some form of negative campaigning and rarely in-depth information. Bellamy also shot specific short videos for social media, on a variety of topics, such as agriculture, immigration, and economics. These were usually more informative videos without much polemic.

The main themes of his campaign were definitely: immigration, economic liberalism, national sovereignty, and national identity. He also took a position against the student strike for Palestine and globally was in support of Israel’s politics in the Middle East. What distinguished him from the RN’s candidate, Jordan Bardella, was mostly the “respectability” aspect, i.e., the fact that Bellamy was more serious in his participation in the Parliament, passed bills and amendments, among other things.

After the dissolution, the political landscape switched to a focus on national politics again, and Bellamy left the picture, for Ciotti (the head of the party), and his alliance with the RN. Interestingly, given the impressions from the center-right feed, it was not a surprise to witness the proximity between the traditional right-wing party and the far-right. As shown in figures 4a and 4b, the political proximity of *Les republicains* with the *RN* and *Reconquête!* was significant. *RN* and *Reconquête!* were the second and third most viewed parties in the feed, which demonstrates that *Les republicains* leaned more toward the far-right than the center.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Far-Right feed

Social media algorithms showed to be highly efficient in catering to the far-right users' interests and quickly restricting the videos to narrow political bias - TikTok much more efficiently than Instagram.

12

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

The most visible and active actors in the far-right feed were Jordan Bardella and Marion Maréchal, the EU head candidates, followed by their respective party accounts, and to a lesser extent, the head of their parties – Marine Le Pen and Eric Zemmour. Other marginal far-right and conspiracy theorist

runners present in the feed were: Popular Republican Union (François Asselineau), Europe that's enough! (Florian Philippot) and The Rural Alliance (Jean Lassalle). Other accounts were not obviously linked or coordinated with the official accounts and were roughly equally divided between private accounts and organizations.

The four types of videos encountered using a far-right profile of a French young male are: (1) political speeches or public appearances (hugging babies, visiting farms); (2) jingoistic videos of young (white) patriots; (3) overtly Islamophobic and anti-immigrant propaganda; (4) black immigrants justifying racist and anti-immigrant political platforms. Main insights about these videos are:

- Prior to the European elections it was impossible to find substantive content about the parties' platforms. The videos focused on the candidates' persona, charisma, and personal mockery of opponents (characteristically, opponents' speeches would be cut out of context and ridiculed whereas the far-right candidates would be presented in a slick light). But after the European elections and before the national ones, the videos radically shifted to discuss financial and immigration policy.
- Surprisingly, a significant number of videos featured Catholic-religious narratives in combination with military/security themes
- The Islamophobic content was highly violent, e.g., presenting Muslims as pigs or criminals.
- In a blatant victim-blaming campaign, some videos featured black immigrants or residents of former French colonies who justified the racist policies of the *RN* and *Reconquête!* parties.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Red-Green feed

The red-green profile followed the leaders of the parties – *La France Insoumise* (Manon Aubry, Luis Boyard, Mathilde Panot, JL Melenchon), *Les écologistes* (Marie Toussaint), *Parti socialiste* (Raphael 15

Glucksmann), *Équinoxe*. The most visible party on TikTok and Instagram was la France Insoumise with popular young influencers Manon Aubry, Rima Hassan, and Louis Boyard. They appeared regularly in the feed and published varied videos to engage young audiences.

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

16

As for other parties, even after subscription to their channels and systematic interaction with the content of their pages, the videos did not appear in the feed. The researcher had to go to their pages in order to see new content. Despite the profile preferences, right-wing content was also present – the videos of Jordan Bardella or Marine le Pen, also anti-migrant and anti-Islam content was daily present.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

17

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The main themes for the EU campaigning for the left parties were – Gaza-Israel war, social and economic inequalities in France, Russia-Ukraine war. In addition, a lot of content was aimed at criticizing the ruling party and Macron’s personality. As with the center-right profile, a lot of videos were short episodes from public debates with other candidates, from parliament interventions or from interviews in important TV media or online media. Most of these videos tended to present the political opponents in a negative light. The feed was quite solid and consistent, but after the dissolution of the French parliament, the campaigning quickly switched to the promotion of the newly formed coalition Nouveau Front Populaire.

Visibility of Political actors

Across the TikTok feeds, Bardella, Maréchal Le Pen, and Marine Le Pen dominate the far-right profile. In the centre-right TikTok profile, Bellamy leads, with Bardella and Maréchal Le Pen following closely. Even on the left-green profile, Bardella got into the top 5 alongside Boyard, Mélenchon, and Aubry. On Instagram, Bardella again tops all three feeds, but the top 5 shows a broader mix of establishment and insurgent actors. In the centre-right, Zemmour featured in third place. The left-green Instagram is rather surprisingly led by Bardella and Macron, with Attal and Hayer outranking Aubry. Finally, the far-right Instagram chart predictably centres on Bardella, Le Pen, Maréchal, Zemmour, and Knafo, but with slightly lower mention counts than on TikTok.

Taken together, these three feeds reveal two converging dynamics: first, Bardella’s extraordinary digital presence; and second, TikTok’s amplification of far-right personalities versus Instagram’s more diffuse feeds of populists and establishment figures.

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in France

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in France

Section 3: France: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

Throughout the data gathering process, the researchers observed marked differences in the frequency, content, and tone of political material across our synthetic and organic profiles. Political content was particularly prominent on TikTok, where far-right narratives dominated, often conveyed through emotionally charged themes such as fear, anger, and indignation. Synthetic accounts aligned with the far-right were shaped by platform algorithms, while left-wing profiles experienced a more heterogeneous and inconsistent feed, with unexpected exposure to right-wing content. Instagram, by contrast, offered less precision and frequently recycled previous content. Across all profiles, political messaging tended to prioritize negative campaigning and personal attacks over substantive policy discussions. Themes such as immigration, national identity, and security were omnipresent and often framed in exclusionary terms. Engaging with this content daily elicited varying emotional responses, particularly in relation to xenophobic or Islamophobic material. Overall, the experience illuminated how algorithmic dynamics influence the structure and emotional tenor of political discourse.

Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

The synthetic and organic profiles were very different, both within and across platforms, even though both were created at the same time and used only during the datagathering process. For the synthetic accounts, we followed a procedure amounting to like, engage with and follow political content close to our defined political position (traditional right, far-right, left-wing). On some occasions, when we were struggling to find political content, we actively searched for personalities to follow, in order to feed the algorithms.

For the far-right synthetic profile, the online platforms seemed to better curate the content along the chosen political narratives because the choices were more coherent ideologically. The center-right profile was exposed heavily to far-right content, and the researcher had to actively search for *Les Républicains*. The red-green synthetic profile seemed to be less consistent as despite the pre-set political preferences, the content from right-wing parties was also present in the feed.

For the organic profiles, we focused on political content, notwithstanding the political affiliations. One of the profiles specifically looked for European topics, and another was browsing content across the political spectrum. One of the organic profiles ended up finding more international content with the organic profiles, even ending up sometimes on English-speaking short videos (while the synthetic profile was French-speaking only content). The other profile was showing national debates almost exclusively,

20

Funded by
the European Union

without much exposure to debates of other EU member states. Overall, organic profiles may have reflected the researchers' personal political views and hence were somewhat more tilted toward left-wing agendas.

Notes on Organic Profiles

In reviewing the organic profiles across TikTok and Instagram, we observed several key patterns and notable divergences in content exposure, frequency, and thematic emphasis. Unlike the synthetic profiles, the organic accounts - although newly created for the purpose of the study - were not designed to follow a predefined political orientation. Still, these profiles reflected, to some extent, the preferences of the researchers. This allowed us to assess a different baseline of political content circulation during the 2024 European election campaign in France. Despite this neutrality, political content was still significantly shaped by algorithmic trends and platform-specific dynamics.

One of the most salient observations was the overwhelming visibility of far-right actors and themes. Across almost all days of the observation period, figures such as Jordan Bardella and Marion Maréchal appeared with high frequency in the feed, regardless of the lack of direct engagement with far-right content. This trend was more pronounced on TikTok, which seemed to amplify polarizing or emotionally charged content more aggressively than Instagram. The most dominant themes associated with these figures included immigration, national identity, and criticisms of the European Union, often framed through sensationalist or fear-inducing narratives.

In contrast, content from centre-right and traditional left-wing actors was less frequent and less emotionally charged. Figures such as François-Xavier Bellamy or Raphaël Glucksmann appeared sporadically and usually in the context of institutional speeches or debate highlights. Left-wing content, while present, was less algorithmically prioritized unless manually sought out. This included topics such as social justice, the Israel-Gaza conflict, and youth mobilization for equality.

The temporal evolution of the content was also noteworthy. In the initial phase of data collection, political content was sporadic, and the feeds included non-political material, such as entertainment or lifestyle video, especially Instagram. The algorithms, especially TikTok, appeared to respond to this broader national context, integrating more campaign-related content into the feed.

At the country level, we noted that the far-right content was not only more frequent but also more consistently adapted to the short-form video format, often relying on meme-like edits, emotional rhetoric, and rapid visual cues. Most left-wing and centrist actors, by contrast, generally employed longer, less visually dynamic formats, which may have been less compatible with the algorithmic logic of platforms like TikTok. The exception is *La France Insoumise*, who has both very popular politicians (such as Louis Boyard) and influencers, driving the popularity of their online campaign.

Overall, the organic profiles revealed the broader media environment encountered by average users, highlighting both the prevalence of far-right messaging and the structural biases embedded in algorithmic content delivery.

Figures 21a and 21b demonstrate the variety of unique political parties and unique politicians the researchers could observe in their organic accounts daily on Instagram and TikTok. The researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic account was consistently exposed to diverse political content throughout the data-gathering exercise. The researcher responsible for the centre-right account

21

Funded by
the European Union

sporadically received content in the early phase and around the election day, 9 June 2024. Finally, the analysis of the organic profiles of the researcher responsible for the red-green profile indicates that they were exposed to a more diverse content in the final days leading up to and after the election.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Differences Observed Over Time

Organic and synthetic profiles displayed gradual changes over time. In particular, the first days were particularly poor in political content – since both profiles were untrained for both platforms. Researchers ended up with a lot of short videos of dance influencers, dogs and cats, or even OnlyFans Models. Nevertheless, the content evolved quickly after three days, focusing more on political content in general, and then more precisely on the political preferences of the synthetic profiles – or the demands of the organic profiles. This was due to active engagement with political content, but also to active disengagement with nonpolitical content (signalling the content was not of interest to us). For instance, the right-wing profile following Les Républicains was first dragged toward the far-right, with a lot of videos of Jordan Bardella, and had to actively and systematically engage with François-Xavier Bellamy (and related) accounts to have Les Républicains in its feed.

The researchers saw a sharp change in the content and messages on the platforms of both the left and right parties after the EP elections. Before the elections, most of the content on both platforms focused on personal campaigns – both positive and negative – of the candidates and was predominantly

designed in entertaining or fear-mongering forms. After the elections, however, the candidates seemed to start shifting their messages to substantive policy statements, increasingly elaborating on specific suggestions for future reforms. It is likely that this change is due to the dissolution of the French parliament immediately after the EP elections and the parties' urgent need to garner support for the national parliamentary elections.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in France over time

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in France over time

Figures 24a and 24b show the visibility of different political parties in the feeds of the three synthetic profiles on TikTok and on Instagram. The radical right synthetic profile was exposed to content featuring different political parties throughout the campaign on both platforms, yet Instagram consistently provided content featuring more diverse political parties than TikTok. The red-green synthetic profile also consistently recorded content with diverse political parties throughout the data-gathering period, yet on Instagram, the party diversity clearly peaked in the second half of the data-gathering exercise, just before and after the election day. The researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic profile could more consistently record different political parties on TikTok than on Instagram, yet Instagram provided content featuring more diverse political parties than TikTok.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

The main trends observed on both platforms were, most notably: immigration, anti-Muslim messages, the Israel-Gaza conflict, and the war in Ukraine.

The content was similar for both platforms, with short, edited videos of debates or speeches (from longer videos, campaign ads, or back-end solutions). Some of the content was created specifically for social media (usually for both platforms), focusing on a more intimate relationship with the followers (facecam, direct address, etc.).

In our experience, TikTok was much more efficient in curating the content along with the political views of the chosen profile, and quick to adapt to the type of videos that were watched to the end. At least for the far-right profile, we felt that TikTok is, at times, attempting to suggest more polarizing and more violent content as the experiment progressed, potentially with the goal of maximizing the time of use of the app. Instagram seemed to be less responsive to the preferences of the profiles and repeatedly showed the content recycled from previous days.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

Both platforms definitely shared content –as social media, parties, and people producing short videos for both. However, TikTok’s algorithm seemed more efficient in providing specific content for political profiles and matching the profiles’ preferences. Instagram was always slower to match preferences and propose content. In addition, it also regularly offered content that was not related to the chosen preferences. We experienced discontinuity with the Instagram feed in terms of political content, which was not the case with TikTok. Also, Instagram offered repetitive videos from previous days or outdated content, while TikTok updated the feed more efficiently. From the content only, it is difficult to state any audience differences.

Section 4: France: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 25: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

The two most prominent themes for right-wing profiles on both platforms were immigration and Islam, especially in relation to security concerns. These were followed by invocations of the conflicts in Gaza and in Ukraine, and then by recent and expected national reforms in access to unemployment benefits, retirement age, and agricultural policy. The most common type of content we encountered was Islamophobic, ranging from concerns about security to blatantly racist statements, which, however included anti-racist statements against the far-right agenda. The traditional right and the center-right adopted themes with less vehemence and also focused on economic innovation in Europe and agriculture policy.

For the left-wing synthetic profile, the prevailing topic was the conflict in Gaza, which was followed by the issues of social inequalities in France and the war in Ukraine. The most common type of content focusing on the Gaza-Israel war included short videos by *La France Insoumise* highlighting their active participation in public demonstrations, media interviews, and confrontations with political opponents. Rima Hassan, frequently featured as a spokesperson in these videos as an advocate for Palestinian rights, played a prominent role in articulating the party's stance. In addition to international conflict, left-wing profiles prioritized social inequality, with a strong emphasis on poverty, housing, labor rights, wealth distribution, and access to high-quality education. Content related to these issues often included short videos from protests, community initiatives, and speeches by prominent figures addressing systemic injustices.

Overall, the discourse focused on the national context and often featured debates in the French parliament rather than in or about the European elections.

The data gatherers tried to remain as distant as possible from the content in terms of emotional engagement despite the alarmingly xenophobic content in some of the profiles.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

AI-generated content was very scant overall. The themes depend on the profiles.

For the center-right profile encountered several anti-migrant contents and was also dragged toward religious content – which may be explained by the fact that François-Xavier Bellamy is himself a fervent Catholic. TikTok, as always, was more specifically political, but Instagram was showing short videos of catholic communities in their daily life as well. Anti-LGBTQ content was, however, almost totally absent.

The far-right synthetic profile was predominantly offered racist and anti-migrant content. Misogynistic and anti-LGBTQ messages were not as prominent and almost no AI content was observed. TikTok videos were consistently more violent and blatantly Islamophobic than Instagram videos. Interestingly, far-right messages were quite often mixed with religious ideology. Catholic and royalist allusions were integrated into masculinist and patriotic ideas, mixing the symbols of the Republic (flag, language) with religious paraphernalia (cross, nuns, churches, etc).

The red-green synthetic profile did not encounter any religious content, however, racist and anti-migrant content was present in the feed. Misogynistic or anti-LGBTQ were not prominent in the profile. AI-generated content was mainly aimed at criticism and mockery of the ruling party.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

In all three synthetic profiles, the content relevant to foreign countries was not frequent. Most of such videos concerned NATO, the Russia-Ukraine war and the Israel-Gaza conflict and were predominantly featured in the red-green synthetic profile, less so for the center and far-right. On the rare occasions these conflicts were mentioned, it was mostly in relation to French students' demonstrations in support

of Palestine, which were criticized by François-Xavier Bellamy and Jordan Bardella. On TikTok, there was more content that “explained” the relationships between France and Russia (promoting the long history of friendship between France and Russia and insisting that Russia is not an enemy). There were only a few videos about the US elections and China-US relationships. Instagram was less responsive to these topics.

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

For the red-green synthetic profile, the conflict in Gaza was the number one topic during the European election campaign. *La France Insoumise* put forward the theme to a great extent. On both TikTok and Instagram, the topic was largely presented. The vote in the European elections was framed as one of the means to impact the Israel-Gaza war and to create more pressure on the Israeli government. Many videos were aimed at the creation of a sense of solidarity with Palestine and featuring pro-Palestine manifestations in France. The Russia-Ukraine conflict was also present and often used as the pretext to criticize Macron’s party (after he announced the possibility of sending French military to Ukraine). An important part of the content was centered on distancing French voters from the Russian-Ukraine war. The far-right and center-right synthetic profiles were less affected by the conflict in Gaza and got 32

relatively few mentions of pro-Palestinian content. Other wars and conflicts were hardly mentioned at all. One exception for the center-right profile was the TV opposition between François-Xavier Bellamy and Rima Hassan on Palestine.

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Threats to Equality and Diversity

The TikTok and Instagram feeds displayed both important levels of anti-immigration content, especially for the right-wing and far-right-wing accounts. The official candidates mostly refrained from blatant racism or misogynistic content, but mostly focused on illegal immigration from North Africa, displaying anti-Muslim ideas. At the same time, unofficial accounts or influencers conveyed more explicit and more extreme content. After one month of data gathering, immigration was observed as *the* most important theme of the campaign for right-wing candidates, such that the feeds displayed this content multiple times a day. For instance, Jordan Bardella, the head of the Rassemblement National, published a number of his talks referring to the “European Swiss Cheese” (*Europe passoire* in French), while the leaders of *Reconquête!*, Eric Zemmour and Marion Maréchal Le Pen defended the theme of a “migratory submersion” (*submersion migratoire*) or “invasion”. Far-right influencers, very visible on the platform for the far-right account, such as Papacito, were even more explicit, with direct insults towards migrants. This prompted left-wing parties to discuss these themes on the platforms. They used their platforms to counteract the narratives promoted by the right, challenging the alarmist framing and emphasizing the societal contributions of migrants. In addition, left-wing candidates sought to redirect their campaigning toward broader issues of systemic inequality, equal access to state benefits, and geopolitical challenges.

Surprisingly anti-LGBTQ+ or misogynistic ideas were not central to the content – probably because of a new “European” positioning on the right, criticizing other cultures for their alleged backwardness.

The reactions of the data-gatherers evolved throughout data gathering. At first, the explicit and open racism of some of the content made us angry or slightly depressed, but within a week the data gathering was perceived as a standardized exercise.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content did not dominate the feed and was primarily used as a supplementary resource to propagate negatively charged content about political opponents. For all three synthetic profiles, there were only a few AI-generated videos in the feed, perhaps less than 5%. Most of them represented satirical or mockery videos criticizing the current government.

Section 5: France: Data Gathering –

Influence and appeal

This section is exploring the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In the section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

The different profiles operated with the same methodology: letting the platform algorithms choose the content and approving political content. At first, the platforms displayed “popular” content on the platforms: animal videos, well-known influencers, music, and, for one profile, a lot of “erotic” content, especially on Instagram. The selection occurred only with the likes and following some political accounts. For most profiles, it was not sufficient to have a feed fitting their political preferences, such that following specific political actors was necessary after 3 days. The left-wing profile in particular had to actively search for left-wing candidates (e.g., Raphaël Glucksmann, Marie Toussaint, Marine Tondelier, etc.), and the centre-right profile too (e.g., François-Xavier Bellamy, Eric Ciotti, Les Républicains’ accounts). For this account, the main difficulty was to identify the main figures beyond Bellamy. However, once the account was set to be a *Les Républicains* supporter, it received all the videos in the feed, even very confidential ones. The far-right profile was the easiest to “tune” as content from that side of the political spectrum was abundant even for other profiles that were not actively seeking it.

Once this was done, TikTok was very efficient in giving the accounts what they searched for, i.e., political content matching their preferences, and mostly stuck with this content. Instagram was less efficient in doing so, and periodically proposed other content, whether it be political or not. The red-green profile periodically received right-wing content despite the profile's preferences.

Overall, the content flow on both TikTok and Instagram did not evolve much in the first three weeks of the data-gathering period. Both platforms continued to show political content aligned with the users’ preferences. However, in the final week, a notable shift occurred due to the announcement of new elections by Emmanuel Macron following the EU results. During this period, political content, especially on TikTok, increasingly focused on the new election campaign.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

Given the demographic of TikTok and Instagram users, it is likely that young voters would be “influenced” more by the short videos (it is hard yet to say how much they are influenced, and if “neutral” or “apolitical” persons can be brought to vote for another party based on their online experience). From the experience on social media, it seems that two parties are particularly present: the far-right *Rassemblement National*, and the far-left *La France Insoumise*. Jordan Bardella and Louis Boyard have both, for instance, political accounts with over one million followers. It is to be expected that these two parties would be most favored by online platforms.

Emotional mechanisms

One month of data gathering with two profiles on TikTok and Instagram entailed a sustained effort, that is, one hour on these platforms every day for, ideally, each day of the week. Consistency was challenging, especially because none of the researchers were using Instagram or TikTok before the data collection.

At first, the content was a little overwhelming: short videos with strong emotions expressed, especially when dealing with sensitive political ideas – racism, anti-immigration was particularly frequent. Some content was also particularly shocking, such as pictures or videos from Gaza, or Russian politicians violently claiming they would bomb France's big cities in retaliation for supporting Ukraine. This produced uneasiness for data-gatherers.

However, after some days of data-gathering, the feed got more aligned with the political preferences of the profiles, and the researchers got more used to the exercise, minimizing the emotional impact of the videos – at least consciously, because it is possible the repetitive screening of a lot of short videos conveying most of the time no substantial information or argument could have an emotional effect.

Finally, the videos were emotionally loaded, with strong appeal to the emotions, especially negative emotions, especially in the case of far-right and right-wing content. In addition, in both right-wing and left-wing profiles, the content about political opponents was also often referring to strong negative emotions such as hate and anger.

Video Typologies

Based on our feeds, both synthetic and organic, the most frequent types of videos include:

- Debate videos: excerpts from televised debates, especially those involving leading candidates and heads of party lists, were heavily circulated (e.g: Bardella vs Attal; Bellamy vs Aubry). Special attention was paid to the failures of the opponents and the most successful moments for the candidates.
- Satirical and mockery Videos: humor and irony were key tools for both left and right-wing content creators. Satirical edits targeted opponents and party leaders, particularly Emmanuel Macron, Marine Le Pen, and Jean-Luc Mélenchon, reinforcing political polarization through ridicule and sarcasm.
- Explainer/commentary videos: this type is also regularly created not only by political actors or party leaders but also by social media users, influencers, or political commentators. The produced short-format videos are aimed at other users and often present an immediate reaction to campaign developments, televised events, or news coverage, creating a reactive and emotional atmosphere around political content.
- Campaign footage and walkabouts: Video content from campaign events (walkabouts, speeches, and local meetings) was widely posted by party accounts. The most influential parties La France Insoumise, Rassemblement National and Reconquête! shared well-produced footage of their candidates engaging with citizens. It was the case too, in a lesser extent, for

Les Républicains. Videos were usually clipped to highlight candidate charisma or responsiveness.

- Rally Coverage: Rassemblement National, La France Insoumise and Les Républicains accounts posted videos from large rallies, emphasizing crowd size, key slogans, and direct attacks on political opponents or the EU elite.
- Violent or highly polarizing content: A subset of videos, mostly affiliated with far right and fringe actors, featured aggressive rhetoric against political opponents or marginalized groups. Immigration, security, and anti-EU conspiracies were common themes, often amplified by accounts close to Rassemblement National or Reconquête!
- Accounts associated with legacy media such as Le Monde, France Info, and Libération provided more structured content, often in the form of interviews or mini documentaries. Online media with important coverage, such as Brut, Hugo Décrypte, or Quotidien, provided for specific topical interviews and short videos. In parallel, alternative media outlets, including those aligned with specific parties, circulated issue-specific or emotionally charged videos on topics such as immigration, security, or the Green Deal.

Interestingly, sometimes non-recent content was also repurposed during the campaign – for example, past clips of Emmanuel Macron were circulated to criticize his unfulfilled promises or to undermine his affiliated party Renaissance. These retrospective materials served to question the credibility of candidates and reinforce distrust.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Narrative 1. Debate Highlights - Short clips from televised or online political debates

(source: az_recorder_20240531_222006.mp4 (min 0.38) The first narrative concerns the content most often distributed by the official accounts of the political actors and parties. Short clips from debates or tv programs are used to highlight the best moments in politicians' political performance. Usually, these clips are edited and/or shortened to spotlight the politician's stance on critical issues, reinforce their credibility, criticise the opponents, and maximize engagement. For example, these two TikTok screenshots are taken from a short video featuring Marion Maréchal, a leading candidate of the far-right party Reconquête! for the 2024 European Parliament elections. In this video, Maréchal responds to a debate question about French military support for Ukraine. She firmly insists that France's national interest must come before foreign commitments, emphasizing the need to protect French citizens and ensure their well-being and security. Tiktok short-form video captures emotionally charged moments of rhetorical performance: Maréchal is shown in a close-up shot, addressing the audience directly, using expressive gestures such as a prayer-like pose or open hands to underscore her emotional appeal. The video also includes wide shots of the debate stage, reinforcing the performative character of her intervention. Textual elements that repeat Marechal address to the audience are selected in bold red and white font, accompanied by national symbols such as flags to indicate the countries discussed. This stylized editing heightens the impact and enhances the video's viral potential on TikTok. The format reflects how far-right political

actors in France use visual and emotional strategies to capture audience attention and amplify their messaging.

(source: az_recorder_20240601_185043 (min: 9.50))

The second example is a video from the official TikTok account of Louis Boyard, a member of La France Insoumise. In this video, Boyard participates in a heated televised exchange with journalists, where he voices his opinion on youth crime and police violence in France. The video is framed in a close-up shot that emphasizes Boyard's facial expressions and gestures, enhancing the emotional impact of his message. Visually, it is designed for TikTok's fast-scrolling environment, and the textual overlays are used to guide the viewer: yellow text highlights direct quotes from the politician, white text indicates broader theme, and red background with white lettering is used to underline the main message of the video. This stylistic combination of different visual cues and confrontational rhetoric positions Boyard as a defiant and outspoken figure, appealing particularly to younger audiences interested in social justice issues.

Narrative 2. Mockery (explainer) videos

(source: az_recorder_20240531_222006, min: 4.40, az_recorder_20240531_222006, min:14.30) Mockery explainer videos represent another recurring type of content in the online political landscape. Such videos are often not produced or shared by official political accounts or party-affiliated creators but rather by independent social media users, influencers, or anonymous accounts. The first screenshot shows a video mocking French President Emmanuel Macron’s proposal to send military reinforcements to Ukraine and explaining why this decision is not justified and damaging for France security and well-being. The second screenshot features another satirical video targeting Valérie Hayer, the lead candidate of Renaissance for the 2024 EP elections. The video ridicules her physical appearance and character traits by describing her imaged shortcomings as a “missing girl”. Such videos often go viral not because of their factual content but due to their entertainment value and emotional appeal.

Narrative 3. Campaign walkabouts and “behind the scenes”

(source: az_recorder_20240601_185043(min 5.24) The screenshot from a TikTok video illustrates a typical example of a door-to-door campaign by the French political party Renaissance. Gabriel Attal and Valérie Hayer are shown visiting French citizens in their apartments to discuss pressing issues ahead of the 2024 European Parliament elections. The video captures conversations between politicians and voters, which are not always easy or comfortable. This type of content aims to show the human side of politicians and reduce the perceived distance between them and the electorate. Other examples include videos featuring politicians before going on stage, such as Jordan Bardella talking to Marine Le Pen backstage, or engaging in casual, everyday activities, like Manon Aubry drinking morning coffee with fellow party members. Additionally, videos of street demonstrations in large cities or visits to small towns and villages are used to enhance visibility and connect with a broader audience.

Discussion on the most interesting videos

The most interesting and surprising videos we encountered were mostly from the far-right private and political actors – who had the most traction on social medias. One type of far-right messages focused on loyalty to the motherland and the French flag, protection of borders, street safety, French Gallic heritage and, surprisingly often, the Catholic Church, without making explicit references to the elections or party candidates. The principal characters in these fragments were young and athletic white males, often in uniform, traditional clothing, or with a proto-fascist aesthetic. Even more disingenuous were examples recorded by black or apparently Muslim individuals who presented themselves as African or French nationals and raised claims in favour of restricting immigration from African countries and fighting against the supposed expansion of Islam in France. Finally, a few days into the study, both platforms began to regularly pitch videos with flagrantly Islamophobic and anti-immigration messages that were not linked to any explicit political campaign or candidate. These were presented in a humorous and mocking tone, using stereotypes that appeal to prejudice. The two most notable videos were a drawing where Muslims were represented as pigs and a portrayal of a train station in France with the announcer inviting new arrivals – including men with hookahs and veiled women – to step off the train and take over France.

On the left side, interesting videos focused more on European policies. Manon Aubry, the leading figure of La France Insoumise, was one of the only political figures, with François Xavier Bellamy, discussing in details European policies. Left-wing videos also made fun of Bardella for his absence in the European Parliament and his lack of grasp over European politics. In one debate video, Manon Aubry even taught Bardella how the institutions worked, while the latter was attacking Bellamy for allegedly supporting Ursula Van der Leyen. A substantial portion of the videos from the left were, additionally, devoted to international problems, such as Gaza-Israel, and the notion of genocide. Overall, the most interesting (in terms of information) videos were watched on the organic profiles, which were less partisan and could access media coverage displaying relevant information about the programs of the candidates. Brut's videos (an online media) on the ecological programs of the different candidates was notoriously informative compared with other TikTok and Instagram content.

On the “Center-right” profile, the most interesting videos appeared at the end of the data gathering, when Eric Ciotti, the leader of Les Républicains, announced he would ally with the Rassemblement National for the upcoming legislative elections after Macron's dissolution. These videos were interesting because they confirmed what the profiles already displayed: that Les Républicains were leaning heavily in favour of the far-right. This led to what can be called the “siege” of Les Républicains' office, because Eric Ciotti locked himself in the building of the party after the decision, with other members of the party trying to dislodge him.

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion on the basis of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?

The European elections campaign in France made little reference to the notion, idea and least of all, the future of Europe. The main focus of the candidates was the national scale, France's geopolitical situation, and its involvement in the wars in Ukraine and in Gaza. The EU featured mostly in a negative way in this discourse, emphasizing its power to curb the democratic will of the French electorate.

The relative discreetness of Europe in an EP election might be explained by the specific context in France: the EP elections took place in the middle of President Macron's second mandate, while his party is being heavily criticized from the right and the left. This created a situation where the EP elections were used as an anti-Macron mid-term referendum.

In our experience, the social media on topics related to the European elections and most burning socio-economic issues on the national agenda were dominated by the far-right MPs and less so by the far-left. Both of these extremes expressed, at the very least, skeptical views about the current EU project, with the far-right arguing for radical reforms in the scope and level of intervention of EU institutions in the national policy of migration, agriculture, and economy. Jordan Bardella and Marion Maréchal dedicated most of their online presence to anti-migrant content, often blaming the EU for imposing "dangerous" policies that threaten the country's sovereignty, culture, and (especially for Maréchal) white Christian population. Their platforms, together with the more fringe far-right parties, consider the current European project as a menace to France and express support for a drastic restriction of the EU mandates. Nevertheless, none of the far-right MPs (save for one marginal party) expressed support for a "Frexit" - which was in the program of the *Rassemblement National*, then *Front National* (National Front), until at least 2017.

Despite the scepticism and the national nature of the debate, the different parties still displayed radical disagreement about what European politics should be about. The far-right parties definitely abandoned the "Frexit" option, to turn to the possibility of alliance with other European right-wing parties and defend a Europe of Nations, whose goal would mostly be to protect borders against "immigrant submersion". This theme permeated the traditional right party, *Les Républicains*, whose leader for the EP elections, François-Xavier Bellamy, campaigned significantly on these issues as well, explicitly defending French citizens in the European Parliament.

In contrast, the left-wing parties advocated for more integration. *Place Publique* defended, for instance, the creation of a European tax, the reinforcement of a Common Defense project or social policies, while *La France insoumise* (previously skeptical about the European project) supported more homogeneous social and economic regulations to soften competition between countries. The left-wing parties put forward a model of "social" Europe against the Europe of Nations of the far-right. These disagreements underline the different conceptions of what the European project should be and what kind of "social contract" should be instituted. In terms of motivation to vote, we observed that social media content is

highly conducive to pushing youth to vote in the EP elections, which is not to say that these voters are rendered more informed or substantive by online content. Although there was some pro-EU promotional and explanatory content, the campaign was mostly driven by populist and personal attacks against opponents.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

In the 2024 French European elections, political actors actively defined “us” by shaping emotional communities and setting affective boundaries. Hence, Palonen’s (2020, see also Vulovic and Palonen 2023) formula applies particularly well. The far-right, mostly represented by Jordan Bardella and Marion Maréchal Le Pen, attempted to position “us” as the white, Christian, patriotic French people under threat from immigration, Islam, and EU overreach. Their use of fear, anger, and indignation (Affect1) built a strong internal identity, while simultaneously constructing a “frontier” against migrants, Muslims, and “Brussels elites” (Affect2), reinforced by nationalist and religious imagery. By contrast, the left *La France Insoumise* and *Place Publique* defined “us” through solidarity, equality, and anti-racism. Their emotional appeals were grounded in empathy, justice, and outrage at global injustices (e.g., Gaza), and opposition to domestic inequality. They too created a frontier – against neoliberal elites and systemic injustice – but framed it through a collective European responsibility, particularly in the case of *Place Publique*. Each group’s definition of “us” was deeply affective. For the far-right, it was nostalgic and exclusionary; for the left, it was inclusive and justice-driven. Populism thrived in all these camps—not only as a style but as an emotional structure shaping boundaries of belonging and exclusion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the data-gathering process for the EP2024 elections in France has offered insights into the mechanisms of political communication on short-form social media platforms. Our main findings highlight the disproportionate visibility and influence of far-right actors, particularly on TikTok, where emotionally charged, polarizing content dominates the landscape. This dominance extended even into left-leaning and organic profiles, highlighting the strength of the amplification. While Instagram provided a slightly more balanced and repetitive feed, it too contributed to the circulation of politically charged narratives, albeit with less intensity. Thematic analysis revealed a consistent prioritization of immigration, identity, and security over substantive policy debate, alongside a worrying trend of normalized Islamophobia and xenophobia, especially in the far-right feeds.

Empirically, these results suggest that users are likely to encounter highly polarized political ecosystems, with limited exposure to opposing views or nuanced policy discussion (Chinelli et al. 2021). Even when exposure to opposing views was present, it principally was exposure to far-right ideas, through the popularity of Jordan Bardella. Based on the polarizing content of these videos, such exposure can also trigger more polarization (Bail et al. 2018).

Theoretically, our observations support and expand on existing work concerning algorithmic bias, affective polarization, and the emotionalization of political discourse (Stier et al., 2018). The study illustrates how the affordances of platforms like TikTok not only reflect but also actively shape political visibility and engagement (Krämer and Klingler, 2021; Zhang and Xu, 2023). Furthermore, the structure

of short-form content incentivizes simplification and spectacle, which may distort democratic deliberation and reduce complex political issues to binary moral framings.

In light of these findings, we suggest several recommendations. First, researchers and educators should further explore the intersection of digital media literacy and platform dynamics, particularly among young users. Second, political actors and institutions might consider developing communication strategies that can engage meaningfully within these fast-paced media environments without resorting to demagoguery. Finally, platform regulators and designers must reckon with the structural biases of algorithmic curation and consider transparency and counterweight mechanisms that can mitigate the overexposure of extreme or harmful content. These are not merely technical questions but ones that directly affect the future of democratic life in Europe.

Bibliography

- Bail, C. A., Argyle, L. P., Brown, T. W., Bumpus, J. P., Chen, H., Hunzaker, M. F., ... & Volfovsky, A.** (2018). Exposure to opposing views on social media can increase political polarization. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(37), 9216-9221.
- Brack, N., & Startin, N.** (2020). Introduction: The 2019 European elections in France-A new political landscape? *French Politics*, 18(3), 265-272. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41253-020-00130-7>
- Cinelli, M., Morales, G. D. F., Galeazzi, A., Quattrociocchi, W., & Starnini, M.** (2021). The echo chamber effect on social media. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(9), e2023301118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2023301118>
- Kahil, A.** (2025). 2024 EU elections and French politics: Rise of populism, eurocentrism, and inter-institutional dynamics. *Frontiers in Political Science*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2025.1545574>
- Krämer, B., & Klingler, M.** (2021). Microtargeting and the changing shape of political communication. In S. J. Barnett & R. K. Nielsen (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Media Disinformation and Populism* (pp. 273-285). Routledge.
- Palonen, E.** (2020). Ten Theses on Populism and Democracy. In E. Eklundh, & A. Knott (Eds.), *The Populist Manifesto* (pp. 55-69). Rowman & Littlefield Publishers
- PsyPost.** (2024, April 22). TikTok's algorithm exhibited pro-Republican bias during the 2024 presidential race, study finds. <https://www.psypost.org/tiktoks-algorithm-exhibited-pro-republican-bias-during-the-2024-presidential-race-study-finds/>
- Sciences Po CEVIPOF.** (2024). European Elections 2024: The Dynamics of the Rassemblement National (Policy Brief No. 1). CEVIPOF. https://www.sciencespo.fr/cevipof/sites/sciencespo.fr.cevipof/files/Noteelectionseuropeennes_PP_dynamiqueRN_mai2024_VA_V3.pdf
- Stier, S., Bleier, A., Lietz, H., & Strohmaier, M.** (2018). Election campaigning on social media: Politicians, audiences, and the mediation of political communication on Facebook and Twitter. *Political Communication*, 35(1), 50-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10584609.2017.1334728>

Vulović, M., & Palonen, E. (2022). Nationalism, populism or peopleism? Clarifying the distinction through a two-dimensional lens. *Nations and Nationalism*, 28(4), 1203–1217.

Zhang, C., & Xu, W. W. (2023). TikTok and political communication: Affordances, uses, and consequences. *Social Media + Society*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231161341>

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Germany

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Sullivan, Gavin B. and Rudolph, Jonas V. (International Psychoanalytic University Berlin); Wiesner, Claudia, Schmidt, Jessica and Boy, Nina (Fulda University of Applied Sciences)
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, Szilvia Horváth, Emilia Palonen (University of Helsinki)
Reviewer(s):	Pinar Uyan Semerci (Istanbul Bilgi University)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Germany: EP Election Results	5
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	7
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	8
Section 2: Germany: Political profiles	11
# Centre-Right feed	13
# Far-Right feed	16
# Red-Green feed	19
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	22
Section 3: Germany: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	24
# Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	25
# Notes on the organic profiles	26
# Differences Observed Over Time	28
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok	31
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	31
Section 4: Germany: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	33
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	33
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram	34
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	36
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	37
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	38
# AI Generated Content	39
Section 5: Germany: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	40
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time	40
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate	40
# Emotional mechanisms	41
# Video Typologies	42
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	43
# Discussion on most interesting videos	44
Concluding section	45
# What was the EU About and Why Vote (Social Contract)	45

Populist mobilisation

46

Conclusions

47

Bibliography

48

Funded by
the European Union

Germany: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

The elections in Germany were expected to be a referendum on and kind of electoral punishment for the heavily criticised Ampel (traffic light) coalition comprised of the Social Democrats (SPD), Greens, and the business-oriented Free Democrats (FDP). Widespread dissatisfaction with the governing Ampel coalition combined with a poor economic outlook and increasing politicization of immigration concerns figured prominently in the campaign and were then also reflected in results showing increased support for the populist right-wing political party Alternative for Germany (AfD). A strong counter perspective in the election campaign has been that the AfD represents a threat to democracy because it has a “suspected extremist” status from the German High Court (Reuters, 2024a, b). While the centre-right Christian Democratic Union (CDU) won the election, the AfD decisively increased its percentage of the vote coming second overall in Germany, confirming a swing to the right. During the research process, it became clear that many top mainstream MEP candidates did not feature prominently on TikTok and Instagram platforms. As opposed to this, AfD candidates were very visible. TikTok produced more coherent political content, and it did so quicker than Instagram. The war on Ukraine and migration were the main topics across the different political profiles and on both social media platforms.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Es wurde erwartet, dass die Wahlen zum Europäischen Parlament in Deutschland eine Art Volksabstimmung über die Ampel-Koalition aus Sozialdemokraten (SPD), Grünen und wirtschaftsorientierten Freien Demokraten (FDP) und eine Art Abstrafung für sie sein würden. Die weit verbreitete Unzufriedenheit mit der Ampel-Koalition in Verbindung mit den schlechten Wirtschaftsaussichten und der zunehmenden Politisierung der Einwanderungsproblematik prägte den Wahlkampf und spiegelte sich in den Ergebnissen wider, die eine wachsende Unterstützung für die rechtspopulistische Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) zeigten. Eine starke Gegenperspektive im Wahlkampf war, dass die AfD eine Bedrohung für die Demokratie darstellt, weil sie vom deutschen Obersten Gerichtshof als „extremistisch verdächtig“ eingestuft wurde (Reuters, 2024a,b). Während die Mitte-Rechts-Partei Christlich-Demokratische Union (CDU) die Wahl gewann, konnte die AfD ihren Anteil an den Wählerstimmen deutlich steigern und wurde in Deutschland insgesamt Zweiter, was einen Rechtsruck bestätigt. Während der Recherche wurde deutlich, dass viele Spitzenkandidaten für das Europäische Parlament, die Parteien der Mitte vertraten, auf den Social-Media-Plattformen TikTok und Instagram nicht prominent vertreten waren. Das Gegenteil galt für die AfD. TikTok produzierte mehr kohärente politische Inhalte, und zwar schneller als Instagram. Der Krieg in der Ukraine und Migration waren die Hauptthemen in den verschiedenen politischen Profilen und auf beiden Social-Media-Plattformen.

Funded by
the European Union

Section 1: Germany: EP Election Results

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate of the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

The European Elections in Germany were won by the centre-right CDU/CSU - Christlich Demokratische Union Deutschlands/Christlich-Soziale Union (Christian Democratic Union/Christian-Social Union)¹ with 30% of the vote in a widely expected victory. The second party was the Alternative für Deutschland (AfD; Alternative for Germany) with 15.90 % of the vote – a 4% increase on 2019 - and a slight decrease for the CDU/CSU (European Parliament, 2024a). There were several notable changes compared to 2019. The new left-populist party, BSW (Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht - Für Vernunft und Gerechtigkeit) secured 6.20% of the vote and appeared to as anti-government (Ampel coalition of the Social Democrats (SPD), Greens and FDP). In the EP 2024 campaign it largely replaced the left-wing Die Linke party – a tendency which has been inversed in the 2025 federal election. The Ampel (traffic light) governing parties “lost overall, with the Greens (Bündnis 90/Die Grünen) especially shedding a lot of votes compared to 2019” only obtaining 11.9% in Germany, and the SPD recording its “worst ever” European election result with only 13.9% (The Federal Returning Officer, 2024). Since the AfD scored 15.9% in Germany it beat the Social Democrats. This result showed that it has become an established party with an increase in support despite being identified as an extremist party in some regions of Germany² and advocating far-right policies.

Voter turnout was higher than 61.4% in 2019, rising 3.4% to 64.7% of the German population (potentially reflecting the changed eligibility of voters aged 16 years and older who voted in roughly equal amounts for the CDU/CSU and AfD but with most votes going to other parties).

The results were broadly comparable with a turn to the right in most European nations reducing support for Green parties and an increase in representation of smaller non-aligned parties (European Parliament, 2024b).

¹ The Christian Social Union (CSU) stands for election exclusively in Bavaria and forms a common parliamentary faction with the CDU at federal level.

² Parties in Germany are organised in different strata of association, reaching from local to federal level. The level of state association takes on a pivotal role. By late 2023, three of AfD's state associations – that of Saxonian-Anhalt, Thuringia and Saxonia – were declared to be “proven right-wing extremist” (“gesichert rechtsextrem”) by the respective State Offices for the Protection of the Constitution. In the case of Saxonia, for instance, the State Office found that there were sufficient factual indications that the AfD-Saxony was pursuing efforts that were directed against the human dignity of certain groups of people and against the principle of democracy (“AfD in Sachsen gesichert rechtsextremistisch“, zdf heute online of 08.12.2023, <https://www.zdf.de/nachrichten/politik/deutschland/afd-sachsen-rechtsextrem-verfassungsschutz-100.html>; “AfD Sachsen darf als gesichert rechtsextrem eingestuft werden“, beck-aktuell, <https://rsw.beck.de/aktuell/daily/meldung/detail/vg-dresden-afd-sachsen-einstufung-gesichert-rechtsextrem>; “Erwiesen extremistisch’: Thüringens Verfassungsschutz beobachtet AfD“, mdr aktuell of 12.05.2021, <https://www.mdr.de/nachrichten/thueringen/verfassungsschutz-afd-beobachtung-100.html>)

Funded by
the European Union

Figure 1.
Results by
national party

Results by national party - 2024-2029

Germany - Official results

Percentage of votes

National Parties

CDU/CSU - Christlich Demokratische Union Deutschlands/Christlich-Soziale Union in Bayern

AfD - Alternative für Deutschland

SPD - Sozialdemokratische Partei Deutschlands

Die Grünen - Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

BSW - Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht - Für Vernunft und Gerechtigkeit

FDP - Freie Demokratische Partei

Die Linke - Die Linke

FW - Freie Wähler

Volt - Volt Deutschland

Die Partei - Partei für Arbeit, Rechtsstaat, Tierschutz, Elitenförderung und basisdemokratische Initiative

Tierschutzpartei - Partei Mensch Umwelt Tierschutz

Familie - Familien-Partei Deutschlands

ÖDP - Ökologisch-Demokratische Partei

PdF - Partei des Fortschritts

Piratenpartei - Piratenpartei Deutschland

Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Funded by
the European Union

National Election Results and Party Affiliations

The election took place against the background of numerous protests against the Ampel government and happened also half a year after the organization “Correctiv” (2024) had revealed secret discussions in Berlin by right-wing extremists, including some leading AfD politicians, about a massive deportation plan to remove migrants from Germany. Subsequent nationwide protests against the AfD for several months from January 2024 appeared to be gathering support against “fascists” and “Nazis” under a broadly pro-democratic and pro-European banner. Despite these efforts, the democratic parties and the government suffered a large loss of support.

In contrast, the AfD secured 15.9% of the German national vote. This result can be attributed to the widespread dissatisfaction with the government coalition. The AfD achieved their result also despite their two leading candidates, Maximilian Krah and Petr Bystron, being publicly convicted of fraud and withdrawn from the official AfD campaign. It is also notable that the AfD won the biggest support of all parties among young voters. The AfD victory most probably was, however, reduced by being in direct competition especially in areas of the former East Germany with the former Left (Die Linke) party leader, Sarah Wagenknecht. Her newly founded “Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht” (alliance Sahra Wagenknecht) secured a surprising 6.2% of the vote with a left populist anti-Ukraine movement. The party heavily promoted an anti-war message which was popular and successful, especially, as already noted, in the former East where it also capitalized upon the dissatisfaction with the government and longer-term grievances about changes after German reunification.

Despite claiming victory, the CDU merely increased their share of the vote in comparison to their poor result at the last general election in Germany. During the election campaign, they had to fend off claims that in their European parliamentary leader in the form of Ursula von der Leyen, would be willing to negotiate with far-right parties if necessary.

On the social media platforms studied, i.e. TikTok and Instagram, Alice Weidel (AfD) and Wagenknecht (BSW) emerged as the two strongest personalities, Robert Habeck, current minister of economic affairs, and Annalena Baerbock, current minister of foreign affairs (both Die Grünen, the Greens), as the two main “villains”, along with chancellor Olaf Scholz (SPD). Portrayals from the right often focused in vitriolic, satirizing and angry terms on the Greens' leading members as woke left-wing elites who did not represent and work for the “normal” population. The AfD was also backed by strong support on platforms such as TikTok which the Greens particularly used to try to engage voters in uplifting and persuasive but ultimately unsuccessful counter campaigns (e.g., #reclaimtiktok). What was surprising was that Bündnis Deutschland, trying to present as an alternative to AfD, lost its one seat in the EP. The CDU appeared not to rely on social media campaigns to communicate their core messages and try to persuade dissatisfied citizens to vote for them. The following overview represents the appearance of party politicians in the social media accounts of the study.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors by party group seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Germany

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

The German top candidates for the EP were Ursula von der Leyen (CDU) and Katarina Barley (SPD), Terry Reintke (Die Grünen), Marie-Agnes Strack-Zimmermann (FDP) and Carola Rackete (Die Linke). In contrast, the AfD had serious problems with their top candidate Maximilian Krah prior to the EP elections (he played down Nazi-crimes during the Second World War, leading to the 9 MEPS of the AfD expelled from the far-right Identity and Democracy group). Krah was removed from the AfD election campaign but still became a member of the European Parliament as a “non-attached member”. In 2025, he won a mandate for the German Bundestag and left the EP.

During the research process, it became clear that many mainstream top MEP candidates did not feature prominently on TikTok and Instagram social media platforms. Strack-Zimmermann, Barley, von der Leyen, Bystron, and Berg occasionally featured, but the main protagonists were national leaders and MPs. An exception to this trend was Terry Reintke of the Greens who appeared regularly in posts that tended to be upbeat and strident yet concerned in their pro-democratic and pro-European stances. Individual supporters of the Greens posted pleas to resist anti-democratic and authoritarian tendencies in other parties with a combination of concern, disbelief and some disillusioned anger (and sometimes also lighter satirical humour). With the AfD, there were a wider range of posts as supporters used humiliating humour, angry rants from supporters and their leaders, as well as videos of marches and protests accompanied by far-right images and cartoons and backed with dramatic or contentious music (e.g., dance music that had been co-opted by the far right and was linked with widely condemned anti-immigrant sentiments in non-election posts). Among all the parties, it was striking that there were very few connections made with the European Parliament groups (e.g., the European People's Party even though it included the CDU's von der Leyen). Prominent figures in the Ampel government, such as Olaf Scholz and Robert Habeck, as well as party leaders provided their own election-related videos, but they were also the target of highly critical and negative posts.

Sarah Wagenknecht of the eponymous “Bündnis Sarah Wagenknecht” (BSW), which had formed only a few months before the election, was also prominent on social media. Her posts were sometimes strident, but she often also presented as calm, professional and focused (in contrast to the chaotic campaign of the AfD). Apart from non-party videos by individuals where specific claims and remarks were unpacked and criticised, there were few posts that focused on ridiculing the BSW leader (e.g., via manipulated images, cartoons). While Wagenknecht did not connect with young people in the same way that the AfD ultimately did, older voters and those from the east appeared to connect with her anti-Ukraine war narrative. The Greens focused much of their campaign on mobilizing resistance to the AfD and their social media dominance, but campaigns such as #reclaimtiktok seemed to do little to stem their loss of supporters or reduce support for the AfD among young voters.

16/07/2024 - 13:26

All times are GMT+2

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

Germany - Constitutive session

National Parties	Votes										Seats
		EPP	S&D	PFE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	
CDU/CSU	30.00%	29									29
AfD	15.90%							14	1		15
SPD	13.90%		14								14
Die Grünen	11.90%					12					12
BSW	6.20%								6		6
FDP	5.20%				5						5
Die Linke	2.70%						3				3
FW	2.70%				3						3
Volt	2.60%					3					3
Die Partei	1.90%								2		2
Tierschutzpartei	1.40%						1				1
Familie	0.60%	1									1
ÖDP	0.60%	1									1
PdF	0.60%								1		1
Piratenpartei	0.50%										0
Other parties	3.30%										0
	100.00%	31	14	0	0	8	15	4	14	10	96

Figure 3a. Breakdown of national parties and political groups. Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Funded by the European Union

Figure 3b. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

CDU > EPP: HILDEGARD BENTELE, STEFAN BERGER, DANIEL CASPARY, LENA DÚPONT, CHRISTIAN EHLEH, MICHAEL GAHLER, JENS GIESEKE, NICLAS HERBST, PETER LIESE, NORBERT LINS, DAVID MCALLISTER, ALEXANDRA MEHNERT, VERENA MERTENS, DENNIS RADTKE, OLIVER SCHENK, CHRISTINE SCHNEIDER, ANDREAS SCHWAB, RALF SEEKATZ, SVEN SIMON, SABINE VERHEYEN, AXEL VOSS, MARION WALSMANN, ANDREA WECHSLER

AFD > ESN: CHRISTINE ANDERSON, ANJA ARNDT, RENÉ AUST, ARNO BAUSEMER, IRMHILD BOSSDORF, MARKUS BUCHHEIT, PETR BYSTRON, SIEGBERT FRANK DROESE, TOMASZ FROELICH, MARC JONGEN, ALEXANDER JUNGBLUTH, MARY KHAN, HANS NEUHOF, ALEXANDER SELL

SPD > S&D: KATARINA BARLEY, GABRIELE BISCHOFF, UDO BULLMANN, DELARA BURKHARDT, VIVIEN COSTANZO, TOBIAS CREMER, MATTHIAS ECKE, JENS GEIER, BERND LANGE, MARIA NOICHL, RENÉ REPAS, SABRINA REPP, BIRGIT SIPPEL, TIEMO WÖLKEN

Die Grünen > Greens/EFA: RASMUS ANDRESEN, MICHAEL BLOSS, ANNA CAVAZZINI, DANIEL FREUND, ALEXANDRA GEESE, MARTIN HÄUSLING, SERGEY LAGODINSKY, KATRIN LANGENSIEPEN, ERIK MARQUARDT, HANNAH NEUMANN, JUTTA PAULUS, TERRY REINTKE

BSW > NI: FABIO DE MASI, RUTH FIRMENICH, THOMAS GEISEL, FRIEDRICH PÜRNER, MICHAEL VON DER SCHULENBURG, JAN-PETER WARNKE

CSU > EPP: CHRISTIAN DOLESCHAL, MARKUS FERBER, MONIKA HOHLMEIER, STEFAN KÖHLER, ANGELIKA NIEBLER, MANFRED WEBER

FDP > Renew Europe: ANDREAS GLÜCK, SVENJA HAHN, MORITZ KÖRNER, JAN-CHRISTOPH OETJEN, MARIE-AGNES STRACK-ZIMMERMANN

FW > Renew Europe: ENGIN EROGLU, CHRISTINE SINGER, JOACHIM STREIT

Volt > Greens/EFA: DAMIAN BOESELAGER, NELA RIEHL, KAI TEGETHOFF

Die Partei > NI: SIBYLLE BERG, MARTIN SONNEBORN

Die Linke > The Left: ÖZLEM DEMIREL, MARTIN SCHIRDEWAN

Tierschutzpartei > The Left: SEBASTIAN EVERDING

PdF > NI: LUKAS SIEPER

AFD > NI: MAXIMILIAN KRAH

ÖDP > EPP: MANUELA RIPA

Ind. > The Left: CAROLA RACKETE

Familie > EPP: NIELS GEUKING

National Parties

CDU/CSU – Christlich Demokratische Union Deutschlands/Christlich-Soziale Union in Bayern

AFD – Alternative für Deutschland

SPD – Sozialdemokratische Partei Deutschlands

Die Grünen – Bündnis 90/Die Grünen

BSW – Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht – Für Vernunft und Gerechtigkeit

FDP – Freie Demokratische Partei

Die Linke – Die Linke

FW – Freie Wähler

Volt – Volt Deutschland

Die Partei – Partei für Arbeit, Rechtsstaat, Tierschutz, Elitenförderung und basisdemokratische Initiative

Tierschutzpartei – Partei Mensch Umwelt Tierschutz

Familie – Familien-Partei Deutschlands

ÖDP – Ökologisch-Demokratische Partei

PdF – Partei des Fortschritts

Piratenpartei – Piratenpartei Deutschland

Other parties – Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

- **EPP** – Group of the European People’s Party (Christian Democrats)
- **S&D** – Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament
- **PfE** – Patriots for Europe
- **ECR** – European Conservatives and Reformists Group
- **Renew Europe** – Renew Europe Group
- **Greens/EFA** – Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance
- **The Left** – The Left group in the European Parliament – GUE/NGL
- **ESN** – Europe of Sovereign Nations
- **NI** – Non-attached Members

According to Parliament’s rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Section 2: Germany: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

For the country report, a total of 3 synthetic and 3 organic accounts respectively were set up on TikTok and Instagram.

Account type/ Platform	TikTok	Instagram
Synthetic	far-right (AfD)	far-right (AfD)
	centre-right (CDU/CSU)	centre-right (CDU/CSU)
	red-green (SPD & Greens)	red-green (SPD & Greens)
Organic	no profile (researcher's interest)	no profile (researcher's interest)

Overall, Instagram presented limited political material for both the synthetic accounts and organic profiles and developed slowly in terms of political profiles. TikTok, on the other hand, featured political content almost immediately. Instagram was to some extent an “only in-group feed”, whereas in TikTok, a lot of political content from the political right featured on the red-green profile. In the days before the election, the red-green account showed an almost overwhelming amount and range of political material.

The data was retrieved by scrolling through TikTok and Instagram for ca. 10 minutes a day. The data was retrieved by watching a video or scrolling further (contrary to the assigned research protocol) as guided by the accounts' assigned political preferences attributed by the researchers. As noted above, the content for each profile was observed in the form of self-reports and field notes and thus is selective and a result of what the profiles and the algorithms delivered. The field notes also may be subject to biases and inaccuracies, even though they were completed immediately after viewing the videos. The researchers have rewatched videos and returned to their notes.

All results and graphs presented below are accordingly based on the researchers' field notes, observations and impressions during the data gathering process. The figures below represent clustering and overviews of these observations. They reflect solely the findings obtained in the synthetic social media profiles and are therefore highly selective. We do not claim any representativeness for the whole of Instagram or TikTok. The indications that the below give therefore refer to the range of the highly selective data. The tendencies represented stem from three types of accounts: radical right, centre-right and red-green. As indicated below, the content retrieved in the account types reflects this political orientation.

In general, TikTok produced more coherent political content than Instagram in the German feeds. Beyond this, as said above, some political parties and/or political personalities seemed to be generally more prolific than others. Especially the far-right Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) had a strong presence on TikTok. As a result, on TikTok AfD-related reels also featured across other synthetic profiles that were deliberately designed to show different political content.

In general, the context and temporal dimension in which these parties were mentioned is not shown in these figures. For instance, often videos would negatively reference other political parties. Another factor may be the search items used to establish the respective political profiles which took a while to feature the desired political content.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Country codes are two-letter ISO

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Country codes are two-letter ISO

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

Centre-Right feed

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Germany

Figure 6: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Germany

The centre-right synthetic profile was organised such that it should represent a CDU supporter, and the respective data gatherer often found it difficult to remember who exactly made what point from what stance. The feed featured videos of prominent figures such as the current CDU leader Friedrich Merz and less well-known members of parliament such as Philipp Armthor or the MEPs (e.g., Hildegard Bentele). Merz’s content was often serious and considered, even though it did not seem to be viewed or shared much. Other videos were much less serious and did not help to outline policies in detail, instead they seemed to be designed to make people like them. Some posts were strategic, introducing particular figures and outlining their local campaigns. Key figures such as Ursula von der Leyen made simple appeals to vote democratically and put forward pro-European values and ideals.

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Debates such as whether and under what circumstances von der Leyen might collaborate with far-right European leaders such as Meloni or Le Pen were not discussed, except in the form of documentaries or news stories that appeared when specific hashtags were used (or followed). The “firewall” or “Brandmauer” – a term that emphasises that centre parties should not collaborate with the extreme right – was a key theme that was repeated in differentiating the CDU and its pro-European values as well as emphatically ruling out any cooperation with the AfD. AfD, BSW and Greens videos frequently appeared in the centre-right feed. In the accounts close to CDU as well as by CDU politicians, far less attention was paid to the details of environmental policies. There was also no evidence of the CDU having a stance to win over some of the supporters who still felt that the AfD, BSW or Greens addressed their concerns and interests. For their part, the AfD made it clear on election night that they also had “the CDU in their sights”.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Far-Right feed

In the far-right feed, it seemed that TikTok had more content and more daily content producers, while on Instagram videos would repeat between days. Perhaps also because the TikTok algorithm was more effective in directing content, on Instagram it was necessary to search several times to go in the right direction. Both platforms tended to feature the same kinds of videos: commented/ framed extracts from parliamentary speeches, talk shows, press conferences, interviews, usually 'refuting' a point or 'revealing' the truth. Toward the end, longer videos and more parliamentary speeches featured on TikTok, which was solid in terms of profile. Instagram had a more diverse range of topics and more international politicians

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

AfD supporter accounts (e.g. TikTok: Deutsche Wahrheit, Wolf1960, Deutsche Freiheit, Taegliche Dosis Wahrheit, Vermieter Tagebuch, Rudfly, wer_wills_wissen78, dieeilmeldung.de, YoungGerman, WorldOfMike, Prinzessin Modder, Mannvonderbemalten, Sven Goldschmied; Instagram: politikpulse, nius.de, deraugenoeffner, ultimativ, Die.da.oben, bloss_mit_biss) seemed to be the fastest to react to and take a position toward current events (e.g. Zelensky's visit in Bundestag; Scholz's statements at the 'Rebuild Ukraine' conference) – alongside with the accounts of left-populist Sahra Wagenknecht.

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

AfD had a very particular type of supporting actor (not officially linked to the party) who zealously framed, attacked and deconstructed positions by the government/ Ampel coalition. Clips from speeches (parliament, talk show, press conference, public event) were taken, edited and framed in such a way that refutation seemed to be self-evident. The main message of the video was often also added as the headline. These devoted supporters of AfD acted as 'extended arm', investing all or a lot of their time into producing promotional material.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Accounts from the opposing political side did not have the same kind of bond/ identification between party and voters. A lot of the zeal came from their self-understanding as ‘real democrats’ fighting the hypocrisy, lies, censorship, and ‘ideology’ of the government (like conspiracy theorists) – with a lot of emphasis on ‘evidence/ pseudo-evidence’. AfD was rhetorically appealing. They were hard to refute because their politicians moved chameleon-like between unrelated topics, but made it sound as if all was resulting in one big exploitation of and injustice to the citizen. For example, in a talk show Habeck (the Greens) was talking about society needing to become more open but a part of society was clinging

to the past, to which Chrupalla (AfD) replied: “It’s humiliating that we need an ‘Ostbeauftragter’” (as if the East was a colony).

Red-Green feed

In the red-green profile, Instagram mostly featured content from the parties whose accounts were followed. It seemed that swiping reels on Instagram somehow did not have much influence on the feed, making it to some kind of self-confirming and self-validating cycle. TikTok instead reacted very quickly to the previously watched content, showing more of the same content as soon as it has been viewed a little longer than usual.

The feed featured content from a range of political actors. Profiles from the SPD and the Greens were mostly very professionally made (especially the videos of the Greens: you could see that there was money invested in the Instagram videos). But in all these weeks, it did not become clear what or who their exact target group was; the videos and the corresponding political messages often stayed diffuse and vague. Political messages were mostly reassuring, not diving into a topic, explaining it in detail, but rather delivering some (to me mostly already well-known) hard facts, not explaining from scratch (to maybe also reach new voters or people not knowing about the background information and political history and so on)

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

In terms of fighting right wing parties like AfD the red-green political parties were also often “just defying” but not showing other options, not really editing, adjusting or customizing their content for the specifics of the respective social media platform, thereby almost “just repeating” the argument, shortly saying that it was racist without further explanation. A good counterexample was Heidi Reichinnek from Die Linke (the Left), who dealt professionally with TikTok, who was really good at explaining topics and using the platforms’ specifics (also she was one of the top ten German politicians having the highest influence on TikTok, whereas the rest was mostly AfD politicians).

On TikTok, far-right parties like AfD also appeared quite a lot in the red-green account, which seemed to speak of their massive dominance on TikTok. Although swiping them fast away, they appeared and reappeared. Also, they often had the objectively better videos in terms of main messages in the first few seconds, cutting techniques, possibilities for followers to repost and so on (see also Berendsen & Schnabel, 2024).

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Funded by
the European Union

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

This section discusses the visibility and the prevalence of the political actors in our dataset. Overall, MEPs did not feature prominently on either of the political profiles. Some political personalities, like T. Reintke, seemed to be generally more prolific than others. In general, the context or temporal dimension in which these personalities were mentioned is not shown in these figures. For instance, often videos would negatively reference other political personalities. For instance, Robert Habeck from the Greens often featured on the far-right profile as the “arch enemy” that was rallied against. Another factor may be the search items used to establish the respective political profiles, which took a while to establish (see Section 5).

A difference between TikTok and Instagram can be found looking at the visibility of political actors: on Instagram the appearing political actors seem to be more consistent with the political preference of the synthetic accounts than on TikTok. On TikTok political actors from the far right like Alice Weidel or Maximilian Krah (both AfD) were present in the feeds, although they do not match the political leanings of the profiles. This is coherent with reports on AfD being very present and professional on TikTok (Berendsen & Schnabel, 2024).

As becoming apparent from the different graphs (Figures 20a and 20b compared to the previous Figure 15 and 16), the researcher in charge of the left green synthetic profile deviated from the data gathering protocol, only mentioning the three most prominent political actors on TikTok and Instagram, instead of naming all political actors visible. However, it becomes clear that the naming of the three most visible political players is also consistent with the research results. On Instagram, we see an ingroup feed, as only politicians from the favoured camp appear. On TikTok, politicians from other political ideologies also appear (left-nationalist populist Sarah Wagenknecht and Alice Weidel from the extremist right-wing AfD). This can be explained by the high level of social media expertise of those two actors.

Funded by
the European Union

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Germany

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Germany

Section 3: Germany: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

The data gatherer responsible for the centre-right profile was intrigued by but then sometimes overwhelmed and even slightly depressed by the emotional stances of the people posting particularly on TikTok. The data gatherer felt solidarity with stirring material that talked about positive and progressive values and themes, such as the importance of resisting the far right and then also the possibility of getting genuine insights into policy issues when they were debated in subtle detail. It is possible that in the end more news and documentary-type videos were being watched than strictly focusing on the posts of political parties and their supporters. However, at other times, the data gatherer felt it was depressing to see how dedicated people were humiliating others, demonstrating little shared understanding, humanity or empathy in the process. A lot of effort had clearly gone into creating caricature comics and bizarre images (e.g., blue Smurfs in a bizarre sunlit AfD "paradise") with designed to upset and distress people, constructing a sense of communities at breaking point, full of tensions and threats everywhere. At data collecting, the data gatherer felt relief when not having to watch more AfD-related content, especially where the imagery seemed very dark. The data gatherer felt that they were exposed to a plurality of views, saw people in situations that they would be unlikely to see directly (e.g., someone marching in an AfD demo livid with anger at the comments from people on the footpath) and in this respect it gave some insights into the depth of feeling out there and how hard it may be to reach some people. This extended to figures such as Sarah Wagenknecht, who the data gatherer felt highly ambivalent about in ways difficult to pinpoint.

The data gatherer responsible for the red-green profile would sometimes feel sadness in seeing all that not-really-thought-through, not-platform-and-target-group-matching content from, for example, the Greens, SPD or the Left and on the opposite high-quality content from AfD. Sharing a similar experience with the centre-right profile data gatherer, the red-green profile data gatherer was therefore quite happy "being allowed" to swipe AfD content away from their synthetic profile. Watching openly anti-democratic content regularly elicited different emotions from getting sad, overwhelmed, feeling powerless to not wanting to believe what one was seeing, getting angry, wanting the data gathering to stop and throwing the phone away.

The researcher responsible for the radical right profile noted that the few politicians from the red-green parties who used the platforms effectively (Mesarosch, Reichinnek, Neubauer, Habeck to lesser extent) did so addressing viewers directly, while AfD politicians hardly ever sought this direct contact, but were instead promoted by devout followers (who might of course be employed or tasked by the party). Both showed a devout dedication from supporting media producers to their party that did not exist in the same way for the rest of the political spectrum and presented AfD politicians themselves in apparent 'objectivity'. Wagenknecht was very effective in addressing viewers directly, and did not have the same kind of 'support' from other accounts.

Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

The centre-right synthetic profile was different from the data gatherer's own political views. Despite following centre-right parties, a wide range of political content appeared in the feed, particularly on TikTok. Initially, the data gatherer attempted to follow CDU figures and found that this took some time before the gatherer started seeing relevant content. Especially before the election, the variety and amount of material reached the point of overwhelming. As a result, the data gatherer felt a wide range of feelings as they also engaged with material from a centre-right perspective which meant avoiding material from individual posts that were not pro-CDU, such as the Greens and SPD. Occasionally, the data gatherer would stay with content that was critical of representatives of the centre-right party in order to hear the arguments and explore the emotions they encoded and enacted. Selections of content from the party leader were often posted to demonstrate a strident and coherent stance, which was mostly unopposed. The Instagram synthetic feed had a lot less political material than TikTok which reached a peak just before the election. With the organic feed, the freedom to explore content felt more relaxed and was driven much more by the data gatherer's own personal curiosity about a wide range of electoral and emotional political issues which were much less likely to encounter extreme stances. The Instagram organic account acted as a kind of control, showing very limited election and political content, while also showing how someone with such a social media account as their focus might largely bypass political content in their everyday life.

The researcher responsible for the red-green profile noted that in the synthetic TikTok account, the presence of AfD seemed to be stronger than in the organic Instagram account. On TikTok, there was some kind of a threefold distinction in relation to the AfD: videos from official AfD accounts, videos from AfD supporters (sometimes the same videos posted again with a different filter or the whole range of sync-lip videos by supporters) and videos from the centre-left but about AfD (and how dangerous they are). A large proportion of the videos overall therefore often dealt with AfD.

The data gatherer responsible for the far-right synthetic profile noted that the synthetic accounts had a slightly stronger profile and homogeneous position than organic ones. In order to get political content for the synthetic profile on Instagram, the data gatherer followed AfDInfo and Rudfly on TikTok, and Larspatrickberg (the MEP for Buendnis Deutschland), Naechste.generation (their youth generation 'next generation' as opposed to 'last generation'), Buendnisde, Deraugenoeffner. The data gatherer imagined the synthetic accounts to belong to a male persona – who was supposed to be right-wing, but not anti-democratic – to be somewhat irritated by Maximilian Krah (who the data gatherer tried to follow but was not accepted probably since the synthetic profile looked like a bot at that stage), whose campaigning led to AfD being excluded from Identity and Democracy Group in the European Parliament. The data gatherer imagined this male persona to be looking for more democratic right-wing groups such as BuendnisDeutschland, which overlap in main policies (anti-immigration and pro-nuclear power, for example). The data gatherer's synthetic profile was followed by fabio_bd_bw, a.breisig, felixunde_, epple_bdbw. On Instagram, the data gatherer got a lot of content from Luisa Neubauer, as well as Robin Mesarosch (SPD), Gregor Gysi (Left) and Heidi Reichinnek (Left). Searching for the 'European election' produced a lot of explainer videos, but not necessarily relevant results. By 28 May, however, there was political content on the synthetic accounts both on TikTok and Instagram.

Notes on the organic profiles

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of references to different political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of references to different individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Not all data gatherers were organic users of either or both platforms or chose not to use their organic accounts in the context of this study. For instance, the data gatherer responsible for the red-green profile had not previously used either TikTok or Instagram. Hence, such ‘organic’ accounts were only created for the project. The Instagram accounts (organic and synthetic) stayed in-group accounts, basically mainly showing content from the political groups, the data gatherer then followed. In handling the data gatherer’s (new) organic Instagram account they felt that there was a little flaw: As they were not following their personal (real) friends with the new organic Instagram account the feed was somehow strange and new to them – only showing political content, but not the personal content which they usually consume on their own Instagram account. The data gatherer responsible for the far-right profile also did not use preexisting TikTok or Instagram accounts but only created them for the project. They had less coherent political content in their organic accounts, which they steered towards climate activism, including Fridays for Future. However, the organic profile did not work as much due to the lack of protocol. Only on the last day did the data gatherer get right-wing content in their organic profile

The data visualized in Figure 21a suggests that Left-Green and Radical Right profiles maintained steady references for different political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher across the pre-election period on TikTok and Instagram, while the Centre Right profile referenced more to different political parties.

For references to individual politicians in Figure 21b the data seems to be more complex (in the case of the left green profile, not complete) as the centre right profile shows no real differences for the number of references whereas the radical right profile shows a decline of references after the election date.

Differences Observed Over Time

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by the EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Germany over time

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Germany over time

The researcher responsible for the centre-right profile noted that the main changes were most visible on TikTok, from the immediate pre-election period to a post-election reduction in political party material. The Greens' official posts contrasted with the wide range of material from AfD and the increasing presence of BSW videos close to the election. After the election outcome was known, the Greens' videos thanked their supporters, expressed disappointment about the result and reiterating the vital need to fight threats to democracy. In contrast, AfD reposts of news interviews represented celebrations and victory speeches in which Alice Weidel talked about the need for an election victory in 2025. Supporters also found it difficult to hide their enjoyment of the dramatically reduced percentage of the vote for the Greens. Instagram showed similar trends but with much lower intensity before and after the election. The organic profile on Instagram remained low on political posts through the entire study period but very quickly increased football content as the 2024 UEFA European Football Championship started in Germany. Some of this material overlapped with criticisms of Germany and arguments about the country's decline propagated by right-wing actors and their opponents (e.g., Muslim men posting criticisms of Germany and German people).

The researcher responsible for the red-green profile remarked that after the election there was much less content from left-wing and green parties. It was as if their job (generating votes for the EP election) was done. To some extent this could be interpreted as feeding anti-democratic and conspiracy narratives saying that politicians are making the actually relevant decisions behind closed doors etc. That decline can be found in the graphs above. In general, TikTok reacted much quicker than Instagram.

The researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic profile also only found the 'reel' button after a while, and it was not possible to search within it. TikTok was quick to establish a 'coherent' feed. Instagram took a lot longer to modulate. It was not clear to the data gatherer what sparked a 100% Arabic content over a few days, but this dynamic was broken when they started to follow some profiles. It also continued to show campaign and European election explainer videos even after the election. TikTok on the other hand immediately featured reactions to the election result, whether from Left politicians admitting defeat, or Weidel demanding a general election in Germany. Instagram featured more 'historical' material, such as clips of Helmut Schmidt or Konrad Adenauer on relevant topics such immigration, social market economy, Israel.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

TikTok was the most responsive in showing current events that were relevant to political debates discussed by parties for the election. For example, a range of individuals and parties responded to the Sylt racist incident in which a group of young German people who appeared to be economically well off chanted the racist, Nazi-era phrase “Deutschland den Deutschen” (Germany for the Germans). Other relevant events were picked up and portrayed quickly from multiple perspectives such as the fatal stabbing of a policeman defending a rally hosted by the counter-jihad and anti-Islam group Citizens' Movement Pax Europa in Mannheim. Instagram was very limited in contrast to including and presenting a range of stances on and reactions to these current events. AI-generated material was very limited and usually very obviously satirical in form. TikTok worked as a current news channel while Instagram lagged behind and played more of the same content on consecutive days.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

The researcher dealing with the centre-right profile noted that roughly 90% of the content watched, specifically videos, was on TikTok. The Instagram content was quite limited and really had to be sought on particular accounts, such as the CDU or European Parliament or specific politicians. Instagram seemed to be quite specific in what was coming up and never seemed to multiply the content based on

previous viewing. TikTok, in contrast, became a cacophony of competing voices, not only from official sources but also a wide range of commentators, which ranged from legitimate news sources (but also fake news pretending to report on scandals) to highly personal comments. The content varied widely in tone also from light hearted attempts to engage that often fell flat (or looked ridiculous and staged) to other expressions of angst or anger that appeared to be genuine or in some way authentic (even if the message was still distorted in some way such as by presenting the current state of affairs as a crisis or intolerable etc. requiring urgent action now). From memory, much more of the content on TikTok was emotional, whether using devices such as shocking or moving images or video (for example, of protesting crowds, angry AfD supporters) or adding music to clips of discussions or debates or commentary.

For the researcher responsible for the red-green profile, there definitely was a difference between TikTok and Instagram. On Instagram, most content matched the political preferences of the profile, making Instagram a social media platform to consolidate previously existing views. On TikTok, other content also appeared, in particular AfD or other fascist content. This might have to do with swiping away such content quite late or sometimes watching rightist videos until the end, being repelled and fascinated at the same time. The red-green synthetic profile hardly ever got content from the CDU or FDP, being rather a confirmation of the fact how good the AfD and its supporters are handling TikTok.

The data gatherer who was responsible for the far-right profile noted that TikTok had more of a national or nationalising focus, while Instagram had a more diverse range of topics and featured more international heads of state. Both platforms offered predominantly 'position videos' or 'revelation videos' that sought to explain or refute a position – or the 'truth'. They were mostly professionally edited. Both also featured a lot of parliamentary speeches, talk show extracts, and comment/ motivation videos.

Section 4: Germany: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 25: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

On the centre-right profile, Social Europe as an entity to value and defend against a range of challenges and threats was presented throughout the feeds, particularly on the TikTok feeds of parties such as the CDU, Greens, and SPD as well as smaller parties like the new pro-European Volt. NATO was not highly prominent except in discussions about support for Ukraine. The Green Deal also was not prominent in TikTok and Instagram feeds. Social Europe featured in the sense that welfare was both bemoaned for those who weren't considered entitled – for instance, refugees – and should not be put above 'Leistung/achievement' in terms of value.

On the red-green profile, at the beginning of the data gathering, the Israel-Gaza conflict was more dominant in the news, also for example, Berlin-based protest actions were very soon appearing in the organic TikTok feed. Depending on the situation and the personal state of mind of the data gatherer, it was sometimes very touching to see all this violence happening. On TikTok, the Israel-Gaza conflict

Funded by
the European Union

was not as prominent as in the organic profile. In the red-green profile, the topic of immigration/migration and connected with that racism, anti-migrant and anti-Muslim content were dominant. As such topics were also talked about and discussed by red-green parties (sometimes defending democratic values and speaking up against racism, sometimes including racist notions in their own political demands) these topics were everywhere.

On the far-right profile, Ukraine-Russia was present on both platforms and both profiles and altogether twice as prominent as Gaza in the centre-right profile. It featured in the form of the pseudo-‘peace’ demanded by BSW and AfD; the German energy crisis, vilification of the heat pump and demand to reactivate nuclear power stations; and the ‘unjust’ welfare benefits (Bürgergeld) received by Ukrainian refugees. Major overarching topics were also the criminality of immigrants; the ridiculing and bemoaning of the financial expense of ‘ideological’ green development policies and government politicians generally; public debt (austerity/ FDP vs investment in infrastructure and public services/ Greens); false elites vs ‘real democracy’ of AfD; the waste of German citizens’ money both at home and abroad.

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

For the centre-right profile, the racist and anti-immigrant as well as misogynistic content was most visible on TikTok. This included individual commentaries, some of which began making one point and then changed to make the real point. The design may have been to draw people in before challenging their views (e.g., issues such as getting rid of all immigrants, which then explored what Germany would actually be like if that were to happen). Much of this material used clips of far-right and AfD representatives such as Maximilian Krah to make their points, so curiously some of the worst material was evident only because it was collected, highlighted and contextualized in a critical way. Nevertheless, there were also limited examples of people posting under AfD and on other feeds (for example, often with “Junge”, an expression often used by youth, in the title) where these themes were implied (for instance, in posters displayed at the event) or when issues were raised and crowds responded with cheering. When the researcher did see such examples, they watched to see what claims were being made, the form that the arguments took, and a lot of it was familiar from reading in the area. Some of the examples were from individuals who claimed to have been the victims of racism or anti-immigrant or anti-Muslim sentiment, with the result that some videos were from individuals who might identify themselves as “good migrants” calling for the deportation or other treatment of the “bad immigrants” (where immigrant was not always clearly distinguished from asylum seeking and refugee groups). Other arguments were about how solidarity needs to be restricted and redirected towards the native population and sometimes also people who have earned the right to be here.

In the red-green profile, anti-migrant, racist themes were also most popular, as they were also present in the content fighting against these or other forms of discrimination. Misogynistic, anti-LGBTQ+ and other forms of discriminatory content somehow “added up on this always present noise floor of racism”. Having a heated debate on the Gaza-Israel conflict and antisemitism in Germany (and elsewhere) at the moment it was not easy to “just tick the antisemitism-box” as in Germany there are different definitions on what antisemitism actually is, having a heated societal debate on whether certain slogans (which also appear in TikTok or Instagram videos) are antisemitic per se or whether they have a different

non-antisemitic origin etc. The question of “Have you seen antisemitic content?” could therefore actually not be answered in this very short form of either yes or no.

Similarly, anti-migrant content was the most prevalent on the far-right profile, particularly following the Mannheim attack on 31 May 2024 where an Islamist immigrant from Afghanistan attacked the prominent Pax Europa speaker Stuerzenberger at an Islamophobic event meant to provoke anti-Muslim sentiments and killed an intervening young police officer. There was an interesting interview with a Muslim Iranian immigrant protesting against Islamism after the event, saying he had not fled Islamism in Iran, only for it to be imported to Germany. Misogynistic content was present in AfD positions seeking to return the German housewife to the stove and kitchen. Anti-gendering content was present occasionally, for example, in political comedy ridiculing green energy policy and gendering at the same time: ‘I’m an oil heater but today I feel like a heat pump’.

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Foreign Countries

There was very little content from other countries on political matters. A little from other EU countries occasionally appeared in the feed and was interesting for different reasons given for what were often pro-European stances (e.g., from the Czech Republic). Occasionally, live streams of events such as a G7 greeting would be shared, or the singing of Happy Birthday for Olaf Scholz encouraged by Biden. When this did appear, it was almost a breath of fresh air, something new and interesting or different

(e.g., for some reason, a speech in German by the new ambassador from Taiwan appeared in the feed of one of the researchers).

As mentioned above, Instagram was more international in its content in general terms, but Ukraine – in the sense of what it is perceived to mean for Germany – present equally on TikTok and Instagram. The US election was not a prominent theme, also China was not particularly present. Brexit only featured once in a video by Robin Mesarosch (SDP), who had travelled to Northern Ireland to demonstrate the devastating effects of Brexit as an example not to be followed.

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

The Ukraine war was a fairly common topic in the centre-right feed. There were AfD arguments that either the money spent on supporting Ukraine could be better spent on the German people (or more obviously appealing to narrow national self-interest with comments such as why we were giving money to non-Germans). This reworking of the restriction of solidarity with the national ingroup is a common feature of populist political parties and movements. The BSW argument that more diplomacy was needed was countered fairly well by Merz and Scholz that appeasing Putin was not a path to long-term security or peace. Protests against Baerbock explaining the government’s stance tended to overlap with protests about her role in approving weapons for use by Israel in Gaza. There was some CDU content also drawing upon evidence that some AfD members had been financed by Putin, ironically reversing the type of conspiracy theories that were presented on the right. The crucial point in such arguments is that it is difficult to find the evidence for their claims, it is difficult to know who can be trusted.

Likewise, in the far-right profile, Ukraine was very present and a key factor in the ‘pseudo peace’ positions of AfD and BSW. Yet the Russia-Ukraine war was only presented through the lens of German politicians and public figures. The interest of Ukraine and European solidarity was only spoken for by Annalena Baerbock. Gaza was only present on Instagram, for example, one video saying that even

Funded by
the European Union

though Gaza-Israel was a major factor in the European election, it did not feature explicitly in the party programmes, and that Yanis Varoufakis was denied participation at a conference about Gaza in Berlin because of the risk of 'public disorder'.

In contrast to the centre-right and the far-right profiles, the Russian war on Ukraine did not appear much in the red-green feed. The situation in Israel-Gaza was much more present. The police and military violence shown in such protest videos was not easy to bear, eliciting sad and helpless feelings.

Threats to Equality and Diversity

On the centre-right profile, the responsible researcher found a lot of material exploring racism and immigration from a wide range of perspectives, including personal videos commenting on these issues, which was interesting. Some seemed genuine, others felt like they could be fake (for instance, a young Turkish man outlining why he was voting for AfD). Often, talk about racism and anti-migrant views was discussed without looking closely at the examples, and sometimes the real examples were difficult to spot initially because the post started in one form and then changed. Some of the comments also seemed to be designed to create division, such as laughing at German people who felt uncomfortable waving flags as the 2024 UEFA European Football Championship started, or seeing how “good migrants” also criticized “bad migrants”. The misogyny of AfD also got a very limited treatment on the platforms, so it was refreshing when this was presented from sources other than national parties or commentaries, such as some of the progress on issues such as domestic violence at the European level. It was surprising to see little on anti-LGBTQ+ themes.

In the red-green profile, the main discriminatory content was racist and anti-migrant. In German discourse, that is also often connected to anti-Muslim stereotypes. As the red-green Instagram feed was mostly in-group, showing videos from the Greens or the SPD candidates and sometimes from their supporters or allies, the researcher was not confronted with very much discriminatory content. On TikTok, nevertheless, videos of right-wing parties, groups or supporters also made their way into the feed, showing the above-mentioned discriminatory videos, mostly with racist content.

On the far-right profile, there was content such as anti-Islamist as referred to above, however, the researcher responsible for the far right profile felt it was not always possible to give justice to the complexity nevertheless present even on these platforms – such as a Muslim joining an anti-Islamist protest, or 'long-term immigrants' being furious at the misbehavior of 'short-term immigrants', or a black German voicing support for AfD and anti-government anger. It was generally not possible to indicate the difference between anti-Muslim and anti-Islamist content on the form, as well as whether a video was endorsing or condemning 'anti-Muslim' sentiments.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

On the centre-right profile, the impression was that there was limited AI content. The data gatherer saw some obvious videos created as jokes or aimed at humiliating candidates which were broadly political but not election-related specifically. For example, a video of Angela Merkel as a trainer giving fitness tips was quite funny. Other material could have been fake because the image quality did not always seem to match what the person was saying. There were also some AI-generated animations which looked odd and somewhat alienating to the data gatherer – for example, an image of eagles soaring in some kind of rural paradise which was lit by a golden sun with the AfD logo was one example. Similarly, on the red-green profile, there were a few videos on TikTok having the label “AI-generated”. It remained unclear what exactly was AI-generated as the videos looked at first sight like “normal” videos. What probably to some extent is AI-based are the English (or German) captions in a lot of videos. Sometimes the voice-over, reading out loud the written parts in videos, was clearly an AI voice.

On the far-right profile, there were a number of instances of AI-generated videos (particularly a talk show clip of peace and conflict researcher Florence Glauck, making her sound as if she were promoting a scam), but as in the other profiles, the overall AI content seemed to be limited. Occasionally, there was a mechanical voice over, or the voice not matching lip movements, which might have been AI-generated.

Section 5: Germany: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In the section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

On the centre-right profile, the most changes in content were on TikTok as the election approached. The researcher received a wide range of material from the AfD (and supporters), Greens and BSW for the synthetic and organic profiles. It's unclear if it was possible to capture what the algorithm was and how it was working exactly as it seemed to become quite chaotic, and the cacophony of voices was at odds with the CDU supporting synthetic stance (e.g., the researcher would see quite a lot of material questioning Ursula von der Leyen and CDU figures as it was pro-CDU).

On the red-green profile, Instagram basically stayed the same throughout the whole data gathering process. Of course, there were some changes sometimes but after liking certain profiles in the beginning, the feed was actually very stable. In the week after the elections there was almost no new content by the centre-green parties, which was surprising.

On TikTok in the first week it was some kind of strange searching and establishing the feed, but it became visible within days and sometimes even after a few minutes after reloading the feed that the algorithm had adapted and stabilized the selection of whatever material the researcher had just looked at, showing more of this plus some viral (right-wing) content.

On the far-right profile, in the first week, no political content was shown on Instagram, which changed when the researcher started following accounts as noted above. At the end all content was political, if still quite diverse. With TikTok, the researcher saw a lot of very similar types of videos in the beginning, after watching one police/ immigrant check video, but at the end having much longer videos, more parliamentary speeches and talk show extracts on both organic and synthetic account. TikTok picked up on election results almost immediately, while Instagram lagged behind – even when searching for 'European election' as recommended by Helsinki in the days after the election - and showed more of the same videos on different days.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

All three researchers agreed that music is underrated for its ability to quickly create an emotional atmosphere and landscape in which the primacy of the image is overridden. Other content also is open to manipulation, such as increasing the noise of protestors when Baerbock is trying to speak at a rally, giving a sense that there is widespread and intense disagreement and dislike which may not actually be the case. The careful curating of the most emotive content to represent and repackage at particular times is also interesting, because there is a tendency to react to any video as if it just happened rather than was spoken months ago, in another context. The imagery of far-right groups was also quite diverse: sometimes dark, sometimes difficult to decode (a clear reading of blue – obviously AfD Smurfs in some kind of paradise sunlit German land), sometimes highly divisive (e.g., using language that is inflammatory and false or offensive etc.). Some of that rage and distress might appeal to young people

Funded by
the European Union

who experienced the pandemic quickly followed by the Ukraine war and new potential crises such as a second Trump term, and so on. It is important to look also at what content was presented before and then after the election results. That deserves close treatment also because it seems possible to be as bad a winner as one can be a bad loser.

Additionally while a lot of the content was in the form of political debate (for example, extracts of parliamentary speeches or talk shows), making this partly a meta question, the researchers believe these platforms will increasingly shape the form and nature of politics as they already are having massive influence, in the worst case increasing social divisions between young and old and between democratic and non-democratic spectrum. Naturally, younger age groups will be more active on these media, however middle-aged people are just as present and older people feature a lot too in interviews.

#Emotional mechanisms

For the data gatherer responsible for the centre-right profile, it is important to distinguish between what they felt and whether it is aligned with the content of the video or whether the emotional reaction registers resistance to or a need to counter the message. Because the data gatherer was using wifi for the study phone and not mobile data, the data gatherer was not in places where the contrast between the videos and the surroundings could be commented on. But also when the researcher was in private spaces watching the videos, they would be annoyed by or angry about some of the content and inspired by other material. The data gatherer found that there was an emotional residue to watching the videos that bypassed the specific figures and content. The other point for analysis is how the framing and editing of videos, including the use of music was emotive and not always obvious. For example, news reports that had music added to them to reinforce mood were obvious examples of manipulation. The directness of being talked to was also interesting as it induced more feelings of sympathy in the data gatherer (e.g., Olaf Scholz seems nice, Luisa Neubauer looks fun and clever, and so on) but also induced some feelings of (even more) antipathy. Finally, there are the emotions evident in the videos – sometimes through the dark imagery, or the yelling or ranty tone of voice, the incomprehension, the deep disappointment, the upbeat tone of the bullshit news story teasing the latest amazing scandal, which is actually never presented. All of this, including showing crowds emoting, the AfD signing the national anthem at a protest etc. provides insights into the construction of political identities and emotions via these forms of media. The data gatherer is wary when imaging what it will be like when the primary way that most people engage with content like this is via the immediacy of a VR headset (and that is the place where they spend most of their leisure or work time).

The data gatherer responsible for the red-green account noted that in general, the (emotional) impact of watching the videos was closely linked to the time and place the data gatherer was watching the videos. If the data gatherer was able to do it during work times in the office, they mostly had enough time for it and were to some extent in a more “professionally distanced role” in the office. When it was not possible to gather data during office hours, especially on the weekends, the emotional impact or effect was higher. It was maybe before going to bed, it was somewhere in between, it was in a more personal environment where also the data gatherer also thinks they may be generally more open to being touched. And, as there was probably no data gathering session, no Instagram or TikTok watching without being reminded of the climate crisis, the ongoing wars in the World and different forms of discrimination in Germany the elicited emotions were mostly of a rather sad nature.

The main emotion of the data gatherer responsible for the far-right profile was a real concern that they had previously underestimated Weidel and Wagenknecht and a dawning realisation of the danger they represented. Generally, the ‘cunning’ of resentment, the difficulty of successfully meeting its

Funded by
the European Union

proponents' rhetorical force and strategy, was somewhat frightening, as was the taboo-breaking malice of AfD parliamentary speeches: 'This government hates Germany. It leads to a war against its people' (Weidel). The data gatherer was also shocked by CDU politicians such as Spahn accusing the Ampel coalition of 'fake news', echoing the far-right. The data gatherer generally empathized with the genuine shock at the AfD result expressed by some #reclaimTikTok videos following the election. Emotion and affect were the main motors for both far-right position videos and their opposition, expressing indignation and outrage.

#Video Typologies

On Instagram, most of the videos featured statements by political actors or party supporters explaining why people should vote for them and in some cases what other parties are doing wrong. TikTok offers a wider range of content and videos—from political debates and speeches in the Bundestag and media appearances to rallies, as well as citizens' (supporters') opinions on various topics, with a particular focus on migration.

A variety of video types were featured on both platforms during the election campaign. Most prominent were **Debate Highlights** with short clips from TV or online debates. Notably on the far-right, often various debates were merged in a "investigative documentary"-style that sought to uncover some hidden or untold truth about the "establishment". At times, this category intersected with another very common type – **Supporter/Critic Videos**, produced by private content creators in support of individual parties or candidates. **Selfie Videos** of candidates were also quite prominent, as were **Campaign Videos** and **Campaign Walkabouts**. Classical campaign videos seemed to be favoured by the centre-right parties and candidates. The red-green seemed to use more innovative campaign videos and content-creator-driven Q&A formats that at times were mixed with creative overlays. Sometimes **Public Event Speeches** were filmed and used with captions and **Explainer Videos** were also rather common, mostly on the red-green and centre-right profiles.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Narrative 1. Mobilizing young voters for EP2024 election

Katharina Barley, official account: Katharina Barley, Spitzenkandidatin (“prime candidate”) for the SPD, sits in chair, takes questions on why young people should vote in the EP2024 election acting as if they were sent to her via mobile phone (presumably social media) and answers them. The questions she answers are being posed by a person on a mobile phone screen. The Q&A session via mobile phone/ social media is a professionally made video with prepared questions. The video does not seek to deceive people about the authenticity of the Q&A situation but openly recreates this communicative situation, with the aim to highlight the directness of political communication and connection between the politician and the (young) voters via social media.

Narrative 2. Generating sympathy and relatability through deliberate non-politics (showing politicians’ “human” side)

CDU Germany official account: A young woman interviews various CDU members about their most prominent contact on their phone. Professionally made video that uses quick changes of scenes (interview partners) and the insertion of big icons representing what is being said (e.g., someone answer – jokingly – that his most important contact was Lionel Messi, so Messi is being stamped onto the screen with a fitting stamping sound).

Narrative 3: Debunking the “other” / Whataboutism

Account “Deutsche Wahrheit” [German truth], AfD supporter: video is a mash-up of interviews, headlines, photos and videos with voice-over. It is made by a layperson but cut with delicacy and deliberateness. The video starts with Beatrix von Storch, member of AfD, highlighting that she has been attacked and the victim of political crime and demanding the same standards of protection and blaming be applied to all public figures, thereby insinuating that the attacks against her and her party companions are not taken seriously and judged by a different standard. This line of reasoning is taken up in the video. The objective of the clip’s mash-up is to debunk this “plot” against the AfD and its supporters as the perpetrators of political violence and the perceived “innocence” of Greens politicians as the victims of right-wing political violence. The video adopts a quasi-documentary style. Interviews and statements are mixed with (pseudo-)legal reasoning and statistics (which are not explained and are always only shown very briefly).

Discussion on most interesting videos

We discussed the most interesting videos above,

See above.

Funded by
the European Union

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion on the basis of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was the EU About and Why Vote (Social Contract)?

Social media posts from groups such as the Greens and CDU during the election campaign presented the European Union primarily as a source of strength, prosperity, and security, with European election voting often presented as a means to reduce the possibility that anti-democratic and authoritarian parties would benefit from political disengagement. The Greens and CDU differed in terms of their support for stronger controls on immigration, with the Greens emphasizing human rights and solutions to asylum seekers and refugees that could be found at a European level. On the far-right, Europe or the European Parliament election hardly featured and in the few instances when it did feature, the EU was portrayed negatively. According to the AfD's Weidel, the only potentially positive role of the EU, which she said it had failed to fulfil, was to secure the EU's borders. She claimed Schengen was supposed to open internal borders in exchange for closing external borders.

A decisive part of the social media campaign played on geopolitical concerns and the Russian War against Ukraine. Some videos compared parties in terms of their different policies, also mentioning their views on issues such as the military rearmament of Europe. However, a differentiated and more subtle analysis on the basis of the geopolitical stances of political parties was often not visible. For example, the issue was reduced to “war-mongering government” versus “peace promotion” by BSW and AfD. CDU and other party posts, in contrast, portrayed the AfD in particular as receiving financial support from Putin and the BSW as naïve in adopting a “Chamberlain”-like diplomatic stance. Left-orientated profiles either did not address the war in Ukraine as prominently or held similar positions to the CDU and SPD. In a range of clips which included speeches and parts of televised interviews, the CDU identified Russia as the clear aggressor in the Ukraine war and the European Union as the key actor capable of resisting.

Another motivation results from the successful rhetoric of AfD (and to some extent BSW) to relate any geopolitical, geoeconomic or geocological expense such as financial support for Ukraine, back to the specific economic harm done to the individual citizen. Although a lot of the information was false (e.g., in regard to climate development policies such as the infamous “bicycle lane in Peru”) or oversimplified (e.g., money for arms to Ukraine could be spent on improving schools instead), the social contract is here reformulated as a contract of financial injustice – again, mostly in national terms. The national parties appeared to be doing national election campaigns, sometimes with content related to the EU. For the far-right there was hardly any genuinely European content that related to the European elections. In fact, there were hardly any references to the EP elections at all. The scant European content was then mostly also “only” highlighting the respective positive or negative effects for Germany and with regard to different views of the future and national interests.

Overall, the research team did get the impression that content on social media platforms can potentially motivate people to vote, can inform people and can influence people's voting decisions by reminding them of broader social values. This became apparent in the AfD's social media strategy which has over several years built a strong network and community especially on TikTok, being the by far leading party in terms of followership, reposts, and likes (e.g., posting for supporters to share so that 50,000 likes could be achieved). Their followers or community know how to repost, stitch, comment and so on so

Funded by
the European Union

that videos will be favoured by the TikTok algorithm. Other (democratic) parties have only recently (e.g., a few months before the EP Elections) started to use TikTok and as a result, they do not have that community on TikTok. This was suggested by the very low levels of views for some of the main parties, including attempts to be engaging that appeared to trivialize important political issues or focus too much on material that might alienate potential supporters. For example, CDU and Greens “fun” videos attempting to connect with voters over the upcoming European Men’s Football Championship or showing “behind the scenes” of a party conference or karate-chopping an AfD symbol, contrast starkly with the bitterness and grievance as well as the passion and pride expressed in some AfD supporter videos. Our research suggested that even though supporters of a party such as the CDU might have the opportunity to view a lot of material from the Greens, BSW, SPD or AfD, ultimately their choices of what to watch and their engagement with it (e.g., reposting, commenting etc.), their posts were often not primarily concerned with political content aimed at attracting new voters, but rather served as self-affirmation for the already existing voters.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

A negative self-understanding and self-identity that worked through critique of the (political) other was very noticeable on reels that supported the AfD or BSW. Reels supporting AfD often would construct an anti-establishment narrative, sometimes through ridiculing the political opponent but mostly through seeking to dismantle ‘fake truths’. Supporter videos often take on the attire of an investigative documentary wishing to unravel the alleged lies being constantly told by established parties and media. A negative identity was also present in reels from or supporting Die Linke and Greens, particularly when it came to LGBTQ+ issues and women. Here often the content creators warned of the AfD agenda on these issues and the negative consequences that would arise for these groups. There were also reels associated with the centre-right profiles that warned of the negative consequences for the EU should the BSW get a strong vote.

Political actors — particularly the AfD, BD (Bürgerbewegung Deutschland [Citizen Movement Germany]), and movements like Nächste Generation [Next Generation] — consistently construct a political “us” that is emotionally and morally superior, under siege from external threats (e.g., migrants, the EU, progressive values, elites). They define:

“Us” as:

- Real Germans (AfD)
- Patriots, tax-paying citizens, or ordinary people
- Victims of EU overreach or elite manipulation

“Them” as:

- Migrants, asylum seekers, Islamists, LGBTQI+
- EU bureaucrats (portrayed as distant, corrupt, inefficient)
- The Greens, mainstream media, left/liberal elites
- The U.S. and Britain (accused of war profiteering)

Affective practices include:

Funded by
the European Union

- Use of victimhood: portraying Germans as punished by unfair policies (e.g., sanctions, immigration).
- Nostalgia and fear: invoking traditional values and painting change as dangerous (e.g., “remigration”, fear of Islam, or loss of national identity, fear of LGBTQI+).
- Righteous indignation: claims of injustice, such as judicial bias or media corruption, to mobilize emotional responses.

Furthermore, the parties and politicians differed in the relation they constructed to the European Union.

Strong EU-criticism was promoted mostly on groups and parties that feature prominently on the far-right profile, such as AfD and BD (Bündnis Deutschland). They described the EU as undemocratic, economically harmful and having too much influence over national politics. These actors also put forward national sovereignty, criticised EU support for Ukraine and called for cutting down EU bureaucracy. The emotional tone used was one of distrust, anger, nationalism and defensiveness.

There was also a moderate form of EU-criticism issued by parties like the left-wing BSW who criticised the EU's foreign policy and especially its alleged militarism. BSW argued that instead of military support the EU should claim peace and economic justice and use diplomacy. The emotional tone used was one of concern, sometimes defensiveness.

Statements from mainstream parties or politicians were often described as elitist or disconnected by both populist groups.

Pro-EU positions were advanced by the Greens, SPD and CDU and their supporters on social media. They argue in favour of environmental sustainability, social cohesion and shared EU responsibility. The emotional tone used was one of idealism, responsibility and moral urgency.

Conclusions

The research generated insights into the ways that users of social media are likely to engage with political material when it appears on their feeds and whether and how they may like, repost, share or comment on those posts in ways that express, capture, communicate or create and focus political emotions. For example, it is possible to some people watch posts when they have time in spaces that are private as well as public. This is not a trivial matter because posts might reinforce what people are seeing around them and draw their attention to ways in which policies are impacting on individuals and communities (e.g., creating a sense of crisis or urgency). Many posts express and address values, identities and positions that people care about, often deeply. When information is presented in emotive ways it may do so in ways that undermine more critical evaluation of the source, as well as possible counterarguments that might, for instance, reduce a sense of outrage. It was interesting, therefore, to see some videos expressly addressing issues such as ways that far right extremists manipulate viewers, although how many viewers might apply their insights is a topic for further research. When watching some of the videos, there can be a temptation to share them with others depending on the emotions involved. In this respect, more work needs to be done to focus on the construction of influential or popular posts, not only in terms of how they make the viewer feel, but also with regard to what emotions are depicted in them. For example, editing a post to show (or simply state without showing) Olaf Scholz as enraged at the anti-war sentiments of what are presented as ordinary, reasonable people with real concerns, might create a sense of outrage. The use of music or extreme images to create a mood is also worth of further investigation (e.g., presenting AfD press conferences with a background of circus music might be amusing but of little value in achieving a deeper understanding of political similarities and points of difference). AfD videos often tried to put forward a strong symbolism indicating

that “we are the AfD and we’re ready to defend tradition and culture”. This may encourage viewers to make connections with wider grievances in people’s lives and how to explore alternative means of empowerment. We also need to give consideration to the way emotions are evoked and portrayed at key points such as in the days before the election and afterwards. It was notable that AfD supporters felt even more empowered to ridicule the losing Ampel (and other) parties and figures and switch quickly to being confident that their momentum could continue. The emergence of new small parties such as Volt presented the possibility that they might be a new home for people disillusioned with the Greens but still wanting to support progressive politics.

Bibliography

- Berendsen, E., & Schnabel, D.** (2024). Das TikTok-Universum der (extremen) Rechten Trends, Strategien und Ästhetik in der Social-Media-Kommunikation Report. #RechteJugend Analyse & Empfehlungen der Bildungsstätte Anne Frank. https://www.bs-anne-frank.de/fileadmin/content/Publikationen/Weiteres_Pädagogisches_Material/Das_TikTok_Universum_der_extremen_Rechten_Report_RechteJugend_2.pdf
- Correctiv** (2024). Secret Plans against Germany. Available online at: <https://correctiv.org/en/top-stories/2024/01/15/secret-plan-against-germany/> Accessed on 29 September 2024
- European Parliament** (2024a). <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/national-results/germany/2024-2029/> Accessed on 29 September 2024
- European Parliament** (2024b) <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/tools/comparative-tool/> Accessed on 29 September 2024
- Reuters** (2024a). <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/year-political-challenges-germany-2024-01-10/> Accessed on 29 September 2024
- Reuters** (2024b). <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/german-court-upholds-extremist-classification-far-right-party-2024-05-13/> Accessed on 29 September 2024
- The Federal Returning Officer** (2024). <https://www.bundeswahlleiterin.de/en/europawahlen/2024/ergebnisse/bund-99.html> Accessed on 29 September 2024

**COntinuous COnstruction
of resilient social COntracts
through societal transformations**

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Hungary

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Szilvia Horváth and Katinka Linnamäki, University of Helsinki; Gabriella Szabó, HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences, Hungary
Editors	Alexander Alekseev and Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki;
Reviewer(s):	Emre Erdoğan, Istanbul Bilgi University

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Hungary: EP Election Results.....	5
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	6
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	8
Section 2: Hungary: Political profiles	12
# Centre Right feed	14
# Far Right feed	18
# Red-Green feed	21
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	25
Section 3: Hungary: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	27
# Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	27
# Notes on the organic profiles	29
# Differences Observed Over Time	31
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok.....	36
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	37
Section 4: Hungary: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	39
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	39
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram.....	41
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	42
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	44
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	45
# AI Generated Content	45
Section 5: Hungary: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal	47
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time.....	47
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate.....	47
#Emotional mechanisms	48
#Video Typologies.....	49
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	50
# Discussion on most interesting videos.....	52

2

Funded by
the European Union

Concluding section	54
# What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?	54
# Populist mobilisation	56
# Conclusion	56
Bibliography	57

Hungary: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

At a record 59%, the turnout for the 2024 European Parliament election was comparatively high, partially because local elections were held on the same day. Despite winning, Fidesz lost two seats in the European Parliament due to a poorer performance than in the 2019 European elections. With almost 30 per cent of the vote, Péter Magyar's recently rebranded Tisza Party as a newcomer political force came in second, taking seven seats and vastly outperforming all other opposition parties. Tisza became a potent force to challenge Fidesz. The left-wing Democratic Coalition's support was cut in half, and the liberal Momentum party lost all of its seats. The far-right Mi Hazánk party secured one seat in the European Parliament with 6.7 per cent of the vote.

The results of the social media data collection showed that the centre-right Tisza Party positioned itself in opposition to the entire Orbán regime, with its campaign themes focusing on domestic issues. As expected, the left-wing campaign's themes were pro-Europe and social, while the far-right's discourse, mainly characterized by Fidesz, was dominated by war and peace. The oppositional far-right made criticisms of the EU's leadership and functioning.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Az EP-választáson rekordmagas, 59%-os volt a részvétel, részben azért, mert ugyanazon a napon önkormányzati választást is tartottak. Habár a választást a Fidesz nyerte, két hellyel kevesebbet szerzett az Európai Parlamentben, mint 2019-ben, mivel rosszabbul szerepelt, mint a korábbi EP-választáson. Magyar Péter nem sokkal korábban induló Tisza Pártja közel 30%-os eredménnyel második helyen végzett és hét mandátumot szerzett, messze felülmúlva az összes többi ellenzéki pártot. A Tisza komoly kihívóként jelent meg a Fidesszel szemben. A baloldali Demokratikus Koalíció támogatottsága meglehetősen csökkent, a liberális Momentum pedig minden EP-mandátumát elveszítette. A szélsőjobboldali Mi Hazánk Mozgalom 6,7%-os eredménnyel egy helyet szerzett az Európai Parlamentben. Adatgyűjtésünk eredménye azt mutatta, hogy a jobbközép Tisza Párt az Orbán-rendszer egészével szemben határozta meg magát, és kampánytémái elsősorban belpolitikaiak voltak. A baloldali kampánytémák, ahogyan az várható volt, Európa-pártiak és szociális karakterűek voltak, míg a szélsőjobb, elsősorban a Fidesz diskurzusát, jórészt a háború és a béke határozta meg. Az ellenzéki szélsőjobb konkrét, az EP vezetését és működését érintő kritikákat fogalmazott meg.

Section 1: Hungary: EP Election Results

The turnout was high compared to the previous EP elections, almost reaching 60%, 16 percentage points higher than the previous one. The governing far-right Fidesz won the election with nearly 45%, but the Tisza Party, which had entered the political scene only a few months earlier, was the political winner with 30%. The opposition parties that had joined forces in the previous parliamentary election were the big losers in the EP election. The left-green opposition coalition (MSZP-DK-Párbeszéd Zöldek) got only 8%, and the liberal party (Momentum) did not get in, nor did the joke party (Hungarian Two-Tailed Dog Party). On the opposition side, apart from the Tisza, only the far-right party (Mi Hazánk Mozgalom) managed to increase its voter numbers and get into the EP.

Results by national party - 2024-2029

Hungary - Final results

Figure 1.
Results by
national party

Percentage of votes

National
Election
Results
and Party

National Parties

Fidesz-KDNP - Coalition Fidesz – Magyar Polgári Szövetség - Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt

TISZA - Tisztelet és Szabadság Pártja

DK-MSZP-P - Coalition DK-MSZP-P (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd-Zöldek)

Mi Hazánk - Mi Hazánk Mozgalom

Momentum - Momentum Mozgalom

MKKP - Magyar Kétfarkú Kutyapárt

Jobbik - Jobbik - Konzervatívok

LMP - Zöldek - Magyarország Zöld Pártja

ZRK - Második Reformkor

MMN - Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt

Memo - Megoldás Mozgalom

Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Affiliations

In 2022, Fidesz decided to change the day when the local elections can be held and by the constitution, put the municipal and the European elections on the same day (Wolters Kluwer Jogsabálytár, 2022).

6

Funded by
the European Union

This might have had a mobilizing effect, as the voters' turnout became 59,46% (4.640.398) (Nemzeti Választási Iroda, 2024) compared to 43,58% (3.470.566) in 2019 (Nemzeti Választási Iroda, 2019). Although Fidesz won the election by mobilizing about 2 million voters (in 2019, 1,8 million), and with 44,82% they gained 11 seats, in fact, they lost 2 compared to 2019. A newly established party mostly challenged their apparent expectation of a minimum of 45% win, Tisztelet és Szabadság Párt (Respect and Freedom Party, abbreviated as Tisza), which got 1,3 million votes and 7 seats. The center-right Tisza, led by an ex-Fidesz member, Péter Magyar, won less than 30% of the votes, thus becoming the strongest oppositional party in 2024. Tisza's appearance on the political scene challenged the government during the campaign and took votes from other oppositional parties from the left.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

The left alliance, MSZP-DK-Párbeszéd Zöldek (Hungarian Socialist Party–Democratic Coalition–Dialogue Greens), led by the biggest left party DK (Democratic Coalition), gathered only 8% of the national votes. The other left-liberal party, Momentum, did not reach the necessary 5% minimum to gain a seat in the EP. Regionally, the Greens performed better in Central, Eastern, and Southern European countries. In Hungary Greens suffered losses, they did not win any seats, like in Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Malta, Poland, or Slovakia. Apart from Tisza, the other party that did not lose from its electoral base was the radical right, Mi Hazánk Mozgalom (Our Homeland Movement), which managed to gain almost 7% of the votes and its first seat in the EP.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Hungary

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

Originally, *Fidesz* planned to put Judit Varga at the top of the party’s EP list. However, she failed in the paedophile scandal that erupted in early 2024 after it turned out that the president legally pardoned a person who supported a paedophile criminal. Varga counter-signed the pardon as Justice Minister. Suddenly, the party had to find a new leading candidate and build its public profile on short notice. Finally, Tamás Deutsch, a founding member of *Fidesz*, a former minister of sports, and a MEP, was selected. He has also been involved in drug abuse scandals before, and this image haunted him throughout the campaign.

In the feeds not following *Fidesz*, Orbán was present almost exclusively, not the candidates. While this is certainly related to local and EP elections being held on the same day, Orbán’s messages had a strong European dimension. Orbán was the main face of the campaign, and for a long time, he toured the country.

The surprise of the elections is the emerging Tisza Party, which, based on TikTok and Instagram, was clearly the one-man party of Péter Magyar, Judit Varga’s ex-husband. As many political commentators agreed, Magyar’s “origin story” was controversial. As an ex-*Fidesz* member, fulfilling prominent roles in the country thanks to his close ties with the government, he stood out against the government only after his ex-wife, Varga was fired. According to him, he waited so long to protect his ex-wife, however, Magyar-critical voices emphasized his possible aim to “avenge” that the political career of his ex-wife was broken at its peak.

Magyar entered the scene as a politician in February 2024 and, in April, took over a legally existing but politically non-functioning party, Respect and Freedom, which was registered for the election at the last minute. The party did not run in the municipal elections (only in some parts of Budapest) but did in the

EP elections and convinced 1.3 million voters. At the same time, the old opposition collapsed. Part of the opposition maintained its previous election coalition of 2022 but performed extremely poorly; the liberal party (Momentum), which primarily targeted young people, has essentially disappeared. The Hungarian Two-Tailed Dog Party (MKKP, *Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt*), a joke party, was hoped to cross its own threshold and become a party of national importance, but this did not happen either.

Mi Hazánk Mozgalom has not lost its electoral base. Their top candidates were the two top party members, László Toroczkai (president) and Dóra Dúró (vice president). However, they both announced that they would not leave the country (due to their commitment to Hungary and their families) and thus would not accept a seat in the EP. Accordingly, the party's main candidate was the third name on their list, Zsuzsanna Borvendég. Borvendég is a newcomer to politics; she formerly worked as a historian for the Historical Research Centre of the Hungarian Research Institute (MKI, *Magyarságtudató Intézet*).

It is also noteworthy that Péter Magyar contacted the EPP already during the campaign, making clear their right-wing and European orientation, even though nothing was decided regarding their future membership. Later, the party was smoothly integrated into the existing political structure of the EP. Fidesz left the EPP earlier in 2021, and it was open for a long time about where they were heading. Although Orbán's search for a coalition pointed towards Meloni, a new fraction was eventually formed on the political fringe, Patriots for Europe. Orbán started an independent European foreign policy activity during the Hungarian presidency in the second half of 2024, which met with sharp rejection and likely further isolated him politically within Europe. However, he was able to convey the image of a strong and potent leader to the Fidesz voters and the international radical right. Discursively, the latter is a direct continuation of what we saw from him on TikTok and Instagram during the research.

The left-leaning progressive parties joined their forces and ran together in 2024. DK, led by former Prime Minister Ferenc Gyurcsány, is known for its pro-European stance and support for a progressive social agenda, consistently positioning itself as a vocal critic of the Orbán government's approach to democracy and rule-of-law issues. MSZP, historically Hungary's main social democratic party, has experienced a decline over recent years, often joining forces with other opposition groups to maintain relevance. *Párbeszéd* (Dialogue), the green-left faction led by the non-party Mayor of Budapest Gergely Karácsony, emphasizes environmental sustainability and social justice. Together, the DK-MSZP-*Párbeszéd* coalition advocates for closer integration with the European Union and a reversal of Hungary's democratic backsliding, a focus on values aligned with European principles and transparency.

Klára Dobrev, the list leader, is a Hungarian politician, economist, and a current member of the European Parliament. She is married to Ferenc Gyurcsány, a former Prime Minister of Hungary. She is a leading figure in the Democratic Coalition, a social-liberal political party in Hungary founded by her husband. Dobrev was elected as an MEP in the 2019 European Parliament elections, where she has been actively involved in various committees and initiatives. She was elected as one of the Vice-Presidents of the European Parliament, a significant leadership role within the institution. Dobrev is known for her advocacy on issues such as women's rights, social justice, and the rule of law within the EU. Dobrev often speaks out on national issues and criticizes the political direction of Hungary under the current government.

Csaba Molnár, second on the list, is a prominent figure in DK with a strong background in EU affairs. With expertise in law and politics, he focuses on democratic governance, economic policy, and social welfare. Molnár frequently addresses Hungary's role within the EU, advocating for initiatives that support a federative European Union, aligning closely with DK's pro-European stance.

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

Hungary - Constitutive session

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PIE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
Fidesz-KDNP	44.82%			11							11
TISZA	29.60%	7									7
DK-MSZP-P	8.03%		2								2
Mi Hazánk	6.71%								1		1
Momentum	3.70%										0
MKKP	3.59%										0
Jobbik	0.99%										0
LMP - Zöldek	0.87%										0
2RK	0.68%										0
MMN	0.64%										0
Memo	0.37%										0
Other parties	0.00%										0
	100.00%	7	2	11	0	0	0	0	1	0	21

Fidesz-KDNP > PIE: TAMÁS DEUTSCH, VIKTÓRIA FERENC, KINGA GÁL, BALÁZS GYÖRFFY, ENIKŐ GYŐRI, ANDRÁS GYÚRK, ANDRÁS LÁSZLÓ, ERNŐ SCHALLER-BAROSS, PÁL SZEKERES, ANNAMÁRIA VICSEK

TISZA > EPP: DÓRA DÁVID, GABRIELLA GERZSENYI, KINGA KOLLÁR, ANDRÁS TIVADAR KULJA, ESZTER LAKOS, PÉTER MAGYAR, ZOLTÁN TARR

DK > S&D: KLÁRA DOBREV, CSABA MOLNÁR

Mi Hazánk > ESN: ZSUZSANNA BORVENDÉG

KDNP > PIE: GYÖRGY HÖLVÉNYI

National Parties

Fidesz-KDNP - Coalition Fidesz - Magyar Polgári Szövetség - Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt

TISZA - Tisztelet és Szabadság Pártja

DK-MSZP-P - Coalition DK-MSZP-P (Demokratikus Koalíció, Magyar Szocialista Párt, Párbeszéd-Zöldek)

Mi Hazánk - Mi Hazánk Mozgalom

Momentum - Momentum Mozgalom

MKKP - Magyar Kétfarkú Kutypárt

Jobbik - Jobbik - Konzervatívok

LMP - Zöldek - Magyarország Zöld Pártja

2RK - Második Reformkor

MMN - Mindenki Magyarországa Néppárt

Memo - Megoldás Mozgalom

Other parties - Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

● EPP - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)

● S&D - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament

● PIE - Patriots for Europe

● ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group

● Renew Europe - Renew Europe Group

● Greens/EFA - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance

● The Left - The Left group in the European Parliament - GUE/NGL

● ESN - Europe of Sovereign Nations

● NI - Non-attached Members

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

In third place on the list is Ágnes Vadai (DK), recognized for her outspoken stance on national defence, security, and human rights. A seasoned politician with experience as a former Secretary of State in the Ministry of Defence, Vadai is deeply engaged in issues related to Hungarian democracy and civil rights. Her advocacy supports DK's pro-European Union orientation.

The fifth position on the list is held by an MSZP candidate. Kata Tüttö, with a solid background in municipal governance and environmental advocacy, brings expertise in urban development and green policies. Formerly serving as Deputy Mayor of Budapest, she is a strong proponent of sustainable urban planning and climate-resilient infrastructure, closely aligning with the coalition's commitment to green initiatives and environmentally sustainable policy solutions.

Despite being a combined list of opposition parties, they collectively won two seats which was a failure compared to 2019. In 2019 DK, MSZP, and *Párbeszéd* ran separate campaigns or collaborated in limited ways. Democratic Coalition (DK), led by Klára Dobrev, gained 16.1% of the vote, securing 4 out of Hungary's 21 seats in the EP. MSZP-*Párbeszéd* ran on a joint list in 2019, which included candidates from both MSZP and *Párbeszéd*. Despite this alliance, the list received 6.6% of the vote, yielding only 1 seat for the alliance. As Figure 2 shows, the presence of accounts linked to left-green EP groups lagged behind those of the right-wing ones and was particularly low on TikTok.

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

Section 2: Hungary: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

Disclaimer: When finalising the report, we noticed that researchers inconsistently coded the national parties' European Party affiliations. This affected Fidesz, which was categorised either as non-inscrit or EPP, and Tisza, for which researchers also used inconsistent categorisation. This was probably because it was not decided where Tisza would join at the time of data collection, and Fidesz was previously a member of the EPP group but left it, even though their coalition partner, KDNP, stayed in the group. Therefore, in the visuals, non-inscrits and EPP can include both parties, who otherwise contradict each other. The issue affects only the visuals of EP party affiliations. The Helsinki team responsible for WP4 plans to fix the issue by the project's mid-term review.

In Hungary, there were only a few parties who appeared on the feeds altogether six Hungarian parties had a significant presence: new opposition party Tisza – Respect and Freedom Party, ruling party Fidesz-KDNP, far-right Our Homeland Movement, and the liberal DK-MSZP-Dialogue Alliance and Momentum. The red-green spectrum covered the DK-MSZP-Dialogue Alliance, Momentum, and the Hungarian Two-Tailed Dog Party. We categorized in the right spectrum: Mi Hazánk Mozgalom to the far-right and Tisza – Respect and Freedom Party as moderate right. In both of them and Fidesz-KDNP party coalition to the radical right had a presence, but it also appeared in the liberal feed.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok.

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

There were no major differences between TikTok and Instagram, and the political content was stable on the platforms, although it intensified towards the end of the campaign. For the far-right profiles, Fidesz dominated Instagram, while *Mi Hazánk* (Our Homeland), TikTok. Both the left-greens and the far-right produced a lot of content, while for the centre-right, non-official content was the most common type. With time, content from foreign parties also appeared on the feeds, consistently with the ideological profiles: for the far-right, AfD, for the left-greens, the European Greens, and for the centre-right, von der Leyen’s videos. The fact that the EP 2024 and local mayoral elections were held on the same day had an impact on the smaller parties; left-green *Párbeszéd* politicians concentrated more on the local elections. On the left side, Socialists (MSZP) had the lowest visibility.

It is true for all three ideological profiles that on TikTok, the party representing the best of the ideology was most markedly present: Tisza for the centre-right, DK-MSZP-*Párbeszéd* Alliance for the left-green, and Fidesz and *Mi Hazánk* for the radical right ideological profiles. At the same time, some peculiar characteristics can be observed: in the centre-right profile, in addition to the dominant party, Tisza, Fidesz’s presence was also significant, while in the radical right-wing profile, *Mi Hazánk*, which is on the radical end of the ideological spectrum, was somewhat more strongly present than Fidesz. Interestingly, the opposition left-green profile included some, although marginal presence of the other right-wing but still opposition party, Tisza. The party, however, remained marginal in the radical right ideological profile, too. The left-wing parties of the ideological spectrum did not appear in the right-wing profiles.

The Instagram profiles produced a surprising result. The leading party of the centre-right profile has become Fidesz. The key party we included here, Tisza, was only the third most frequently appearing. The centre-left coalition was also very strongly present in this centre-right ideological profile. The results of the left-wing ideological profile are similar to this in that the presence of the leftist party coalition was

13

surprisingly modest here as well. Fidesz was also present here to a small extent. The results of the radical right-wing ideological profile best meet our expectations; the two far-right parties, Fidesz and *Mi Hazánk*, were strongly present here. Compared to TikTok, their place has been reversed on Instagram: Fidesz, stronger in terms of political support, has gained the upper hand.

Comparing TikTok and Instagram, we see that the results of the radical right-wing profiles are the most similar, and the presence of associated parties is the strongest of all profiles. The very weak presence of left-green parties within the left-green ideological profile is surprising. One explanation could be that, despite the three parties' electoral alliance, the left-green political spectrum is rather fragmented. The party alliance may find it difficult to acquire substantial traction as a result of this fragmentation, which may reduce its overall impact and visibility. At the same time, the centre-right profile is similar to this: the frequency of the centre-right party's appearance was also much more modest here. It can be said on Instagram that Fidesz dominated all right-wing ideological profiles, and the presence of the opposition challenger, Tisza, was definitely significantly lower than their election results would suggest.

Centre Right feed

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

The centre-right position was occupied by the newcomer Péter Magyar (and the Tisza Party) who was mainly active on TikTok. The party and Magyar had a presence on Instagram, but with a negligible amount of their own content. The party or Magyar did not create most of the content accessed, but by their followers. It is significant in this social media context that Magyar participated in a country campaign during the data collection period. This was unique in the history of the opposition after 2010 and enabled an interesting interplay between social media presence and the corporeal experience of followers. Magyar visited about 200 mainly small and medium-sized settlements. Most of the content shared on TikTok came from his speeches at these events. Most of the content that reached the data collector’s feed was recorded and shared by those who participated in these events. This was practically Péter Magyar’s one-man show; next to him, only the medical doctor András Kulja was present in the feed (Kulja became a MEP later.)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Most of the topics were almost exclusively domestic in character and reflected the party's self-positioning vis-à-vis Fidesz. This is visible in the graphs of Figure 7-9 where the most recurring topics were "other": showing clearly that the focus of the EP-campaign was largely domestic in nature. Magyar said several times that the EP elections were only one step in dismantling the Orbán regime. The policy proposals were related to this, the most important of which was anti-corruption and stopping the transfer of the national wealth to the Orbán family and his friends. An equally powerful theme was the critique of the propaganda machinery. Through Kulja's presence, the situation of health care (a classical policy problem) was also thematized. However, policy offers were not strong and mostly matched with previous offers by the "old" opposition.

The party's European orientation was clear, but at this time, their relationship to Russia's full-scale invasion in Ukraine – which dominated Fidesz's EP campaign (see Figure 12) – was still vague or ambivalent. Contents from Fidesz also appeared in the centre-right-oriented feed. However, traditional far-right or directly Putinist content remained relatively rare. TikTok kept the synthetic profile in the centre-right terrain strongly. However, the presence of the topic of war is clearly visible in Figure 7. Also noteworthy was the appearance of critical, or critical plus humorous contents of Orbán and the Orbán regime after a point (with traditional right-wing characteristics, such as references to rurality or countryside life), which shows a spontaneous, popular appearance of regime opposition in the social media space.

Far Right feed

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

In the far-right feeds, the main figure of the campaign was Prime Minister Viktor Orbán, most of the Instagram posts were clips and images with captions from his speeches or interviews during the campaign. On TikTok they released mostly the same clips, but in a bit longer and less edited format. The top candidate, Tamás Deutsch was almost never present on the feed. Their main message was about the war in Ukraine, and the stakes of the EP election became a question of life versus death (see Figure 12). First, the war was mostly framed from an economic perspective; with time, more and more fearful messages were released, targeting one’s fears for their own and for their family members’ lives. Besides, the government has posted a lot of negative campaigns against Péter Magyar, in the form of short videos made by young individuals paid by the government.

From *Mi Hazánk* the key influencers were László Toroczkai and Dóra Dúró, the president and vice president of the party. Toroczkai was banned from Meta (Instagram and Facebook), so he was absent from Instagram but dominated the TikTok feed. He made lots of content, mostly videos, where he explained certain corruption cases. He strongly targeted Ursula von der Leyen and the EPP and the EU’s connection to the WHO and their common way of building out a “global COVID dictatorship”. Besides, he targeted domestic cases of corruption, mainly related to the cases of evictions and “executive mafia”, which handles private people’s personal credits. Occasionally anti-immigration and anti-Ukrainian content was also shared. Dóra Dúró was mostly active on Instagram. She mostly shared posts in the form of images with written messages on them. She mostly addressed domestic political issues, on the policy level (like the right to use cash, the right for men to retire after 40 years of service).

Zsuzsanna Borvendég was *Mi Hazánk* party’s main candidate, because the two top party leaders, László Toroczkay and Dóra Dúró announced that they would not accept the European parliamentary position. Borvendég, who was only the third on the party list, thus, became the candidate for the EP membership. However, she was mostly absent from the feed.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Red-Green feed

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

The red-green ideological spectrum encompasses the left opposition to the government. Their key actor was the party coalition, which included the leftist parties in the broad coalition formed prior to the 2022 national elections. These parties were *Párbeszéd*, a small party whose key figure was the mayor of Budapest, Gergely Karácsony. Besides them, the Hungarian Social Party, a party that was in power in the 90s and the 2000s but has become even smaller during the Orbán era and has struggled for sheer existence in the past years. DK was a party formed in 2011 by Ferenc Gyurcsány, the leftist prime minister in the 2000s, who became the most important adversary, the “Other”, for the Fidesz government. Klára Dobrev, Gyurcsány’s wife and prominent party member, was the leader of the party’s EP list. Besides the party alliance, there were two parties visible in the feeds: Momentum, the liberal party originally formed against Orbán’s plan to hold the Olympic games, and MKKP, a joke party, even though the latter presence was marginal (for party and key party figures’ visibility see Figures 4a, 4b, and Figures 20a, 20b).

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Gergely Karácsony, Richárd Barabás, and the *Párbeszéd* party placed significant emphasis on addressing the ongoing housing crisis, advocating for policies that ensure affordable and accessible housing for all citizens. They were also staunch supporters of LGBTQAI+ rights, calling for equal protection under the law for all individuals, regardless of sexual orientation or gender identity.

Environmental sustainability was a central concern for the coalition, with plans to protect natural areas, improve public transportation, and ensure animal welfare, particularly in urban settings. Their policies aimed to create greener, more sustainable cities while ensuring that economic development does not come at the expense of the environment.

In addition, the promotion of cultural initiatives was part of their broader agenda, with events like book fairs being highlighted as key to enriching and diversifying the community's cultural life, which is very much relatable for urban upper-middle-class people.

Particularly, the Socialists emphasized urban and rural development as core elements of their campaign messages. They advocated for policies that promote sustainable growth and investment in human capacities (education and health) in both urban centres and rural areas, with special emphasis on the failure of the Fidesz-led government. The pro-European stance was also a key component, as they continued to support Hungary's place within the progressive European Union and pursued policies that aligned with European values and cooperation with Western European allies.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

In their campaign, Gergely Karácsony, Richárd Barabás, and the *Párbeszéd* party took a proactive approach in addressing criticisms directly. Responding to the negative campaign targeting the mayor of Budapest, they emphasized transparency (“nothing to hide”-approach) and communicated the achievements of Karácsony’s administration, showcasing the progress made during his tenure. This strategy promoted the positive outcomes of their policies and highlighted the contrast with the opposition’s shortcomings.

Criticism of political opponents was a key tactic, focusing on pointing out flaws and contrasting policies. At the same time, the campaign emphasized the personality of Gergely Karácsony, positioning him as a relatable and approachable figure. By sharing personal anecdotes, such as his high school experiences, and showcasing his leisure activities, the campaign sought to humanize Karácsony and make him more relatable to the public. His frequent presence among supporters further solidified his image as a "people's politician."

Klára Dobrev, the EP list leader, also similarly engaged with her supporters, fostering an image of being close to the people (physically with hugs and handshakes, and verbally with comforting words such as “I understand you”, “Hang in there”, “I know that it is hard for you”). Part of her campaign strategy involved addressing her opponents' weaknesses, focusing on flaws in their policies to distinguish herself and her platform. Her leadership was portrayed as driven by a commitment to democratic integrity, progressive reforms, and gentle leadership (empathy, compassion).

This strategic combination of personalized politics, policy advocacy, and criticism of opponents forms a comprehensive campaign that seeks to resonate with a broad spectrum of voters, aiming for a balanced approach to social and economic challenges.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

Péter Magyar had the most significant presence in the center-right TikTok profile, while the other Tisza candidate, András Kulja, who took on some public appearances, was far behind him. Péter Magyar was probably the political protagonist on TikTok for voters with moderate right-wing ideological orientations. However, Viktor Orbán was not far behind—this may be due to the far-right party's propaganda on TikTok, but it may also be due to the fact that Tisza challenged the entire Orbán regime, including Orbán himself. Presumably, this strongly drawn frontier is the reason why Antal Rogán was also a visible actor within the profile: he led the propaganda machinery of the Orbán regime and was also a key player in corruption (a few months later, he was added to the list of the Global Magnitsky Act, although he was removed from there by the Trump administration shortly after). Although not a dominant presence in the profile, Trump is also important, probably because of the radical right-wing proximity and frontier demarcation.

An interesting feature of the liberal left-green profile is that the palette of political actors was also diverse due to the broad left-wing coalition cooperation. However, the key player was Gergely Karácsony, candidate for mayor of Budapest, and also for the mayor of the city elected in 2019. So, he was not an EP candidate, which is explained by the two elections held on the same day. At the same time, it is worth paying attention to the anti-autocratic and democratizing role that the mayors of metropolises can play and which democratization (and possibly direct support for cities bypassing the level of nation-states) may also be in the interest of the EU. Karácsony is, therefore, an important political figure even if, in this case, he has no direct connection to the EP elections. The other most frequently mentioned character is Klára Dobrev, which is in line with DK's importance within the electoral coalition at the time. Behind them, Péter Magyar is also present. The mention of Orbán and the appearance of Gergely Karácsony's challenger, Dávid Vitézy, in the profile are essentially negligible.

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Hungary

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Hungary

The two key figures of the far-right profile on TikTok are Toroczkai and Orbán. It may be somewhat unusual that Toroczkai is mentioned more often than Orbán, but this may be the operation of the TikTok algorithm, which probably preferred ideological radicalism. Dóra Dúró, the other *Mi Hazánk* candidate, significantly lagged behind the two main characters. Still, interestingly enough, her presence was essentially the same as that of Péter Magyar.

On Instagram, we see a surprising thing in the case of right-wing profiles. While the political figures appearing in the moderate right-wing profile become diverse, in the far-right profile, they are reduced. Compared to what we saw on TikTok, the left-green profile remained balanced. In the moderate right-wing profile, the two main characters were still Magyar and Orbán, and the third most significant is the right-wing (moderate) former coalition PM candidate, Péter Márki-Zay. Next to them are a number of left-wing opposition figures and global political figures such as von der Leyen or Macron. In the radical right-wing profile, Dóra Dúró took the lead, who is a key player at *Mi Hazánk*, but her TikTok's presence was very faint. Since Viktor Orbán is the most significant player in this space in terms of political power and financial resources, Dúró's success may probably be due to her knowledge and clever use of this branch of social media. The leading politicians of the left-green profile are still Karácsony and Dobrev. It is noteworthy that foreign actors also appear in the profile due to ideological proximity. Based on the data, it seems that this was not typical of the far right. At the same time, in the case of other countries in this data collection, we see Hungarian political actors, above all Orbán, appear in foreign profiles as well.

Section 3: Hungary: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

All of the data collectors followed the protocol to get the relevant data, and after a beginning period, they started to come. At the same time, there was a decline in political or new political content after the election. We observed an intensification of posts as we were getting closer to the elections. As the election approached, all feeds sometimes showed ideologically non-preferred content as well as government-related content. For the far-right feed, governmental content clearly dominated both platforms. In the red-green feed, they appeared as paid content aimed at framing opposition. Videos of Viktor Orbán were present in the centre-right feed as well.

None of the data gatherers had used TikTok or Instagram before; we only set up our organic profiles for the research. When managing the accounts, we used the same principles as applied to the synthetic profiles, but the centre-right followed the same type of content, and the far-right collector followed red-green and was interested in Tisza as well. The red-green gatherer noticed the appearance of political advertisements; even though we did not actively search for political content, the pro-government content on Instagram aggressively penetrated the profiles, although some red-green advertisements were also present. Both far- and centre-right noticed that political content sometimes faded, on some particular days, with no apparent reason, especially on Instagram.

Political content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

The researcher responsible for the *centre-right synthetic profile* intentionally tried to follow centre-right content, which was, in this context, related to either Péter Magyar or the Tisza Party. TikTok could be taught quickly, although it needed 2-3 days to reach the first native content, then political content, and finally, the ideologically preferred content. After that, TikTok kept the profile inside an almost-rabbit hole. The profile-keeper tried to stick to this ideological direction strictly on the synthetic profile while letting some more leeway for the organic, also using the same tactic with Instagram; however, political content came almost always “wrapped in” other, non-political content. Although we planned beforehand that a male right-wing profile should behave like an imagined stereotypical male right-wing person (e.g., watching motorcycles or John Deere tractors), this strategy was not been able to be used as we perhaps over-specified these characteristics compared to the logic of how TikTok and Instagram work. It is noteworthy how strongly Instagram tried to navigate the feed *away from* political content, despite ticking the box that enabled the system to offer the profile manager political content outside their preference. This means that political content came barely from here. It is true, however, that the following

party/political personae have not created enough political content. The overall experience is that TikTok functioned better for political purposes.

The organic profile was used as a secondary or extended source to get the preferred political content; the profile owner followed the same ideological direction in most cases. It was a somewhat surprising experience that after not getting enough or any political content, the profile manager started to receive them after *not* sticking firmly to the synthetic protocol (which was not mandatory here), that is, by watching humorous or cat videos. Behaving like a normal person navigated the profile to the intended political content. So, the organic profile was managed a bit more casually by letting some other ideological content in, mainly the green joke party (MKKP). This has not influenced the whole feed so much as to distract it from the centre-right ideology.

The manager of the *red-green synthetic profile* deliberately searched for progressive accounts' (individual profiles: Gergely Karácsony, Klára Dobrev, Richárd Barabás; party profiles: *Párbeszéd* and *Demokratikus Koalíció*) contents and liked them. Even though the searches focused on specific and ideologically homogenous political content, videos that contained counterviews occasionally appeared. Such videos are produced and disseminated as paid content from *MegaFon*. During the 2024 European Parliament elections in Hungary, *MegaFon*, a pro-government collective (Government-sponsored Non-Governmental Organization), played a crucial role in shaping the ruling party's narrative. A central theme in *MegaFon's* output was framing the opposition, particularly left-wing parties and the newly emerged Péter Magyar from the Tisza Party, as aligned with a "globalist elite". This narrative painted them as proponents of war, migration, and progressive social policies—issues that Fidesz and its supporters framed as harmful to Hungary's sovereignty. The videos also questioned the left-leaning political leaders' professionalism and mocked them.

The researcher did not use their organic profile before the data collection. That was apolitical which looked for no political content. However, the amount of political content on the profile's feed has increased significantly. Political advertisements, for example, have appeared on this profile, even though the owner did not actively search for political content. Videos, which are reacting to current affairs by content creators, also appeared.

The researcher responsible for the *far-right synthetic profile* was following *Mi Hazánk* and the government (Fidesz-KDNP). The researcher set up an account so that it would invite such contents, with a bio "*party, foci, haza*" that is, "party, football, homeland". Political content flooded the profile from day 2, and only relevant political content was available. Later, content from the newly founded centre-right Tisza also emerged in the feed, but the user tried to skip it. Later, content from other far-right parties and their supporters emerged, which the researcher also watched entirely. It was mostly from Germany, related to AfD or content about a Europe-wide far-right turn.

The researcher set up her organic account for this research and has not actively used Instagram or TikTok. They followed their personal preferences regarding politics, the left, and green parties on the organic account. The researcher was also very interested in Tisza and followed them. They used the same strategy when setting up the profile as with the synthetic account and saw a lot of political content from day one or two. Later on, however, this content sometimes faded, on some particular days, with no apparent reason, especially on Instagram. On those days, they tried again to search for political content, but that did not help much either. Similarly to the synthetic account, comments were not liked or shared.

Notes on the organic profiles

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Data on mentions of parties suggest that the campaign's intensity increased to varying degrees around election day. It is noteworthy, however, that it was *not* the day of the election that was the most intense, but on the one hand, the 3-5 days not immediately preceding the election and – in the case of the centre-right profile – a couple of days after it. Generally, it is true that the campaign was not the most intense on election day, although there is some correlation between the intensity and the election date.

For the centre-right data gatherer, the organic profile was used as a secondary or extended source to get the preferred political content. The organic profile was managed more casually, letting some other ideological content in, mainly the Green Joke Party (MKKP). However, this has not influenced the whole feed so much as to distract it from the centre-right ideology. The content received was more or less the same as on the synthetic's centre-right feed. TikTok remained consistent in offering political content, while Instagram sometimes navigated away from politics altogether. However, getting political content from the organic profile was easier than from the synthetic.

Both the far-right and red-green data gatherers followed red-green content on their organic profiles (the far-right was also interested in the newly risen Tisza), one of them handling the profile with active interest. For the red-green oriented organic profile, the left-green (Momentum, DK, MKKP) parties

mainly were present on Instagram. Momentum often posted just a folder of images of rather boring campaign events, like how they met in a park with their supporters and grilled together, every time the same: park, grill, Anna Donáth smiling (president and top candidate). Their message was rather unclear. Katalin Cseh (other candidate) was much less present than Donáth. A few times some clips of her were released as she was speaking in a debate or roundtable (not available for the wider public) and every time she was very passionate and convincing about their message (around women's rights and Russia's war in Ukraine). From DK, short videos starring Klára Dobrev (party president and top candidate) appeared. She announced a challenge that she would visit a lot of places during her campaign tour. It was rather uninteresting. Their message was also unclear. MKKP started the campaign relatively late. Their content was quite scarce. They primarily focused on the Budapest elections. TikTok was dominated by the Tisza Party, which had long videos of Péter Magyar talking from a truck to the crowds. It was a bit boring after a while because it was the same setting every time. Sometimes, in the opinion of the gatherer, Magyar came off as arrogant and aggressive, but at least those moments were not boring. Their main message was to challenge the government domestically. Gradually, as the campaign went on, more and more content from the government was visible on the organic profile as well. The political content on Instagram was not stable, sometimes, it showed different content. There was not much intensification of the content visible with time from any of the parties.

Differences Observed Over Time

Throughout the data-gathering period on both platforms, there was a constant flow of the EPP content, as evidenced in the visuals (Figure 22) of the combined synthetic feeds in Hungary based on researchers ticking the boxes in their research notes. Also characteristic of the Hungarian politics, the political figures appeared quite unevenly, and comparatively very few of them were mentioned in the research notes.

As the figures show below, both on TikTok and Instagram, the red-greens accounts presence was quite uneven, while EPP was constantly present. Non-inscrits had a relatively low start that surged afterward, although with fluctuations, with a fallback around election day, and this surged after the election.

The cumulated data on the visibility of political actors show a later appearance of the red politicians but a more substantial presence of the greens compared to their party visibility. EPP politicians' visibility was initially lower; however, this is the same pattern we can see in the case of parties. Non-inscrit actors have a similar pattern to the EPPs. On Instagram, a stronger red presence is detected compared to TikTok. EPP actors' visibility is similar to what we can see on TikTok, although with more fluctuation. Non-inscrits had a permanent presence here.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Hungary over time

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Hungary over time

From the perspective of the data gatherers, in the centre-right profiles, the tendency that can be clearly determined is a gradual growth of political content. However, TikTok and Instagram differed in terms of how much political content they offered. TikTok showed a significantly higher number of political videos than Instagram. Instagram had an uneven distribution of political content during the observation period, while TikTok remained constant in this respect, and it even excluded content unrelated to the profile's preference. It can be noted that both types of profiles managed to stick to the pre-given political orientation, strictly on the synthetic and more flexibly on the organic. As the organic profile enabled us to deviate from the original (or synthetic) orientation, the strategy to behave like a normal person helped the profile return to (relevant) political content, especially on Instagram.

Instagram diverged from political content as such after the EP elections on both profile types. However, it is hard to recall when and whether this was related to the elections, as the algorithm also tried to diverge from political content despite the data collector's strong – sometimes even desperate – efforts. TikTok has also changed after the EP elections and started showing celebration videos with uplifting moods. So, Instagram's algorithm used a direct depoliticizing strategy, depriving the profile of political content, while TikTok remained political, but these had less political intensity and became less political. It seems that TikTok reflected on humans' emotions better, or at least the emotional character of the post-election days videos was clear.

It seemed that the two platforms' algorithms differ significantly. Instagram was very cautious with political content. The party the researcher followed did not share many videos there, perhaps because they were aware of this. The profile management experience suggests that a too strict protocol that only focuses on political content will not reach the aim of getting – relevant – political content, especially if the algorithm tends to be apolitical.

The researcher responsible for the red-green profile noticed that the amount of political content has increased significantly in the organic account. Especially paid content: the pro-government content on Instagram aggressively penetrated the profiles of indifferent users. However, some paid advertisements from the left-leaning party alliance's mayoral candidates were also visible on the organic profile, though to a lesser extent. The algorithm started to show an increasing amount of international political content, including Hirsi Ali discussing the risks of Islamization and a Jewish content creator highlighting the rise of antisemitism in the United States. The synthetic profile maintained a stable feed of political content, as the data collector consistently followed accounts of left-leaning and green politicians and parties. As the parties and politicians increased the number of updates, more content was seen. Despite the profile's left-leaning progressive orientation, pro-government *Megafon* advertisements began to appear on the feed in the days leading up to election day.

Both far-right accounts started to show political content quite early on. Two profiles were created at the same time and with the same strategies, but the researcher only followed different content. Still, it seemed the synthetic profile was more stable in terms of political content, meaning it almost never showed anything else but politics after the first couple of days. On the other hand, the organic account sometimes completely “forgot” the data collectors' interest in politics and showed a wide range of videos from recipes to dances. We cannot tell the reason behind this; far-right content was probably more strongly attached to the algorithm than the left-green. Interestingly, the left-green content was less on the organic profile, and there was more repetition of older contents. One probable reason is that those parties simply did not produce enough content for social media, whereas the far right and the government produced lots of new content every day. The researcher observed an intensification of posts the closer we got to the elections, especially from the government. They clearly dominated both platforms during the elections and also came into their organic account in significant numbers. After the election, there was a decline in new political content. The organic account may not have even shown much political content. The synthetic, however, repeated old, pre-election content or thank you posts. The researcher noted that the organic profile was quicker to drop political content than the synthetic.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Suppose the mention of politicians and parties indicates an increase in the campaign's intensity. In that case, it can be said that only in the case of the left-green profile can there be a detectable connection between election day and the increase in intensity. In the far-right profile, the campaign is most intense about 6-12 days before election day, but we do not see anything on election day. In the case of centre-right, it is higher about 3-11 days before and normal on election day, and for some reason, it jumps again about a week later. Overall, there is no clear connection between election day and the increase in the intensity of the political campaign across the profiles. This can only be seen in the left-green profile, where the key political actor did not run in the EP elections.

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

The Russian war on Ukraine dominated the government's (Fidesz-KDNP) whole communication throughout the campaign. However, the topic of war was not present in the centre-right campaign. Other topics, like the Green Deal, the Israel-Gaza conflict, and NATO-related discussions, were almost completely missing from the campaign on the right side of the spectrum. The oppositional far-right's (*Mi Hazánk*) topics were anti-vaccine, anti-corruption, and sometimes anti-immigration. Red-green profiles highlighted the importance of the European Union in ensuring social justice, economic equality, and the

protection of employees' rights, and from the left-green mayor of Budapest, the support of the European Green Deal. AI-generated content was noticed in the right-wing feeds.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

At the beginning of data collection, the centre-right profiles' TikTok was non-Hungarian and non-political, not even finding the continent correctly. It took a while to start showing the intended national political content. But as time went on, the account started to show a lot of national political content, creating a feed that looked like a small ideological-political echo chamber. Instagram, on the other hand, took a more laid-back stance, continuously giving preference to non-political content that represented the kinds of media that the general public usually consumes. Preferred content emerged, especially on Instagram, as a result of normal user behaviour, which is defined by watching non-political videos, such as those about food, pets, and travel, combined with political orientation.

There were significant parallels between the content of the European Parliament and mayoral candidates on the red-green profiles. For example, compared to Instagram, Gergely Karácsony's TikTok account had more Q&A-style content. Because it promotes interaction and makes knowledge transfer easier, Q&A-style content frequently strikes a deep chord with social media audiences. By answering targeted questions, content producers establish a direct line of communication with the audience, creating a sense of community and promoting more engagement. This strategy can foster loyalty and repeat engagement by making viewers feel valued and appreciated.

Creators encourage followers to actively participate by posing questions, turning passive consumption into an interactive experience that lets viewers influence the direction of the content. Furthermore, Q&A formats help audiences obtain information on topics of interest quickly by providing targeted, succinct answers to questions. In professional domains or specialized communities where audiences are looking for knowledgeable commentary or useful guidance, this is especially alluring. Bloopers and live Q&A sessions are frequently seen as unplanned and impromptu, which increases politicians' legitimacy and fosters public trust. Transparent responses can increase voter attachment by making politicians more relatable and approachable. This format also allows audiences to learn from the questions posed by others, addressing topics they may not have considered or felt hesitant to inquire about themselves.

The "We're" trend also showed up on the profile of the European Greens. Usually starting with the phrase "We're," this social media phenomenon starts with a funny, self-evident, or sarcastic comment and ends with "of course," so underlining the fact that the claim is generally accepted. Often stressing shared experiences or ideas among a group, this trend deftly uses sarcasm, humour, or exaggeration to transmit a message. These kinds of posts are relevant to a large audience and have a greater chance of going viral since they successfully mix a feeling of commonality with humour. These comments' humour or irony encourages likes, shares, and comments, which greatly helps them to be popular. These statements are meant to inspire the audience by presenting the speaker as a representative of the ordinary person, thus forging a connection with them.

Regarding far-right profiles on Instagram, the Fidesz-KDNP party dominated while *Mi Hazánk* oversaw TikTok, particularly considering the ban on their president. Deeper interaction with the material and the party officials resulted from the more intense viewing experience provided by the TikTok video style used. On Instagram, the effect of images and captions was seen as less important. Still, videos posted on Instagram—mostly from Fidesz—turned out to be rather interesting.

On the far-right organic TikTok account, left-green parties were almost non-existent. The monotonous material of the Tisza Party consisted of recordings of their leader speaking to a gathering, usually taken from a distance that limited interaction. Usually long and boring, these videos lack the dynamic appeal of live speeches. Instagram material mostly consisted of images and short videos showing party leaders during their campaigns. Such entries lacked viewer interest and resembled commercials. Notably interesting were a few scenes with liberal politicians (from Momentum) directly addressing the camera with emotional resonance. On the other hand, the Democratic Coalition (left-leaning) party produced no similarly interesting material.

Section 4: Hungary: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 25: Distribution of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

The centre-right political profiles offered a different terrain during the campaign, particularly lacking in debates on European policy subjects. The only notable exception was a public speech given by medical doctor András Kulja on the need for minimum standards in European medical infrastructure. Still, this speech was closely entwined with the current crisis in Hungary's healthcare system and acted as a pointed critique of the Orbán government and its policies. Both the Tisza Party and Péter Magyar kept addressing the healthcare crisis after the elections, so they maintained this topic in public debate all through the summer. This was an exceptional situation during the past 14 years of the Orbán regime. The politicization of health care is important in the case of our research as well, as the crisis – or collapse – of state services is directly related to the crisis of the social contract.

Tisza broadened the topic of the healthcare crisis in 2024–2025, tying it to the shortcomings in public transport as a state service. The main social media themes of the campaign were the corruption of the Orbán government, government control over media, and the Tisza Party's project "taking back our homeland brick by brick." Often with a religious undertone, this emotionally charged rhetoric included exhortations to "not be afraid". The centre-right movement was essentially focused on opposing the Orbán government with hopes for a regime change. Though framed inside the European Parliament (EP) campaign, the issues brought up were mostly domestic. The EP campaign was just a justification to launch a longer domestic campaign to reach regime change, or as Péter Magyar put it, the EP election was only the first step in the "we will take back the homeland" process.

Fascinatingly, although subtly, international leaders like US Presidents Donald Trump and Joe Biden emerged in the profiles, while the emphasis was mostly on national topics. Especially, European leaders who matched the intended ideological standpoint seemed to show more often just before and after the EP election. But especially with the Tisza Party, the centre-right material conspicuously lacked debates on Social Europe or reference to the Green Deal.

By stressing the need for the European Union to give social justice, economic equality, and worker rights top priority, the red-green profiles actively engaged with social grievances. Advocates of policies meant to improve social welfare systems, lower income disparity, and promote fair labour practices all around the EU, politicians like Klára Dobrev pushed Dobrev's vision of a stronger social Europe, necessary for building an inclusive society whereby everyone gains from economic growth.

The Mayor of Budapest, Gergely Karácsony, expressed strong support for the European Green Deal, stressing its relevance for long-term sustainability and quick climate action. Arguing for investments in green technologies and policies that cut carbon emissions, he said the Green Deal is essential for solving the climate crisis. Reflecting Karácsony's dedication to sustainable urban development, his campaign highlighted how environmental issues should be included in Europe's social and economic policies.

In a more targeted thematic area, the organic profile addressed a war-related grievance, so addressing the Israel-Palestine conflict via the prism of a Jewish content producer covering growing antisemitism in the United States. This viewpoint underlined the emotional weight of global problems inside local settings.

Within the far-right profiles, the Ukraine-Russia war became a major motif that dominated Fidesz-KDNP's campaigns on both social media channels. Although *Mi Hazánk* made more efficient use of TikTok, their material usually focused on anti-corruption and anti-vaccine issues together with sporadic anti-immigration rhetoric. AI produced mostly funny pictures of government officials dressed as ninjas.

With other issues such as the Green Deal, the Israel-Gaza conflict, and NATO-related debates conspicuously absent, Fidesz-KDNP's campaign was essentially focused on the Ukraine-Russia conflict. Researchers and the audience were left terrified, anxious, and depressed by this great concentration on the war, which provoked strong emotions.

On the other hand, *Mi Hazánk* raised corruption and vaccination as problems at the European level. Their messages caused people to consider their own ideas of reality, which made them feel as though an elite class was victimizing them and betraying their faith in politics and the European Union. These

emotional effects shed light on the experiences of common people regularly consuming this material during the campaign.

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the distribution of common themes that appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Though this could be a distorted view given the generally embarrassing nature of these videos, AI-generated content appeared surprisingly often in the centre-right political profiles. Frequently featuring leaders like Putin and Biden or drawing comparisons between the two, these videos tended to arouse negative emotions, mostly a mix of fear and disgust, because of their odd presentation. While this type of content could emotionally capture one’s attention, the most common type was the quite average personal videos about politicians’ speeches shared by ordinary users. Mostly non-political, the content on Instagram reflected more general user interests.

By contrast, the red-green synthetic profile made clear comments opposing anti-LGBTQ organisations. Often spoken by Richárd Barabás, these little statements denounced exclusionary rhetoric and policies. However, the organic profile offered a more striking contrast by including political material from the other ideological spectrum, frequently leaving the researcher between surprise and frustration. This stuff covered immigration problems, anti-Islam attitudes, antisemitism, and war-related messages. English-

language videos from politically active but formally unaffiliated content creators expressed concerns about Islamization and depicted Muslim migration as a threat to European cultural integrity and security. Such stories appealed to fears about cultural dilution by presenting immigration as a "civilizational" threat that might replace local communities' sense of belonging. The organic feed also included accounts of growing antisemitism in unnamed Western countries and references to violent events involving Israeli nationals, thus strengthening the emotional impact of the material. Though several emotional themes were present, no clearly AI-generated content came up in this setting.

On far-right profiles, government messaging occasionally mixed the subject of war with religious themes, presenting peace as a Christian deed. Especially clear in the messages of the Christian Democrats (KDNP), this strategy lacked emotional depth and came across more as a platitude than a sincere value. By distributing anti-immigration materials, especially stressing how immigration might harm the Hungarian working class, *Mi Hazánk* also participated in the debate. The constant repetition of this message caused the observer to become numb, thus reducing the impact of the arguments and making it challenging for viewers to participate actively with them. The material of these profiles revealed a complex interaction of ideas and emotions that shaped the political narrative in ways that were both powerful and, occasionally, confusing.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

The most often included foreign content in the centre-right political profiles was US presidential candidates, especially Trump and Biden. Videos showing Putin also surfaced, usually connected to Russian propaganda campaigns, many created by artificial intelligence. Also included were positively presented clips of European leaders including Macron and Meloni. Content about the European

Parliament started to show as the elections drew near, including calls to vote, messages from Ursula von der Leyen, and materials from several EP parties—especially the Greens.

The European Union was portrayed favourably in many respects in the red-green synthetic profile. Democratic Coalition (DK) politicians pointed to the EU as providing development financing, stability, and economic security. Emphasising its commitment to LGBTQ protection, inclusivity, and social justice, they presented the EU as defender of democratic values and civil rights. This representation presented the EU as a counterpoint to the autocratic inclinations connected with the Hungarian government. Green politicians especially praised the EU's environmental initiatives, including the European Green Deal, meant to make Europe the first continent with a zero-carbon footprint. On the other hand, the organic TikTok profile highlighted China's fast economic expansion, technological developments, and infrastructure projects by including pro-China material. Often featuring comparisons with the United States, these films offered a positive perspective of China's development. Pro-government influencers on the organic Instagram profile meanwhile attacked the EU for aggravating the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. TikTok turned out to be a rich source of world politics content, triggering viewers' emotional responses ranging from surprise to moral disgust to a feeling of isolation.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Far-right profiles also discussed the US elections, stressing not only presidential contenders but also Trump's friendship with Orbán. Content from *Mi Hazánk* made reference to the German AfD. Though *Mi Hazánk's* anti-Ukraine narrative focused on Ukraine, such material was rare. Particularly unlike the organic red-green profile, *Mi Hazánk's* messaging lacked references to China or Russia. Emphasising their trips to build economic ties and implying that the Middle East would import Hungarian agricultural products, the party presented the area favourably. Reflecting their larger ideological stance, this story sought to place *Mi Hazánk* favourably in the framework of international relations.

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

The Hungarian government set the background for the centre-right profiles' reflections on war in Ukraine. Hungary was a particular case concerning the war in Ukraine, as the Hungarian government has a specific position. Orbán positioned himself and the government as standing against the war, being "anti-war". In contrast, the domestic opposition and almost all the European governments (except for the Vatican under Pope Francis or Trump in the US) were portrayed as pro-war. This was a strong discursive construction that dominated the Hungarian political landscape, and it was hard to challenge by the opposition parties, including Tisza, as any pro-Ukraine announcement positioned them according to this strong division and on the discursive side of being pro-war and wanting to extend suffering and death. This discursive challenge came to the fore with the right-wing challenger of the regime, the Tisza Party, as they intentionally hid their opinion from the public because the audience was conditioned to be critical of the war or Ukraine as such by the Orbán government (as Péter Magyar later answered in an interview). In the centre-right feed, it was no surprise that there was no relevant amount of pro-Ukraine content, although the one that broke this wall was deeply emotional (Zelenskiy visiting WWII veterans).

In the organic red-green TikTok profile, solidarity with Gaza claims appeared. In the organic Instagram profile, pro-government *Megafon* influencers criticized the EU for fuelling the war between Russia and Ukraine. They were very similar to each other and were advertised by the content creators. Strategic cooperation amongst the content creators is very much likely.

In the synthetic red-green profile, gender inclusivity messages and pro-LGBTQ+ messages appeared. Progressive parties, such as *Párbeszéd*, DK, and MSZP, were vocal in their support for LGBTQ+ rights and gender equality. Candidates, including prominent figures like Gergely Karácsony and Klára Dobrev, emphasized the need for inclusive policies within the EU framework and criticized Hungary's restrictive laws on LGBTQ+ rights. They linked the struggle for LGBTQ+ and gender equality with broader democratic values, portraying Hungary's stance as out of line with European standards. The emotional reactions they induced in the researcher usually oscillated between surprise, moral disgust, elevation, and loneliness.

In the far-right profiles, we can observe the government's effort to depict Ursula von der Leyen as the main "face" of the pro-war elite in the EU. She was also frequently represented by *Mi Hazánk* as the main figure behind the "vaccine scandal" and the global "COVID dictatorship". Just like in the case of the centre-right profiles, the conflict in Gaza was absent in both far-right profiles as well.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Threats to Equality and Diversity

The fact that anti-migration content was present on centre-right profiles has not come as a surprise, as this has been one of the government’s core messages since 2015. However, it was not dominant there and appeared less frequently than expected. In the Tisza Party’s own content (or videos about Magyar), the topic appeared concerning the job market. This position looked moderately anti-migrant but not racist compared to the regime’s position.

In ren-green profiles, grievances were communicated: complaints about the lack of inclusivity and equality of the LGBTQA+ community and alternative lifestyles. In the organic TikTok profiles, the danger of multiculturalism and the harmful influence of Islam were recurring themes. The emotional reactions these induced were an oscillation between surprise, frustration, and being overwhelmed.

Somewhat surprisingly, on far-right profiles, there was no dominant anti-migration content present; if so, it was scarcely posted by *Mi Hazánk*. This content does not have much effect on the observer.

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content was present in the centre-right feeds and appeared more often with the approach of the elections, although most of them were contradictory in their effort to convince. When it appeared more frequently, we discussed it among our colleagues, and it seems they may have a similar emotional effect; they alienated from the message as they induced negative emotions due to their oddity—one may feel something strongly unnatural about them.

While some AI-generated content was on the centre-right profiles, it was completely missing in the red-green ones. This is somewhat surprising, as most of us detected some, including the far-right profiles.

However, there was not too much there either. What was memorable was the aforementioned ninja video of the government members, where AI-generated images of them as ninjas. It was supposed to be funny but not in a satirical way; we assume that even the politicians featured would find it funny. In the worst case, they might even consider themselves muscular ninja fighters. Our observer figured it must be some sort of channel for all those middle-aged male politicians to boost their egos; to quote her, it felt like my dad would play with AI a bit and release his inner teenage fantasies. It made the observer feel bored, distanced, and annoyed.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Section 5: Hungary: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In the section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

Examining the centre-right political profiles revealed a clear trend in the degree of political content, especially on TikTok, where changes were most noticeable over time. On political involvement, Instagram displayed a more hectic attitude. Both platforms saw a similar drop in political content during the post-election week, varying between clearly political messaging and a more subdued presence. While Instagram allowed for a wider spectrum of content from across the political spectrum, at times lacking relevant political material entirely and showing a notably weak representation of centre-right viewpoints, TikTok kept its ideological preferences throughout the data collection.

On the other hand, the red-green synthetic account showed political content right from the beginning of the data collection. The volume of such posts grew dramatically as political leaders increased their social media activity; paid ads became especially noticeable as election day drew near. This account clearly aligned with green-progressive-socialist ideas, yet occasionally *Megafon*'s material showed up as sponsored posts on the feed.

Conversely, far-right profiles included political materials from the very first week across both platforms. Particularly on the synthetic account—which included both centre-right and far-right material—the intensity of far-right content rose as the data collection went on. This change was more noticeable on TikTok than on Instagram, where far-right content was typically more common because Meta banned *Mi Hazánk*'s leader from the platform. Government messaging dominated Instagram and grew more prevalent as election day approached, a trend ascribed to government content production rather than platform dynamics.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

Audiovisual content is popular and very convincing and is present on already popular platforms like Facebook and YouTube. We expect their popularity to rise or even transform platforms like Facebook in this direction. Still, the popularity of Instagram and TikTok leans generational, appealing more to younger viewers than to older ones. While Fidesz keeps a strong hold among older populations, Tisza has effectively captured the youth vote, as party supporters often reflect these generational differences. This dynamic suggests that politicians will probably increasingly use audiovisual channels to draw in or keep younger voters.

Gergely Karácsony, for example, has deftly negotiated this terrain by creating casual, relevant material that emphasizes authenticity, humour, and civic participation—often matching his message to current platform trends to appeal to younger voters. Often referring to himself as "*Apu*" ("Dad"), as social media followers called him, Karácsony engages young people with material meant to present him as a

Funded by
the European Union

relatable figure by using TikTok as a communication tool. Using conversational tones and personal anecdotes to highlight his down-to-earth character, this method seeks to create a personal connection with viewers. Usually captured through selfies and casual interactions with common people, Karácsony's material shows him in everyday environments, such as local events or community meetings. This approach creates familiarity and accessibility since he wears casual clothes instead of formal wear. Leveraging TikTok's trend-driven culture, he uses comedy and creative forms—Q&A sessions—to make his messages interesting and unforgettable. Visual elements highlight the involvement of young people in grassroots events and volunteer work, and viewers are taught about local governance and civic participation. His posts also frequently feature calm images of an urban environment, including parks and green areas, usually accompanied by upbeat music, including tracks by Taylor Swift.

One cannot stress the effect of this kind of material on viewers. Emphasizing social media's great impact on public consciousness, it shapes views, influences ideas, and causes emotional reactions. Those interacting with this material may find themselves impacted even though they are professionals with a reflective attitude to their observations. Given the length of official political debates, more and more voters will probably rely on social media as their main source of political knowledge. Usually, highlights from debates show up on these sites the next day, which makes it simple for users to access the most interesting parts.

Moreover, far-right content takes up a sizable portion of TikTok in Hungary, surpassing its coverage in conventional media; thus, far-right voters could be driven to use these channels for information and interaction. Social media did give a rather accurate picture of the political landscape. However, far-right commentary is conspicuously absent from journalistic work, which might unintentionally support social media's ability to incite emotions of injustice among supporters of far-right parties.

Often through succinct, well-edited posts, social media's fast access to information makes it more accessible and interesting than conventional news consumption or protracted discussions. These platforms thus have great future prospects especially as their usage transcends the younger generation to become a major information source for a larger audience.

#Emotional mechanisms

The content the researchers encountered had a strong emotional effect ranging from distress to sympathy. Stress sometimes resulted from the sheer volume of data acquired, the nature of the content itself, or the repetitious and ineffective elements of the data collecting process. Unexpected discoveries, like the knowledge that many people were missing out on important political information because of their reliance on conventional media, occasionally helped offset these negative emotions, though.

Regarding Tisza, most of the political campaign activity took place behind the scenes, usually on social media platforms or in rural areas, so drawing attention to the public knowledge gaps. The content itself presented more difficulty, especially when it contradicted the political views of the data collectors. This situation highlighted the polarized character of Hungarian politics, which can influence even academics. Every person reacted to this polarisation with different emotions and managed them differently. Following the idea of separating personal views from professional obligations, one of the researchers decided to distance herself from the research subjects in order to preserve mental well-being and keep an objective viewpoint. She found it helpful to express her emotions freely in family circles, which helped her negotiate the emotional terrain more successfully.

48

Funded by
the European Union

On the other hand, another researcher discovered she was growing more emotionally involved with the content—especially with far-right materials that frequently used fear-mongering strategies. This participation over time caused emotions of anxiety, especially related to geopolitics and issues for the next generations. This researcher even started to see Orbán as a possibly sensible leader who could offer safety, a view that, although transient, had a long-lasting effect on her emotional state and heightened war and future uncertainty anxiety. Understanding these emotional reactions helped the data collectors to overcome obstacles and preserve their mental stability, proving the strong impact of social media on opinions and emotions. Interacting with viewpoints from those other than their own political affiliations also had unanticipated results. One researcher related to the far-right party *Mi Hazánk*'s story of injustice, which helped the party to seem sympathetic and like an underdog deserving of support. Her increased transparency let her thoroughly investigate their ideas, political tactics, and messages. Fascinatingly, she noted a slow comeback of her former left-green perspective across the data-gathering process, so she enhanced her knowledge and dispelled several preconceptions she had about *Mi Hazánk*. This encounter shed important light on the emotional and intellectual dynamics that might lead people towards far-right politics. It showed how exposure to different points of view might subvert preconceptions and promote better knowledge.

#Video Typologies

1. The most common types of videos (especially on TikTok) were *walkabout and campaign event speeches*. The moderate right campaign, for example, incorporated an intensive campaign tour (visiting over 200 places over a month).

Campaign walkabouts, which feature political figures interacting directly with the public in outdoor or informal settings, are often represented with specific audiovisual techniques designed to convey authenticity, connection, and relatability. The typical audiovisual narrative of campaign walkabouts includes casual, on-the-ground footage in the Hungarian context. These scenes are shot in public spaces like markets, streets, or town squares. The camera typically follows the candidate in a handheld, dynamic way, emphasizing movement and spontaneity. This style helps to create an impression of real-time interaction with the public, reinforcing the notion of accessibility and grassroots engagement. Close-up shots of the candidate engaging with the public—shaking hands, hugging, talking with people, or listening intently—are common. These images help humanize the candidate and emphasize their connection with voters.

Additionally, capturing the reactions of everyday people, often smiling or reacting positively, helps frame the candidate as approachable and popular. Shots of the crowd cheering, applauding, or engaging with the candidate are typically interspersed to highlight public support and enthusiasm. This is designed to convey momentum and show the candidate's broad appeal.

The sound in these videos usually includes background noise from the environment, like traffic, crowd chatter, or distant conversations. The presence of these "real-life" sounds adds to the authenticity of the scene and helps create a more immersive atmosphere for the viewer. In the Hungarian case, usually uplifting music was the background noise. In many instances, these videos will emphasize the candidate's direct, personal communication style. This could include moments where the candidate listens attentively, shakes hands, or speaks intimately with voters. It reinforces the image of the candidate as relatable and responsive.

Editing plays a significant role in shaping the visual narrative of the meetings. Quick cuts, upbeat music, and selection and inclusion of positive interactions between the candidate and the people create a sense of bonds and enthusiasm. It is especially important in the Hungarian case in which the polls suggest that socialist-green parties are lagging behind right-leaning parties in popularity.

2. *Influencer/celebrity plus politician videos* were not common, but they were present, and they might have impacted support. There are two cases in which an extremely popular singer expresses his support for the politician, and the politician meets with an influencer/entrepreneur (selling sneakers) who is also extremely popular on TikTok and Instagram. It is not easy to detect these from a technical perspective, but this could be an important categorization in general.

3. *Explainer videos* can also be specified, or we even *entertaining explainer videos*. Another option is the *entertaining commenting* video. An example: "Jólvanezígy" is a popular channel. They "analyse" political events, but they are two young guys commenting on political events from a critical and humorous angle.

4. *Grassroots (naive/non-professional) political humour video* would deserve a separate category. They were present in the second half of the data-gathering process.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

The three most interesting videos we selected represent the heterogeneity of the feeds we saw, but it was also not easy to choose good narratives from the Hungarian environment. Perhaps it is understandable to be averse to selecting a model to follow from the autocratic far-right Fidesz, which was often markedly present in our feeds. Thus, below, we present the examples that we think were interesting and noteworthy in some way, and we can learn from them in a good way regarding the operation of social media.

Narrative 1. Péter Magyar in a countryside town speaking to the mass
 (From "magyarpeterofficial" channel, ORG HU1 ID174, 5/23/2024, 18.59-)

The video is an example of a professional video: it was published by Péter Magyar's official channel.

50

The video has a strong visual reference to countryside towns: church towers, emblematic buildings of some well-known major rural centres, and close-ups of ordinary people. It also portrays Péter Magyar in an air of immediacy—on the back of a pick-up truck shot from behind so that the politician is seen with the crowd listening to him. The music accompanying the footage is uplifting and supports the politician’s message, focusing on “hope” and the unification of left and right. The video is notable because it collects the character traits that can be used to describe the party’s identity and targets its own voters. It should be emphasized that at this time, Magyar and his staff were on a countryside campaign tour, which the opposition did not do and which had been typically a Fidesz voting environment for decades. The video is similar to a professional advertising spot, which in itself may not be the most ideal format in this medium. However, it still can have a place here due to the ability to migrate through platforms.

Narrative 2. Péter Magyar in a sneaker shop having a conversation with the owner, a popular young influencer (From Syn HU1 No449 5/28/2024, 4.56)

Péter Magyar buys sneakers from Balázs, the owner of the brand and shop Balázs Kicks. Although this video is not an amateur video, it is not an advertising spot either, it fits much more into the logic of how this communication space works; however, it is static in the sense that, for example, it is not Q&A-like.

It seems to be a promotional video, but the interesting and significant thing is that Balázs Kicks is a very popular channel; it is specifically targeted at young people, and the politician is also talking about topics that are typically related to young people (but with masculine overtones): relaxing and sleeping (or lack of them), sports, weight loss. In the end, he pays with his bank card, or more precisely, his mobile phone (contradicting one of the members of government’s message earlier: “cash only, obviously”). The video is interesting because (1) it connects with young people in topics, visual appearance, and by the brand itself (bridging the age gap of about 20 years between the politician and the young person present), (2) it is linked to an already very popular young businessman/brand and thus probably also increases the reach within this age group.

Narrative 3. A campaign from the European Greens, exemplifying a straightforward application of the "We're" trend. (From Syn HU3 No449 06/01/2024 5:56)

In this visual narrative, we see four women who closely resemble each other—white and aged between 20 and 30—walking with purpose in front of the European Parliament building in Brussels. Their dynamic movement captures attention and aligns with the trend by highlighting the essential pillars of green identity through the repeated structure of "we are... of course...". The first speaker sets a victimized tone by stating, "of course the far-right hates us," immediately framing the Greens as a target of political opposition. This bold declaration serves as an entry point into their identity narrative, which encompasses several key elements: advocating for taxing the wealthy, protecting nature and small farmers, promoting intersectional feminism, and expressing a fondness for tote bags. The absence of music in the background allows the viewers to focus solely on the speakers' voices, accompanied only by the ambient sounds of traffic, further emphasizing their message's urgency. However, by executing the "We're" trend this way, the EU Greens inadvertently reinforce certain

stereotypes associated with their movement. They appear to represent a specific and somewhat narrow segment of society, primarily reflecting the views and values of a demographic that may not resonate with all citizens. Additionally, their use of terms like "intersectional feminism" while parading in the streets of Brussels suggests an alignment with the EU elite, which raises questions about their accessibility and relatability to the general public.

Furthermore, this portrayal positions them as an ideology-driven and idealistic group, seemingly disconnected from the everyday experiences of the broader population. The narrative also paints them as a young, urban, and cosmopolitan collective, which could alienate those outside of these characteristics. Lastly, the fact that they are all women may imply a deliberate distancing from male voices, potentially reinforcing the perception of them as a separate entity within the political discourse. Collectively, these elements create a complex narrative that not only celebrates their identity but also invites scrutiny regarding inclusivity and representation within their messaging.

Discussion on most interesting videos

Our overall impression is that TikTok was more suitable for conveying political messages than Instagram. At the same time, TikTok typically focused on our own original ideological profile. Viktor Orbán's direct videos or the government-paid *Megafon* influencers were noteworthy in right-wing or sometimes in organic feeds. Videos by Fidesz generating fear made a significant impression on the viewer. Tisza's videos were repetitive and often boring, even though we can reasonably assume that their local, interpersonal influence had a politically reinforcing effect, so it was significant. The videos of the red-green parties were notable for their non-polarizing tone. The videos of the joke party were

52

Funded by
the European Union

entertaining and relaxed, but the party itself was unsuccessful in the EP elections. In addition to the videos of parties and political figures, influencers and explainer videos also played a significant role, and grassroots satirical videos also had a serious entertainment power. Videos with political content by ordinary people should also be highlighted. We are closing our manuscript when Fidesz submitted a bill following the Russian model of foreign agents law that aims to restrict or shut down independent media and civil organizations influencing public debates (cf. Reuters 2025). In this context, our attention is drawn to the video creators of the latter category, who can potentially have a significant impact in this kind of environment: citizens.

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion to the bases of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?

There were two main sources of motivation to vote for people following centre-right ideology on social media we researched: the calls to vote by videos issued by the European Parliament; the second type came from the party activities in the domestic context. Regarding the social contract, domestic motivations may have come from the high stakes the government set for the elections and the possible reflections it induced in prospective voters. As the topic section of our report suggests, the European social contract offered by these parties was sometimes surprisingly missing a well-defined content, and this is especially true for Tisza (even though they used a “social contract” vocabulary in some key videos, but referring to some kind of national contract). However, domestic messages may be understood as claims of a type of social contract in the European context if they appear in relation to the EP elections despite remaining in the domestic field. For Fidesz and specifically Orbán, the stake for the EP elections was, quoting Orbán, “besieging Brussels” and changing the direction of politics in various fields; stopping migration was present earlier, so it may be part of the social contract offer even if it was not at the centre of Orbán’s messages during the campaign. The main focus was on war, framed in this way: the government is against war and wants peace, while their opposition, domestic or European (“Brussels” and most of the European countries), wants to continue the war (because their support Ukraine by weapons, sanctions etc.); thus they have a pro-war stance. For Fidesz voters, the stake of the EP elections could be peace (on the European continent), while for opposition voters, the country’s European orientation and self-positioning were at stake, as the social contract offered by Orbán might have meant a diversion – or disintegration – from Europe.

The newly emerging challenger, Tisza Party’s position on the Russian war on Ukraine was unclear. However, the sheer fact that they targeted to get seats in the EP conveyed a powerful message about their pro-European position. In other words, the stake of the EP elections in terms of a social contract was either belonging to Europe or not on the opposition side, while on the government’s side, transforming Europe in their favour, and for their voters, living in peace without fear and better economic conditions. It must be noted that by the war/peace logic, the government followed a discursive path they became dependent on after successfully initiating it as an answer to the eruption of the war in 2022 when they won the elections shortly afterward. The data collection experience proved that the topic of war could maintain a certain level of fear, especially after several repetitions. The election results, however, showed that the fear-mongering logic by the discursive separation between pro- and antiwar stances has a certain kind of inner limitation, especially if there is a successful challenger who deliberately builds its message on being against any kind of fear (not necessarily this) in society induced by the government.

The government (Fidesz-KDNP) had one clear message during the campaign: the question of “war versus peace”. This became their main narrative as the stake of this election. Orbán promised that with enough seats, they could pressure the elite of the EP to change their stance on Russia’s war in Ukraine. That is, his main message was that if they got enough seats, they would make the EU stop supporting

Ukraine and become fully uninvolved in the war. The EU's support for Ukraine was demonized from many different aspects. First, from an economic perspective EU leaders were accused of causing higher living costs for Hungarians and wasting taxpayers' money to the war instead of domestic investments. Secondly, political memories (stories, images, videos) of past world wars have often been evoked. They were used to make the war in Ukraine more tangible. Besides, its comparison to WWI and WWII evoked distinct national historical traumas connected to world wars, like Trianon and the huge losses Hungary suffered both in terms of human lives and economically and politically after WWII. Based on such comparisons, Orbán's message that it is essential and the only sensible way for Hungary not to get involved in another potential world war, sounded rational and straightforward. It also evoked a lot of fear, fear of the future economically but also fears for one's life and for the life of their children.

Mi Hazánk was the only party during the campaign that talked about concrete political issues and had a detailed political program about what they aimed to achieve in the EP for Hungary. They were very critical of the EPP, especially Ursula von der Leyen. Their messages targeted von der Leyen's corruption scandal around the EU's COVID vaccine tender (that she apparently made huge vaccine deals in text messages with his husband involved in the vaccine business). Further, *Mi Hazánk* criticized how von der Leyen's investigation is being delayed due to political reasons. Besides, as their main message, *Mi Hazánk* mobilized against the so-called "COVID-" and "vaccine-dictatorship" of the EU and the questionable health advice of the WHO during the pandemic. All in all, in the *Mi Hazánk's* campaign, all the above-mentioned issues of the EU and the WHO were often merged as symptoms of a "global dictatorship", be it COVID or EU-related.

Mi Hazánk's main promise was to reform the EU (EPP) elite by forming a new group in the EP with fellow radical right parties, especially with German AfD. Even if this message is similar to the government's, *Mi Hazánk* used concrete cases of corruption to show why the EP and the EPP need drastic change and not (just) their stand on war (*Mi Hazánk's* stand on the war is very similar to Fidesz, combined with strong anti-Ukrainian messages). Eliminating corruption was *Mi Hazánk's* main message regarding the EP elections and positioning themselves domestically. Corruption was communicated as an act when the elite gained more and more riches at the expense of the poor ones. The main effect for mobilization was injustice. They harshly criticized the hype around Péter Magyar and the Tisza Party because, as *Mi Hazánk* claimed, they have been discussing the same issues as Magyar for years. They especially highlighted that *Mi Hazánk* was a leading force behind the investigation and discovery of the Völner-Schadl corruption case, that Magyar also rode on during the campaign.

The DK-Socialist-Dialogue Greens coalition, comprising the DK, MSZP, *Párbeszéd*, generally advocates for a vision of Europe that emphasizes democratic values, social justice, environmental sustainability, and stronger European integration based on progressive values and policies. The coalition emphasizes the importance of upholding democratic principles and the rule of law within the European Union. They advocate for measures to protect judicial independence, media freedom, and civil liberties. Promoting inclusivity and equality for all citizens, regardless of gender, ethnicity, or social background, is a key part of their vision. The coalition is committed to protecting human rights within the EU and globally. They advocate for policies that support refugees, migrants, and marginalized communities. The coalition advocates a strong Western orientation and harmony with EU and NATO leaders. The coalition pledges to liberate Hungary from what they call "the permanent troublemaker" (Viktor Orbán) of Europe. Klára Dobrev's content on social media was in accordance with the vision. Additionally, the economic growth was also mentioned to increase the well-being of the Hungarians.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

The defining topic of the Hungarian government was the war. Since they defined themselves as being against the war, their opponents became pro-war. Thus, the EU elite became pro-war, and Ursula von der Leyen was painted as the main face of pro-war Europe. The EU is contributing to Russia's war in Ukraine, so the election is at stake in life and death. However, Fidesz did not want to leave or abolish the EU but to occupy (and then change) it. In addition to the current EU, the other negatively portrayed opponent was the opposition, including left-wing parties and also Péter Magyar. They were framed as part of the "globalist elite" who want war, support migration or progressive social policies. All of this is dangerous to the nation's sovereignty.

The position of the red-wing alliance was pro-Europe. They highlighted the role of the EU in social justice, labour rights and economic equality, and they also took a positive stance on the European Green Deal. The EU appeared to be defending democratic values against the Hungarian government. The dominant opponent is the government, which is autocratic, while they defend democratic values such as inclusivity or LGBTQ rights. Not only did they define themselves in this way against the government, but the regime also defined itself in this way against them, who rejected LGBTQ rights on the grounds of "family" and, with it, everything they considered liberal (left-wing). The red-greens' criticism of other political actors was to compare policies and question the competence of the other.

Although running in the EP elections, Tisza used almost entirely domestic political topics. Their decisive identity-forming frontier was drawn against Fidesz and Viktor Orbán; in short, they defined themselves against the regime. According to their assessment, the EP elections are only a step in dismantling the regime. Essentially, they did not deal with other left-wing opposition parties; they were unanimously rejected as being an integral part of the Orbán regime's self-sustaining political dialectic (Fidesz vs "left"). Tisza's position on Europe was not stated, but it was perceptible as pro-European (let us not forget, the party was formed a month before the election). They eventually joined the EPP. While the government condemned both the war and the current EU and Ukraine, Tisza's position remained vague.

The emotional dynamics of Hungarian politics were that Fidesz wanted to arouse fear; this was suitable for making Orbán appear a strong leader who could save the country from danger. The left has focused on positive emotional elements such as emphasizing humanity, relatability, empathy and compassion. The most significant emotional dynamic provided by Tisza existed and was created in connection with the fear-mongering politics, and the overall fear-dominated climate of the Fidesz regime. Magyar's core, most emotionally powerful message – with a religious tone – was "Do not be afraid".

Conclusion

In the Hungarian-language profiles, two types of external influences threatening democracy were apparent: one was foreign, but often European, and the videos were linked to the far-right. The other type is external and typically generated by AI. We found that AI videos often convey a Russian narrative. However, they were clearly artificial with an alienating effect, and their quantity was below what we expected. Hungary's situation is special, however, because the threats to democracy are not external but internal, that is, the party in government itself. In this context, two things are worth pointing out: first,

the anti-democratic far-right, and Orbán in particular, has appeared in the feeds of other countries as well; and second, videos of the Orbánist far-right have appeared in domestic, but ideologically distant, feeds as well, and that the videos of the other, opposition far-right party have, in the experience of the data collectors, indeed been persuasive. The latter is consistent with what we know about the far-right's successful use of social media. The Hungarian situation is, therefore, a special one as the question is what control instrument can be used against a party in government in a member state. The success of the far-right in using social media suggests that one response to the anti-democratic challenge is learning to use social media effectively and actively.

TikTok and Instagram handle information from EU citizens that cannot be released outside the EU either individually or in aggregate, and their research is essential for EU democracy and stakeholders, so in any regulation the EU should put its own research interests ahead of the private interests of companies. For effective control of social media, which has the potential to protect democracy, we should first of all know how it works and how it affects citizens, voters, the demos. In general, we think it is true, based on the research, that we should know more about how social media works, which implies that research cannot stop. Also, given the knowledge we have, we should probably be more aware of how to use social media, and media literacy education for young people is key to this.

We can draw the conclusion that TikTok and Instagram can be used to communicate with voters but are not really suitable for debate. An example of this is the video selected by the researcher of the red-green profile, where she describes in the analysis that it can be a point of identification for a very specific, narrow group of voters. However, it could also imply that voter groups are approachable and that segmentation is one strategy for reaching them. The generalisable experience of the researchers is that creating credibility, familiarity and the possibility of connection (including Q&A structures) are important elements of successful communication on social media platforms. Informal environments and personal authenticity are elements that apply across the ideological spectrum. At the same time, it is also worth pointing out the emotional dynamics researchers managing right-wing profiles have experienced: the Orbán government's communication strategy of explicitly fear-mongering has an impact on people (us) even when they (we) are ideologically on the opposite side. Fear-mongering is an effective strategy, and it seems hard to find a regulatory response to it.

Bibliography

20k – Hungarian Helsinki Committee – Mérték Media Monitor – Political Capital – TASZ/HCLU – Unhack Democracy (2024). *Hungarian Citizen Election Report: European Parliament and Local Elections 2024.* (1-19.) https://politicalcapital.hu/pc-admin/source/documents/HungarianCitizenElectionReport_240620.pdf and https://politicalcapital.hu/pc-admin/source/documents/CivilValasztasiJelentes_240618.pdf

Aujeszký, N. I. & Döbrentey, D. & Hegyi, S. & Kunos, Z. & Mécs, J. & Perczel, M. M. (2025). Jelentés az európai parlamenti képviselők, a helyi önkormányzati képviselők és polgármesterek, valamint a nemzetiségi önkormányzati képviselők 2024. évi, közös eljárásban tartott választásáról. Budapest: Társaság a Szabadságjogokért. (1-101.) <https://tasz.hu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/TASZ-valasztasi-jelentes-2024.pdf>

Elections to the European Parliament, Nemzeti Választási Iroda, <https://vtr.valasztas.hu/ep2024>

57

Funded by
the European Union

Európai parlamenti képviselők választása 2019, *Nemzeti Választási Iroda*, <https://www.valasztas.hu/ep2019>

Magyarország Alaptörvényének tizenegyedik módosítása (2022. július 19.), *Wolters Kluwer Jogszabálytár*
<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A2200719.ATV&txtreferer=00000003.TXT>

Political Capital (2024). *A kormánytól független narratívák tarolnak a nyilvános Facebook-csoportokban*. 2024-06-07 https://politicalcapital.hu/hirek.php?article_read=1&article_id=3387

Political Capital – Mérték Médiaelemző Műhely – Lakmusz (2024). Fidesz & Co. flooded social media with anti-Western hostile disinformation in Hungary's election campaign, reaching EU spending records. Summary report of the project "The marketplace of (false) ideas: Uncovering, analyzing, debunking and researching sponsored disinfo" funded by the European Media and Information Fund. Budapest. (1-23.)
https://politicalcapital.hu/pc-admin/source/documents/Uncovering_analyzing_debunking_and_researching_sponsored_disinfo_project_summary_2024.pdf

Reuters (2025). Hungary ruling party drafts bill to crack down on foreign-funded organisations. May 14, 2025.
<https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/hungary-ruling-party-drafts-bill-crack-down-foreign-funded-organisations-2025-05-14/>

Tóka, G. (2025). A 2024. évi európai parlamenti választások Magyarországon. In Tóth, I. G. & Gábos, A. & Medgyesi, M. (eds.): *Társadalmi Riport 2024*. Budapest: TÁRKI. (457-473.)
https://topap.hu/cms/uploads/457_473_TRIP_2024_Toka_9d93993b19.pdf

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Portugal

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Cristiano Gianolla, Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra; Michael Guanyao Wang, Centre for Social Studies, University of Coimbra; Kleber Carrilho, University of Helsinki
Editors:	Alexander Alekseev, University of Helsinki; Szilvia Horváth, University of Helsinki; Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Emre Erdoğan (Istanbul Bilgi University)

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Portugal: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024.....	4
Abstract	4
Abstract in the national language(s)	4
Section 1: Portugal: EP Election Results	5
# National Election Results and Party Affiliations	6
# Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	7
Section 2: Portugal: Political profiles.....	9
# Centre-right Feed	11
# Far-right Feed	16
# Red-Green Feed	20
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	24
Section 3: Portugal: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles	27
# Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	27
# Notes on Organic Profiles	28
# Differences Observed Over Time	30
# Differences between Instagram and TikTok	34
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	35
# Open Space and Conclusions	35
Section 4: Portugal: Data Gathering – Thematic Content.....	36
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	36
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram.....	37
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	38
# Content Related to Defence, War, and International Conflicts	40
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	41
# AI Generated Content	42
Section 5: Portugal: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal.....	44
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time.....	44
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate.....	44
# Emotional mechanisms	45
# Video Typologies.....	45

# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	46
# Discussion on the most interesting videos	47
Concluding section	48
# What was Europe about, and why vote (the Social Contract)?	48
# Populist mobilisation	49
# Conclusion	49
Bibliography	50

Portugal: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

This report results from using TikTok and Instagram in Portugal during the 2024 European Parliament election campaign three weeks before and one week after election day. It explores how political parties from different ideologies adapted their strategies to short-form video platforms, revealing engagement, visibility, and narrative style differences. While traditional parties remained cautious and institutionally focused, emerging parties (particularly on the far right) leveraged emotionally charged, algorithm-friendly content to boost their reach. The campaign was primarily centred on national issues, with limited reference to European matters. Far-right narratives emphasised cultural identity and anti-migrant sentiment, while left-wing content focused on policy and social justice. AI-generated and entertainment-oriented content also featured prominently, highlighting evolving digital tactics. In the election results, the Socialist Party narrowly won, while the far-right Chega and the liberal IL each elected their first MEPs. Meanwhile, the Left Block and Communist Party lost seats. These outcomes underscore how digital visibility and affective engagement increasingly shape electoral performance, challenging traditional democratic communication.

Abstract in the national language(s)

Este relatório resulta da utilização do TikTok e do Instagram em Portugal durante a campanha para as eleições ao Parlamento Europeu de 2024, abrangendo três semanas antes e uma semana após o dia da eleição. Analisa como os partidos políticos de diferentes ideologias adaptaram as suas estratégias às plataformas de vídeo de curta duração, revelando diferenças em termos de envolvimento, visibilidade e estilo narrativo. Enquanto os partidos tradicionais se mantiveram cautelosos e focados numa abordagem institucional, os partidos emergentes (particularmente à direita radical) recorreram a conteúdos emocionalmente carregados e compatíveis com os algoritmos para ampliar o seu alcance. A campanha centrou-se sobretudo em temas nacionais, com poucas referências a assuntos europeus. As narrativas da extrema-direita enfatizaram a identidade cultural e o sentimento anti-imigração, enquanto os conteúdos da esquerda se focaram em propostas políticas e temas de justiça social. Também foi visível a presença de conteúdos gerados por inteligência artificial e orientados para o entretenimento, destacando a evolução das táticas digitais. Nos resultados eleitorais, o Partido Socialista venceu por uma margem estreita, enquanto o Chega e a Iniciativa Liberal elegeram os seus primeiros eurodeputados. Por sua vez, o Bloco de Esquerda e o Partido Comunista perderam lugares. Estes resultados demonstram como a visibilidade digital e o envolvimento afetivo moldam cada vez mais o desempenho eleitoral, desafiando os modelos tradicionais de comunicação democrática.

Section 1: Portugal: EP Election Results

The results of the European Parliament (EP) elections in Portugal in 2024 showed a slight victory of the Centre-left Socialist Party (PS) over the leading competitor, and the Centre-right Democratic Alliance (AD) coalition was the winner of the recent national election. The Democratic Alliance (AD), primarily composed of the Social Democratic Party (PSD) and the Christian Democratic Party–Popular Party (CDS-PP), lost one seat compared to the 2019 European elections. Nevertheless, the overall result for AD remained comparable to the previous election. No major surprises were observed with the election of two MEPs from two relatively new parties: the far-right Chega party and the neoliberal right-wing Liberal Initiative (IL). While Chega's performance fell short of expectations, IL's result was a mild surprise, as it came close to becoming the third most voted political force. On the left, both the Left Block (BE) and the Portuguese Communist Party (PCP) managed to secure one MEP each, though both parties lost one seat compared to 2019. A third left-wing party, Livre (Free), could not elect its MEP even though it came close to it, while this party raised its representation in the recent national elections. The People Animal Nature party (PAN) lost its only seat compared to 2019. The image below summarizes the results.

Results by national party - 2024-2029

Portugal - Official results

Percentage of votes

National Parties

PS - Partido Socialista

AD - Aliança Democrática (Partido Social Democrata, Centro Democrático Social-Partido Popular, Partido Popular Monárquico)

CH - CHEGA

IL - Iniciativa Liberal

BE - Bloco de Esquerda

CDU - Coligação Democrática Unitária (Partido Comunista Português, Partido Ecologista "Os Verdes")

L - LIVRE

PAN - Pessoas-Animais-Natureza

Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Figure 1. Results by national party

National Election Results and Party

Affiliations

The expected success of the major centre-left and centre-right parties marked the results of the 2024 European Elections in Portugal. Unlike the national elections held in March 2024, the Socialist Party (PS) secured a narrow victory over the centre-right Democratic Alliance (AD), which had won the national vote earlier in the year. A notable outcome was the performance of the far-right Chega party, 6

which entered the European Parliament for the first time. Although Chega did not exist in 2019 (its leader had attempted an unsuccessful coalition at the time), its vote share in the European elections was significantly lower than in the recent national elections, falling short of expectations. Overall, the remaining results aligned with forecasts: no other new party won a seat in the European Parliament. The People–Animals–Nature Party (PAN) lost its only seat, and the main left-wing parties, Left Block (BE) and the Portuguese Communist Party (PCP)—each retained just one seat, losing ground compared to 2019. A new left-wing contender, the Livre Party, came close to gaining representation with nearly 4% of the vote but ultimately failed to elect an MEP.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by the EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Portugal

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

A domestic-oriented narrative has characterised the EP campaign compared to countries where the continental debates prevailed. This dynamic has been favoured by the engagement of national leaders in the campaign. However, different parties have adopted different strategies. The centre, right-wing and left-wing parties generated a campaign based on the lead candidate for the elections. The IL party, a challenger, also embraced this strategy as it ran for the EP election for the first time. Its candidate, João Cotrim de Figueiredo, is the former party leader who renounced his leadership when his reputation was very high within the party. His popularity is at least comparable to that of the current party leader, Ricardo Rocha. On the contrary, all other parties who did not have a seat in the national or EU parliament saw the party leader campaigning as a top candidate. Marta Temido was the lead candidate for PS, a former minister of health, during COVID; she is very popular. Sebastião Bugalho is a growing star in Portuguese journalism and has been identified by the PSD party as its lead candidate, not without generating controversy. Finally, without previous representation in the EP, the Chega party chose António Tânger Corrêa, former Portuguese Ambassador and national MP, as the leading candidate. However, the party leader, André Ventura, was the most active in the campaign, leading the party's public image. Tânger Correia remained in the shade of Ventura, representing a hybrid configuration

Breakdown of national parties and political groups - 2024-2029

Portugal - Constitutive session

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PfE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
PS	32.75%		8								8
AD	31.74%	7									7
CH	9.99%			2							2
IL	9.26%					2					2
BE	4.34%							1			1
CDU	4.20%							1			1
L	3.83%										0
PAN	1.24%										0
Other parties	2.65%										0
	100.00%	7	8	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	21

PS > S&D: FRANCISCO ASSIS, ISILDA GOMES, BRUNO GONÇALVES, SÉRGIO GONÇALVES, ANA CATARINA MENDES, ANDRÉ RODRIGUES, CARLA TAVARES, MARTA TEMIDO

PSD > EPP: PAULO CUNHA, PAULO DO NASCIMENTO CABRAL, SÉRGIO HUMBERTO, LÚDIA PEREIRA, HÉLDER SOUSA SILVA

CH > PfE: TIAGO MOREIRA DE SÁ, ANTÓNIO TÂNGER CORRÊA

IL > Renew Europe: JOÃO COTRIM DE FIGUEIREDO, ANA VASCONCELOS

PCP > The Left: JOÃO OLIVEIRA

CDS-PP > EPP: ANA MIGUEL PEDRO

BE > The Left: CATARINA MARTINS

Ind. > EPP: SEBASTIÃO BUGALHO

National Parties

- PS - Partido Socialista
- AD - Aliança Democrática (Partido Social Democrata, Centro Democrático Social-Partido Popular, Partido Popular Monárquico)
- CH - CHEGA
- IL - Iniciativa Liberal
- BE - Bloco de Esquerda
- CDU - Coligação Democrática Unitária (Partido Comunista Português, Partido Ecologista "Os Verdes")
- L - LIVRE
- PAN - Pessoas-Animais-Natureza
- Other parties - Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

- EPP - Group of the European People's Party (Christian Democrats)
- S&D - Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament
- PfE - Patriots for Europe
- ECR - European Conservatives and Reformists Group
- Renew Europe - Renew Europe Group
- Greens/EFA - Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance
- The Left - The Left group in the European Parliament - GUE/NGL
- ESN - Europe of Sovereign Nations
- NI - Non-attached Members

According to Parliament's rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

compared to other parties. This was the first time that André Ventura, the most representative and reputed person in the party, would not be the party's main candidate in an election. The parties on the left opted for two well-known party figures as lead candidates, BE opted for former party leader Catarina Martins; at the same time, PCP chose João Oliveira, one of the most popular leaders of the party.

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

Section 2: Portugal: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok

The chart shows the prominence of Chega (Enough), particularly within the radical right profile, where it dominates the feed almost exclusively. Its strong presence is not only in the radical right but also in the centre-right and even the red-green profiles. This data suggests that Chega's content was not confined to its ideological base but invaded the feeds, possibly due to the messages' emotionally charged and provocative nature, which aligns well with TikTok's algorithm.

In the centre-right feed, while parties like the Social Democratic Party (PSD), Liberal Initiative (IL), and Democratic Alliance (AD) were present, they were overshadowed by the number of mentions Chega received. This can indicate that radical right content appeared even within moderate or mainstream conservative profiles, pointing to a broader algorithmic trend that amplifies more polarising material. Interestingly, parties on the left, such as the Socialist Party (PS) and the Left Block (BE), also appeared in this feed, suggesting either a spillover effect or a lack of clear ideological boundaries in how content is distributed.

On the other hand, the red-green profile shows a much lower overall level of engagement. Parties like the Socialist Party, Left Block, and others were mentioned in significantly lower numbers. Chega maintained a presence even here, underscoring the difficulty left-wing parties face in gaining visibility.

Overall, the chart reflects not just the distribution of political content on TikTok but also the dynamics of visibility and engagement that favour certain ideological styles over others. The dominance of Chega in all ideological feeds suggests a platform environment where radical right messages benefit disproportionately from the algorithmic logic. In contrast, left and moderate parties struggle with visibility, highlighting their challenges in competing with far-right content.

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

The chart shows a balanced distribution of party mentions across centre-right, red-green, and radical-right profiles. In the centre-right feed, the most visible party is Volt Portugal, followed closely by the Social Democratic Party (PSD), Liberal Initiative (IL), and the Democratic Alliance (AD). These results show a more traditional political landscape within this ideological space, where moderate and pro-European parties have significant visibility. The Socialist Party (PS) and Left Block (BE), traditionally associated with the left, also appear. Chega (Enough), while present, registers minimally compared to its presence on TikTok, showing that Instagram may filter or distribute radical content with less frequency or impact.

In the red-green profile, the Socialist Party appears as the most mentioned entity, followed by the Christian Democratic Union of Germany. This somewhat unusual result may reflect the pan-European nature of some Instagram content. Chega again appears in this feed, though less prominently, reaffirming its algorithmic visibility across ideological lines. The lower mention count in this category mirrors what was seen on TikTok: left-oriented content tends to circulate less widely or less virally on visual social media platforms.

In the radical right feed, Chega once again dominates, followed by New Right (Nova Direita) and a mix of Portuguese and European far-right parties, such as Vlaams Belang (Belgium) and Alternative for 10

Germany (AfD). This configuration suggests that the radical right profile on Instagram includes a more substantial presence of transnational far-right narratives, probably boosted by the interconnected nature of far-right content networks online. However, Chega’s dominance is less stark here than on TikTok, pointing to different engagement mechanisms or moderation practices on Instagram.

In summary, Instagram presents a more fragmented and ideologically diverse landscape. While radical right content remains present and even prominent in specific feeds, its dominance is less pronounced. Centre-right parties maintain visibility through a mix of national and European actors, as well as red-green content. The challenges of visibility and ideological balance remain, particularly for left-wing actors who struggle to break through the noise of more emotionally charged or polarizing narratives.

Centre-Right Feed

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Working with a young male character with a centre-right ideological profile was difficult. In Portugal, despite having one of the main parties (Social Democratic Party, PSD) since the country's democratisation, the centre-right was “squeezed” in media discussions and social networks between the traditional left (Socialist Party, PS), which has been in government in recent years, and the far-right (Chega), which, as in many places around the world, manages to speak a language very close to young people in digital environments, developing highly competent content in engaging with this audience. After a victory in the March parliamentary election and a government without an absolute majority or the possibility of forming alliances, as it would have to be with the historical adversaries of the Socialist Party or with the extremist party Chega, the Democratic Alliance (AD), headed by the Social Democratic Party (EPP in Europe), a traditional centre-right party in Portugal, decided to launch Sebastião Bugalho as the lead candidate for the European elections. Bugalho, a young man with no political experience but a recent history as a (supposedly neutral) political commentator on television, was controversially chosen to head the list and be the main figure in the campaign.

In addition to this alliance, the Liberal Initiative, a new party affiliated with Renew Europe and having eight representatives in the Portuguese Assembly, was also visible in the feed of the centre-right account. Their lead candidate, João Cotrim de Figueiredo, was not as young, being in his fifties, but had a youthful and dynamic discourse on social media. Figueiredo appeared much younger than Bugalho on TikTok and Instagram.

Since elections in Portugal are held with closed lists, communication focused heavily on the main candidates. Besides the main leaders, Prime Minister Luis Montenegro was also present in most social media appearances, supporting Bugalho, especially during the campaign's final phase.

However, maintaining a centre-right profile was challenging, especially on TikTok. On several occasions, the algorithm promoted far-right content from Chega's candidates and national leaders and 12

anonymous users, micro- or nano-influencers who supported André Ventura (Chega's national leader) and his candidates for the European Parliament. Additionally, there was a lot of content from television programmes or podcasts on TikTok that showed embarrassing moments, particularly of Bugalho, who often found himself in difficult situations due to his lack of experience as a candidate.

While the IL's profile, with a strong presence of Cotrim de Figueiredo, remained stable, featuring content tailored for social media audiences, particularly with good humour and formats appealing to young people, Bugalho's Democratic Alliance had few standout moments. Their content for TikTok or Instagram was largely comprised of clips from events, meetings, debates, and interviews. Only in more informal moments, such as car ride videos featuring Prime Minister Montenegro and candidate Bugalho, can be seen as specifically developed content with social media language and concerns in mind. Furthermore, Bugalho's significant presence in youth-focused podcasts and TV shows can be considered a highlight.

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

The most prominent theme, by far, is “Arguments for Europe (why you should vote),” appearing in 22 instances, suggesting a strong emphasis, particularly from pro-European or institutional actors, on promoting voter participation and affirming the value of the EU. In contrast, themes aligned with “Grievance politics (anti/pro-democratic)” appear only 7 times, and “War” 5 times, indicating that polarising or geopolitically charged narratives, while present, were not dominant. A minimal number of cases (2) fell under “None of the above,” suggesting that most political content aligned with clear narrative categories. Overall, the data reflects a campaign discourse where pro-EU messaging held a clear lead. However, undercurrents of discontent and global conflict were not absent, hinting at a tension between institutional reassurance and populist or critical counter-discourses.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

The most dominant theme is immigration, appearing 21 times, underscoring its central role in the digital campaign discourse, likely driven by right-wing and far-right narratives that associate migration with cultural and security concerns. Following that, Social Europe (13 mentions) and Economy (12 mentions) also feature prominently, reflecting concerns over social protection and economic stability. The Green Deal or environmental issues were mentioned 8 times, showing moderate engagement with climate and sustainability topics. In contrast, issues like Gender, Agriculture, Defence, and Scandal were marginal, each appearing only once. This distribution suggests a campaign heavily influenced by identity and security politics, with traditional left-wing concerns like welfare and environmentalism present but not dominant, and other policy areas largely sidelined in the short-form video discourse.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The most prominent category by far is anti-immigrant content, appearing 20 times, which clearly indicates the central role of xenophobic narratives, especially within far-right digital campaigning. Anti-Muslim content and miscellaneous discriminatory content (labelled as “None of the above”) follow, each with five instances, reflecting additional layers of identity-based hostility. Meanwhile, anti-democratic, anti-LGBTQ+, misogynistic, and antisemitic content were less frequent but still present, suggesting a broader pattern of exclusionary discourse. The prevalence of such themes highlights the emotional and polarising nature of much of the political communication on platforms like TikTok and Instagram, where algorithmically amplified messages tend to favour sensationalism, grievance, and fear over deliberative democratic dialogue. These findings raise concerns about the normalisation of hate-based rhetoric in digital spaces during electoral periods.

Far-Right Feed

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by the EP group on TikTok and Instagram

The experience of collecting data was very intense and varied over time. In the beginning, data was collected somewhat mechanically. On TikTok, the feed filled more quickly. In contrast, several searches were necessary on Instagram before generating a feed conforming to the profile. On Instagram, the researcher also looked for other parties of the extreme right that were challenging the Chega electorate; the main one was Nova Direita (New Right), and the other one was Ergue-te (Rise Up). This last one is the heir of PNR (National Republican Party), which has campaigned in Portugal for many years without entering the parliament. Both parties, however, were unsuccessful in electing MEPs. Chega had a result below expectations, with two MEPs and almost half the percentage obtained only three months earlier at the national election.

The far-right profile was fed consistently with video of the Chega party leader, André Ventura. In contrast, other party leaders of the Chega or other parties of the far right and international leaders were less prominent. There was a time when international leaders, such as Nigel Farage and Jair Bolsonaro, were also prompted. For the first time in the party's history, André Ventura was not the main party candidate. António Tânger Corrêa was the main candidate; however, he operated in the shade of Ventura. Generally, one could see him at his side in the video, but in silence. Ventura was also questioned on this, and comedians joked that Tânger Corrêa was not presentable as a candidate.

On both platforms, content aligned with the Identity and Democracy (ID) group, typically associated with the far right, dominates the landscape, appearing 23 times on TikTok and 20 times on Instagram. This reflects the group's highly effective and algorithm-savvy use of short-form video to disseminate emotionally charged and populist messaging. In contrast, mainstream groups such as the European People's Party (EPP) and Socialists & Democrats (S&D) appear far less frequently, with only marginal representation, suggesting traditional parties have struggled to achieve comparable digital visibility.

16

Notably, the Non-inscrits (unaffiliated MEPs) show up more frequently on Instagram than TikTok, and progressive groups like GUE/NGL (the Left) and Greens-EFA barely register. The disparity highlights a significant imbalance in online campaigning, where right-wing populist forces have clearly outpaced their competitors in terms of presence and influence on major social media platforms.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram

The leading category, with 22 mentions, is “Arguments for Europe (why you should vote),” indicating that a significant portion of digital content aimed to promote democratic participation and convey the relevance of the EU to citizens’ lives. However, this pro-European messaging competes with more adversarial or emotive themes. “Grievance politics (anti/pro-democratic)” appears 7 times, suggesting the presence of populist or anti-system narratives that frame political elites or EU institutions as corrupt or disconnected. “War” is featured in 5 instances, reflecting concerns with geopolitics and security, particularly in light of current international conflicts. Only 2 videos did not fit these categories. The data suggests that while efforts were made to present a positive case for EU engagement, the digital campaign also hosted a noticeable undercurrent of discontent, polarisation, and crisis framing.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Immigration emerges as the dominant topic, with 21 mentions, highlighting its centrality in political discourse, likely driven by right-wing and far-right narratives portraying migration as a cultural or security threat. In contrast, traditionally progressive themes such as Social Europe (13 mentions) and the Economy (12 mentions) also received significant attention, suggesting that welfare and employment concerns remained relevant across ideological lines. The Green Deal or environmental transition 18

appeared in 8 instances, indicating a moderate presence of climate-related messaging, though not dominant. Gender, agriculture, defence, and scandal were marginal, each with only 1 to 4 appearances, revealing a striking imbalance in thematic focus. Overall, the campaign discourse on short-form platforms skewed heavily toward identity and insecurity narratives, with socio-economic and environmental issues present but clearly less prominent in terms of digital visibility.

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 13: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The overwhelming majority of such content (29 instances) was classified as anti-immigrant, reflecting a strong focus on migration as a political wedge issue, particularly exploited by far-right actors. Anti-Muslim content and a catch-all “None of the above” category follow with 5 mentions each, suggesting additional, albeit less dominant, discriminatory narratives. There are also visible instances of anti-democratic content (3), anti-LGBTQ+ (2), misogyny/anti-feminism (2), and antisemitism (1). This distribution highlights how certain forms of exclusion (especially those targeting immigrants) have become central to political messaging on platforms like TikTok and Instagram. The presence of broader hate speech and anti-democratic rhetoric underscores how digital spaces are being used to promote divisive, identity-based politics that can threaten inclusive democratic discourse.

When presenting political content, Instagram proved to be significantly more “undisciplined” than TikTok. The platform frequently reverted to unrelated videos, requiring new searches to retrieve political material. Over time, engaging with the profiles of followed users helped streamline access to political videos without the need for repeated searches. This shift also led to greater visibility of other party figures, such as Rita Matias, the youngest national MP from Chega, who demonstrates considerable skill in creating content for social media. As more profiles associated with Chega sympathisers were followed, video commentaries by non-MPs began to appear more frequently. These videos provided valuable insights into the political culture surrounding Chega’s rise. Some individuals who had

previously engaged in such content production and were affiliated with the party have since been elected to the parliament.

The Chega communication office generally made up video content. Some videos had a proper narrative concerning a specific issue; in these videos, you would see Venura in some side room of the parliament talking about a topic for a few minutes. The media reported other videos, especially when not proposed by official Chega profiles. The content related to EP elections was inconsistent, and the topic mobilised by Chega seemed to be especially related to the party's national ideas, myths, objects, and objectives. This may be due to the expected low turnout of the EP elections, and, although the turnout improved, this has to be related to the fact that it was permitted to vote in all the country schools as opposed to the residence place on 9 June.

Red-Green Feed

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by the EP group on TikTok and Instagram

On TikTok, the most visible group is Identity and Democracy (ID) with 5 appearances, indicating strong far-right representation on the platform. This is followed by both the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D) and None of the above with 4 mentions each, and The Left in the European Parliament (GUE/NGL) with 3. Mainstream centre-right and centre-left groups like EPP and S&D are noticeably underrepresented on TikTok.

On Instagram, by contrast, EPP and S&D are the most prominent, each with 7 instances, highlighting a more balanced or traditional party presence. Far-right ID appears only twice, while GUE/NGL, Greens/EFA, and Renew Europe each appear once. This distribution suggests that far-right groups dominate TikTok, whereas Instagram supports greater visibility for centrist and left-leaning parties, possibly due to platform demographics or differing campaign strategies. The findings reinforce the idea

that TikTok is more fertile ground for populist and radical-right messaging, while Instagram remains a more moderated political space.

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram

On TikTok, the largest category is “None of the above” (8), suggesting a significant share of political content either not clearly aligned with any parliamentary group or coming from unofficial or individual voices. Among identified groups, Identity and Democracy (ID) has the highest presence (5), followed by S&D, GUE/NGL, and Renew Europe, each appearing 4 times. In contrast, traditional centrist groups like the European People's Party (EPP) and ECR appear only once.

On Instagram, the picture changes: EPP and S&D both lead with 10 appearances each, indicating that mainstream and institutional actors have a stronger presence on this platform. ID drops to 3, while left-leaning groups like Greens/EFA, Renew, and GUE/NGL show modest but balanced representation.

The red-green profile was designed for a young persona of left-wing political leanings, hence, data was collected with the presumption of following primarily the traditional centre-left party in Portugal, the Socialist Party (Partido Socialista). In the aftermath of the recent change in government after almost 9 years of party leadership headed by Prime Minister António Costa, the party sought to revamp its social media presence to engage a younger, more dynamic audience. Marta Temido, the party's candidate for the 2024 European election, was a prominent figure in this strategy. Temido, who served as the Minister of Public Health between 2018 and 2022, was featured extensively on the party's official TikTok and Instagram accounts. Despite controversies during her tenure, most notably her comments during the COVID-19 pandemic condemning nurses who participated in strikes, Temido remained a popular figure on social media. Her presence was marked by frequent short videos and reposted interviews from primary news sources like RTP and TSF, which helped amplify her reach and engagement with the public.

Parallel to the Socialist Party, the Left Block has also maintained a significant presence in Portugal's political landscape and social media representation. The party, known for its progressive and left-wing policies, has been influential in the Assembly of the Portuguese Republic.

Catarina Martins, one of the most emblematic figures of the Left Block, served as a deputy in the Assembly from 2009 to 2023 and as the party leader from 2014 to 2023. Her leadership period coincided with a critical phase in Portuguese politics, including the aftermath of the 2022 parliamentary elections. Martins' departure from the leadership position marked the end of an era for the Left Block, but her influence continued to be felt through the party's social media activities. This is demonstrated through BE's social media, which promotes her candidacy for the European election.

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

The most frequent theme is “Arguments for Europe (why you should vote),” with 9 instances, indicating a proactive effort by some actors to encourage electoral participation and emphasize the importance of the EU. However, this is closely followed by both “Grievance politics (anti/pro-democratic)” and “None of the above,” each appearing 6 times, suggesting a significant presence of either discontent-driven narratives or content that doesn't fit standard categories, potentially satire, personal expression, or unaffiliated commentary. “War” was scarcely mentioned, with just 1 occurrence, implying that international conflict played a minimal role in the Portuguese digital discourse. Overall, the data reflects a mixed information environment: one where pro-European messaging exists alongside notable undercurrents of dissatisfaction, political cynicism, and unaffiliated or ambiguous narratives.

Immigration was by far the most dominant topic, with 18 mentions, underscoring its central role in the electoral discourse, likely driven by far-right parties and algorithmically amplified narratives focusing on identity and border control. Economic issues, such as inflation and unemployment, were closely followed with 14 mentions, indicating continued public concern about cost-of-living pressures. Both religion and Social Europe (welfare, healthcare, social protections) were mentioned 9 times, reflecting the tension between cultural identity debates and left-leaning socioeconomic agendas. Media criticism 22

also appeared prominently (7 times), often linked to populist distrust of traditional journalism or digital censorship. Meanwhile, issues such as gender, defence, and the Green Deal were less visible, suggesting that more progressive or technical policy areas were marginal in the short-form political media landscape. The data reflects a campaign marked by polarisation, material anxieties, and limited attention to climate and gender justice.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The leading theme is “Arguments for Europe (why you should vote)”, which appears 9 times, reflecting a strong presence of pro-European discourse encouraging electoral participation and civic engagement. However, this is balanced by six instances each of “Grievance politics (anti/pro-democratic)” and “None of the above,” indicating a substantial portion of content either critical of the political establishment or outside conventional narrative categories, possibly satirical or neutral in tone. Notably, “War” appears only once, suggesting that geopolitical issues such as Ukraine or global conflict had minimal resonance in Portuguese digital campaigning. Overall, the graph suggests a contested discursive environment where democratic messaging coexists with populist scepticism and narrative ambiguity, underscoring the fragmented and emotionally varied nature of political communication on platforms like TikTok and Instagram.

While both PS and BE have made strides in utilising social media, their approaches often lack the same level of innovation and immediacy seen in right-wing strategies. There is significant potential for these parties to enhance their digital presence by adopting more interactive and visually engaging content, leveraging trends and platforms that resonate with younger demographics. Despite following exclusively left-wing political content and official accounts of left-wing parties and influencers, a large amount of right-wing content, and occasionally far-right content, was still prevalent. Observations indicate that right-wing and far-right parties, such as the Liberal Initiative and Chega, appeal more to young audiences. This is reflected in their innovative content and effective use of the post-pandemic economic predicament to evoke anger and frustration among young people. The Liberal Initiative capitalised on dissatisfaction with taxation, arguing that it hinders economic development. At the same time, Chega focused on blaming migration, stirring up anger related to national identity, and appealing to financially vulnerable individuals. These strategies have allowed right-wing parties to resonate more effectively with the youth in the Portuguese context, highlighting the need for left-wing parties to adapt and innovate in their communication approaches to regain traction with this crucial demographic.

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

The figure 20a shows that one dominant figure emerges across all three ideological profiles: André Ventura, leader of Chega (Enough). Ventura's prominence is especially stark in the radical right segment, where he dominates the feed. However, what stands out is that he is also the most mentioned political actor in both the centre-right and red-green profiles. This cross-profile visibility shows Ventura's central role in TikTok's political landscape and suggests a high level of algorithmic amplification. His strong social media presence, controversial rhetoric, and confrontational communication style likely contribute to this reach, making him a frequent subject of support and criticism.

The second most visible actor in the centre-right category is Sebastião Bugalho, lead candidate for the Democratic Alliance (AD), followed by Marta Temido (Socialist Party), Pedro Santos, and Prime Minister Luís Montenegro. This mix includes governing figures and candidates, suggesting that TikTok content in this ideological stream is not limited to party insiders but also reflects broader public figures and campaign personalities. Temido and Catarina Martins (from BE) also appear here, indicating some ideological overlap or content circulation beyond traditional political lines.

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Portugal

In the red-green profile, visibility is significantly lower and more evenly distributed among figures like Pedro Santos, Catarina Martins, João and Francisco Figueiredo. Again, André Ventura appears to have many mentions, which points to either algorithmic intrusion of right-wing content or critical engagement by left-leaning users. This suggests that far-right narratives or figures remain highly visible even within progressive feeds, which may reflect TikTok's content promotion dynamics or user interactions that inadvertently boost such profiles.

The radical right profile reinforces the centrality of Ventura, followed by a set of party members and sympathisers, including Patrícia Pinto, Pedro Frazão and José Pacheco. Most of these names are associated with Chega or other far-right movements, and their appearance in the data implies a coordinated or at least consistent communication effort. These actors benefit from a content style that is emotive, polemical, and shareable, ideal for TikTok's viral logic.

Figure 20b reveals a little more diverse visibility across actors and ideological profiles. While some patterns mirror those found on TikTok, Instagram exhibits a more fragmented distribution of political visibility.

In the centre-right profile, Sebastião Bugalho, the lead candidate for the Democratic Alliance (AD), stands out as the most mentioned political actor. His strong presence shows the centrality of his candidacy and the media attention it drew during the campaign. He is followed by Francisco Figueiredo and former Prime Minister António Costa, indicating that both campaign figures and established political leaders continued to maintain relevance on Instagram. Pedro Santos, a Socialist Party figure, also appears, showing that content from other ideological backgrounds is present in the centre-right feed.

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Portugal

In the red-green profile, the visibility is notably more international and mixed. Ursula von der Leyen appears to be the most mentioned figure, which reflects a more Europeanised content pattern in this feed. Other visible figures include Marta Temido, André Ventura, and Sebastião Bugalho, indicating some algorithmic crossover or widespread content circulation. Additional figures like Carlos Moedas, Pedro Lopes, and Francisco Paupério suggest that other political voices also gained attention, particularly among progressive-leaning Instagram users. The frequency of mentions remains modest, showing no single left-wing figure was dominant.

The radical right feed is led by André Ventura, who maintains a consistent top position across platforms and ideological feeds. He is followed by Olivier Liberato, António Tânger Corrêa, and Rita Matias, all linked to Chega or far-right political movements. Their visibility points to a deliberate communication strategy on Instagram, where their content resonates with their target audience. The presence of figures like Pedro Pinto, Rui Rocha (Liberal Initiative), and even Sebastião Bugalho in the radical proper feed highlights Instagram’s broader algorithmic blending, where figures from different ideological spectrums appear across profiles, potentially due to shared hashtags, reposts, or engagement patterns.

While André Ventura remains the most consistently visible political actor across all platforms and profiles, Instagram hosts a more diverse and internationally aware content environment. Nevertheless, the far-right maintains a strong digital presence, demonstrating its ability to adapt to multiple social media ecosystems with tailored messaging and high engagement.

Section 3: Portugal: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build a feed of red-green, centre-right or far-right orientation as quickly as possible, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what was out there or watching something of the researcher's choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content and mention the activity of the organic profiles.

The three researchers involved in the data collection in Portugal were not TikTok or Instagram users. While they created the respective profiles for red-green, centre-right and radical right emulation, they also created their organic profiles. The team had a similar experience with data collection: TikTok was quicker and more consistent in offering political content than Instagram. Moreover, the three organic profiles were offered unsolicited far-right content even when they were being trained to find political content of other political orientations. This may be linked to the increasing availability of more engaging (and more viral) content produced by the far-right, though further research is needed to develop appropriate hypotheses. Such work could shed light on how platform algorithms function and how they influence the spread of far-right politics. Finally, it is worth noting that two types of content were observed across the three profiles: content specifically created for social media — such as short monologues or curated thematic segments — and content repurposed from television — such as excerpts from interviews or news broadcasts.

Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

The first synthetic profile was set to simulate a radical right young male voter. The researcher responsible for this profile had no organic profile before the data collection, and one was created for that purpose. Both profiles were instructed simultaneously. In the organic profile, the researcher wanted to follow the general trends of the political debates, without following a specific party; however, in the initial searches, the researcher started by looking at the content made by left-leaning parties. This, however, was not a reason for right-wing content not to be offered on these platforms. Moreover, in the different searches, the researcher tried to look for different parties and people in both profiles, but only a few stood out. Ventura stood out for Chega and the right in the synthetic profile. At the same time, Joana Mortagua was surprisingly more active than Mariana Mortagua, her sister and leader of the Left Block party on the left. However, both sisters were able to produce informative content-related content, as opposed to grievance-related content, in their videos. They debated ideas and policies. Catarina Martins, Left Block's leading candidate (and only MEP elected), was in the stream but less so than the two sisters. João Oliveira, leader of the Portuguese Communist Party, was also very active. Still, his videos were mostly a report of his campaign on the ground or a reproduction of his interviews or speeches. The researcher responsible for the radical right experienced a big difference between how the two platforms work and how the profile characterisation reacted to their initial searches. TikTok is a quick learner, while Instagram is much more undisciplined in offering political content. This was replicated in both profiles. Nonetheless, a search for a greater variety of parties was made in the organic profile. Later, the researcher also searched for a bigger variety of party followers. This made the video

27

stream more varied as well. Surprisingly, far-right videos were also included in the organic profile, and the researcher had not searched for or followed people and parties with such an ideological orientation.

Likewise, the researcher responsible for the Lef-Green profile had no organic profiles set up on TikTok and Instagram before the study. After creating both organic profiles for TikTok and Instagram, respectively, the researcher followed the directions per the provisions outlined for this online ethnographic study. However, after the first week, the researcher encountered an abundance of content that was not politically relevant. To address this, the researcher manually adjusted the organic profiles to generate more politically oriented content. This involved following prominent political figures from across the political spectrum on TikTok and Instagram. These figures included, but were not limited to, the President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen, the Prime Minister of Portugal, Luís Montenegro, former Prime Minister António Costa, and the official pages of the EU Parliament and the European Commission. The researcher also followed various political parties such as the Socialist Party, Left Bloc, Social Democratic Party, and several political commentators from Portugal. This procedure resulted in a significant increase in political content, with videos from official channels of European and national authorities starting to appear. Initially, the most relevant and recurring content focused on migration and asylum seekers, which was particularly interesting for the study. The content on the red-green synthetic profiles predominantly reflected left-wing viewpoints. In contrast, the organic profiles featured more right-wing and far-right content, alongside international issues such as the conflicts in Gaza and Ukraine and the American elections. This led to a more diverse array of content on the organic profiles compared to the synthetic ones.

The researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic profile noted that the profile, due to its ideological proximity to right-wing values, especially in economic terms, had a great presence of far-right content. The organic profile, which was used solely for the development of this research, was adapted to a perspective more aligned with the left and green movements, bringing different content, particularly on Instagram. Far-right content also appeared on TikTok in certain circumstances, even with a different ideological tendency. Despite significant differences in content, some elements, such as candidates' appearances in debates and news programmes on television, were common between the synthetic and organic profiles, albeit with different cuts and moments where opposing candidates performed better. It was noticeable that traditional media, particularly television, were very present in the Portuguese political discussion, mainly because much of the content on social networks originated from it. This includes content shared on candidates' and parties' profiles and by supporters aiming for political influence.

Notes on Organic Profiles

Figures 21a and 21b demonstrate the variety of unique political parties the researchers could observe in their organic accounts daily on Instagram and TikTok. The researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic account was consistently exposed to diverse political content throughout the data-gathering exercise. The researcher responsible for the radical right account received more diverse content in the early and middle phases. The number of mentions of different political parties in their organic profiles peaked before the election, indicating a front-loaded approach. Finally, the analysis of the organic profiles of the researcher responsible for the red-green profile indicates that they were exposed to more diverse content in the final days leading up to and after the election, reflecting a late but intense push for visibility.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

These figures (21a and 21b) show the daily mentions of unique politicians recorded by each data gatherer. In their organic accounts on TikTok and Instagram, the researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic account was consistently exposed to content featuring different politicians. Yet the intensity of this exposure reached its climax in the days leading up to the election day, 9 June 2024. The organic feeds of the researcher dealing with the radical right profile exhibited a similar pattern with an increase in the exposure in the early and mid-campaign period and peaks between days 13 and 20, indicating a strategy focused on the early phase. Finally, the organic accounts of the red-green researcher recorded more daily mentions of different politicians in the later stages of the campaign: the mentions rose from day 18 onward, reaching their highest levels just before and after the election. This suggests a high intensity of the public debate in the final days of the campaign. It must be noted that these data are also the result of the usage of the respective platform. With the increase in search for videos by the researchers, the content may have shifted away from or approximated the content of the political parties they searched for.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

Differences Observed Over Time

The main difference that the researcher responsible for the radical right synthetic profile observed in both organic and synthetic profiles depends on two variables. The first is that both profiles started from zero memory; they were both new and evolved through the researcher's interaction with them. As mentioned above, TikTok was very disciplined in offering a political profile quite early, while Instagram would always return to non-political and sensational content. The second variable is related to the content of the electoral campaign. As the Portuguese campaign was not very much related to European topics but much more to the national disputes between parties, the issues varied greatly depending on political appetite. For instance, there was a case when André Ventura was faced by an immigrant who accused him of spreading a racist ideology and defended himself for the fact that he was a hard-working individual but feels racial discrimination in Portuguese society, notwithstanding his engagement within it. Ventura showed no empathy and was heavily criticised in the media. He used his social network profile to tell a different story of the events. He attacked one national broadcaster, which had failed to show the whole event and selectively opted to show only a part of it.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by the EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Portugal over time

Thus, Ventura turned the campaign event into a victimisation process to dismiss the allegations of mistreatment and lack of humanness that he received. This argument was not so prominent in the organic profile, probably because the researcher responsible for the radical right followed more political leaders and fewer sympathisers than in the synthetic profile. Moreover, during the third week of data collection, the researcher responsible for radical rights started receiving content from international politicians unrelated to the European elections. The examples include Nigel Farage and Jair Bolsonaro. After the elections, there were no real follow-up videos, neither celebratory nor condemnatory. This may be because, on the one hand, the Chega party elected its first two MEPs, and, on the other hand, the fact that this result did not allow the party to continue its growing trend but, on the contrary, it represented a setback. Other far-right parties remained generally passive about the European election.

In the case of the researcher focused on red-green political parties, a similar trend was observed. Based on initial observations, TikTok appeared significantly more responsive in curating content aligned with political views, comments, and current events, offering more politically relevant videos necessary for the study than Instagram. Within the first week of the study, migration issues began to emerge, followed by content addressing the politicisation of Portuguese immigration policies, reflecting public dissatisfaction. Given that the organic profile was designed for a young persona with a left-wing political inclination, the researcher manually followed profiles of left-wing leaders and parties to receive content on left-wing perspectives on migration. Two key factors may explain this trend.

First and foremost, migration is a critical issue shaping voter behaviour and influencing the broader social discourse. Secondly, the recent shift in political power in Portugal underscores public discontent with the migration policies enacted by the previous Socialist Party-led government. As mentioned, even after adjusting Instagram followers to focus on left-wing content, far-right perspectives on migration remained prevalent. This was evident in videos posted by young Portuguese users showcasing Martim Moniz, a neighbourhood they claimed was “taken over” by South Asian migrants. However, some content also highlighted an appreciation for migrant cultures, as seen in Portuguese content creators trying Indian street food in Martim Moniz.

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)*

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Portugal over time

Regarding official political leadership, the Left Block (BE) stood out as the only party explicitly criticising the current far-right approach to migration policies, particularly the government's decision to end the “manifestação de interesse” (expression of interest). These critiques only appeared after manual adjustments were made to the researcher’s organic and synthetic profiles, which still reflect the underlying unpopularity of migration policies in Portugal and the EU. The researcher responsible for the centre-right profile has an organic and synthetic profile experience that is aligned with the other two. Communication on social networks in the initial weeks was closely tied to internal political issues, still stemming from the Portuguese parliamentary election held in March 2024 that resulted in the formation of a new government. Criticisms of the Socialist Party were prevalent in both the synthetic and organic

profiles, particularly on corruption-related issues, which had led to the end of the previous government and the early legislative elections.

Discussions on European issues became more prominent only in the period immediately before the election (about ten days), but these were always linked to internal matters such as immigration and economic solutions for the country in relation to European funds, with little content related to concrete proposals. The scandal that dominated social networks in the last week involving Chega leader André Ventura (who was not a candidate but was the main campaigner for the Chega party) in a confrontation with a Bangladeshi immigrant (reported in more detail by the researcher responsible for the Radical Right profile) who confronted him over the racism in his speech was crucial for attacking the new party. This incident was featured in both the organic and synthetic profiles. After the election, TikTok and Instagram continued spreading campaign videos for some days, together with celebration and interview videos about the results.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

Figures 24a and b show the visibility of different political parties in the TikTok feeds of the three synthetic profiles. The researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic profile recorded a consistent presence of different political parties throughout the data-gathering period. The red-green synthetic profile on TikTok was exposed to more different political parties before the election, indicating a push in essential moments. TikTok's radical right synthetic profile was particularly exposed to content featuring different

political parties in the middle of the campaign, particularly between days 9 and 15. Post-election exposure declined in all profiles, showing the campaign-driven nature of most content.

The intensity of exposure to the content featuring different political parties on Instagram was more sustained and pronounced than on TikTok, particularly in the feeds of the radical right synthetic profile. The red-green synthetic profile experienced an apparent surge in the number of political parties mentioned in the final campaign stretch, especially from days 18 to 25, suggesting a coordinated digital effort leading up to the election on Instagram. The researcher responsible for the centre-right synthetic profile was exposed to the content featuring different political parties early in the campaign and after the election. Instagram appears to have supported a broader ideological balance than TikTok.

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

Differences between Instagram and TikTok

Generally speaking, the main difference between the two platforms, Instagram and TikTok, is that the latter is quicker in learning users' preferences and proposing similar videos. As a result, Instagram was more open to offering a diversified set of videos which did not include political videos. Consequently, TikTok was more consistent in proposing political videos than Instagram. Moreover, Instagram was generally more persistent in proposing sensational content that was not politically related, while TikTok

seemed more skilled in offering sensational content of a political type. Overall, TikTok seemed more centred on user preference about content type and interest. Instagram, instead, was more centred on viral content.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

Both platforms had different reactions to the instruction phase. TikTok was a quick learner and provided political videos sooner and more consistently than Instagram. Instagram was generally more dispersed, generating content of a sensationalistic type. It seemed that Instagram was more interested in keeping the user interested with new and stimulating content without necessarily being of a political kind. It was not untypical that the stream would include non-political but shocking videos after searching and watching political content on Instagram. As political videos were shown, Instagram was more open in including videos from people around the political parties analysed than those identified with the parties. This may also be because researchers have followed more people and liked more content to stimulate Instagram to include political videos in the list of videos. While on TikTok, the need to show one's interest was reduced, and the platform would include content strictly related.

Open Space and Conclusions

The algorithms of the two platforms analysed are sensibly different. The perspective that emerges from the study of the Portuguese country profile is nuanced due to the peculiarity of the team composition. The three researchers involved did not use these platforms before and created an organic profile simultaneously with the synthetic ones. This symmetry between the researchers involved was particularly useful in observing how the two platforms work and which algorithmic logic lies behind them. While both seek to retain users and increase content visualisation, they have different strategies. Overall, it seems that, for new profiles, such as those created by the research team of the country profiles in Portugal, Instagram is led by the content-virality principle, while the user-interest principle leads TikTok. The content-virality principle leading the Instagram algorithm privileges viral content with less regard for the user's concerns. The user-interest principle leading the TikTok algorithm privileges users' searches and content type, identifiable by the user's interest, based on search and video visualisation.

Section 4: Portugal: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

This section reviews the themes and topics in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for TikTok and Instagram. We highlight her important themes for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and note AI-produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 25: List of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

During the campaign for the European Parliament elections in Portugal, European and international issues played only a marginal role. Topics such as the Green Deal, Social Europe, the Ukraine-Russia war, the Israel-Gaza conflict, and NATO-related discussions were notably absent from the core of the parties' political discourse. Instead, the campaign was dominated by national issues in official communications and grassroots messaging. Some parties with a significant international connection, such as the Portuguese Communist Party, represent some exceptions to this.

Europe was referenced primarily to underline the need for EU support in addressing domestic concerns, particularly immigration regulation. The narrative framed the European Union not as a platform for broader cooperation but as a means to legitimise national policies, especially regarding border control

and reducing migrant inflows. This utilitarian view of Europe positioned the EU as a tool rather than a political space for engagement or debate.

Campaign materials, especially videos shared online, reflected this national focus. Most content emphasised pressing political matters such as the economic crisis and immigration, themes that resonated strongly with the electorate’s everyday concerns, according to far-right discourse. European or international subjects were rarely featured, and when they appeared, they were typically linked to domestic anxieties or used to reinforce nationalist rhetoric.

In essence, the campaign in Portugal was characterised by a strategic sidelining of broader European and global issues in favour of a narrative grounded in national sovereignty and internal affairs. This approach partially results from the country’s peripheral position in shaping the international impact of European politics. Moreover, it amplifies a broader trend in which radical right politics impact Europe: engaging with Europe only to the extent that it serves national political goals while deliberately minimizing the importance of transnational solidarity or multilateral dialogue.

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)*

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

Figure 26 illustrates the evolution of common themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds. This visual, which tracks the content of synthetic profiles, reveals shifting priorities in the data collected about identified political issues, with specific national topics dominating the conversation. A clear trend is the prominence of immigration, which consistently remains one of the most visible themes throughout the period. Its frequency spikes around early June, indicating a surge in related content likely tied to campaign messaging or external events. The economy, covering topics such as taxation and unemployment, maintains a more moderate but steady presence, showing its relevance as a domestic concern. Another dominant theme was Social Europe, particularly topics related to education, healthcare, and the welfare state, which peaked around 9 June 2024 before declining slightly. However, its presence never surpasses immigration in visibility.

In contrast with these three dominating themes, others were more marginal. Media and communication and gender are relatively stable but not dominant themes. They emerged along with the intensification of the political campaign, towards the end of May, with gender conserving a strong presence while media and communication were more fluctuating. The Green Deal or environmentalism and defence appear far less frequently, with defence being more constant throughout the period observed and environmentalism appearing more intensely but sporadically. This supports the observation that international or broader EU issues were marginal in the data collected. Religion is a theme that appears consistently throughout the time observed, but without strong emphasis. Agriculture remains a minor theme, with only slight appearances in visibility over the period.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

As referred above, in Portugal, national topics overwhelmingly dominated the political debate. European and international issues were largely marginal, with occasional appearances in the feed. The focus remained on domestic concerns, reinforcing the centrality of national narratives in the Portuguese online 38

political space. Although rare, content from foreign contexts – particularly the UK and Brazil – did appear, especially around the third week of observation. These videos often showcased prominent far-right personalities or highlighted international events tied to far-right movements. Much of this content was satirical or humorous, mocking political opponents in other countries.

On TikTok, international content tended to centre on high-profile geopolitical developments. Although remaining marginal in the overall content reproduced in the respective feeds, the ongoing Israel-Palestine conflict appeared frequently, along with occasional posts about Russia, typically focusing on President Vladimir Putin. American political content was also common, including videos covering diplomatic visits, such as the U.S. Secretary of State's trip to Albania. Also in the centre-right feeds, international content appeared sporadically, with most videos still emphasizing domestic priorities. However, certain global narratives occasionally surfaced, especially those tied to European integration and security. For example, the conflict in Ukraine was framed through Portugal's support for European solidarity. The Social Democratic Party's leading candidate emphasized NATO's role in ensuring regional stability and highlighted Portugal's involvement in defence and energy security discussions.

Far-right figures like Viktor Orbán and Marine Le Pen occasionally appeared in the feed of synthetic profiles other than the radical right one. American conservative movements were referenced less often, though comparisons with figures like Trump, Bolsonaro and Farage surfaced occasionally. These parallels were drawn more cautiously, reflecting ideological sympathies without overt alignment. Meanwhile, China's global trade role was occasionally mentioned, typically in the context of urging balanced economic relations and avoiding over-dependence.

As the researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic profile noted, all these topics were very marginal in Portugal, where national issues dominated the debate. However, at some point (third week), some content from the UK and Brazil was also suggested in the feed. This content recalled the work of the far-right internationally, showing known personalities of the far-right at work, or commenting on specific issues. Political videos from other countries were often sarcastic or based on humour. They made fun of their political opponents.

The researcher responsible for the red-green profile encountered some feeds on TikTok focusing on non-EU countries, particularly regarding the ongoing conflict between Israel and Palestine. Additionally, while there are fewer posts, some content addresses Russia, often centred around President Vladimir Putin's actions and policies. American content appears frequently, such as videos detailing recent diplomatic activities, like the U.S. Secretary of State's visit to Albania. These themes collectively reflect TikTok's tendency to highlight high-profile geopolitical events, albeit with a regional emphasis that varies in prominence and depth across different countries.

Content related to foreign countries appeared sporadically in the centre-right feed, with most videos emphasizing domestic issues. Sometimes, some international themes emerged, often tied to broader European and global narratives. On TikTok, the content was more dynamic and personalized, while Instagram provided less political content. A recurring theme was the conflict in Ukraine, framed through Portugal's role in supporting European solidarity. Videos from the Social Democratic Party's primary candidate highlighted NATO's importance in maintaining regional security and often connected Portugal's participation in defence initiatives to broader European stability. The videos were inclined toward practical concerns, such as energy security and the economic impact of sanctions on Russia, reflecting a pragmatic approach. Leaders like Viktor Orbán and Marine Le Pen also appeared occasionally, in far-right videos that 'invade' the centre-right profile. American politics appeared less

frequently but was present through discussions of conservative movements and comparisons with leaders like Donald Trump. These narratives sometimes sought to draw parallels with Portuguese centre-right leaders, though with a more tempered tone. China's influence in global trade was occasionally mentioned, framed as a call for balanced trade relations and caution against economic over-dependence.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Defence, War, and International Conflicts

The researcher responsible for the radical right synthetic profile noted that content on the wars in Ukraine and Palestine was rare in the TikTok and Instagram feeds. Political parties on the far right of the ideological spectrum, namely Chega (Enough), Nova Direita (New Right) and Ergue-te (Rise Up), did not prepare content related to these international issues and references to them were relatively marginal in those videos, in which these parties made a political assessment of the multiple problems.

Meanwhile, the researcher dealing with the red-green synthetic profile remarked that it was hard to form a detailed observation on the impact of content related to the Russian attacks on Ukraine due to its limited visibility. However, there was an evident trend of European solidarity in response to Ukraine's situation, prominently displayed by Instagram users, influencers, and official accounts. Support for Ukraine appeared consistently, though less visibly compared to discussions around European unity. In

40

contrast, the discourse around the Gaza conflict showed significantly more polarized debate, particularly regarding whether the EU should provide Israel with financial and military support. This topic sparked considerable controversy, especially within discussions linked to left-leaning and green political accounts. Notably, the researcher observed posts from figures like Irish parliamentary member Clare Daly. Daly's content included vocal criticisms of the EU's support package to Israel, arguing that such aid compromises European solidarity and undermines collective values on human rights. This stark difference in coverage suggested a nuanced hierarchy in European social media discourse on solidarity and foreign intervention, highlighting an implicit preference in support strategies across different geopolitical contexts.

Content related to defence and conflicts also appeared sporadically in the centre-right feed. Focusing on the Russian invasion of Ukraine and Portugal's role in European solidarity, videos highlighted NATO's importance, humanitarian aid to Ukraine, and the need to reduce dependency on Russian energy, emphasizing stability and pragmatic solutions. The Gaza conflict appeared less often, framed as a diplomatic challenge requiring caution. TikTok featured emotionally charged videos, while Instagram leaned toward analytical content from think tanks and official accounts. Though it often lacked deeper human narratives, the content reflected centre-right priorities of responsibility, collective security, and alignment with European allies.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds

Threats to Equality and Diversity

Across the political spectrum, social media feeds in Portugal revealed the persistent and widespread circulation of anti-migrant, xenophobic, and exclusionary narratives, albeit with variations in tone, frequency, and framing depending on the political alignment of the profile.

On the radical right, the content was particularly saturated with racist and anti-immigration rhetoric. While overtly anti-LGBTQ+ material appeared less frequently, the dominant narrative centred on

national identity and the portrayal of migrants as threats to the social fabric. Parties such as Chega, despite having parliamentary representation, publicly distanced themselves from accusations of racism or xenophobia. Their leaders instead framed their positions as a defence of ‘the people’ against generic outsiders. Isolated incidents involving migrants (one in particular, reported above) were often used to justify calls for restrictive migration policies and tougher law-and-order measures.

The feeds associated with the red-green profile were neither immune to anti-immigrant content. Despite ideological alignment with inclusivity, these feeds featured videos with xenophobic undertones, including high-profile clips of Chega leader André Ventura criticizing South Asian migrants. This content, framed as commentary on social integration and economic hardship, could alienate migrant communities by suggesting that hard work and contribution do not guarantee acceptance in Portuguese society. Moreover, anti-Muslim rhetoric appeared across all feeds, often depicting visible religious gatherings as threats to European identity. This cross-feed presence of divisive content points to algorithmic amplification of polarizing themes, regardless of user ideology.

The centre-right feed displayed a more moderate version of these narratives. Explicitly discriminatory content was rare, but subtle references to migration and LGBTQ+ issues occasionally appeared, particularly on TikTok, through themes of national cohesion and cultural preservation. Far-right figures like Ventura also made occasional appearances in these feeds, indicating the reach of their discourse beyond the far-right bubble. Instagram, by contrast, featured less political content and fewer polarizing themes overall.

Despite the dominance of negative portrayals, some voices across platforms worked to counter the narrative. Political commentators and social advocates highlighted the valuable contributions of migrant communities, such as paying taxes and sustaining the welfare system. These narratives also called attention to structural inequalities – low wages, poor access to services, and limited mobility – emphasizing the need for stronger support systems and inclusive public policies.

The portrayal of migration and identity on Portuguese social media reflects a contested and polarized media environment. Exclusionary narratives dominate, but counter-discourses persist, striving to reframe public perception and promote a more equitable and inclusive society.

AI Generated Content

AI-generated content appeared with varying frequency and style across the different ideological profiles monitored during the data collection process for the 2024 European Parliament elections in Portugal. Identifying and interpreting this content also depended on the researcher's familiarity with recognising AI-driven formats.

The researcher responsible for the radical right did not distinguish whether the AI-generated content. As a result, it remained unclear whether or not AI played a substantial role in shaping the visual and narrative strategies of the radical right feed. The red-green profile encountered a more distinct presence of what appeared to be AI-generated content, particularly on TikTok and Instagram. These videos typically addressed immigration issues in Portugal and were characterised by trendy music, minimalistic design, and a fast, image-caption format. The production style suggested a strategic use of AI tools to produce content that subtly reinforced negative perceptions of immigration. The simplicity and repetition of these videos show an intent to influence public opinion, capitalising on social media trends and user engagement algorithms. On the centre-right profile, AI-generated content was less frequent but more clearly identifiable when it appeared. It often uses satirical or entertaining videos involving international

42

political figures. A notable example included animated clips of leaders like Joe Biden, Emmanuel Macron, or Vladimir Putin humorously depicted dancing to popular songs. These videos, while light-hearted, reflect an emerging trend of using AI for political parody and infotainment, rather than direct ideological persuasion.

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

While AI-generated content was seen particularly in subtle or humorous formats, it signals a growing role of automated tools in political communication, especially for emotional impact and quick dissemination.

Section 5: Portugal: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores how the features of short social media platforms are offering effective political content. We use research notes and reflections after the data-gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

During observation, TikTok and Instagram demonstrated distinct dynamics in delivering political content shaped by algorithmic behaviour and the research interaction protocol. Initially, political content was sparse on both platforms. TikTok, however, quickly adapted, progressively offering more politically relevant material by the end of the first week. Instagram, in contrast, remained inconsistent, providing political videos primarily when prompted through searches or profile follows. Its feed was often populated with non-political and distracting content, particularly in the early phase.

As the data collection protocol required changes in user interaction midway through the process, such as actively searching for “friends” or keywords, this influenced the type of content presented. Toward the end of the period, both platforms began to reflect more political content, though TikTok maintained a better pace in delivering it organically. This evolution was particularly noticeable in the context of the centre-right profile, where TikTok’s algorithm surfaced centre-right narratives and leaned toward radical right content. Videos featuring figures like André Ventura and Chega supporters frequently reflected ideological overlaps that blurred boundaries between the centre and the radical right. Left-leaning content appeared only rarely, primarily as criticism of right-wing agendas.

When it presented political content, Instagram tended to favour structured and official posts, often shared by party accounts. However, its slower and less consistent delivery reduced the platform’s effectiveness in fostering sustained political engagement. As the European elections approached, political content on TikTok became more frequent and relevant, covering campaign events, debates, and core issues like immigration and economic policy. After the elections, TikTok maintained political content through celebratory or reflective posts, whereas Instagram quickly reverted to general, non-political material, highlighting a weaker political engagement algorithm.

Both platforms showed increased responsiveness to user behaviour, adapting their feeds based on interaction changes. Yet TikTok proved more dynamic and effective in aligning with political themes, albeit at the cost of sometimes amplifying polarising content, particularly from far-right actors. This pattern points to an inherent risk in algorithmic curation: the reinforcement of ideological echo chambers. Despite diverse political profiles, the limited visibility of red-green content underscores a tendency toward ideological alignment, rather than plurality. Platform algorithms shape political discourse; they can be powerful tools for engagement, but they also risk narrowing the spectrum of visible political viewpoints.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

During the observation period, TikTok quickly adapted to the three profile types, offering increasingly frequent political content, especially from the second week onward. While initially focused on

mainstream profile themes, the algorithm often pushed radical-right content, including posts from Chega and André Ventura, in centre-right and red-green profiles, blurring ideological lines and reinforcing polarising narratives. Red-green content was rare and usually critical. In contrast, Instagram delivered political material mainly upon direct user interaction (searches or follows) and featured more structured, official content from party accounts. As the election approached and the profile training intensified, political content became more prominent on both platforms. TikTok maintained engagement even after the vote, while Instagram returned to general content. A shift in user interaction mid-study (as per protocol) revealed that more active engagement helped both platforms tailor feeds more effectively. Overall, TikTok proved more responsive but more prone to reinforcing ideological echo chambers, while Instagram remained slower and more passive in political content delivery.

Emotional mechanisms

Throughout the data collection process, researchers remained largely unaffected on an emotional level, regardless of the emotional appeal of the videos screened. Although some content, particularly around delicate topics such as immigration and political polarisation, was emotionally charged, researchers engaged with it critically and analytically, maintaining a clear focus on the research objectives. Even when exposed to provocative or exclusionary rhetoric, especially from far-right sources, researchers did not experience strong emotional responses such as anxiety or distress. Researchers' detachment allowed them to treat the material almost as if it belonged to a fictional narrative, separate from personal experience or belief. Anxiety was rare and tied to procedural concerns, specifically the concern of fulfilling all the technical requirements of the data collection protocol. This professional distance ensured that researchers' observations remained objective and uninfluenced by the emotional tone or ideological framing of the content reviewed.

Video Typologies

The three researchers of the Portuguese case were exposed to similar typologies of videos. However, different actors have mobilised video typologies differently. The type 'Behind-the-Scenes Clips': several parties reproduced informal moments of candidates preparing for debates or other campaign events, interacting with their teams, or travelling, giving a relatable and humanised perspective. 'Memes and Humour': far-right parties, especially Chega, leaned heavily into humorous content, including memes and ironic commentary on political rivals or policies, tailored for TikTok's casual audience. 'Mainstream Media Excerpts': several parties used heavily edited clips from interviews, podcasts, and televised debates. These excerpts highlighted key statements or controversies, often reframed to align with a particular narrative. 'Cultural References': several parties used videos leveraging Portuguese cultural elements to connect with voters emotionally. 'Infotainment Content': the radical left mainly used a mix of informative and entertaining videos explaining policies or party ideologies in engaging formats, often using animations or infographics. 'Event Recaps': several parties produced summaries of political rallies, public speeches, or significant campaign moments, often condensed into short, shareable clips. 'Provocative Confrontations': clips showing confrontations, such as André Ventura's interactions with migrants or critics, sparked polarised reactions. These videos become viral and are reproduced by parties of opposite political orientation. 'Inspirational Stories': several parties used videos highlighting candidates' journeys or the struggles of their supporters, crafted to evoke empathy and loyalty. 'Parody Content': satirical impersonations or exaggerated depictions of opposing parties or leaders, aiming to discredit rivals through humour. 'Institution from inside-out': the radical right party *Chega* made a video of political leaders walking within the parliament and critically engaging with a polemic issue, showing how they would sort it quickly. 'Policy-focus': the Left Block was particularly keen on proposing that

party leaders explain a specific societal problem and indicate public policies that would sort them out. 'Walk-through-the ordinary': political leaders filmed while visiting daily life settings and facing the general problem of the contacted population. This video typology includes a range of subgroups, and the use by different parties was differentiated. 'Interviews-slices': several parties would cut and circulate part of a journalist's interview with a political leader in the campaign setting, inquiring about the day's hottest issue.

The PCP mainly used the leading party candidate conversing with a reputed scholar or expert.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

While observing political content on social media platforms in the context of the 2024 European elections, several profiles stood out for their unique communication styles and strategic messaging approaches. On the left, some of the most compelling content came from Joana Mortágua (Left Block national MP) and Catarina Martins (MEP candidate), whose short videos condensed complex policy issues into clear, persuasive arguments. Their ability to communicate public policy proposals in a brief and accessible format highlighted a firm grasp of social media dynamics, offering informative and engaging educational and politically impactful content. A specific and particularly interesting video from a Left Block (Bloco de Esquerda) perspective is the one where European Parliament candidate Catarina Martins participates in a debate and responds to journalist José Rodrigues dos Santos, who invokes Venezuelan inflation to discredit the Left Bloc's economic platform.

In stark contrast, though less frequent, radical right content stood out for its provocative tone. The party *Ergue-te (Rise Up)* produced bold, old-style videos characterised by overtly racist and anti-immigration rhetoric. *Chega* also delivered noteworthy content, particularly through parliamentary footage featuring André Ventura, who styled himself as a political outsider challenging the status quo. These videos contributed to a confrontation and rebellion narrative aimed at rallying discontented voters. Among all the entries, the most interesting video is one where André Ventura speaks in the Portuguese parliament, engaging directly with visiting citizens rather than addressing fellow MPs. When interrupted by the President of the Parliament, who reminds him that he must speak to the assembly, Ventura theatrically responds by declaring that he is "in love with the Portuguese people" and laughs, turning the moment into a populist performance.

From a centre-right perspective, the most dynamic and engaging content did not come from the leading Democratic Alliance (AD) and its figurehead Sebastião Bugalho. Instead, *Iniciativa Liberal (Renew Europe)*, led by João Cotrim Figueiredo (MEP candidate), successfully leveraged the informal nature of TikTok to communicate its message. Figueiredo's participation in viral trends and challenge videos allowed the party to deliver political messages in a humorous yet relatable format, significantly increasing its resonance with younger audiences. This youth-centric approach focused on themes such as economic freedom, entrepreneurship, and reduced taxation—issues that connect directly with the aspirations of younger voters. The party's creative use of informal video styles, mock debates, and casual conversations marked a deliberate shift from traditional political communication. Compared to AD's more rigid, conventional messaging, *Iniciativa Liberal's* strategy stood out as a modern, authentic, and platform-savvy form of political engagement. A particularly interesting video featuring Sebastião Bugalho, the leading candidate for the Democratic Alliance (AD-EPP), is the humouristic interview on the TV program "Bom Partido" by comedian Guilherme Geirinhas.

Discussion on the most interesting videos

Political parties used different videos for seemingly similar purposes. However, the nature of the political appeal they aimed to motivate provides a more nuanced understanding of their differences. For example, the Liberal Initiative and the Left Block aimed to appeal to supposedly intelligent (and young) people, who were confronted with the campaign of traditional parties such as the centre-right (PSD) and the centre-left (PS). These 'traditional' parties, including also the Communist Party (PCP) together with PS and PSD, used more obsolete communication formats that were less directed towards providing a different kind of content (appropriate for social media) and more replication and systematisation of information circulating in mainstream communication channels (such as TV and radio). The radical right parties appealed to a sense of ownership and anti-systemic politics, in contrast to the institutional politics they essentially wanted to oppose. They claim the common-sense interest of the electorate, generally understood as a homogeneous majority population disillusioned with the institutions supposed to represent it. While Ergue-te would directly mobilise harsh nationalist rhetoric and Nova Direita would argue for the need for a (radical) right-wing policy, Chega would mobilise its advanced communication skills to offer a diversified type of content, with the party leader in the institutions (but against them) and in the people (and against migrants). The involvement of qualified professionals by the political parties and the corresponding budgetary investments were certainly different. However, it seems that the radical right parties, especially Chega, could benefit from a more active network of sympathisers producing their videos. Some of these were interesting in originality, but the majority were cheaper, consisting of parody or simple commentary, often irritated by specific events.

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion based on the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place, as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

What was Europe about, and why vote (the Social Contract)?

The 2024 European Parliament election campaign in Portugal was predominantly shaped by national concerns, with European issues playing a marginal role across the political spectrum. This trend was evident in the communication strategies of parties on both the left, the centre and the right, suggesting a broader disconnection between domestic politics and European policymaking. The low voter turnout reinforced this perception of disaffection, underscoring the limited public engagement with EU-level politics.

Despite the EU's minor presence in campaign narratives, Portuguese political parties generally maintain a pro-European stance. This is largely tied to the country's historical trajectory. Portugal joined the EU (then the European Economic Community) in 1986, just 12 years after the Carnation Revolution ended decades of authoritarian rule. EU accession has since been widely perceived as part of the country's democratic consolidation and a key factor in its economic modernisation. Particularly for a nation that experienced widespread poverty until the 1970s, EU membership symbolised political alignment with Western Europe and access to vital development funds and structural reforms. As a result, overt Euroscepticism remains uncommon among mainstream parties.

An exception is the Portuguese Communist Party (PCP), the oldest party in the country, founded in 1921. While not anti-European in a populist or nationalist sense, the PCP holds a critical stance towards the EU, viewing it as a neoliberal structure that perpetuates capitalist and class-based inequalities. However, even the PCP's campaign largely centred on national social and economic issues rather than directly confronting EU integration.

The Left Block (BE) also adopted a critical but fundamentally pro-European position. Its messaging focused on defending public services, workers' rights, and social equality within the European framework, often using national case studies to illustrate broader European trends. While EU policies were not the primary focus, BE used the campaign to highlight how Brussels' decisions impact domestic realities.

On the centre-right, the Democratic Alliance (AD) and the Liberal Initiative (IL) framed their campaigns around themes of economic stability, institutional credibility, and competent national leadership. Their content largely avoided specific EU debates, instead showcasing figures like Prime Minister Luís Montenegro and AD's lead candidate Sebastião Bugalho. IL, in particular, used dynamic and youth-oriented social media strategies to promote economic liberalism and entrepreneurship, which were again rooted in domestic contexts but aligned with broader EU values. Both parties reflected the mainstream Portuguese consensus that sees EU membership as beneficial, yet they rarely advanced concrete European policy proposals.

In contrast, far-right parties like Chega and Ergue-te concentrated their efforts on polemical domestic issues, particularly around immigration and national identity. Their campaign rhetoric was primarily cultural, rather than economic, and focused on reinforcing in-group narratives rather than addressing

Funded by
the European Union

EU policies. European themes appeared only insofar as they could be linked to domestic grievances, suggesting a use of the election to build national support rather than engage in European-level policymaking.

Overall, the Portuguese EP24 campaign illustrates how national narratives continue to dominate electoral discourse, even in contests ostensibly focused on the European Union.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

Populist mobilisation during the 2024 European Parliament elections in Portugal showed how political actors constructed the political “us” versus “them.” Most notably, Chega (Enough) stood out as the primary populist actor, leveraging a strong “us, the real people” narrative against a broad “them” composed of elites, migrants, the EU bureaucracy, and national media. Chega’s communication drew heavily on affective rhetoric, particularly anger, outrage, and nationalist pride. Its leader, André Ventura, framed the party as the sole defender of ordinary Portuguese citizens and national sovereignty, often portraying Europe as a distant and technocratic entity out of touch with domestic concerns. This positioned Chega as a paradigmatic case of Euroscepticism, though with strategic instrumental support for specific EU mechanisms, especially those that could be reframed as defending Portuguese borders or “traditional values.”

The Socialist Party (PS), the Social-Democratic Party (PSD) and the Liberal Initiative (IL) held a Europhilic position. These parties showed the EU as a developmental partner, integral to Portugal’s economic stability and democratic consolidation. Their “us” narrative about Europe, which is not so present, is aligned with a vision of modern, progressive, and cooperative Portugal embedded in the European project. Emotional appeals in this camp focused more on hope, pragmatism, and responsibility, promoting a professionalised and institutional image of politics. However, emotional intensity was lower, which may have limited their resonance among younger or disillusioned voters.

A critical European position was adopted by parties like the Left Block (BE) and the Portuguese Communist Party (PCP). They acknowledged the EU’s structural role in Portugal’s trajectory while denouncing its neoliberal economic model, democratic deficits, and migration policies. Their construction of the political “us” was rooted in solidarity, workers’ rights, and resistance to austerity. Emotions evoked included frustration, mobilisation and solidarity, often appealing to social justice and anti-elite sentiment, but not in a nationalist frame.

Conclusion

The growing influence of non-European actors in spreading misinformation and polarising narratives seriously threatens democratic integrity across the EU. To safeguard electoral processes and public discourse, the EU must enhance its ‘European democracy shield’ through a series of coordinated and forward-looking measures.

First, transparency must be a cornerstone of digital political communication. The EU should enforce stricter requirements for online political advertising, including mandatory disclosure of funding sources and sponsorships. This will help identify and prevent foreign interference in European democratic

processes. Alongside regulatory measures, empowering citizens through comprehensive digital literacy campaigns, especially targeting younger demographics, will bolster society's resilience against disinformation and manipulative content.

Second, enhanced monitoring systems are essential. Investment in advanced AI-driven tools can support the detection and mitigation of coordinated disinformation campaigns, whether foreign or domestic. However, such systems must be carefully designed to uphold the right to freedom of expression and avoid arbitrary censorship.

Major online platforms – designated as Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) – like TikTok and Instagram, play a critical role in shaping political discourse. Given their immense reach and influence, regulatory oversight must be reinforced. Algorithmic accountability is vital; platforms should be required to disclose how their content recommendation systems work and implement measures to prevent the amplification of extremist or misleading content. Independent EU-regulated oversight bodies should audit these platforms to ensure democratic principles and fairness are upheld. Additionally, the EU should encourage a more diverse digital ecosystem by supporting alternative platforms that prioritise ethical engagement and user-centred models.

Political content regulation must also be strengthened. VLOPs should be required to comply with EU election laws and take proactive steps to prevent the spread of harmful or deceptive political content. Regulation must be tailored to the evolving nature of digital media without stifling legitimate discourse.

Beyond regulation, fostering meaningful citizen engagement on social media is key. Political actors should adopt participatory communication models, using tools like live sessions and interactive policy discussions to build trust and inclusion. At the same time, emotionally compelling narratives – rooted in fact – can be used responsibly to connect with citizens and make complex policy issues more relatable. This approach must avoid manipulation while promoting authenticity and transparency.

To mitigate algorithmic bias and echo chambers, platforms must ensure that diverse viewpoints are represented in users' feeds, broadening the scope of civic discourse. Finally, governments and civic organisations should take an active role in disseminating reliable, accessible, and fact-based information across social media, providing essential context to counter misinformation and reinforce democratic debate.

Together, these measures can enhance the EU's democratic resilience, ensuring that digital spaces serve as arenas for informed, inclusive, and transparent political engagement.

Bibliography

Alves, H. C., & Queirós, J. (2024). Social media and the rise of radical right populism in Portugal. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03224-w>

Silva, M., & Mendes, M. S. (2023). From emotion to virality: The use of social media in the populism of Chega and VOX. *Social Sciences*, 14(5), 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci14050255>

Canavilhas, J., & Santos, S. (2024). It glitters, but is it gold? Negative campaigning on social media in Portugal. *The International Journal of Press/Politics*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20570473251323766>

50

Funded by
the European Union

Santos, M. L., & Fonseca, R. (2017). Where's populism? Online media and the diffusion of populist discourses and styles in Portugal. *Acta Politica*, 52(4), 516–535. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41304-017-0137-4>

Mourão, R. R., & Magalhães, J. (2020). Populism by the people: An analysis of online comments in Portugal and Spain. *Proceedings of the 11th ACM Conference on Web Science*, 281–289. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3400806.3400831>

COntinuous COnstruction of resilient social COntracts through societal transformations

WP4 Country report:

EP Election Results Sweden

Dissemination Level:	Public
Work Package:	WP4
Document ID:	
Delivery Date:	30 May 2025
Type:	
Version:	1.0
Author(s):	Annika Teppo, and Mats Hyvönen, Uppsala University; Viljami Vaarala, University of Helsinki
Editors	Alexander Alekseev, Szilvia Horváth, Emilia Palonen, University of Helsinki
Reviewer(s):	Tuğçe Erçetin, Istanbul Bilgi University

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Section 1: Sweden: EP Election Results	4
# National Election Results and Party.....	5
Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties	6
Section 2: Sweden: Political profiles	9
# Centre-Right Feed.....	10
# Far-Right Feed	14
# Red-Green Feed	17
# Visibility of Parties and Political Actors	21
Section 3: Sweden: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles.....	24
# Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles	24
# Notes on the organic profiles	25
# Differences Observed Over Time	28
# Differences between Instagram vs TikTok.....	32
# Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram	32
Section 4: Sweden: Data Gathering – Thematic Content	33
# Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram	33
# Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram.....	34
# Content Related to Foreign Countries	35
# Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts	36
# Threats to Equality and Diversity	37
# AI Generated Content	38
Section 5: Sweden: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal.....	40
# Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time.....	40
# Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate.....	40
# Emotional mechanisms	41
# Video Typologies.....	42
# Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics	42
# Discussion on most interesting videos	45
Concluding section.....	46
# What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?	46
# Populist mobilisation	47
# Conclusion	48
Bibliography	50

Sweden: EP Data Gathering Exercise 2024

Abstract

Prior to the 2024 European Parliament election, according to Swedish television's polls, the issues of peace, democracy, climate, and crime were the main concerns of the electorate. The issues of equality and social welfare were less interesting, even when they are causing multiple problems in Sweden today.

This election was the most successful for the Green Party, now Sweden's third biggest party after the Social Democrats (S) and the Moderate Party (M or Moderaterna). This was also the first time that the populist far-right Sweden Democrats (Sverigedemokraterna or SD) lost support. Their message, blaming the immigrants for Sweden's problems, did not draw in as many votes as in the previous European Parliament elections.

After the elections, local commentators suspected that this would not be a permanent trend or any kind of turning point in Swedish politics. However, according to the Swedish national public television broadcaster *Sveriges television* (SVT) polls in September 2024 and in May 2025, the increase in popularity of the red-green opposition parties seems to be continuing. The decrease in support for the SD has continued ever since, as indicated in the election barometer. (SVT 2024, 2025)

Our three-person team carried out data gathering, which included interacting with the feed, in other words: when working with the videos, we could like or follow them, but we were not supposed to comment on them. We were immersed in this task for four weeks around the European Parliament election in May-June 2024.

Abstract in national language(s)

Section 1: Sweden: EP Election Results

The first section discusses the election results overall. The researchers reflect on both the actual election outcome and the insights from the data gathering. The visualisations from our dataset demonstrate the three politically profiled synthetic accounts' aggregate visibility of different parties in the whole period of the data gathering.

The election was won by the Social Democrats (Socialdemokraterna, S), followed by the Moderates (Moderaterna, M), the Green Party (Miljöpartiet, MP), and the Left Party (Vänsterpartiet, V). Both the Centre party (Centerpartiet, C) and the Christian Democrats (Kristdemokraterna, KD) lost some following. Of all parties, the biggest additional growth in 2024 was gained by the Left Party which got 11.06% of the votes with a growth of 4.1% of the votes, and 1 additional seat (2 now). Another successful party was the Green Party who kept its 3 seats but gained more votes. The Social Democrats kept their 5 seats, and the Moderates kept their 4 seats out of the 21 seats held by Sweden. The Sweden Democrats lost votes but kept their mandate of 2 MEPs. The Centre Party kept their 2 seats, the Liberals kept their 1 seat, while the Christian Democrats lost 1 of their 2 mandates.

Election participation decreased from 55.3% to 53.4%. All candidates were elected from the predetermined party lists. The most popular candidate was Jonas Sjöstedt, a new candidate from the Left party, however, a veteran politician. Alice Bah Kuhnke from the Green Party was again second (as in 2019), and the third was Thomas Tobé of the Moderates (winner of the 2019 EU elections).

In comparison with the rest of the EU, both the Left and the Greens were more victorious in Sweden.

National Election Results and Party

16/07/2024 - 09:44

All times are GMT+2

Results by national party - 2024-2029

Sweden - Official results

Figure 1.
Results by
national party

Percentage of votes

National Parties

S - Socialdemokraterna
M - Moderaterna
MP - Miljöpartiet de gröna
SD - Sverigedemokraterna
V - Vänsterpartiet

C - Centerpartiet
KD - Kristdemokraterna
L - Liberalerna
Other parties - Other parties

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

There were two most unexpected turns of events in the 2024 European Parliament elections:

One of the most infamous events just prior to the election, which had a tremendous impact on the tone and debate of the whole, was the exposure of so-called troll factories of the Sweden Democrats (TV4, 2024), which they had been running on party subsidies. According to many analysts, this was one of the main reasons for the unexpected decrease in their votes.

Another highlight was the good result of the Green Party (MP) and the Left Party (V). Their success was largely due to that of their top candidates, Alice Bah Kuhnke's (MP) and Sjöstedt's (V) successful campaigns leading to landslide victories.

Figure 2: Distribution of political actors seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Sweden

Top MEPs & Major Developments within Parties

The primary interest of the political commentators, and the public during these elections, was directed at the campaign of the Sweden Democrats (SD) and the overall success of the far-right parties in Europe. For SD, while they managed to keep their three seats, the election was a disappointment. Despite being the second-largest party in the national parliament, they secured only 13.2% of the vote in these elections, 2% less than in 2019. Significantly, the party lost ground in elections for the first time since entering the Swedish parliament in 2010. Despite SD retaining its three MEPs, expectations were higher given that the party also sought to reflect its status as Sweden's second-largest party in the European Parliament. In the post-election search for a culprit, some in-party criticism was levelled at top candidate Charlie Weimers for running a “weak” campaign.

The election was mildly disappointing for the center-right governmental parties, which were the Moderate Party, the Centre Party, the Liberals, and the Christian Democrats. The Moderates kept their four seats, the Centre Party kept their two seats, the Liberals kept their only seat, but the Christian Democrats lost their other seat. Tomas Tobé from the Moderate Party gained the most votes from the center-right parties but lost the 2019 title of the top vote-puller by being the third most popular candidate in Sweden. Other popular candidates from center-right parties were Alice Teodorescu of the Christian Democrats and Emma Wiesner from the Centre Party.

In contradiction to these, the left-green axis consisting of the Social Democrats (five seats), the Green Party (three seats) and the Left Party (two seats) gained more votes, keeping their seats, and the Left Party gained a second seat. These results were mainly due to the popularity of their top candidates. The most popular candidates were Alice Bah Kuhnke (the Green Party), and Jonas Sjöstedt (the Left Party), whose successful campaigns led to landslide victories. The Green party also had several much-publicized candidates such as Pär Holmgren and Isabella Lövin. The Social Democrats also had candidates who were not seen as winners by the Swedish press, such as Heléne Fritzon, who made it through anyway. It might be a coincidence that she was also among the few Social Democrat candidates relatively visible on social media.

Interestingly, Carl Bildt, the former Moderate leader and prime minister, congratulated Jonas Sjöstedt of the Left Party, publicly complementing his campaign in an exceptional gesture (Aftonbladet TV, 2024). The comment was Bildt's stance towards increasing populism in Swedish politics, as Jonas Sjöstedt's campaign was informative and not populist. The statement must be seen against the background of the Sweden Democrats's extensive troll factories, which were revealed just weeks before the election to a big national uproar. Bildt's comment was thus also a senior statesman's moral statement on Swedish politics. However, a year after the election, in May 2025, it was published in Swedish media that these troll factories were still working (Expressen, 2025).

Breakdown of national parties and political groups – 2024-2029

Sweden – Constitutive session

Figure 3. Breakdown of national parties and political groups

National Parties	Votes	EPP	S&D	PfE	ECR	Renew Europe	Greens/EFA	The Left	ESN	NI	Seats
S	24.77%		5								5
M	17.53%	4									4
MP	13.85%						3				3
SD	13.17%				3						3
V	11.06%							2			2
C	7.29%					2					2
KD	5.71%	1									1
L	4.38%					1					1
Other parties	2.24%										0
	100.00%	5	5	0	3	3	3	2	0	0	21

S > S&D: JOHAN DANIELSSON, ADNAN DIBRANI, SOFIE ERIKSSON, HELÉNE FRITZON, EVIN INCIR

M > EPP: ARBA KOKALARI, JESSICA POLFJÄRD, TOMAS TOBÉ, JÖRGEN WARBORN

MP > Greens/EFA: PÅR HOLMGREN, ALICE KUHNKE, ISABELLA LÖVIN

SD > ECR: DICK ERIXON, BEATRICE TIMGREN, CHARLIE WEIMERS

C > Renew Europe: ABIR AL-SAHLANI, EMMA WIESNER

V > The Left: HANNA GEDIN, JONAS SJÖSTEDT

L > Renew Europe: KARIN KARLSBRO

KD > EPP: ALICE TEODORESCU MĂWE

National Parties

- S – Socialdemokraterna
- M – Moderaterna
- MP – Miljöpartiet de gröna
- SD – Sverigedemokraterna
- V – Vänsterpartiet
- C – Centerpartiet
- KD – Kristdemokraterna
- L – Liberalerna
- Other parties – Other parties

Political groups in the European Parliament

- EPP – Group of the European People’s Party (Christian Democrats)
- S&D – Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament
- PfE – Patriots for Europe
- ECR – European Conservatives and Reformists Group
- Renew Europe – Renew Europe Group
- Greens/EFA – Group of the Greens/European Free Alliance
- The Left – The Left group in the European Parliament – GUE/NGL
- ESN – Europe of Sovereign Nations
- NI – Non-attached Members

According to Parliament’s rules of procedure, a political group shall consist of at least 23 Members elected in at least seven Member States.

Source: Provided by Verian for the European Parliament

Section 2: Sweden: Political profiles

This section discusses the overall differences between the feeds of the synthetic political profiles that the researchers were using and developing. The point is to offer a comparative overview.

Figure 4a: Visibility of political parties by political profile on TikTok in more than one mention

Looking at the graph from left, in the Centre-Right profile, the far-right Sweden Democrats were highly present, leaving the Moderate party in the second place. Even material from the Social Democratic Party and the Left was visible and received some mentions. The smaller Centre parties were also visible, but the liberals were even less visible than the Social Democrats. There was also more international content than in the other feeds.

The Left-Green feed showed most material from the Social Democrats. The second closest was the Left Party, which is a smaller party than the Social Democrats, but managed to be well represented. Also, other parties, even from the far-right and center-right were represented in this feed. Considering their success in the elections, it is surprising that the Green Party was only third, as it was generally well-represented on social media.

The Sweden Democrats (SD) completely dominated the Radical Right TikTok feed, but their material was most prevalent in the Centre Right feed and even appeared in the Left-Green feed. In the Radical Right feed, there were only a few mentions of two other parties, and no mentions of Centre or Left parties.

Figure 4b: Visibility of political parties by political profile on Instagram

On Instagram, there are clear similarities with the TikTok results. Reading figures from the left: the Centre-Right profiles were again penetrated by content affiliated with Sweden Democrats, followed by the Moderate Party, and again by the Social Democrats. Other parties were mentioned as well, albeit much less than these three. Interestingly, the Centre Right Instagram feed again showed some content outside of Sweden and the EU, making the feed more international than in the other profiles. The difference in the presence of international content between the profiles was also higher on Instagram than on TikTok.

The biggest difference between TikTok and Instagram is found in the Left-Green profile, where the Green Party dominates the Instagram mentions, followed by the Social Democrats. The Left Party has received many fewer mentions on Instagram than on TikTok. The other parties are mentioned in this profile as well.

The Radical Right profile was, again, dominated by the Sweden Democrats. The Moderate Party, is getting more visibility on Instagram than on TikTok, but the general picture remains that of the Sweden Democrats' domination.

Centre-Right Feed

The synthetic profile focusing on center-right parties, namely the Moderate Party, Christian Democrats, The Liberals and The Centre Party, showed unexpectedly a lot of content from other parties. The content by the Sweden Democrats and other affiliated accounts infiltrated the center-right feeds, especially on TikTok. Apart from that, the most prominent content was from the Moderate Party. One central reason for this is the fact that the party leader, Ulf Kristersson, was also the prime minister of Sweden.

Figure 5: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

Figure 6: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 7: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 8: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

12

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 9: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

The coherence of the feeds was highly dependent on the social media platform. TikTok offered content that was mostly associated with official political parties. The content changed and aligned quite aggressively with content that had been watched most recently, such as interviews by news media outlets with top candidates and party leaders. Conversely, the feed was very incoherent on Instagram, and it took rather long for political content to occur. For instance, during the first few days, the content mainly was entertainment with dance videos of young, scantily clad women.

After this, the Instagram feed started to show only a few political videos daily (between one and three videos). These were aligned only occasionally to the center-right profile, as there was mostly content by the Sweden Democrats and Social Democrats. The other videos were mostly lifestyle or humor-related. During the last few days of data gathering, the content on Instagram started to pivot towards US-originating conspiracy theories, with political figures like Joe Rogan and Elon Musk regularly appearing in the content.

It could be concluded that most of the relevant content relating to established Swedish politics was seen on TikTok, and all other centre and center-right parties apart from the Moderate Party (and the far-right Sweden Democrats) were mainly prominent on TikTok.

The center-right feeds were mixed with themes on voting *for* the EU policies and voting *against* the EU policies. The arguments framing the EU as a positive asset related to national security, where the EU was seen as a resource for wider European defense against external threats. Moreover, the Sweden Democrat troll factory occurred as a prominent topic, questioning the legitimacy of the party and calling citizens to vote *for* democratic Europe by not voting for the Sweden Democrats.

The most prominent themes were related to immigration and religion through negative content on gang crimes and the Islamization in Sweden, endorsed almost solely by accounts affiliated with the Sweden

Democrats. The Moderates also channeled some criticism of the EU by emphasizing national sovereignty in deciding over national matters, such as the snuff sales and land use.

Far-Right Feed

Figure 10: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

The parliamentary far right in Sweden in 2024 consisted entirely of the Sweden Democrats (SD). While the SD was represented in parliament, it was not in the sitting government. However, due to a pact (so called *Tidöavtal*) uniting the right-wing and central parties, SD had a lot of influence on governmental matters. Although the policies of several right-wing parties overlap with those of the Sweden Democrats in quite a few areas, the SD occupied a unique position on the far right of the political scale. It was therefore not surprising that the SD almost completely dominated the political content of this synthetic profile's accounts, especially on TikTok.

Figure 11: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Figure 12: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 13: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 14: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

From its distinct position on the Swedish political spectrum, the party and its supporting accounts concentrated heavily on immigration, which is also evident in Figures 12, 13, and 14. Immigration was also a topic for the other parties in the present right-wing government, which in accordance with the

2022 Tidö Agreement (*Tidöavtalet*), cooperated with SD. However, the Sweden Democrats define themselves most prominently through a strong anti-immigration and anti-Islam stance.

However, the picture was more nuanced when it came to the accounts that recurred the most during the period of data gathering. Although many of their posts came from the party's official accounts, and those of leading politicians (especially party leader Jimmie Åkesson) as well as some lower-ranking candidates (such as Rebecka Rapp in 27th place on the SD list of candidates), there were other, informally affiliated accounts which were very active. Among these, the accounts '*riks*', '*jimmie moments*' and '*sdmicke*' recurred frequently throughout most of the data collection.

Common to all these accounts was a strong prevalence of negative campaigning, focusing on pointing out what other parties had failed to do in the past, particularly on immigration and crime policy (see Figures 12, 13, and 14). Furthermore, all these accounts maintained a rather aggressive tone (by Swedish standards), which many in the post-election analysis said contributed to the election result not being the success many had expected it to be. It seems that the aggressive, negative campaigning of the SD and SD-supporting accounts exceeded what is usually perceived as a reasonable tone (*tonläge*) in Swedish politics. Strengthened by the political successes of the last few years, SD seems to have concluded that in the run-up to the EU elections, it could employ tougher rhetoric than before on what it repeatedly portrayed as a completely failed migration and crime policy.

Red-Green Feed

Figure 15: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram

The three main parties on this profile were the Social Democrats, the Green Party (an openly left-wing party in Sweden), and the Left Party. As also evident in Figures 17, 18, and 19, these parties were generally focused on social issues (such as the welfare state), economy (such as taxation and unemployment), environment, and activating their supporters to vote. From these parties there was no

material that is covered in Figure 19, which could be interpreted as racist, anti-migrant, or misogynist. Any content of that nature came from far-right videos that occasionally appeared on the feed.

The Green Party was the most memorable content producer in these profiles. The most prevalent character was their absolute vote queen, Alice Bah Kuhnke, the ever-so-perky MEP, who produced content almost every day. A lot of it was, understandably, connected with environmental issues, but also more down-to-earth, everyday issues such as sustainable fashion. Her fame originated from childhood when she was a member of the Mickey Mouse Club of Sweden, and she was, in fact, the best performer of all the politicians, always on, always sharp. It seems that for young voters, she represented both a safe and secure society, continuity of the Welfare state, as well as important environmental matters. Other well-known Green Party candidates were meteorologist Pär Holmgren and Isabella Lövin, who had also previously received a lot of publicity.

Another memorable top candidate was Jonas Sjöstedt from the Left Party, a veteran politician who now received a new mandate as an MEP. Sjöstedt was most interested in social and economic justice questions, thus following the Swedish “Folkhemmet” (the home of the people) tradition but offering a more left alternative for those who felt that the Social Democrats had lost their edge. His approach was human-centered, focused on solving social issues, showing a lot of interest in the troubles of the working-class Swedes. The Left Party also won a historical second seat in this election and was congratulated by the former prime minister Carl Bildt (Moderate) as they had run a clean and factual campaign (Aftonbladet, 2024). This shows a resistance against populism throughout the political spectrum

Figure 16: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups in TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 17: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Broad Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 18: Top Themes visible on TikTok and Instagram (Detailed Categories)

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 19: Type of political content shown in the feeds of TikTok and Instagram

Regardless of their different parties, both Carl Bildt (who was not a candidate) and Left Party MEP Jonas Sjöstedt clearly represented security, *trygghet*, for the Swedish voters. This point came up constantly in the commentary of TikTok and Instagram feeds. The theme of *trygghet* also surfaced in the feeds of the Social Democrats, who have been emblematic of the Swedish political scene for decades, even with the recent successes of the right-wing parties. While the Left Party and the Greens' social media campaigns were much driven by their top candidates, the Social Democrats were focusing on their party leader Magdalena Andersson, who was their most prominent person on social media. For a lot of Swedes, she represents security and continuity of the Social Democratic "folkhemmet". In her entries, she consistently emphasized the Swedish tradition of the social welfare state. She personifies the appreciation of the established cultural codes of discussion, meeting each other halfway as equals around a round table, and trying to find a negotiated solution instead of going to political extremes. Magdalena Andersson's popularity might have depended on her short stint as the former Prime Minister.

The Social Democrats aimed to and did run a clean campaign. When the election day approached, their tone hardened against their political opponents. They did, for example, regularly mention the SD-funded troll factories. There were also several concerns about the state of democracy in Sweden, as well as in the whole of the EU. All the left-green parties had active youth organizations and other followers, who campaigned on social media, urging their young followers to vote. There was a clear age difference, with the emphasis on the younger activists producing a lot of content. The older establishment of the Social Democrats was more focused on Instagram posts and stories, while the younger party activists would also produce TikTok content.

Visibility of Parties and Political Actors

Figure 20a: Visibility of Political Actors on TikTok in Sweden

Reading from the left: The presence of the party leader for the far-right Sweden Democrats in the centre-right feed was significant, leaving the prime minister of the Moderate party in second place. After the party leaders, the most perceptible politicians on TikTok were the top candidate Tomas Tobé (M) and candidate Maria Rosander (SD). The list confirms that TikTok was able to show mainly Swedish candidates, with the only international politician being the Irish MEP Claire Daly.

In the left-green profiles, the trend with the party leaders continues. Most visible was the former Swedish Prime Minister Magdalena Andersson, the chairperson of the Social Democrats. In the second place was Jonas Sjöstedt, who was an extremely popular candidate of the Left Party. Only after him in third place was the Left Party chairperson Nooshi Dadgostar. The popular Green Party politician Alice Bah Kuhnke was only the sixth on TikTok. Interestingly, the Irish MEP Claire Daly was in fourth place, which is remarkable as no other non-Swedish candidates have been so prevalent in this profile. There was thus less content on international political actors, except for Palestine-related content, which would have filled the feeds if this were allowed.

On the radical right TikTok profiles, the party leader trend continues. There are also fewer names than in other parties. Interestingly, Jimmie Åkesson and Charlie Weimers appeared to switch places between Instagram and TikTok. Åkesson had a stronger presence on TikTok, while Weimers was more prominent on Instagram. This difference may reflect the party's strategic use of each platform: Instagram seems to serve as a more formal channel for campaigning, whereas TikTok is used in a more informal and experimental way. Weimers' visibility on Instagram may also be explained by his role as the party's main candidate, making him more central to the official election campaign. Overall, the party's formal campaign efforts still appeared to lean more heavily on established, widely recognized platforms rather than on newer ones with a narrower and younger audience.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Country codes are two-letter ISO

Figure 20b: Visibility of Political Actors on Instagram in Sweden

The trend of the party leaders being the most visible political actors in the time preceding and after the EU election of 2024 continues on Instagram. Again, the party leaders of the Sweden Democrats and the Moderates were visible.

At this point, the feeds of the center-right synthetic profiles both on TikTok and Instagram could be confirmed as having been highly penetrated by content relating to both the Sweden Democrats and especially its party leader, Jimmie Åkesson. However, the Instagram feed stood out with a higher number of international politicians, like Joe Biden and Vladimir Putin, but also populist politicians, like Nigel Farage, Donald Trump, and Giorgia Meloni. This emphasizes the difference between Instagram and TikTok where the latter played a more important role in channeling political matters relating to the local Swedish context. Nationally significant matters were often mediated through SD leader Åkesson (e.g., street gangs, immigration) and the Moderate prime minister/party leader Kristersson (e.g., defending the right to sell white snuff in Sweden; importance of the EU for Swedish national defense).

In the left-green feed on Instagram, the party leader of the Social Democrats was again the most visible character. Here, however, we can see a difference from TikTok. Alice Bah Kuhnke, who was sixth in TikTok mentions, is in second place on Instagram. The Green Party leader, Isabella Lövin, is only sixth. Jonas Sjöstedt of the Left party is the third, which shows his visibility on both platforms.

As mentioned above in connection with Figure 20a, it is interesting that the party leader Jimmie Åkesson and MEP candidate Charlie Weimers appeared to switch placements between Instagram and TikTok, which may have to do with the nature of the various platforms as more or less official channels for the party's political campaigning.

One of the interesting things is that the party leaders seem to be more prominent in these feeds than the EU candidates. This seems to be a trend, although we were three different people working on these feeds, which means that we trained our feeds differently.

Section 3: Sweden: Developing the Feed across Platforms and Profiles

This section explores the development of the feed for different profiles. The political profiles were supposed to build as quickly as possible a feed that would be of red-green, center-right or far-right orientation, while the organic feed was more of a control mechanism for seeing what is out there or watching something of the researcher's own choice. The differences between the platforms over time are also discussed. The researchers discuss the differences between the feeds and the development of the feed over time. Graphs indicate transformations to the synthetic accounts' content, while also mentioning the activity of the organic profiles.

All the researchers experienced that it was hard to receive political content on Instagram (max 1-3 videos daily). Coincidentally, every researcher's previous interaction with short-form content has been very limited on Instagram, and TikTok was a completely new platform for all.

All the synthetic accounts needed constant training to not become filled with only entertainment videos: cat videos, dance videos, and other non-political stuff. Since the synthetic accounts were defined as more determined to look content on the European election, and defined political direction for each researcher, there was more political content on them.

The organic accounts were allowed to flow more freely, and we could thus be less consistent with the synthetic (political) accounts. However, free flow often led to researchers receiving only entertainment content. Consequently, there was a need to train the organic accounts more, and that is where there was more individual variation. It is very important to note that on some days we trained them more than on others, depending on the data available, and one data gatherer did not train their organic account at all, letting it flow completely freely.

TikTok was generally easier to train than Instagram to show any political content that we were looking for. This does not even mean specifically party political or European election-related content, but that if we had not aggressively looked for the political content on Instagram, there would have been none, which could be frustrating. Also, the TikTok feed turned very easily towards entertainment.

Political Content on Organic and Synthetic Profiles

The organic profiles of the researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic profile were at first dominated by non-political content, although the political content gradually increased over time. The synthetic profiles were quickly filled with Sweden Democrat content, depending on which posts and accounts the researcher liked and followed. On TikTok in particular, the feed was filled with both Sweden Democrat messages, but also other posts and accounts critical of immigration. After the first week, other European far-right accounts started to reappear, such as Alternative for Germany (AfD) and the AfD-positive accounts from Germany and supporters of Nigel Farage in the UK.

The free-flowing organic profile of the researcher dealing with the center-right synthetic profile on Instagram remained highly unpolitical throughout the data-gathering period. The organic profile on TikTok offered more political content, but it rarely related to Swedish politics. Instead, the content was

about the war in Ukraine and the conflict in Gaza. For the centre-right synthetic profile, the content was more related to national and established Swedish politics on TikTok but less so on Instagram. As mentioned above, it was challenging to receive political content on Instagram (max 1-3 videos daily). In the end of the data gathering period, the content was more about conspiracy theories.

Getting the feed to produce political content on TikTok was easier than on Instagram with both the organic and synthetic profiles of the researcher responsible for the red-green synthetic profile. With a lot of training, the synthetic TikTok profile was producing almost exactly the type of red-green content that the synthetic profile owner insisted on: this was much harder to achieve on the Instagram accounts. With the organic profile, there was more variety, as the researcher was browsing more freely around the political field, although consciously avoiding the far-right sites. Regardless of these attempts, the far-right content tended to pop up, and no matter of training kept them away completely. In both the organic and synthetic TikTok profiles, the content was habitually led to other MEPs election feeds, especially that of Irish leftist Claire Daly (who could not renew her mandate despite what was apparently a very social media-savvy campaign).

Notes on the organic profiles

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 21a: Number of mentions of political parties in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

To examine the progression of the elections in social media we draw from Figure 21a above. For a more detailed comparison, the team chose three days in the gathered data – these were also days when everyone in the team had been commenting on what they saw. Day 10 (29.5) was seen as the beginning of the most fervent social media activity, while day 20 (8.6) was guaranteed to be interesting, as this was the eve of the election day (21), and day 25 (12.6), which was four days after the election, to examine the aftermath.

During the data gathering, the researchers applied different strategies. In the organic profile, the researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic profile followed the content that genuinely interested them. The only orientation that would differ from their usual usage of social media was that they actively sought out political content, following how differently the various parties related to social media and TikTok in particular. The difference was apparent between the parties that appeared more professional and aware of the specific characteristics of the media (The Green Party and The Left Party) and those that did not. Throughout the entire period under review, a broad range of political parties, their representatives, and various election-related topics appeared in the organic profile feed. Notable peaks in activity occurred toward the end of May and again in early June, on the eve of the election. These surges may also have mirrored the timing of opinion polls published during those periods, which may have intensified public interest and media attention.

The researcher responsible for the red-green profile also followed in the organic profile things that interested them, expanding their interests from the synthetic red-green, very politically oriented profile, even towards other parties. They also followed quite a few political commentators and even political entertainment, which is very popular in Sweden, and there are quite a few programs dedicated to this genre. In these videos, the parties and the coming election were topics often handled with the means of satire, which pulled no punches. These were irreplaceable both from the point of view of information, as well as providing new perspectives. Also, videos with content on Gaza and Ukraine often popped up. The temporal progression reflected the closeness to the election: in Figure 21a, there is more activity on the days just before the election (days 20 and 21 in the figure). This was not caused by a more diverse political landscape as much as all the candidates, supporters and political commentators' intensified activities being at peak. In the days after the election, there was also more activity, not because of the parties' efforts, which had pretty much ended at the election, but because the researcher was following in the organic profiles throughout the political spectrum, examining how the different parties reacted to the election results.

The use of the organic profiles of the researcher responsible for the center-right profile was highly algorithm-driven, and the profiles were not trained actively. In other words, the research did not try to affect the feed too much by focusing on certain content or by following any users. Instead, they used the organic profile in TikTok to explore more freely how the algorithm worked, since the platform was new to the research. In TikTok, the content was very much characterized by global political content (War in Ukraine, Israel–Gaza conflict) but also, to some extent, conspiracy-like content relating to US politics. National issues pertaining to Sweden were mainly about immigration or gang crime and the Swedish Democrats were a prominent party in the feed. Even though this researcher was already more familiar with Instagram, it was a surprise that the feed showed more conspiracy-related and AI-generated content than TikTok. In general, Instagram came across as more incoherent than the TikTok feed (e.g. sometimes there were just AI-generated moving or evolving pictures of dragons or mushrooms). The Instagram feed remained highly apolitical throughout the data-gathering period, with only momentary political content appearing in the feed, whereas TikTok was more political from the beginning. The TikTok algorithm conformed more aggressively to the content that was watched

previously (i.e. the algorithm seemed to identify engaging content), whereas similar changes were not observed on Instagram.

Figure 21b: Number of mentions of individual politicians in organic profiles by day and researcher (on TikTok and Instagram combined)

To comment on Figure 21b above, the team compared days 11 (30.5), 20 (8.6) and 25 (12.6) of data gathering to examine the temporal difference between different time points in the organic social media feeds.

In the process of data gathering on day 11, a variety of parties and their representatives appeared in the organic profile feed of the researcher responsible for the far-right synthetic profile. One possible explanation is that two voter opinion polls were published earlier in the week before day 11. These polls showed that three parties – the Liberals, the Christian Democrats, and the Centre Party – were still hovering near the critical four per cent threshold required to enter parliament. On the eve of the election, on 8.6, all parties' candidates appeared in the feed. However, the Centre Party and the Green Party stood out as the most active, each employing rather unconventional elements in their outreach. The Centre Party focused on the role of artificial intelligence and its potential impact on the election, while the Green Party featured a celebrity endorsement, with the figure speaking warmly about the party's leading candidate.

At the beginning of the data gathering on day 11, the organic feed of the researcher responsible for the center-right organic profile was showing a lot of material on the war in Ukraine and the national defense of Sweden. On day 20, on the eve of the election, there was content on Ukraine and NATO, as well as material on US politicians, especially Bernie Sanders and Joe Biden. In addition, there was material on conspiracy theories, e.g. parts of a Joe Rogan episode with Elon Musk. On day 25, there was again content on the war in Ukraine and Gaza, as well as conspiracy theory content, all attached to Joe Rogan's podcast. In brief, war in Ukraine and Gaza were very prevalent in the sample days, and even on days before them. In the content, the national leaders prevailed; presidents, (prime) ministers and some party leaders. These politicians were mainly representing right-wing parties.

At the beginning of the data gathering, on day 11, the organic profile of the researcher dealing with the red-green synthetic profile was already showing the left and green parties' election campaigns at full swing. All the politicians, who would be prevalent until the end of the campaign, were already presented, and also the youth alliances of the parties were producing content. The same continued on the eve of the election on day 20, when the election commentators were also very active. On day 25, four days after the election, the activity of the political actors had decreased considerably. As this was the organic profile, the researcher followed different commentators.

Differences Observed Over Time

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 22: Distribution of accounts seen by EP group on TikTok and Instagram in Sweden over time

28

Right from the start, the far-right TikTok was more political. The impression was that while the political content on Instagram originated mostly from party or party-related accounts, the content on TikTok came from a broader set of accounts. At the same time, these were more explicitly critical of immigration and the EU as an institution. After the elections, the political content on Instagram decreased rather quickly, while TikTok continued to be more political. The impression was that TikTok more clearly treated the allocated synthetic profile as a clear Sweden Democrat with leanings even further out to the right on the political scale.

The differences between center-right TikTok and Instagram profiles were conspicuous (similarly to the red-green profiles). While the TikTok algorithm seemed to align quite fast and aggressively with the content watched the previous day, the Instagram algorithm seemed to react slowly. Sometimes it took a lot of training to get the Instagram feed to show political content, even when the researcher actively engaged with political content (e.g. liked political content and followed politicians). Also, the Instagram profile pivoted from lifestyle and sexually appealing content to conspiracy theory-related content. Although the topics of the videos were different for organic and synthetic profiles, both on TikTok and Instagram, the changes over time seemed to be quite similar for both accounts.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 23: Visibility of Political Actors in EP groups on TikTok and Instagram in Sweden over time

In the red-green profiles, the differences between TikTok and Instagram were remarkable. Instagram was slow to follow the preferences of both the synthetic and organic profiles and had to be trained throughout the data-gathering period. TikTok got onboard very fast but was also quick to diverge from both organic and synthetic profiles' preferences. If the researcher made a mistake of looking at, for example, a dance video for more than a few seconds, the algorithm picked the clue and filled the feed with dance videos the following day. This applied both to organic and synthetic profiles. In general, TikTok was always easier to teach to follow the profiles' preferences, while Instagram was more "passive". After the election, the political content in both Instagram and TikTok decreased.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure

24a: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on TikTok

To understand the progression of the elections in all the social media profiles in TikTok and Instagram, based on figures 24a and 24b, the team chose three days in the gathered data for a more detailed comparison – these were also the days when everyone in the team had been commenting on what they saw. We initiated the research on 20 May 2024, and Day 10 (29.5.) was seen as the beginning of the most fervent social media activity, while day 20 (8.6) was guaranteed to be teeming with activity, as this was the eve of the election day (21), and day 25 (12.6), which was four days after the election, to examine the aftermath.

Based on EP2024 Data
 Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
 Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 24b: Number of mentions of political parties by day and profile type on Instagram

In the far-right profiles, throughout the entire period studied, political actors from the right wing appeared more consistently on TikTok than on Instagram.

The synthetic and organic profiles for the center-right show that the day before the election day, there were many Swedish politicians present in the TikTok feeds, but also to some extent on Instagram, which generally showed more international politicians. This signaled some intensification of the EU campaigns towards the election day. While the centre-right feed had been dominated in previous days by content relating to war and immigration, this time there was more content relating to climate policies.

In all the red-green synthetic and organic profiles, on both TikTok and Instagram, the results were concurrent with those gleaned from Figures 21a and 21b: the party activity increased as the elections came closer. It peaked on the eve of the election and the election day and quietened down very soon after the election. One difference was that Instagram became even more passive after the election, while TikTok still offered some content, especially from some political comment feeds by local TV stations and newspapers.

Differences between Instagram vs TikTok

In general, the political content from the parties on TikTok and Instagram was very similar, and the parties often had the same videos for both platforms. TikTok was quicker than Instagram to provide alternative (political) content, and this is where the main differences began to occur.

In the far-right profiles, the official content from the Sweden Democrats (SD) was largely consistent across both platforms. What set SD apart from other parties, however, was the heightened activity of affiliated accounts with informal ties to the party, particularly on TikTok. These accounts appeared more frequently and seemed to operate with greater latitude, often expressing sharper criticism—especially concerning immigration in general and Islam in particular.

The major difference between TikTok and Instagram in the center-right profiles was the degree of content focusing on international politics on Instagram. This was perceptible, for instance, in the presence of international non-Swedish politicians (like Joe Biden, Donald Trump, and Vladimir Putin). TikTok was more focused on national and European issues regarding immigration, criminality, and national defense, and these themes were portrayed more through Swedish politicians.

In the red-green profiles, there was little content from Ukraine, or racist or anti-migrant or anti-Islam content, and none of it originated from the red-green parties. The Israel-Gaza conflict would appear often, as well as MEP Claire Daly's videos. There was more variety to this type of content in TikTok, but it also sometimes appeared on Instagram. This is possible because the Swedish political Instagram videos could be much longer, so there was less screen time for other voices. There was also some AI content in all the feeds, but it was very random.

Audience Appeal on TikTok and Instagram

Both platforms presented similar political content. However, there were differences. Instagram could feature long political speeches, and was generally more like a traditional political communication channel. TikTok contained more informal (political) content published by users further away from the parties' official candidates and election programs.

Overall, TikTok, in comparison with Instagram, seemed like we had to make more of an effort to find political content on Instagram, while TikTok quickly started providing it, especially on the synthetic profile. Seems like the TikTok algorithms caught on quicker to what the viewer was interested in or looking for. The content for profiles on TikTok and Instagram differed according to the intensity and engagement of the viewer. TikTok offered more short-form videos, whereas Instagram showed longer videos (sometimes lasting for minutes).

As mentioned above, the themes were also different and Instagram offered more random content in the sense that it did not align with national or established politics, and it pivoted towards conspiracy theories. If the algorithm were allowed to run free, a lot of the content would become apolitical entertainment (dance videos, jokes etc.). We tested this a few times, always with the same result.

Section 4: Sweden: Data Gathering – Thematic Content

In this section, we go through the themes and topics that were present in the EP2024 election debates in our data gathering process. The research draws on the reflections researchers wrote for their synthetic accounts in the data gathering process simultaneously for both TikTok and Instagram. We highlight here themes that are important for the collaborating research consortia, which the researchers were asked to see as present or not. The last sections explore outside influence and contested themes and make a note on AI-produced content.

Popular Topics on TikTok and Instagram

In the far-right accounts, criticism of migration dominated the political content. In terms of attitudes towards the EU, there was concern about uncontrolled migration and criticism of the EU as an overly large and powerful supranational institution. Overall, exaggerations and a sense of impending crisis were common.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X

Figure 25: Distribution of common themes which appeared on the TikTok and Instagram feeds

The most prominent content in both the center-right accounts on TikTok and Instagram related to the war in Ukraine and the Israel-Gaza conflict. Also, the national concern about gang crime was prominent, especially on TikTok. The Instagram content was more conspiracy-related and sometimes even more racist (e.g., humour about religion and immigrants), whereas on TikTok, these same issues were addressed through the national security framework (e.g., religions and immigrants as a threat to

Swedish values and society). It seemed that there was a crisis-like feeling in the videos, which felt both exaggerated and adversarial.

In the red-green accounts, there was some material on the Ukraine war, but especially a lot on Palestine and Gaza. This came up in both the feeds, as well as in the feeds of other MEP candidates (notably the Irish MEP Claire Daly). There were also concerns about the democratic development of Europe, and over the issues of climate change – especially in the context related to Sweden. Social justice was discussed a lot by the Swedish left, equality in society, including LGBTQ+ matters and other human rights issues. All these issues were topical, although at times the focus on Gaza felt overpowering.

Content Themes on TikTok and Instagram

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 26: Changes in the list of common themes which appeared on TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

In the far-right feeds, there was surprisingly little AI-generated material. Instead, there was a lot of criticism of immigration. Anti-immigrant content took many forms, from more formal and factual criticism of immigration policy to outright racist content, often conveyed through humour. As mentioned earlier, it was mainly on the accounts that were not formally linked to the Sweden Democrats, in which the anti-immigrant content was most pronounced. This anti-migrant content was mostly synonymous with anti-Islam.

On the center-right TikTok profile, the transgressive content was often provided by Sweden Democrat politicians or affiliated accounts. Many of these affiliated accounts were also listed in the Sweden Democrat troll factory controversy. On Instagram, the transgressive and xenophobic content was, similarly to far-right feeds, communicated through conspiracy theories and humor. For instance, there were mocking videos about Muslims and videos suggesting Jewish conspiracies. These were also the types of videos that appeared like they were partly generated by AI, with some strange edits and cuts in the videos.

The red-green axis feeds contained the least amount of racist, anti-migrant or misogynistic content. This is not to say that there were none, and a note was made every time that happened, but this was still clearly less than in the other two profiles, seeing that the red-green parties did not produce this type of content. Most of such content was in the TikTok account, but some also occurred on Instagram.

Content Related to Foreign Countries

*Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X*

Figure 27: Distribution of broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Early on, the far-right accounts included a view of the rest of Europe, since those critical of Islam and immigration were often drawing examples from, or referring to developments in Germany, France, or the UK. TikTok also quickly began to link the interest in SD to content on Nigel Farage, AfD (Alternative for Germany), and other European far-right parties and politicians. It soon became obvious that the synthetic profile was categorised as far-right on Instagram and especially on TikTok.

While following the content for the center-right profiles, it was surprising how little the US elections or NATO-related discussions were present. The foreign political matters were mostly discussed in the context of the war in Ukraine and the Israel-Gaza conflict, which were quite different from the far-right profiles. This content was a cause of uneasiness while watching the content because there was battle cam material from Ukraine, and a lot of the conflict-related content, probably created by the propaganda machines in Russia, Ukraine, Israel, and Palestine.

The red-green profiles provided little material outside Sweden, with the exceptions of the above-mentioned Gaza/Palestine situation, the Ukraine war, and Claire Daly. The parties of the red-green axis occasionally expressed concern about the democratic development in the EU and the global issues of climate change.

There was also occasional material on US elections, which at that point seemed depressingly uneventful. This data gathering took place before Trump was shot, and Kamala Harris stepped on the stage. At first, the researcher had to reach out to get political material on the topics outside Sweden, which gave the impression that the red-green parties were not linked with similar international movements in a similar manner to far-right, or to the same extent.

Based on EP2024 Data
Binary Logic Used: 1 = Seen on Day X
Day 1: 20th May 2024; Election Day: 9th June 2024 (Black line)

Figure 28: Changes over time in the visibility of the broad themes in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Content Related to Defense, War and International Conflicts

Gaza appeared in the far-right feed, as anti-war protests were sometimes employed by SD sympathizers to point out how intransigent and militant the ‘pro-Palestine protesters’ really were. One example of this was a clip of protesters trying to disrupt a speech by Jimmie Åkesson, which more than hinted that these (mostly racialized) protesters were a threat to Western democracy.

The center-right profiles were mainly showing pro-Ukraine and pro-Palestine content. The organic profile on Instagram tended to show more pro-Russian content in comparison to TikTok. The content

on Instagram was, however, also mostly pro-Ukraine and pro-Palestine. It was interesting to see how Instagram content was more suspicious in the way that it also showed dubious material that was certainly coming from Russia. It would have made sense that TikTok, as a probable psy-op platform, would have shown more pro-Russian content, but Instagram was indeed also affected.

In the profiles of the red-green parties, there was some pro-Ukraine material, but especially a lot of pro-Palestine content, and the Gaza war as a humanitarian catastrophe. These featured frequently in videos about daily life in war-torn Gaza. These came up in the feeds of MEP candidates (especially Claire Daly, who was vocally pro-Palestine). During the observation period, the most internationally noted Sweden-related event in this regard was the (now famous) protest of a Swedish, Iraqi-born MEP, Abir Al-Sahlani (Centre Party), who protested the genocide in Gaza in the EU parliament by staying silent for most of her allotted speaking time.

Figure 29: Distribution of the Type of content visible in TikTok and Instagram feeds

Threats to Equality and Diversity

As pointed out above, in the far-right synthetic accounts, anti-Muslim content appeared regularly. However, these views were often expressed indirectly, through innuendo rather than explicitly. In particular, the large-scale immigration to Sweden was portrayed as a permanent crisis that manifests itself primarily in crime and religious extremism. On a few occasions, this content also overlapped with questions about gender, in connection with how ‘Swedish values’ such as gender equality are challenged by ‘imported’ values from Muslim countries.

In the center-right profiles, topics regarding equality and diversity-related matters, religion and foreign cultures were prominent. The meanings were mainly created through discussions about gang crime that originates from foreign cultures, which was presented as a danger that degraded the unity of the Swedish state and society. In this regard, the border control of the EU was a prominent theme, mostly

advanced by candidates from the Sweden Democrats but also by some candidates of the Moderate Party.

The data gathering from the red-green axis seemed to produce the least of the racist, anti-immigrant or misogynist content. There was some, but this was not a daily occurrence in these feeds. This could be, since the data gatherer would not focus on these videos but would swipe over them quickly if there were any signs of that type of content. This could have trained both profiles to avoid them. In this regard, it is still surprising that there were some. The red-green accounts were constantly emphasizing social justice, equality, inclusion and diversity as fundamental values of Swedish society.

Figure 30: Changes in the type of content visible in TikTok and Instagram feeds over time

AI Generated Content

In the far-right profiles, AI-generated content only popped up a couple of times, and in those instances, it was obvious that it was that type of content. There was no subtle use of AI; the few elements on this theme were obvious manipulations of a humorous nature rather than attempts to mislead the audience.

AI-generated content was rare in the center-right profiles. However, it was hard to be completely sure how much there actually was. The observation was that there was more AI-generated content on Instagram than on TikTok. On Instagram, the AI content was mainly psychedelic pictures about dragons

and flowers, but also conspiracy theory-related content where symbols and music might have been edited into the videos by using AI.

In the red-green profiles there was not very much AI-generated content, except in the campaigns of the EU Greens but even this was very little, and these were mainly on TikTok. These AI-generated contents were clearly AI-made, using colors, psychedelic effects and cute characters in an exaggerated manner.

Section 5: Sweden: Data Gathering – Influence and appeal

This section explores the ways in which the features of short media platforms on social media are offering affective and effective political content. In the section we use research notes and reflections after the data gathering process.

Changes in Political Content Frequency over Time

In the far-right profiles, reminders and calls to vote gradually increased in number and intensity across the political spectrum on all accounts, as the election approached. The observation was that these synthetic accounts, especially on TikTok, drifted further and further to the right on views on migration and Islam. A lot of content was repeated over time, especially towards the end of the election campaign, when the political content increased.

In the center-right profiles the changes were different on the two platforms. On TikTok, the political content started off as the Moderate Party content by news media outlets interviewing party leaders. In the beginning, there was only a little campaigning content, mostly provided by the candidates of the Moderate Party. Already during the first week, the content by the Sweden Democrats started to infiltrate the feed. By the end of the data gathering, the data gatherer had to skip lots of Sweden Democrat content to receive content from the center and center-right parties.

On Instagram, the content was very non-political for a long time. During the last week of data gathering, the content was more political, but it rarely related to national Swedish politics. Instead, it was political content in the form of conspiracy theories and US-related issues. It was interesting, however, that at the time, there was no direct link to the US elections in this type of content. As an afterthought, it could be assumed that the presence of Elon Musk in this type of content probably had something to do with the US elections as he had become a renowned supporter of Donald Trump's campaign and appeared in clips from channels that accordingly were supporting Trump for president (e.g. The Joe Rogan Experience podcast).

In the red-green profiles, throughout the campaigns, repetition was rife, as these parties used the same content on TikTok and Instagram. This was an issue even when the red-green parties began to add variety to their topics, the closer the election came. The question remains if they had been coordinated somehow so that they had a different theme for each week? As the election day was closing, they mostly served reminders to vote, and after the results were clear, there were videos on multiple celebrations of better-than-expected red-green results. Some candidates also published content where they thanked their voters. The week after the election was largely uneventful, although these parties, especially the Green and Left, published some perky content on how they travelled to Brussels (the Green Party would “naturally” show how they took the train), and how they initiated their work there.

Influence of Audio-Visual Content in Political Debate

In the far-right profiles, social media certainly had an impact on all those (young and old) who used TikTok or Instagram, and for whom social media is a recurring source of information about society and

politics. It is perhaps more about how the issues are highlighted and framed, rather than a more direct impact on an individual's views. The deceptive thing about these kinds of audiovisual content is the necessary oversimplifications combined with the absence of any accountability. The short form content pushes the pace, and the messages tend to be formulated more aggressively than in other genres. Furthermore, the informal approach (in combination with the absence of accountability) allows for humour and irony to be used to 'soften' racist content. All of this put together can contribute to a change in how political communication is conducted, and how we expect it to be conducted.

In the center-right profiles, the impressions after the data gathering are that the short-form videos endorse a hectic political culture, where ideas and policies need to be introduced provocatively and in a polarizing manner. It is apparent that this type of content does not endorse a vivid political debating culture where ideas are communicated, discussed, debated, and reflected upon. Instead, the viewer is invited to draw conclusions about an issue at a fast pace.

In the red-green profiles, it was obvious how visible the young generation, young voters and youth organizations were on TikTok but also Instagram, and it can be assumed that today's youth will be much influenced by social media also in the future. One of the most striking things about this election was the meta-debate on the boundaries of social media, and how one is allowed to talk about their opponents, and what kind of means are acceptable to win the voters. This debate was launched by the exposure of SD troll factories, which especially caused some young red-green influencers to satirize in their videos, making fun of their conformist and misogynistic organisational culture in a very entertaining way on TikTok.

Emotional mechanisms

Researcher SE1, far-right: After the initial technical problems and frustrations, the data collection became smoother. However, on some days the researcher responsible also had other work commitments, and carried out the data collection late at night or miss edit altogether. It was very valuable for the researchere to regularly use Instagram in this way for such a long time and especially TikTok, which the researcher had not used before. The political content turned out soon generally to be quite boring and often repetitive (the same things said or the same posts repeated). The observation was that the political parties were investing in social media but had not yet learnt to use it as a fully integrated part of their communication with voters. For example, many of the posts on the parties' official accounts were clearly designed with a mass media mindset in terms of both form and aesthetics. During the data collection the researcher found themselves thinking much more than usual about immigration and Islam.

Researcher SE2, red-green: Most of the time, the data gathering and commenting work was quite repetitive, and in the beginning, there was also the whole nervous element of getting the phones working properly. All in all, the whole process took more time and energy than anticipated. Even if everything went well, the researcher was exhausted afterwards. Yet, they were also happy to have done this, as it has been an opportunity to learn more about Swedish politics and the relevant issues and concerns. This exercise was also an opportunity to process these issues on a new level, with new means. Also, the use of TikTok, and social media in general in political influencing were completely new topics to this researcher, who finds all this knowledge extremely helpful when conducting further research on the social contract.

Researcher SE3, center-right: The first days were exciting for this researcher, this was doing something new and quite concrete in an academic setting. The beginning also included some frustrating moments

41

Funded by
the European Union

with the VPN connection and screen recording interruptions. After this, the work got routinized and sometimes a bit dull. Especially going through the feed on Instagram's organic profile was annoying as there was very little political content, and the researcher had to skip most of the videos and swipe their phone during my lunch break (which they often used for data gathering). The last week of data gathering was maybe the most enjoyable as the political content "peaked" and all the profiles offered at least some political content. Emotionally, this was a mixed bag, as seeing so much war, gang crime and people getting hurt for "funny" videos could be depressing, not to mention politicians communicating their messages provocatively. During the data gathering, the researcher reduced their own use of Instagram, as they felt a bit uncomfortable with the content it offered them on their synthetic and organic profiles. However, in general, they experienced it as a good introduction to TikTok, which they had not previously used.

Video Typologies

1. In our discussions on the data, we found that the classifications given above were reasonably equivalent to what we found: Debate videos, satire, videos focused on one person, campaign walkabouts, public event speeches, and explainer videos. We can add here the videos where people were doing everyday things and talking about politics (for example, cooking and applying makeup). During the election, there were a number of videos where people were voting, and in some cases, celebrating. Some parties even showed a video of their MPs left for Brussels. There was also news and news-like content from legacy media accounts with interviews with candidates but also news reports on polarizing topics, such as immigration, from alternative media accounts that are affiliated with the far-right Sweden Democrats party (for example, Riksstudio). Many of these social media accounts were discovered to be part of the Sweden Democrats' systematised trolling operation.
2. We developed a preference for the videos where political commentators discussed the parties and their chances for success. These independent commentators provided somewhat more distant perspectives and insights. As we were watching a lot of videos produced by the parties to convince the voters, more detached perspectives were important and helpful. It was somewhat surprising that there were not more of these third-party commentator videos.
3. This election seemed somewhat atypical as the discussion was more tense and polarized than what has usually been the case in Sweden. The term *tonläge* (which refers to a pleasant and factual tone) is very important in public discussions in Sweden. This impression of hardened tone might be in fact due to the use of social media, and the way all the fast-paced visual information creates black and white contradictions as a medium.

Attractive content: Narratives from audiovisual politics

Video from the Riksdagen (Swedish parliament) where Magdalena Anderson (Social Democrat) talks about Sweden Democrats initiatives, which will threaten to weaken the position of health care workers.

This is a very typical video where the left criticizes the right-wing ideas to roll back the welfare state. It also shows to which voters these two parties want to appeal.

Narrative 1. Right wing as threat to Social Welfare in Sweden (From SE2/2024-05-22, 195423 OTT, Organic Instagram 00:05:11-00:06:08)

Riksstudio's (a right-wing troll account) video showing how pro-Palestinian protesters disrupt the Sweden Democrats' (SD) election rally is also repeated several times on Instagram. The protesters are obviously people of colour and immigrants, which adds to the sense of polarization but also shows that SD's opponents are rabid and will stop at nothing to oppose them (= they are anti-democratic).

Narrative 2. Immigrants as threat to Swedish social peace (From SE1/2024-06-03, Synthetic Instagram profile, 00:00:00-00:01:00)

Alice Bah Kuhnke published a long and action-packed video about one day (from morning to evening) of her campaign work. She shows how she walks from debate to debate, from meeting to meeting. Interesting how she makes a kind of meta-reflection on being a politician and on the campaign work.

Narrative 3. The important day-to-day work of the Swedish MEPs

(From SE1/2024-05-30, Organic TikTok profile, 00:01:35–00:04:59)

Riksstudio often interviews politicians or citizens with hard opinions about migration or gang crime and what Swedish society should do about it. In this video, there is a man (presumably) of Iraqi decent who claims that the Swedish neighbourhood where the video is filmed is sometimes worse than Baghdad. I think this video is a prime example of Riksstudio's content – a social media account that was affiliated with the Sweden Democrat troll factory.

Narrative 4. News-like crime reports from Swedish neighbourhoods
(From SE3_TikTok_(3)_Synthetic_profile_20240522 00:00:07–00:01:30)

Discussion on most interesting videos

Swedish commentators have a long tradition of political satire, and these are also prevalent in the TikTok and Instagram videos. They were not sparing anyone, and especially party leaders got their share. The party leaders were presented as caricatures doing ridiculous things. Even when the Swedish tradition of satire is relatively mild in comparison with some other countries, especially those under the influence of the British press, these videos were effective.

Another interesting group is the youths over the political range who were busy doing everyday things such as driving, cooking or putting on makeup while talking politics. These videos combined two genres: political infotainment and the more usual influencer content.

Also, failure is interesting: in this election Sweden Democrats failed to find the success they thought was theirs. In public discussion, this is often seen to be due to their aggressive campaigning, but they were also seen as too self-assured. For example, the video where Jimmie Åkesson tells a fairy tale with the leader of the Social Democratic Party as the main character. Even his body language presents self-assurance of an election winner. The video is interesting because it is an unusually unintelligent way of critiquing an opposition party (even for the Sweden Democrats). [SE1, synthetic TikTok, 2024-05-20, 00:02:10–00:03:14] Their self-assurance might be due to the fact that they are really dominating the Swedish social media, and having many more followers than what they call the left-wing accounts (of which they are keeping tabs).

Concluding section

This section provides some discussion on the basis of the social contract, reasons for voting or setting up as a candidate in the first place as an act of sharing the EU social contract. It also includes the conclusions of the whole study for the country case.

It is hard to deduce or measure the influence on the elections in Sweden by actors outside of the EU. Within the country, the Sweden Democrats' troll factories steered the discussion in Sweden to internal influencing and spreading of disinformation by the Sweden Democrats party. These troll factories were discovered in 2024 by a popular investigative TV program, "Kalla fakta" (literally, cold fact) (TV4, 2024). To national outrage, the Sweden Democrats party had paid for these illicit activities with the state-granted communication funds, which they were not supposed to use for political influencing or marketing purposes. "Kalla fakta" disclosed that this communication department, or troll factory, operated in the building above the party headquarters and paid their employees to operate multiple troll accounts. Moreover, as citizens are using social media in an increasing manner to read and receive news (e.g. Newman et al. 2024), and as some of these troll accounts draw on journalistic forms and methods in their content and representations, such activity on these social media platforms poses a multifaceted internal threat to democratic institutions.

It is not viable to ignore these platforms, seeing that they have become such an important part of the citizens' lives. However, engaging with these platforms requires the same level of planning, professional competence and investment as any other (traditional) media or campaign channels would require.

Limiting access for individual users of the VLOPs (Very large online platforms) is difficult. However, perceiving that some organizations and groups are using them clearly for the purposes of propagating disinformation is a fact, and something that the EU is and should be limiting in the future. Banning the troll accounts that have been proven to be orchestrated by official parties or other organizations could be a viable option.

A recommendation for parties using social media: Before engaging with social media in political work or communication, make sure that you fully understand the medium and its specific traits. Otherwise, there is a real threat that you give off an impression of unprofessionalism and being unserious. The danger here is that the younger generations, especially, will not find you credible, and in the worst case, anachronistic. Also, a lot of the campaigning was focused on what the opponent failed to do, instead of focusing on their own policies and visions and what they wanted to accomplish. Negative campaigning, as effective it might be, creates an environment only focused on passing the blame, which makes this type of political discussion seem irrelevant and uninviting.

What was Europe about and why vote (the Social Contract)?

The reasons for voting look different from different political perspectives. There were several discussions on the importance of social media in this election in Sweden.

The Moderates and Sweden Democrats were constantly bringing in the rhetoric of borders, and the need to control migration. There was a tendency towards limiting the might of the EU, which was presented as a threat to national independence, and to Sweden's ability to control its domestic affairs. In the Sweden Democrats' election campaign, party leader Jimmie Åkesson was very visible, especially

on social media. Top candidate Charlie Weimer's appearances stuck to the party's election manifesto, and he expressed both Eurosceptic views and criticism of migration. While he usually had a more formal approach, Åkesson's appearances were more aggressively Eurosceptic, and similarly critical towards immigration. In the Sweden Democrats' campaign, some social media accounts not directly/formally linked to the party played an important role. The accounts 'sdmicke' and 'riks', for example, focused almost exclusively on migration and conveyed their messages (bordering on racism) in a way that the party's politicians could not convey with their own names and faces.

The campaigns of the center-right parties were built around top-candidates but also around governmental figures, such as the prime minister of Sweden, Ulf Kristersson (The Moderate Party). Also, other ministers who also acted as party leaders were prominent, such as the minister of industry and business Ebba Busch (Christian Democrats). In many social media videos and interviews, the politicians talked about the sovereignty of the Swedish state to decide about their own matters. One such matter was the EU-wide ban on snuff or tobacco-free snuff, which was regarded as needless by the politicians as snuff reduces the harms of smoking. Many center-right politicians also advanced a view that Sweden should be the one deciding on how the Swedish forests are being used.

In the red-green axis, the Left and the Green Party voiced their concerns regarding the climate crisis, perceiving the EU as a possible regulator against the evils of climate change as well as other pressing issues that required transnational solutions. They were also bringing up concerns both at the European and national level regarding the slide of Europe towards the extreme right, and thus on the state of democracy in the EU. Their top candidates were active on social media and ran truly effective campaigns with different emphases. Jonas Sjöstedt and Alice Bah Kuhnke stood out as particularly effective campaigners, especially when it comes to using social media to reach potential voters. Jonas Sjöstedt employed the rhetoric of social justice in a very concrete, human-centered manner in social media. This was also commented upon in Swedish media.

While the Left party and Green Party campaigns were led by well-known top candidates (although the Lefty leader Nooshi Dadgostar also made several appearances), the Social Democrats were showing mostly their party leader Magdalena Andersson. The idea of the *social contract* was implicit especially in her statements within the discussions touching the existence and threats to the Swedish "*folkhemmet*" (People's home), a label used to refer to the Swedish welfare society. The danger was that democracy would be undermined in the whole EU. (This discussion is addressed in length below). The Social Democrats were also the ones talking most about the importance of a peaceful Europe.

Populist mobilisation

$$\text{Populism} = \text{Us}^{\text{Affect1}} + \text{Frontier}^{\text{Affect2}}$$

Radical right saw aliens, immigrants and Islam as a threat to the Swedish welfare state and social contract. They were presented as irrational, loud and unpredictable (e.g., the chaotic Palestine protests). The us-affect was related to Swedishness, which was presented as the ability to exert rational common sense and behave in a calm and controlled manner. The boundary-affect was overlapping with the boundary of the welfare state, which was drawn at the Others, who were not to benefit or participate in it. The general idea was to keep the outsider religions (especially Islam) out, and guard against the signs of "not belonging" such as clothing, behaviour etc., which was not seen as Swedish.

The center-right narrative was all about “Take the power back”. In their content, decision-making has slipped too much out of Swedish hands into the EU. The us-affect was especially visible in the nationally important, emotionally laden symbols such as white snuff (*vit snus*), or control of the use of Swedish forests as an economic resource. The boundary-affect would be drawn to decision-making power, where the threat was that the EU would push the frontier and take away the national power to make decisions and thus weaken the democratic decision-making in Sweden. This was, however, an equivocal frontier, as the EU was also seen as a resource against external military threats.

Red-green narrative presented the right-wing policies and politicians as a threat to the Swedish welfare state and the democratic social contract. The us-affect was formed around a representation of the Self, an ideal Swede: tolerant, loving peace and democracy always willing to negotiate, supporting gender equality and having great respect for human rights. The boundary-affect was marked at the *åsiktskorridor* (lit “corridor of opinion”), which defines the boundaries of acceptable opinions, and the ways a proper Swede expresses them. It was also important to uphold a proper, polite *tonläge* (the boundaries of a socially acceptable tone and expression). This affect was also protected with the representation of the Others as moral human beings, instead of seeing them as threats.

Conclusion

It soon became apparent that all the Swedish parties had a different approach to the campaign, and to what were the most important issues, as well as different ideas and competence on creating alluring content to voters. In Sweden, the voter turnout was 53, 39 %, which was higher than the whole EU turnout of 50,74%. The election showed a turn away from the centre-right and far-right parties towards the left-green axis.

Regarding the platforms, TikTok and Instagram, the former offered more political content for all the synthetic profiles. Instagram, on the one hand, was incoherent in terms of political content but on the other hand, also offered more directly conspiracy theory-related content. It was also harder to steer the Instagram algorithm towards political content, whereas the TikTok algorithm was faster to react to changes in viewer preferences.

Sweden Democrats ran a campaign that was aggressive, bordering on hateful and arrogant, which clearly failed to reach their audiences in the same manner. Their aggressive campaigning was also underscored by the discovery of the so-called troll accounts on social media that were directly affiliated with the party. The visuality and narratives on these videos were built on internet meme culture but also on established forms of news reporting. The openly confrontational style distinguished the content by Sweden Democrats and accounts that support them from other parties that were more moderate in their narratives and framings, even when the left-wing opposition parties tried to challenge the governmental parties. The content by Sweden Democrats and their supporters circulated mainly around the issues of immigration and gang crime. The planned EU ban on snuff was also a widely used topic in undermining the legitimacy of the EU to do decisions about Sweden’s matters (this topic on snuff was also prominent in the content relating to the Moderate party). Their approach to the social contract was shielding it from the alien elements.

The Moderate party ran its social media campaign through the top candidate Tomas Tobé who was regularly present in the feeds. The support was given by the presence of Prime Minister Ulf Kristersson of the Moderate Party, commenting on national matters. The questions of social contract pertaining to the European Union were mobilised on the centre-right feeds through calls for taking back power from the EU in deciding on national matters in the form of, for instance, discussions on the restrictions on

selling *vit snus* (white snuff) and the limitations on forest and land use. The European Union was also articulated as an asset in preparing against external threats. This was done through imagery and discussions on War in Ukraine and calls for a collective armament of Europe. The centre-right was aiming to protect Sweden from the unwanted interventions and elements yet keep intact the benefits of being an EU member state.

From our material, those red-green MEPs who ran the most successful campaigns either knew how to or had very adept teams producing their material. Especially Green Party campaign was extremely professionally done, focusing on Alice Bah Kuhnke. The election winners Alice Bah Kuhnke (The Green Party) and Jonas Sjöstedt (The Left Party) managed to talk to their viewers on a personal level. Their campaigns managed to create a feeling of them speaking with the viewer rather than at the viewer. They also managed to create a more informal atmosphere by letting the viewers follow them through their campaigns. Their videos had very different styles: While Sjöstedt focused on talking to people, Bah Kuhnke was always active, doing something political and important, which was always interesting to watch.

Social Democrats were running a much more dispersed and multivocal campaign. The party establishment had a more traditional media feel to their content, seemingly without considering the specificities of social media: they used long clips, long speeches, and less was happening visually. This was possibly not always appealing to the viewers. Their focus was less on the top candidates and more on the party leader, Magdalena Andersson. Their youth organisations and activists were an exception to this, as they in general succeeded better in creating appealing videos on the candidates and important issues, clearly directed to younger voters. The Social Democrats presented themselves as protectors of the democratic social contract in Sweden, and at the very core of what it means to be culturally Swedish.

When it comes to the question of finding out about changes in the social contract, a once-off study such as this will remain a scrape on the surface. To reveal something majorly significant about its continuous transformation, there would need to be more similar repeat studies for comparisons, and more focused, comparative questions from the beginning (perhaps informed by the opinion polls, when possible). A longitudinal approach would reveal much more about the changes in the social contract.

However, in this study, it has become clear that all the political directions and parties presented themselves as defenders of the Swedish social contract, yet their means and aims differed vastly.

Bibliography

Aftonbladet (10 June 2024). “Här vägrar Carl Bildt svara vad han röstade på: ”Inte Sjöstedt iallafall.”

Available online at: <https://tv.aftonbladet.se/video/370883/haer-vaegrar-carl-bildt-svara-vad-han-roestade-pa-inte-sjoestedt-iallafall> Accessed on 11 June 2024.

Newman, N. Fletcher, R., Robertson, Ross Arguedas, C. A., Nielsen. R. (2024). *Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2024*. Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism. Oxford. DOI: 10.60625/RISJ-VY6N-4V57

TV4 (2024). *Kalla Fakta – Undercover i trollfabriken*. Available online at:

<https://www.tv4.se/artikel/2VCWExxK0L1Xmai2Y60Z2/kalla-fakta-avsloejar-sd-driver-en-trollfabrik> Accessed on 26 November 2024.

Expressen (7 May 2025). *Ett år efter trollfabriken – SD-konton fortfarande kvar*. Available online at:

<https://www.expressen.se/nyheter/sverige/ett-ar-efter-trollfabriken-sd-konton-fortfarande-kvar/> Accessed on 15 May 2025.

Väljarbarometern SVT (2024 and **SVT** (2025). Available online at:

<https://www.svt.se/special/valjarbarometern/> Accessed on 15 June 2024 and 19 May 2025.

**COntinuous COnstruction
of resilient social COntracts
through societal transformations**

REPORT

**UKRAINE IN THE EUROPEAN
ELECTION 2024**

**Petro Baykovskyy
Yuriy Pidlisnyy**

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101132631. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	
2. Methodology.....	
3. European People's Party (EPP).....	
4. Party of European Socialists (PES).....	
5. The Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe Party (ALDE Party)	
6. European Green Party (EGP).....	
7. Party of the European Left (PEL).....	
8. European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) Party.....	
9. Patriots for Europe (PfE or Patriots)	
10. The Europe of Sovereign Nations (ESN).....	
11. Conclusions.....	
12. List of References.....	

1. Introduction

The European Parliament Elections were conducted in 27 EU member states from 6-9 June 2024, culminating in the election of 720 deputies. The majority of national parties that surpassed the electoral threshold are affiliated with pan-European parties, which subsequently form party groups within the European Parliament.

Consequently, four groups of pro-Europeans, in conjunction with a number of non-aligned MEPs, maintained a majority in the European Parliament (approximately 65% of MEPs), while various Eurosceptics received approximately 35% of the seats. The figure provides a detailed representation of the party composition of the European Parliament.

2. Methodology

The principal objective of this study was to ascertain the positions of the Europarties (their groups in the EP) and their national parties with regard to Ukraine. Specifically, the following aspects were examined:

Firstly, attitudes towards the prospect of Ukraine's European integration and accession to the EU, and the identification of the main arguments used in political rhetoric on this issue. Secondly, the parties' attitude to Russian aggression and its consequences for Ukraine and Europe. Thirdly, the position on providing economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine. Fourthly, the parties' vision of possible scenarios for ending the war.

The analysis of party positions was conducted through a qualitative analysis of election manifestos, party websites and social media of parties and party leaders on the eve of the European Parliament elections. The time period of the data analysis covers January-June 2024 (until the EP elections).

The research is grounded in an extensive examination of eight European political parties: the European People's Party (EPP), the Party of European Socialists (PES), the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe Party (ALDE Party), the European Green Party (EGP), the Party of the European Left (PEL), the European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) Party, Patriots for Europe (PfE or Patriots), and the The Europe of Sovereign Nations (ESN). The analysis further extends to encompassing their respective national member parties that have secured seats in the European Parliament. It is important to note that, on occasion, some europarties form coalitions with other European parties (like Green/EFA Group, Renew Europe Group), or party groups of the European Parliament include national party delegations that are not members of European parties (such as the French ruling party Renaissance).

Four European parties (EPP, PES, ALDE, EGP) are pro-European. The remaining four parties represent various forms of Euroscepticism: PEL - soft left-wing Euroscepticism; ECR - soft right-wing Euroscepticism; PfE - hard right-wing populist Euroscepticism; ESN - hard nationalist Euroscepticism.

Within each European party, a regional differentiation was made into parties of Western (Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Germany, France), Northern (Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Sweden), Southern (Greece, Italy, Spain, Cyprus, Malta, Portugal) and Central and Eastern Europe. The latter category comprises countries that became EU members following the year 2004 and were previously part of the socialist bloc. Consequently, in addition to Poland, Slovakia, Hungary, and the Baltic States (Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia), the Central and Eastern European grouping also encompasses the countries of South Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, and Slovenia).

3. European People's Party (EPP)

The European People's Party (EPP) has issued a robust condemnation against the aggressive actions perpetrated by Russia, including the exploitation of energy and food resources as instruments of warfare, in addition to the issuance of nuclear threats. The EPP has expressed its support for Ukraine in its efforts to defend itself and uphold common European values, pledging to provide political, economic, humanitarian and military assistance "as much as is needed". The EPP has advocated for an augmentation in military assistance to Ukraine, notably through the formulation of a unified victory strategy and an escalation in the EU's contributions to Ukraine's aid to 0.25% of GDP. The party also endorses long-term funding for Ukraine's post-war reconstruction, supports Ukraine's accession to the EU and NATO after it meets the necessary criteria, and proposes a strategy for assessing its readiness. In relation to Russia, the EPP supports the continuation of sanctions pressure, the combatting of

4

Funded by
the European Union

propaganda, and the reduction of dependence on Russian resources. It also calls for the use of frozen Russian assets as reparations. Despite the desire for reforms in the EU's migration policy, the party assures that the current changes will not affect Ukrainian refugees in the EU. However, the approaches adopted by national EPP member parties from different regions of the EU are subject to variation depending on historical, geopolitical and domestic political factors.

Western European EPP political parties demonstrate common support for Ukraine in its fight against Russian aggression, but significant differences emerge on the issues of European integration and military assistance. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's accession to the EU, the parties in general recognise the possibility of membership, albeit with divergent conditions. For instance, the CD&V (Belgium) and CDA (Netherlands) advocate for maintaining close relations with Ukraine and advocating for gradual access to EU benefits, whilst underscoring the imperative of fulfilling all accession criteria. The CDU/CSU (Germany) has proposed a model of incremental integration, while the Christian Social People's Party (Luxembourg) has explicitly expressed support for accession subsequent to the cessation of hostilities. Conversely, Les Républicains (France) are opposed to any further expansion of the EU, and are instead proposing the status of an associated state for Ukraine. Similarly, the Austrian People's Party are excluding the possibility of accelerated accession, and are demanding an end to the war before negotiations can begin. In the Netherlands, the BBB and the NSC advocate for Ukraine's integration, but underscore that this process will be protracted, taking many years. Generally, the more economically conservative a party is, the greater its concern about the possible consequences for the EU economy. The stance on Russian aggression is predominantly robust, with a focus on providing support to Ukraine. CD&V (Belgium) has articulated the necessity for sustained assistance to ensure the defeat of Russia. The CDU/CSU (Germany) emphasises that "freezing the conflict" is unacceptable, while the CSV (Luxembourg) explicitly states that Europe's security depends on Russia's defeat. In the Netherlands, the NSC has advocated for the establishment of a tribunal to prosecute Russian war criminals. Conversely, the Austrian People's Party, while condemning the aggression, maintains a neutral stance and calls for peace negotiations involving the EU and the BRICS countries. With regard to military aid, CD&V (Belgium), CDU/CSU (Germany) and CSV (Luxembourg) advocate for increased military aid and punishment of Russian war criminals. In contrast, Les Républicains (France) has voiced criticism on the grounds that military assistance from Paris is insufficient and has called for an increase in such assistance. In the Netherlands, the CDA and BBB advocate for sustained support for Ukraine, while the BBB also contemplates the prospect of resuming economic relations with Russia in the future. Conversely, the Austrian People's Party maintains a neutral stance, refraining from supplying weapons, and instead concentrating its support on humanitarian aid and the establishment of refugee shelters. Significant differences of opinion emerge with regard to the matter of the cessation of hostilities. The CDU/CSU (Germany), CD&V (Belgium) and CSV (Luxembourg) emphasise that the war should end with a Ukrainian victory. The NSC (Netherlands) has advocated for the punishment of war criminals and the continuation of military support. Conversely, the Austrian People's Party has opted for a different approach, favouring negotiations involving the EU and BRICS countries, thereby indicating a reluctance to become directly involved in the conflict.

A thorough analysis of the political parties of the EPP members from **Northern Europe** reveals a general support for Ukraine's accession to the EU, albeit with specific stipulations. For instance, the Conservative People's Party (Denmark), the Liberal Alliance (Denmark) and the National Coalition (Finland) underscore the necessity for Ukraine to fulfil all the criteria for membership. A similar position is adopted by Fine Gael (Ireland) and Kristdemokraterna (Sweden), although the latter do not provide a definitive response. With regard to the issue of Russian aggression, a unanimous condemnation is expressed by all parties. Fine Gael (Ireland) explicitly states that "Russia cannot win this war", while Moderaterna (Sweden) criticises attempts to negotiate with Putin. It is notable that the closer a country is to Russia, the more robust the positions of its political parties, a phenomenon that is particularly evident in Finland and Denmark. The provision of economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine is a position that is endorsed by all the parties analysed. There is a desire to expand the European Peace Fund (National Coalition, Finland), increase arms production (Liberal Alliance, Denmark) and introduce energy support for Ukraine (Moderaterna, Sweden). With regard to the vision of ending the war, all parties emphasise the need for Ukraine to prevail and for Russian troops to

withdraw. However, the specific mechanisms by which these objectives are to be achieved are not always delineated. For instance, Fine Gael (Ireland) pledges unwavering support to Ukraine "as long as it takes", while Kristdemokraterna (Sweden) underscores the significance of EU defence reform, acknowledging NATO's primary responsibility in defending Ukraine.

In EPP parties from the **Southern Europe**, most parties do not express open opposition to Ukraine's accession to the EU. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's accession to the EU, the majority of EPP parties do not openly oppose this. New Democracy (Greece) has expressed support for the reform of EU enlargement procedures, while simultaneously avoiding direct mention of Ukraine. The Nationalist Party of Malta, through its representatives in the European Parliament, notably Roberta Mecola, has expressed unequivocal support for Ukraine's European aspirations. Conversely, Forza Italia (Italy) and the Spanish People's Party (PP) have expressed support, albeit with caution and without detailing Ukraine's specific path to membership. Southern European countries, in contrast, place a greater emphasis on the necessity of internal reforms within the EU than on the issue of enlargement. With regard to the matter of Russian aggression, a majority of the parties condemn Russia's actions, albeit with differing degrees of resolve. Forza Italia and the PP talk about defending "common values", but avoid making any harsh statements, stressing that the EU is not at war with Russia. New Democracy refrains from any direct reference to Russia, instead focusing on security challenges. Conversely, the Nationalist Party of Malta has overtly expressed support for Ukraine, with its representatives in the European Parliament calling for more active assistance. In contrast, the Social Democratic Party of Portugal has expressed concerns about an alleged "militaristic drift" within the EU, advocating instead for negotiations as a preferred course of action. With regard to the provision of economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine, the majority of parties demonstrate commitment. Spain's PP advocates the utilisation of frozen Russian assets to finance aid to Ukraine. Conversely, the Nationalist Party of Malta has voiced criticism regarding the country's perceived "neutrality" and has advocated for more active support for Ukrainian refugees. Forza Italia, while expressing support for Ukraine, is categorically opposed to the deployment of Italian troops. Conversely, the Social Democratic Party of Portugal is opposed to the militarisation of the EU and considers military assistance to be an exacerbation of the conflict. With regard to the ultimate objective of the war, the parties' stances vary from support for Ukraine's triumph to the call for negotiations. The PP and the Maltese Nationalist Party advocate for sustained support for Kyiv. Forza Italia articulates a need for peace, yet it remains ambiguous as to the nature of the peace it seeks. Southern Europe

Political parties from **Central and Eastern Europe** have generally demonstrated strong support for Ukraine in its fight against Russian aggression. However, there are some differences of opinion on the issues of EU accession, military assistance and the future of relations with Russia. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's European integration, the majority of regional political parties advocate for Ukraine's accession to the EU, underscoring the imperative to meet all the stipulated criteria. Explicit support for Ukraine's full membership is expressed by the CDU (Croatia), KDH (Slovakia) and SDS (Slovenia), who regard this as beneficial for the whole of Europe. Conversely, Isamaa (Estonia), Homeland Union - Lithuanian Christian Democrats (Lithuania) and Jaunā Vienotība (Latvia) regard Ukraine's accession as being of geopolitical significance for the security of the region. Conversely, the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (Romania) underscores the imperative to guarantee the rights of the Hungarian minority prior to Ukraine's integration into the EU. Meanwhile, GERB-SDS (Bulgaria) adopts a circumspect stance, contemplating Ukraine's accession within the broader context of European security. With regard to Russian aggression, the majority of parties adopt a robustly anti-Russian stance. Isamaa (Estonia), Jaunā Vienotība (Latvia), Homeland Union (Lithuania) and KDH (Slovakia) explicitly state that Russia must be defeated, while PP-DB (Bulgaria) and the Czech Christian and Democratic Union - Czechoslovak People's Party and TOP 09, which were part of the Razom electoral bloc in the elections, draw parallels between Russia's invasion and historical examples of military aggression by the Soviet Union. The Croatian Democratic Union (Croatia) emphasises that Ukraine is not only fighting for its independence, but also determining the future of Europe's relations with Russia. Conversely, GERB-SDS (Bulgaria) has expressed a desire to maintain political dialogue with Russia, while Tisza (Hungary) and the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania (Romania) have refrained from issuing direct statements. A broad consensus exists in favour of providing economic, humanitarian

and military support to Ukraine. The political parties KDH (Slovakia), SDS (Slovenia) and Isamaa (Estonia) advocate for increased military support, sanctions pressure, and the use of frozen Russian assets. The Lithuanian Homeland Union emphasises the pivotal role of Ukraine's success for the entire region, while the Latvian Jaunā Vienotība party supports all forms of assistance, including military and economic aid. The Croatian Democratic Union (Croatia) pays special attention to humanitarian support, refugee reception and rehabilitation of the wounded. The Hungarian parties, including Tisza, have avoided the issue of military aid, while the Democratic Alliance of Hungarians in Romania has criticised the redistribution of subsidies to European farmers in favour of Ukraine. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, the regional parties as a whole are in favour of Ukraine achieving victory. Isamaa (Estonia), Jaunā Vienotība (Latvia) and Homeland Union (Lithuania) advocate for a definitive victory of Ukraine, the liberation of occupied territories, and the pursuit of accountability for perpetrators. Conversely, KDH (Slovakia) and SDS (Slovenia) have underscored the imperative to bolster the EU's defence capabilities to forestall prospective threats. Conversely, GERB-SDS (Bulgaria) and Tisza (Hungary) have refrained from issuing explicit statements on the resolution of the conflict.

Generally, the EPP parties have expressed a unanimous condemnation of the Russian invasion, though their positions vary. The countries of Central and Eastern Europe and Northern Europe have demonstrated the harshest anti-Russian rhetoric, while the parties of Austria, Bulgaria and Hungary have adopted a more moderate approach, without ruling out the possibility of dialogue with Russia. With regard to military assistance, the majority of parties in Western, Northern and Central and Eastern Europe advocate its enhancement, including the utilisation of frozen Russian assets. Conversely, Austria, Portugal and Hungary adopt a more circumspect stance, emphasising humanitarian aid and diplomatic approaches. With regard to Ukraine's European integration, the majority of parties support its accession to the EU, but with the caveat that all necessary criteria be met. Notably, those representing France, Austria and Southern Europe have expressed the most scepticism regarding the prospect of EU enlargement. These countries have emphasised the necessity of implementing reforms within the EU itself prior to any further expansion. Conversely, Central and Eastern Europe, in conjunction with the Baltic states, advocate for Ukraine's accession as a strategic imperative for regional security. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, divergent positions are evident: Western European parties generally support the continuation of assistance to Ukraine, but differ in their vision of the ultimate goal – some insist on Ukraine's victory, while others do not openly articulate the end result. In contrast, Central and Eastern Europe, along with Northern Europe, advocate for Ukraine to achieve a comprehensive victory and hold Russia accountable for its actions. Conversely, Austria, Bulgaria and Hungary advocate negotiations as a potential means to conclude the war. The overall support for Ukraine within the EPP is robust, yet significant variations emerge concerning pivotal issues, attributable to geopolitical, historical and economic factors. The approach adopted by political parties demonstrating a closer alignment with Russia or those with established economic interdependencies with Russia are characterised by a more circumspect stance, whilst those states with a documented history of confrontation with Moscow adopt a more robust stance.

4. Party of European Socialists (PES)

The Party of European Socialists recognises the Russian aggression as a 'turning point in history' which is 'a violation of Ukrainian sovereignty and international law, a threat to European security and values, and a war against democracies'. The association supports the provision of political, humanitarian, financial and military assistance to Ukraine "for as long as necessary" to restore its territorial integrity and achieve sustainable peace. In particular, its representatives call for an acceleration of military aid and state that support for Ukraine will be "one of the main priorities" of the S&D group in the European Parliament. The party supports the creation of a sanctions mechanism that would exclude European funding for authoritarian regimes, including Russia, and calls for the transfer of frozen Russian assets for the reconstruction of Ukraine. The PES officially supports Ukraine's accession to the EU, stressing

7

Funded by
the European Union

the importance of democratic reforms, the rule of law and the fight against corruption. For the party, this is not only about integrating the new state, but also about strengthening the EU itself as a geopolitical actor. It stresses that supporting Ukraine is a moral obligation to the people who are fighting for common European values. This position is also shared by national parties, although their approaches to the implementation of this process differ.

In **Western Europe**, most of the socialist and social democratic parties analysed support the process of Ukraine's accession to the EU, but also stress that all the necessary accession criteria must be met. The Vooruit Party (Belgium) explicitly states that there can be no accelerated procedures and no concessions in the areas of democracy, anti-corruption and minority rights. A similar position is taken by the SPD (Germany), which is in favour of Ukraine's European integration, provided that the necessary reforms are carried out. The Réveiller l'Europe electoral bloc, which includes the French Socialist Party and the Public Space party, is in favour of EU enlargement to include Ukraine, Moldova and the Balkan countries. At the same time, other parties in the region (the Netherlands, Austria, Luxembourg) are more cautious, stressing that accession should be gradual and in line with the EU's strategic interests. On the issue of Russian aggression, all the parties analysed unequivocally condemn Russia's actions. The PvdA (Netherlands), LSAP (Luxembourg) and Réveiller l'Europe (France) stress that defending Ukraine is defending Europe. The SPD (Germany) considers that supporting Ukraine is a moral obligation, while trying to avoid an escalation of the conflict. Vooruit (Belgium) stresses that sanctions against Russia should not only be maintained but also strengthened, eliminating all possible loopholes for their circumvention. An important regional peculiarity is that parties from countries with extensive economic ties to Russia (e.g. Germany) show some restraint in their rhetoric on the escalation of the war, while the Benelux countries and France are in favour of more radical sanctions. Support for Ukraine in the form of economic, humanitarian and military aid is also widespread among centre-left parties in Western Europe. The PvdA (Netherlands) stresses that Ukraine should receive all the weapons, ammunition, financial and intelligence support it needs. Réveiller l'Europe (France) supports the transfer of frozen Russian assets to Ukraine, and Vooruit (Belgium) calls for a complete end to the trade in Russian diamonds, one of the Kremlin's main sources of income. The SPD (Germany) supports military aid, but with certain restrictions, particularly on the type of weapons, in order to avoid a direct military conflict between the EU and Russia. On the question of ending the war, Western European parties are divided into two groups: those who see Ukraine's victory as the only way forward, and those who seek diplomatic solutions. The PvdA (Netherlands) and Réveiller l'Europe (France) stress that Russia must suffer a strategic defeat and its leaders must be brought before an international tribunal. Vooruit (Belgium) supports the strategy of economic exhaustion of Russia through sanctions. The SPD (Germany), while supporting Ukraine, is more inclined to diplomatic efforts, including the possible involvement of China in a peaceful solution.

Most centre-left parties in the **North of Europe** are also positive about Ukraine's accession to the EU. The Social Democrats (Denmark), Socialdemokraterna (Sweden), the Labour Party (Ireland) and the Social Democratic Party of Finland (SDP) state that the EU should remain open to all countries that meet its standards. The SDP focuses on workers' rights and social guarantees as mandatory elements for Ukraine's membership. In general, the Nordic countries support EU enlargement, but with a special focus on social standards and adherence to democratic principles. Northern Europe Regarding Russian aggression, the parties' positions are clearly pro-Ukrainian. All the parties analysed recognise Russia as a threat not only to Ukraine but also to European security in general. The SDP (Finland) and Socialdemokraterna (Sweden) advocate tougher anti-Russian sanctions, including the use of frozen Russian assets. Labour (Ireland) draws attention to the threat of cyber-terrorism and transnational crime from Russia. The Swedish Social Democrats stress the importance of ending the EU's dependence on Russian energy resources and of establishing mechanisms to support democratic movements in Russia and Belarus. There is also a consensus on the issue of support for Ukraine. All parties surveyed support economic, humanitarian and military aid. The Socialdemokraterna (Sweden) and the SDP (Finland) explicitly state that military assistance should not only be continued but also increased. In Sweden, the Social Democrats demand that Ukraine be supplied with ammunition and that its own defence production be increased. The Finnish Social Democrats support the use of Russia's frozen assets to finance aid to Ukraine. In Ireland, the Labour Party calls for the development of a strategy for Ukraine's

post-war reconstruction using Western funds. On the question of ending the war, Northern European parties stress the need for Ukraine's victory. The SDP (Finland) openly supports the destruction of military targets in the Russian Federation, which is the harshest position among the parties analysed. Socialdemokraterna (Sweden) states that Ukraine is fighting not only for its freedom but also for the security of the whole of Europe and that Ukraine's victory is necessary for the stability of the region. The Labour Party (Ireland) and the Social Democrats (Denmark) support the active use of economic levers, including sanctions and asset confiscation, to weaken Russia's military potential.

On the question of Ukraine's accession to the EU, most centre-left parties in **Southern Europe** support integration, but with different conditions. The PSOE (Spain) and the Partido Socialista (Portugal) clearly support EU enlargement, describing it as a geopolitical necessity and a way to strengthen Europe. The Partito Democratico (Italy) also supports Ukraine's membership, stressing that the EU should be a political reference point for all those striving for democracy. At the same time, Partit Laburista (Malta) and PASOK-KINAL (Greece) do not have a clear position on Ukraine's accession, although the Maltese party generally supports merit-based enlargement. On the issue of Russian aggression, most southern European parties strongly condemn the Kremlin's actions. The PSOE (Spain), the Partido Socialista (Portugal) and the Partito Democratico (Italy) directly name Russia as the aggressor and stress that its defeat is necessary to preserve European security. The Democratic Party (Cyprus) draws a parallel between Russia's invasion of Ukraine and the Turkish occupation of northern Cyprus, which makes its position particularly harsh. At the same time, Partit Laburista (Malta) takes a neutral position, calling for diplomacy and stating the need to avoid "premature actions" that could exacerbate the conflict. On aid to Ukraine, most parties support economic, humanitarian and military aid. The PSOE (Spain) and Partido Socialista (Portugal) stress that support for Ukraine should be long-term and include funding from frozen Russian assets. Partito Democratico (Italy) states that refusal to support Ukraine would mean capitulation to the aggressor. At the same time, Partit Laburista (Malta) opposes military aid and insists on a diplomatic solution to the conflict. On the question of ending the war, the parties have different approaches. The PSOE (Spain) and the Partido Socialista (Portugal) stress that a just and lasting peace is only possible if Ukraine's territorial integrity is restored. The Partito Democratico (Italy) stresses the importance of diplomatic efforts, but notes that Ukraine's capitulation is unacceptable. At the same time, Partit Laburista (Malta) advocates dialogue and diplomacy, calls for the avoidance of further escalation and criticises military aid.

Most centre-left parties from **Central and Eastern Europe, the Baltic States and the Balkans** support Ukraine's accession to the EU, but with different conditions. The LSDP (Lithuania) and Nowa Lewica (Poland) clearly state that they will work for Ukraine's integration into the EU, in particular through the harmonisation of social, environmental and labour standards. PSD (Romania) and SDP (Croatia) are also positive on this issue, believing that Ukraine's accession will strengthen security in the region. The SDE (Estonia) stresses that Ukraine's membership in the EU is crucial for the future security of Europe. At the same time, the BSP (Bulgaria) supports the opening of accession negotiations, but also advocates a gradual normalisation of relations with Russia. Demokratikus Koalíció (Hungary) notes that Ukraine must meet all the conditions for membership, while Socialni Demokrati (Slovenia) supports EU enlargement without mentioning Ukraine. On the issue of Russian aggression, most parties in the region condemn Russia's actions and support Ukraine. The SDE (Estonia) and LSDP (Lithuania) stress that Ukraine's victory is a guarantee of security for the whole of Europe and must therefore be supported by all available means. Nowa Lewica (Poland) explicitly calls for the establishment of an international tribunal to punish the Russian leadership for war crimes. PSD (Romania) stresses the need for the international community to be united in confronting the threat posed by Russia. At the same time, BSP (Bulgaria) takes a more neutral approach, insisting on a diplomatic solution to the conflict and the gradual lifting of sanctions against Russia. Saskaņa (Latvia) avoids taking a clear position on the war, instead stressing the importance of developing cooperation with post-Soviet countries and China. On the question of aid to Ukraine, most parties in the region support economic, humanitarian and military assistance. SDE (Estonia) calls for more arms supplies and stresses that NATO and the EU should increase military assistance to Kyiv. Nowa Lewica (Poland) supports both military aid and a post-war reconstruction programme for Ukraine, as well as the cancellation of its foreign debt. PSD (Romania) said it was actively working with Poland to coordinate the policy of assistance to Ukrainian refugees.

SDP (Croatia) supports the provision of material and technical equipment to the Ukrainian army. At the same time, BSP (Bulgaria) opposes the militarisation of the Black Sea and does not support military assistance to Ukraine. Saskaņa (Latvia) avoids any mention of assistance to Kyiv and focuses on protecting the rights of national minorities, in particular Latvia's Russian-speaking population. Regarding possible ways to end the war, most parties in the region believe that it should end with a Ukrainian victory. The SDE (Estonia), LSDP (Lithuania), Nowa Lewica (Poland), PSD (Romania) and DK (Hungary) state that the war can only end with the restoration of Ukraine's territorial integrity and the military defeat of Russia. At the same time, BSP (Bulgaria) takes a more cautious stance, calling for peace talks and the normalisation of relations with Russia, including the lifting of sanctions. Saskaņa (Latvia) does not take a clear position, confining itself to general statements about the need to "improve prosperity" through foreign policy.

In general, the Party of European Socialists shows common trends: all the parties analysed support Ukraine in its fight against Russian aggression, although the level of support depends on regional political and economic factors. Northern Europe and Central and Eastern Europe take the toughest stance towards Russia, advocating stronger sanctions and military aid. Western European parties generally support sanctions and military aid, but are more cautious in their approach, especially in Germany. Southern Europe shows support for Ukraine, but emphasises diplomatic solutions to the conflict. The issue of Ukraine's European integration is widely supported, but with an emphasis on the need to meet EU standards. Thus, the PEP remains one of the main political associations supporting Ukraine, although approaches to support vary according to national interests and political context.

5. The Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe Party (ALDE Party)

For the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe and its representatives in the European Parliament (the Renew Europe group), the topic of Ukraine constituted a significant element in the electoral proceedings. The party called for "votes for liberals to support Ukraine in these European elections" and considers the war in Ukraine to be a common struggle against the Russian Federation to protect democratic values. The party has advocated for the augmentation of military support for Ukraine until the achievement of victory, the provision of assistance in post-war reconstruction, and the establishment of a mechanism for the transfer of frozen Russian assets to the victims. In this regard, the party has called for an increase in the capacity of the defence industry to assist Ukraine in achieving victory in the war, and has promised to appoint a special representative for these issues. Furthermore, the party encourages Ukraine's involvement in joint defence initiatives and the imposition of additional sanctions on Russia. The alliance endorses Ukraine's membership of NATO and the EU, contingent on the provision of appropriate security guarantees, with the objective of achieving the Copenhagen criteria by 2029.

In **Western Europe**, the Belgian liberal parties Open VLD and MR support Ukraine's European integration, as does NEOS (Austria), but believe that full membership is possible only after the war is over. The French Renaissance Party has articulated a clear stance on Ukraine's security, defining it as a matter of broader European significance. Consequently, the party has expressed active support for Ukraine's accession to the European Union. In Germany, the FDP supports European integration but emphasises the need for structural reforms in Ukraine, while the FW sees Ukraine's accession as a way to ensure stability, albeit criticising excessive imports of Ukrainian agricultural products. The Demokratesch Partei (Luxembourg) acknowledges the strategic significance of Ukraine's accession, yet underscores the necessity for the EU to reform its Common Agricultural Policy as a prerequisite for

this. The Dutch VVD and D66 express support for Ukraine's European integration, yet underscore the imperative for the fulfillment of all accession criteria. Notably, D66 highlights the ramifications for EU agricultural policy. With regard to the Russian aggression, all of the aforementioned parties have issued a strong condemnation of it. NEOS (Austria) considers the war not only a threat to Ukraine, but also to European values and freedom. MR (Belgium) has advocated for the reinforcement of sanctions against Russia and the utilisation of frozen assets. Renaissance (France) asserts that providing assistance to Ukraine is instrumental in ensuring European security. The German FDP characterises Russia as an imperialist threat and has called for its isolation in international organisations. The FW regards the war as a challenge to global security, while the Luxembourg DP supports increased defence spending in response to Russian aggression. The Dutch parties VVD and D66 emphasise the importance of international justice and punishment of the Russian leadership. The majority of parties advocate for the provision of economic, humanitarian, and military assistance to Ukraine. NEOS, MR, FDP, Renaissance and VVD openly advocate increased military supplies, while FDP supports the provision of long-range missiles and permission to strike Russian territory. MR and NEOS have also advocated for financial support, including the utilisation of frozen Russian assets. DP and D66 emphasise the need to reform the EU's agricultural policy in connection with Ukraine's potential membership. The majority of parties advocate also for the cessation of hostilities upon the restoration of Ukraine's territorial integrity. The FDP (Germany) has explicitly stated that if Russia is not ready for negotiations, the war should end militarily. Renaissance emphasises the necessity to establish the conditions for Ukraine's victory in order to avert potential risks in the future. FW's position is that the terms of peace should be determined by Ukraine itself, and that the EU should guarantee sanctions pressure on Russia. VVD and D66 have advocated the establishment of an international court for war criminals, a proposal which includes Putin.

In terms of regional dimensions, liberal parties in the **North Europe** have expressed support for Ukraine's accession to the European Union. The Danish Venstre Party has emphasised the necessity of establishing an interim defence partnership between Ukraine and the EU, given the potential duration of the accession process. The Danish Social Liberal Party also supports Ukraine's gradual integration, depending on its progress in implementing reforms, while the Moderates party recognises the complexity of the integration process, proposing a phased approach to membership. In addition, the political parties of Finland, namely Suomen Keskusta and Svenska folkpartiet i Finland, have underscored the significance of EU enlargement in terms of security, while concurrently emphasising the imperative to fulfil all the necessary accession criteria. Fianna Fáil (Ireland) has articulated the most pronounced support for a swift integration process for Ukraine, perceiving it as a pivotal factor in ensuring Europe's stability. Sweden's Centre Party and Liberal Party advocate for EU enlargement and pledge to provide enhanced assistance in implementing reforms, while the Liberal Party underscores the necessity for a special membership review procedure for Ukraine. The attitude of all the parties in the region towards Russian aggression in Ukraine is unequivocally negative, with the exception of Independent Ireland, which generally avoids discussing international issues. The Moderates (Denmark) acknowledge that the West underestimated the threat from Russia back in 2014, following the annexation of Crimea. The Swedish People's Party in Finland explicitly articulates the strategic objective of Russia's complete defeat, while Fianna Fáil (Ireland) conceptualises the war not only in a military context, but also in relation to Europe's energy security. With regard to the provision of assistance to Ukraine, the majority of parties express support for military, economic, and humanitarian aid. The Danish Moderates consider arms supplies to be pivotal to Ukraine's victory, while the Finnish parties propose the utilisation of frozen Russian assets to finance its reconstruction. Liberalerna (Sweden) advocates for the establishment of a special EU representative to oversee military assistance to Ukraine. Fianna Fáil emphasises support for Ukrainian youth through educational programmes such as Erasmus. Conversely, Independent Ireland has voiced concerns regarding the financial implications of providing assistance to Ukraine, perceiving them as potentially profligate. On the matter of ending the war, the majority of parties concur that it should end in a Ukrainian victory. Liberalerna (Sweden) explicitly states that Europe must defeat Putin. The Svenska folkpartiet i Finland and Moderates (Denmark) emphasise the need to increase sanctions and pressure on Russia, while Fianna Fáil focuses on achieving Europe's energy independence from Russia as part of its strategy to combat Russian aggression.

It is notable that, within the current European Parliament, only one party from **Southern Europe** - the Portuguese Iniciativa Liberal, represents the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe (ALDE). This party notes that the Southern European war in Ukraine remains a powerful attack on the integrity of Europe and the rules-based international order. In light of these considerations, the party asserts that Portugal should continue to bolster its capabilities, both in terms of logistical and military support for Ukraine and in terms of fortifying NATO's borders in the face of the Russian threat through its armed forces. Moreover, the Iniciativa Liberal advocates for Ukraine's accession to the European Union, asserting it to be a "geopolitical imperative" due to the fact that, in this war, Ukraine is also fighting for "the security of the European continent and the preservation of European values".

Liberal parties in **Central and Eastern Europe** have expressed considerable support for Ukraine. While most parties in this region advocate for Ukraine's accession to the EU, the conditions they propose vary. For instance, the Estonian Reform Party, Latvian Unity Party and Lithuanian Freedom Party advocate for expedited integration, perceiving it as a pivotal factor in ensuring European security. Progresívne Slovensko (Slovakia) advocates for accession, underscoring the economic benefits it would bring to Slovakia and the EU. Conversely, both Eesti Keskerakond (Estonia) and the United Right Alliance (Romania) advocate for Ukraine's European integration, yet they emphasise the necessity for Moldova's accession to be addressed separately, citing Ukraine's need for additional time to assimilate. Gibanje Svoboda (Slovenia) also focuses on EU enlargement for the Western Balkans, without mentioning Ukraine. All parties in the region unequivocally condemn Russian aggression, perceiving it as a threat not only to Ukraine but also to the entire European continent. Eesti Reformierakond (Estonia), Latvian Attīstībai (Latvia) and Progresīve Slovence (Slovakia) emphasise that the defeat of Russia is a strategic goal. The United Right Alliance (Romania) underscores the pivotal role of the EU in countering Russian invasion and economic aggression. The Baltic states, in particular, advocate for the imposition of heightened sanctions against Russia, a position that encompasses the confiscation of Russian assets in favour of Ukraine. Conversely, Gibanje Svoboda (Slovenia) condemns the aggression, yet simultaneously underscores the significance of peace negotiations and a cessation of hostilities, a stance that contrasts with the more resolute positions adopted by the Baltic and Central European countries. With regard to the provision of assistance to Ukraine, all parties except one Balkan party support military, economic and humanitarian aid. Eesti Reformierakond (Estonia), Eesti Keskerakond (Estonia), Progresīve Slovence (Slovenia) and the United Right Alliance (Romania) have explicitly stated their support for the provision of arms and military equipment. The Baltic parties emphasise that Russia's frozen assets should be utilised for the reconstruction of Ukraine. Conversely, the Eesti Keskerakond (Estonia) endorses assistance to Ukraine, yet refrains from explicit statements regarding military support. Gibanje Svoboda (Slovenia) places greater emphasis on the humanitarian and diplomatic dimensions of assistance, refraining from explicit endorsement of military aid.

Consequently, the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats for Europe (ALDE) and its members in the European Parliament have demonstrated a robust stance in their support for Ukraine, albeit with discernible variations in their approach to European integration, military assistance, and sanctions against Russia across different regions. Northern Europe is characterised by its advocacy for increased military assistance to Ukraine, the imposition of sanctions on Russia, and its endorsement of Ukraine's accession to the European Union, contingent upon the fulfilment of specific criteria. Ireland's Fianna Fáil party is the most open supporter of rapid integration. In contrast, Western European liberal parties, while generally supportive of Ukraine's European integration, emphasise the necessity for substantial reforms before accession, as espoused by the NEOS, FW and D66 parties. There is a broad consensus in support of military aid and sanctions, with the war in Ukraine being viewed as a threat to the entire European continent. Central and Eastern Europe, notably the Baltic states, has emerged as the most enthusiastic proponent of Ukraine's European integration, viewing the defeat of Russia as a strategic imperative. Conversely, certain political parties in the region, notably in Romania and Slovakia, adopt a more pragmatic stance regarding Ukraine's accession, taking into account economic factors. In Southern Europe, ALDE is represented by the Portuguese Iniciativa Liberal, which regards Ukraine's accession to the EU as a geopolitical imperative and supports increased military assistance.

6. European Green Party (EGP)

The European Green Party accuses Russia of violating the principles of international law, peace and security, emphasising the threat of dependence on authoritarian regimes. Party representatives have articulated a consistent anti-Putin stance, emphasising the imperative to "counter Russian influence in European politics". The party has voiced support for the provision of financial and military assistance to Ukraine, asserting that Europe's security is inextricably linked to its own. Furthermore, the party asserts the necessity for democratic states to collaborate in the defence of human rights, shared values, and the rule of law. In their election manifesto, the Greens emphasise that Ukraine's future lies in the European Union. The manifesto calls for the expansion of the EU and pledges to assist aspiring candidates in attaining the Copenhagen criteria. Moreover, the Greens advocate for the reconstruction of Ukraine through the provision of renewable energy sources, modern infrastructure, and the establishment of a sustainable, inclusive economic framework.

In **Western Europe**, green parties advocate for Ukraine's European integration, yet emphasise that all the necessary conditions for accession must be fulfilled. The Green Alternative (Austria), ECOLO (Belgium), Alliance 90/The Greens (Germany) and GreenLeft (Netherlands) have overtly expressed support for Ukraine's membership of the EU, while Groen (Belgium) and The Ecologists (France) have refrained from making explicit statements. A strong consensus exists among these parties regarding the condemnation of Russian aggression, with ECOLO (Belgium) emphasising the restoration of the 2014 borders. The Alliance 90/The Greens (Germany) and GreenLeft (Netherlands) actively advocate for the implementation of sanctions and a refusal to procure Russian energy. Their positions diverge, however, on the matter of military aid, with Alliance 90/The Greens (Germany) advocating for the provision of arms, albeit with constraints on their utilisation in accordance with international law, while GreenLeft (Netherlands) is in favour of augmenting it. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, GreenLeft (Netherlands) is calling for the establishment of an international tribunal to punish Russian war criminals, while Alliance 90/The Greens (Germany) is insisting on providing security guarantees for Ukraine after the war.

National green parties in the **Nordic region** have voiced their overt support for Ukraine's accession to the European Union, underscoring the significance of democratic principles. The Green Left (Denmark) and the Green League (Finland) emphasise the need for institutional development and compliance with the Copenhagen criteria, while the Green Party (Sweden) focuses on the rule of law and the functioning of a market economy. A collective stance has been adopted by these parties in expressing disapproval of Russian aggression, perceiving it as a menace to the foundations of democracy and stability within the European continent. Notably, the Green League (Finland) has not ruled out the possibility of sending a military contingent to Ukraine. In alignment with this stance, all three parties advocate for military, financial, and humanitarian aid. The Green Party (Sweden) has advocated for an immediate cessation of Russian energy imports and the establishment of a compensation fund to support the reconstruction of Ukraine. On the matter of the cessation of hostilities, the parties are unequivocal: Ukraine should emerge victorious and Russia should be defeated.

In **Southern Europe**, the Italian Green Europe party is the sole representative of the green party movement in EP. This party is less inclined to actively support military assistance to Ukraine and avoids specifics about Ukraine's accession to the EU, focusing on general anti-war rhetoric. Despite its condemnation of Russian aggression, the party's rhetoric is oriented towards diplomacy and the cessation of hostilities, rather than a military victory for Ukraine. The party opposes arms supplies, emphasising the necessity of international negotiations for achieving a peaceful settlement.

In **Central and Eastern Europe**, while most green parties generally support Ukraine, there is a variance in the emphasis placed on this support. We Can! (Croatia) and Vesna - Green Party (Slovenia) acknowledge Ukraine's European perspective, but do not detail the accession mechanisms. The

Progressives (Latvia) sidestep this issue, instead emphasising the reinforcement of the EU's defence. The Union of Democrats "For Lithuania" (Lithuania) asserts that Ukraine's triumph is paramount for the security of the region and advocates for the limitation of the veto on decisions concerning Ukraine's accession to the European Union. With regard to the issue of Russian aggression, the majority of parties strongly condemn Russia's actions. The Progressives (Latvia) emphasise the necessity to enhance the defence capabilities of the Baltic States, while the Union of Democrats "For Lithuania" (Lithuania) expresses direct support for military assistance to Ukraine. The Union of Democrats "For Lithuania" (Lithuania) places emphasis on the provision of humanitarian aid and expertise in demining. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, positions are divided. For instance, the Union of Democrats "For Lithuania" (Lithuania) asserts that peace is possible only after a complete victory of Ukraine, while We Can! (Croatia) believes that the EU should facilitate the development of a peace agreement between Ukraine and Russia.

It is evident that there is a diverse array of trends in support for Ukraine among the EU green parties. Parties in Northern, Western Europe and the Baltic states advocate military assistance to Ukraine, insist on sanctions against Russia and emphasise that Ukraine's victory is a prerequisite for peace. Conversely, southern Europe and the Balkans place greater emphasis on diplomatic efforts, often eschewing the issue of arms supplies. With regard to the matter of European integration, all parties that advocate for it underscore the necessity for Ukraine to adhere to all stipulated requirements and implement the requisite reforms. It is evident that the green parties in Northern and Central and Eastern Europe are more inclined to offer support to Ukraine, while in Southern Europe, the inclination towards a diplomatic resolution of the conflict is predominant.

7. Party of the European Left (PEL)

The European Left Party has issued a condemnation of the invasion of the Russian Federation, in accordance with international humanitarian law, and has expressed support for the implementation of sanctions against its military-industrial complex. The party's position is in favour of immediate peace negotiations between the parties involved in the conflict, the implementation of a ceasefire, and the withdrawal of Russian troops from Ukrainian territory. The party's opposition to the militarisation of the EU is reflected in its stance against military support for Ukraine, as it is against "NATO enlargement and a new arms race in Europe". The party asserts that the EU's membership criteria should entail a commitment to uphold human rights, the rule of law, and the socio-political rights of all citizens, including minority groups. Furthermore, the integration process should, in their opinion, not result in an escalation of military tensions.

Western European parties, including the french La France Insoumise (LFI), the Workers' Party of Belgium and the Party for Animals in the Netherlands, adopt a nuanced stance, characterised by critical evaluation while maintaining a degree of balance. While they generally support Ukraine's sovereignty, they advocate for the imposition of limits on military aid, emphasising the imperative for peaceful negotiations. For instance, the Belgian far left has voiced criticism of sanctions imposed on Russia, perceiving them as detrimental to the general populace rather than the political elite. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's integration into the EU, Western European leftists advocate this course of action on the condition that strict democratic and human rights standards are met. They regard the consolidation of European democratic principles as a favourable consequence of integration, while perceiving economic pressures on EU member states, notably the economically disadvantaged, as a menace. The Ukrainian issue is frequently employed as a rhetorical instrument to criticise the excessive militarisation of the EU. For instance, the political movement known as "Rebel France" has advocated for diplomatic solutions and denounced the escalating budget allocated to the EU's defence expenditures, perceiving it as a deviation from the Union's historical commitment to peacekeeping operations.

In contrast, the extreme left-wing parties in **Northern Europe**, including the Sweden Democratic Party, the Left Union of Finland and Sinn Féin in Ireland, have adopted a more consistent pro-Ukrainian stance. These parties have been known to advocate for a multifaceted approach to the crisis, encompassing support for humanitarian and economic aid, as well as military assistance, with a particular emphasis on safeguarding democratic principles. For instance, the Sweden Democratic Left Party has put forward a proposal to reinforce sanctions against Russia and maintain military support for as long as necessary. With regard to Ukraine's integration into the EU, these parties support the process but insist that all membership standards be met. The political left in northern Europe places significant emphasis on the potential benefits of Ukraine's accession, including the stabilisation of the region and the reinforcement of European unity. However, these actors simultaneously caution against the potential for deterioration in relations with Russia. The Ukrainian issue is employed as a symbol of the struggle for democracy in their rhetoric. For instance, Sinn Féin underscores the imperative to endorse the Ukrainian peace proposal, whilst concurrently censuring Western nations for their perceived inadequacy in enforcing international law. The northern left demonstrates the greatest unity on the issue of Russian aggression: Russia is unambiguously identified as the aggressor, and support for Ukraine is unequivocal. Their appeals encompass calls for increased military aid and the imposition of economic sanctions targeting Russia.

The stance adopted by far-left parties in **Southern Europe** is more nuanced. For instance, Spain's Podemos and Italy's Five Star Movement advocate for the de-militarisation of the conflict, emphasising the provision of humanitarian aid. Greece's Syriza, while expressing support for Ukraine's territorial integrity, also criticises NATO, perceiving it as a factor contributing to the conflict's destabilisation. Conversely, the Greek Communist Party and AKEL in Cyprus partially accuse Ukraine of provoking the conflict due to its aspiration to integrate into NATO, thereby demonstrating an anti-American stance. In regard to Ukraine's potential accession to the European Union, the southern parties' position is confined to calls for reforms and respect for human rights. ACEL and the Left Bloc in Portugal advocate for the cessation of military blocs as a prerequisite for Ukraine's accession, while Podemos underscores the potential economic implications of integration, namely the exacerbation of economic inequality. Among the merits, left-wing parties recognise the democratic potential of Ukraine's European integration, while they perceive a possible exacerbation of social and economic problems in the EU due to the significant costs of Ukraine's reconstruction as a threat. The utilisation of Ukrainian issues in their rhetoric is predominantly employed for the purpose of criticising NATO and Western military strategies. Their advocacy for diplomatic negotiations is indicative of their pacifist leanings and their apprehension of the war's escalation. While the majority of parties recognise Russia as the aggressor, their criticism is often directed at the West, which they accuse of instigating the conflict. Concurrently, support for Ukraine is predominantly manifested through humanitarian programmes, with military assistance being regarded as unacceptable due to the risk of escalation.

In **Central and Eastern Europe**, there are no political parties that espouse this stance.

The Party of the European Left (PEL) has issued a condemnation of Russia's invasion, has expressed support for sanctions, but has advocated for peace talks and a ceasefire, and has avoided endorsing military aid to Ukraine due to its anti-militarist stance. The Party's stance on Ukraine's integration into the European Union is contingent upon the respect of human rights and democratic principles. The stance adopted by left-wing parties on the Ukraine crisis is subject to considerable variation depending on the geographical location. In the Nordic countries of Sweden, Finland and Ireland, for instance, there is a notable pro-Ukrainian stance, with support for both economic and military assistance, as well as stringent sanctions against Russia. These parties regard the war as a struggle for democracy and European stability. Conversely, Western European leftists (France, Belgium, the Netherlands) advocate for Ukraine's sovereignty, though they are circumspect regarding military assistance, emphasising the role of diplomacy. These parties utilise the Ukrainian issue as a platform for criticising the EU's militarisation and sanctions policy, perceiving them as detrimental to the European population. Conversely, the stance adopted by leftist parties in Southern Europe (Spain, Italy, Greece, Cyprus, and

Portugal) is more equivocal. While they recognise the territorial integrity of Ukraine, they criticise NATO and military assistance, emphasising the risks of escalation. Some parties (e.g. AKEL, CPG) even accuse the West of provoking the conflict. Their position on Ukraine's European integration is nuanced, conditional upon the implementation of reforms and the maintenance of neutrality in security matters. In general, the left-wing parties in Europe can be divided into three main groups: the northern left is the most pro-Ukrainian, the western left balances between support for Ukraine and anti-war rhetoric, and the southern left is the most sceptical, criticising both Russia and the West.

8. European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) Party

The European Conservatives and Reformists condemn the full-scale invasion as a manifestation of Russian colonialism, which was condoned in Europe by neglecting security. In this regard, the party has made several pledges, including an augmentation of its support for Ukraine (including military assistance), a reinforcement of the efficacy of sanctions against Russia in order to achieve Ukraine's victory, and a support for the authorisation of Western weapons to strike at Russian territory and the confiscation of Russian assets.

In the context of **Western Europe**, the New Flemish Alliance (Belgium) advocates for Ukraine's European integration, while underscoring the imperative of strict adherence to the Copenhagen criteria and the pursuit of anti-corruption measures. SGP (Netherlands) is sceptical about further EU enlargement, pointing to the need for internal reforms in the Union, while ADR (Luxembourg) takes a clear anti-Ukrainian position, stating that Ukraine does not meet the criteria for membership and should remain a neutral country between the West and Russia. IDL (France) also opposes EU enlargement, arguing that it is a threat to national sovereignty. Attitudes to Russian aggression also vary. The SGP (Netherlands) has openly condemned Russia's actions and has called for increased sanctions pressure. The New Flemish Alliance advocates for sanctions and humanitarian aid, while underscoring the significance of diplomatic solutions. The ADR adopts a pro-Russian stance, contending that Ukraine must "find ways of reconciliation" with Russia. IDL refrains from overtly condemning Russia, instead advocating for a diplomatic resolution to the conflict. With regard to the means of ending the war, ADR and IDL advocate negotiations and compromise solutions with Russia, while SGP emphasises the strengthening of deterrence and sanctions pressure. The New Flemish Alliance also supports a diplomatic approach, seeing it as the main way to avoid further escalation. The provision of economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine remains a contentious issue for the regional parties. The SGP is in favour of providing political, military and humanitarian support to Ukraine, and also supports the provision of assistance to Ukrainian refugees. The New Flemish Alliance advocates for humanitarian aid, while refraining from active military engagement. ADR, on the other hand, emphasises the provision of economic aid for post-war reconstruction, while also advocating an end to all military support. The stance of IDL does not explicitly address the issue of aid, but rather underscores the potential risks of conflict escalation. The conclusion drawn from this analysis is that political actors espousing a strong Eurosceptic rhetoric are, in general, opposed to the provision of active support to Ukraine, while those representing more moderate conservative forces acknowledge the necessity for assistance but underscore its limitations.

In contrast, **Northern European** parties have adopted a generally pro-Ukrainian stance, expressing support for Ukraine's efforts in combating Russian aggression and offering military assistance. However, these parties hold divergent views on Ukraine's accession to the EU and the means to bring an end to the war. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's membership of the EU, the Finns Party is the most open to this concept, advocating for Ukraine's accelerated accession for security reasons. Concurrently, the party emphasises the necessity of adapting EU agricultural policy to the specific

Ukrainian context. The Danish Democrats and the Swedish Democrats have not yet articulated a definitive stance on EU enlargement, instead focusing their energies on European defence capabilities and domestic issues within their respective nations. A strong anti-Russian stance is adopted by all three parties with regard to the issue of Russian aggression. The Danish Democrats argue that Russia's attack on Ukraine demonstrates the necessity for an autonomous EU defence policy, emphasising the importance of avoiding reliance on "despotic regimes". The Finns Party has articulated its stance on the necessity of curbing the Kremlin's imperialist aspirations and has expressed support for the implementation of sanctions. The Sweden Democrats, for their part, have declared an "unwavering" support for Ukraine, though they have not yet provided detailed proposals or strategies to support this stance. In terms of providing assistance to Ukraine, the Danish Democrats advocate military aid and the development of the European military-industrial complex to enhance the defence capabilities of Ukraine and the entire EU. The Finns Party, on the other hand, advocate for sustained economic and military assistance, the utilisation of frozen Russian assets, and the imposition of sanctions. The Sweden Democrats, too, have declared their support for Ukraine, albeit without specifying the measures they advocate. The Finns Party underscores the imperative for Ukraine to triumph in its war as a means to effectively deter Russian aggression. Conversely, the Danish Democrats perceive the war as underscoring the necessity for collective defence within the European Union. The Sweden Democrats, meanwhile, have adopted a strategy of focusing on domestic issues rather than offering a definitive stance on foreign policy.

The Southern European parties demonstrate a divergence in their approaches to Ukraine. With regard to Ukraine's membership in the EU, the positions of the analysed parties differ significantly. The Brothers of Italy (Italy) advocate for Ukraine's integration, contingent on a "merit-based approach," implying the fulfillment of all EU requirements. The Greek Solution (Greece) does not provide a direct response regarding Ukraine's membership prospects, but rather emphasises the necessity for a religious "bridge" between Ukraine and Russia, suggesting a potential inclination towards compromise with Russia. The National Popular Front (Cyprus) and the Spanish Left Front (SALF) do not address this issue. A further notable point of divergence is evident in attitudes towards Russian aggression. The Brothers of Italy have unequivocally expressed support for sanctions against Russia and military assistance to Ukraine. While not offering any justification for the invasion, Greek Solution accuses Ukraine of fuelling the conflict and calls for a halt to arms supplies. SALF, on the other hand, has adopted a stance that attributes the war to NATO, effectively denying Ukraine's agency in the conflict. The National People's Front of Cyprus refrains from evaluating the conflict, instead emphasising the defence of Cyprus' interests. With regard to the provision of military assistance to Ukraine, the analysis reveals that the Brothers of Italy are the sole party that explicitly endorses military aid. Greek Solution is opposed to the supply of weapons, while SALF and the National Popular Front of Cyprus have not commented on the issue. On the issue of ending the war, Brothers of Italy calls for diplomatic efforts in parallel with military assistance to Ukraine. The proposal by Greek Solution of the utilisation of Orthodoxy as a means of achieving reconciliation is indicative of an approach to conflict resolution that is not aligned with contemporary best practice. SALF and the National People's Front of Cyprus have not yet formulated detailed proposals, but the former party has indicated a preference for agreements between the US, China and Russia.

Significant variations are evident in the approaches adopted by political parties in **Central and Eastern Europe**. Nevertheless, common patterns can be identified: parties with a more pro-European orientation support Ukraine's integration, while right-wing and populist parties are more likely to take an isolationist or even pro-Russian stance. With regard to the matter of Ukraine's accession to the EU, Prawo i Sprawiedłospolita (Poland) advocates for the provision of an early membership prospect to Ukraine, perceiving it as a guarantee of European security. The ODS (Czech Republic) advocates for a gradual approach to EU enlargement, acknowledging the necessity to provide support to Ukraine. The Lithuanian Farmers and Greens Union (Lithuania) and Eesti Keskerakond (Estonia) advocate for Ukraine's economic, social and political integration, albeit without explicitly mentioning membership. Conversely, political parties such as AUR (Romania) and There is Such a People (Bulgaria) have adopted a stance that is neither explicit in its support nor explicit in its opposition, maintaining a stance of ambivalence. Attitudes towards Russian aggression also differ. PiS (Poland) considers Ukraine's

victory to be pivotal to Europe's security, while ODS (Czech Republic), Lithuanian Farmers and Greens Union (Lithuania) and National Alliance (Latvia) adopt a similar stance, advocating for more stringent sanctions and support for Ukraine. AUR (Romania) has adopted a stance that emphasises the necessity of energy independence from Russia, without explicitly condemning the aggression. Such a People (Bulgaria) and Dom i nacionalno okupljanje (Croatia) have refrained from issuing explicit assessments of the war, while LLRA-KŠS (Lithuania) has issued equivocal statements that condemn the invasion and also criticise anti-Russian media activities. With regard to the provision of assistance to Ukraine, the most active are PiS, ODS, Lithuanian Farmers and Greens Union and Eesti Keskerakond, which support military, economic and humanitarian aid. Dom i nacionalno okupljanje (Croatia) and National Alliance (Latvia) have focused on the defence of their countries, but also expressed support for Ukraine. Conversely, AUR, There is Such a People and LLRA-KŠS have either refrained from commenting on the issue or adopted a neutral stance. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, the most unequivocal stance is adopted by PiS, ODS and National Alliance, who emphasise that the triumph of Ukraine is indispensable for the establishment of peace in Europe. Conversely, other parties either refrain from issuing specific statements or emphasise the necessity for a political settlement, as evidenced by the positions adopted by LLRA-KŠS and There is Such a People.

A comprehensive analysis of the positions of the European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) member parties on Ukraine reveals significant regional variations in attitudes towards Ukraine's EU membership, support for the war, and policy towards Russia. In Western Europe, the prevailing sentiment among the parties is one of either overt opposition or a moderate stance on Ukraine's EU membership. A minority of parties advocate military assistance, with the Socialistische Partij (SGP) being a notable example. Conversely, other parties either restrict military assistance to a humanitarian level, as observed in the New Flemish Alliance, or are opposed to it, as evidenced by the stance of the ADR and IDL. Attitudes towards Russia also vary. SGP condemns the aggression and supports sanctions, while ADR and IDL adopt a more conciliatory stance, emphasising the need for a diplomatic solution. In Northern Europe, support for Ukraine is more pronounced, especially in the military and sanctions spheres. The Finns Party has overtly expressed support for Ukraine's accelerated accession to the EU, while the Danish Democrats and Sweden Democrats have focused on European defence capabilities, refraining from making specific statements on EU enlargement. While all three parties condemn Russia and advocate for sanctions and military assistance, the Sweden Democrats have demonstrated a limited degree of initiative in practice. Conversely, southern European parties demonstrate a less pronounced level of support for Ukraine in comparison to their northern or central-eastern counterparts. The Brothers of Italy are the only party that consistently supports Ukraine in the military and sanctions aspects, while the others either take a neutral position (the Greek Solution) or covertly pro-Russian stance (SALF). The provision of assistance to Ukraine is predominantly constrained to humanitarian domains, or remains unaddressed. Two distinct groups of parties can be distinguished in Central and Eastern Europe. The first group consists of the pro-Ukrainian forces (PiS, ODS, Lithuanian Farmers and Greens Union, National Alliance, Eesti Keskerakond), who advocate Ukraine's rapid accession to the EU, military assistance, and condemnation of Russia's aggression. In contrast, populist and isolationist forces (AUR, LLRA-KŠS, There is Such a People, Dom i nacionalno okupljanje) eschew overt support for Ukraine, prioritising national interests and often adopt a neutral or pro-Russian stance. A number of key trends are identifiable. The degree of support for Ukraine, particularly with regard to security issues, is at its highest among the political parties in Northern and Central and Eastern Europe. Conversely, Western European parties evince a predominantly sceptical stance regarding Ukraine's EU membership and exhibit minimal support for the war. Southern Europe, in contrast, has demonstrated minimal engagement in providing support to Ukraine, with the notable exception of certain political parties, such as the Brothers of Italy.

9. Patriots for Europe (PfE)

While the PfE officially condemns Russia's invasion of Ukraine and supports Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity, including regions like Donbas and Crimea, it is important to note that PfE does not explicitly advocate for the territorial integrity of Donbas and Crimea. It emphasises the sovereignty of each EU member state in deciding the extent of their financial, military, and diplomatic support to third countries. This position was evident when the PfE proposed an alternative motion in the European Parliament, which, despite condemning Russian aggression, emphasised national discretion in supporting decisions. The formation of the group has exposed the divergent perspectives among its constituent parties with regard to the Ukraine conflict. For instance, while the PfE collectively criticises Russian aggression, some member parties advocate for agreements with the Kremlin, reflecting a more conciliatory approach. These internal differences suggest that, despite a unified condemnation of Russia's actions, the PfE lacks a cohesive strategy on supporting Ukraine, leading to a fragmented stance within the group.

Moreover, in **Western Europe**, the majority of parties have adopted a sceptical or negative stance on Ukraine's European integration. The Austrian Freedom Party (FPÖ) categorically denies the possibility of such integration, arguing that it is Austrian neutrality. The National Rally (RN) in France also opposes Ukraine's membership, explaining that it could pose potential threats to European farmers. The Flemish Interest (VB) in Belgium does not explicitly voice support or opposition, but emphasises the imperative for strict adherence to all accession conditions, including the imperative to combat corruption. The Freedom Party (PVV) in the Netherlands, an openly Eurosceptic force, is generally opposed to any EU enlargement, as it believes that it will increase the financial burden on donor countries, including the Netherlands. With regard to the issue of Russian aggression, the FPÖ has called for immediate negotiations and categorically does not support any assistance to Ukraine, as it believes that this contradicts the principle of Austria's neutrality. The VB has rarely commented on the war. The PVV's position on the matter is nuanced, with the party supporting the transfer of frozen Russian assets to Ukraine, but opposing the involvement of French military instructors in training the Ukrainian military. PVV clearly recognises Russia as the aggressor and supports Ukraine's struggle, but avoids concrete proposals for practical assistance. The issue of providing economic, humanitarian and military support to Ukraine is a contentious one, with the various parties holding divergent views on the matter. The FPÖ is firmly opposed to any allocation of financial resources or provision of weaponry, believing that these resources should be utilised for Austria's domestic requirements. The RN's stance is limited to financial measures, such as the transfer of frozen assets, and it does not endorse military assistance. PVV permits support for Ukrainian refugees in Europe, although it generally adheres to anti-immigration rhetoric. The VB has refrained from issuing explicit statements on this matter. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, the FPÖ is insistent that negotiations be initiated without delay, a position that in essence entails achieving a compromise with Russia. RN and VB have not proffered any concrete solutions, instead focusing on domestic issues. While the PVV supports Ukraine's struggle, it does not explicitly advocate for any particular diplomatic or military approach to end the war.

In the context of **Northern Europe**, the Danish People's Party (Dansk Folkeparti) stands as the sole representative of the region within the European Parliament. Its position is moderate in comparison to that of other Eurosceptics. While maintaining a degree of scepticism with regard to Ukraine's accession to the European Union, the party is willing to consider integration, albeit with the caveat that all strict criteria are met. In the context of the ongoing war, Dansk Folkeparti advocates military assistance to Ukraine, while concurrently underscoring the imperative of safeguarding Danish national security. This approach is indicative of a pragmatic foreign policy that seeks to balance support for Ukraine with the protection of domestic interests.

In **Southern Europe**, the analysis of the parties reveals a lack of explicit support or rejection of Ukraine's accession to the EU. Chega (Portugal) avoids adopting a definitive stance, instead focusing on broader issues of European security and the EU's reliance on external suppliers. Vox (Spain) does

not mention the topic of EU enlargement in its manifesto or election campaign. The attitude towards Russian aggression in Ukraine is controversial. While Chega officially states that war crimes in Ukraine must be punished, party representatives express divergent opinions. One leader speaks of the possibility of sending Portuguese troops, while another asserts that an agreement is necessary to make Russia "feel comfortable". While Vox supports military assistance to Ukraine, it primarily employs this topic for political attacks on opponents and to draw parallels with the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, Chega's position is not one of consensus; a faction within the party posits that Ukraine's defeat is not an option, while another faction advocates for a "profitable compromise" with Russia. Vox has not proffered any solutions of its own on this issue. On the subject of economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine, these parties demonstrate an absence of consensus. The party has not put forward any specific measures of support, and its representatives hold divergent opinions on arms supplies and negotiations. Vox has expressed support for assistance to Ukraine as part of the Spanish government's broader policy agenda, though this issue does not occupy a prominent position in the party's agenda.

In **Central and Eastern Europe**, most parties either do not openly support the idea of Ukraine's European integration or avoid discussing it. ANO 2011 (Czech Republic) has a generally positive stance on EU enlargement, yet Ukraine is not specifically mentioned among potential members. Fidesz (Hungary) supports enlargement, but only in relation to the Western Balkans, avoiding any mention of Ukraine. Ruch Narodowy (Poland) is categorically against Ukraine's accession, arguing that it would be an economic burden for other EU countries. Latvija Pirmajā Vietā (Latvia) has not articulated a position on this matter. Consequently, the prevailing sentiment among populist and right-wing parties, which prioritise economic risks and social expenditures, is one of disinclination towards Ukraine's accession. In terms of a resolution to the war, Fidesz is calling for an immediate cessation of hostilities and the commencement of negotiations, regarding the war as a protracted conflict with no clear victor. Other parties have either failed to articulate any concrete proposals or have not engaged in the discourse at all. ANO 2011 does not explicitly name Russia as an aggressor, instead characterising the war as a problem exclusively for the Czech Republic and the EU. Fidesz adopts a "reconciliation" stance, asserting that the conflict lacks a military resolution and advocating for coexistence with Russia, whilst maintaining economic relations. Ruch Narodowy and LPV have scarcely mentioned the war, focusing instead on domestic issues such as the economy and migration. With regard to the provision of economic, humanitarian and military assistance to Ukraine, the parties adopt a predominantly sceptical or neutral stance. ANO 2011 criticises the EU's preoccupation with supporting Ukraine, focusing instead on the problems of its own citizens. Fidesz has accepted Ukrainian refugees but has not supported military assistance, as it seeks to avoid escalation of the conflict. Ruch Narodowy advocates for the reduction of social benefits for Ukrainian citizens in Poland and the imposition of restrictions on the import of Ukrainian goods. LPV has refrained from engaging in discourse on this matter.

An analysis of the positions of Patriots for Europe (PfE) reveals the absence of a cohesive strategy for Ukraine, despite the official condemnation of Russian aggression. The prevailing sentiment is one of scepticism about Ukraine's membership of the EU, particularly among parties in Western and Central and Eastern Europe, who perceive economic and political risks. In Western Europe, parties such as the FPÖ (Austria), RN (France) and PVV (Netherlands) oppose EU enlargement and generally avoid actively supporting Ukraine, although they recognise Russia as an aggressor. In Northern Europe, the Dansk Folkeparti (Denmark) adopts a more pragmatic stance, supporting military assistance but emphasising national interests. In Southern Europe, parties such as Chega (Portugal) and Vox (Spain) have adopted a position that is ambivalent on the matter of Ukraine's European integration, employing the Ukrainian issue primarily for domestic political purposes. In Central and Eastern Europe, parties such as Fidesz (Hungary) and Ruch Narodowy (Poland) either refrain from discussing Ukraine's EU membership or openly oppose it. These parties' stance on Ukraine's EU membership is informed by a nationalistic perspective, with some advocating for direct negotiations with Russia and others offering support to Ukraine exclusively in the form of humanitarian aid. The overall position adopted by the PfE

on Ukraine is one of ambiguity and inconsistency. For the majority of these parties, the issue of war and Ukraine's European integration is regarded as a domestic political tool rather than a strategic priority.

10. The Europe of Sovereign Nations (ESN)

The Europe of Sovereign Nations (ESN) is a recently formed political party that emerged in the aftermath of the European Parliament elections in July 2024. It comprises representatives of extreme right-wing nationalist parties from EU countries who espouse a strong Euroscepticism. The national member parties are represented in only two regions: Western Europe (France and Germany) and Central and Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland and Slovakia).

Notable far-right parties in **Western Europe**, such as the Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) in Germany and Reconquête! (R!) in France, have adopted a stance that is sceptical or openly pro-Russian with regard to the support of Ukraine, its European integration and the continuation of the sanctions policy against Russia. These views are in stark contrast to those espoused by the mainstream parties in their respective countries, who have voiced staunch support for Ukraine. With regard to Ukraine's accession to the European Union, both parties adopt a negative or evasive stance. The AfD refrains from direct comment on the matter, but its rhetoric on the need to restore cooperation with Russia and criticism of EU enlargement indicate its rejection of Ukraine's European integration. Similarly, the French party Reconquête! also avoids making specific statements in its programme documents, but opposes further EU enlargement as part of its nationalist ideology. Consequently, both parties regard Ukraine's accession to the EU as being incompatible with their political and economic interests. With regard to the issue of Russian aggression in Ukraine, these parties either downplay Russia's responsibility or even accuse the West of fuelling the conflict. The AfD characterises the war as a "complication" for Germany that harms its economic interests and calls for the immediate restoration of trade relations with Moscow, including the lifting of sanctions, the resumption of Nord Stream 2, and cooperation with the Eurasian Economic Union. Moreover, certain AfD representatives overtly disseminate the narrative that the West is responsible for perpetuating the war, thereby rationalising the Kremlin's actions. Reconquête!, a political movement led by Eric Zemmour, adopts a less radical stance yet one that echoes similar sentiments. Zemmour has advocated for the utilisation of Western weapons by Ukraine exclusively within its own borders, deeming the deployment of instructors and military personnel from France as a transgression of a "red line". In expressing this stance, Zemmour alluded to Putin's statements, thereby underscoring the party's pro-Russian ideological inclination. The political party AfD has adopted a stance of opposition to the provision of military, economic and humanitarian aid to Ukraine, advocating for the immediate cessation of all such support. They contend that such aid poses a threat to the German economy and asserts that their stance is not intended to "intensify the conflict". Reconquête! also opposes an increase in military aid and emphasises the necessity to avoid any actions that could "draw" France into the war. On the humanitarian side, the AfD criticises the costs of supporting Ukrainian refugees, while Reconquête! does not comment directly, but in the context of their general anti-migration rhetoric, it can be assumed that they also disapprove of the open door policy for Ukrainians. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, both parties advocate the initiation of peace negotiations; however, neither party has specified what conditions they deem acceptable. The AfD has advocated for the resumption of dialogue with Moscow and the lifting of sanctions, a position that, in effect, conveys a readiness to compromise on Russia's terms. Similarly, the Reconquête! party refrains from specificity in its discourse, yet its general rhetoric concerning "red lines" and the risks posed to France suggests a desire to bring the conflict to a close in a timely manner.

Nationalist parties in **Central and Eastern Europe** are predominantly sceptical or openly anti-Ukrainian, and they are opposed to Ukraine's accession to the EU and NATO. Furthermore, these nationalist parties criticise the sanctions policy towards Russia. Concurrently, in certain countries, such as the Czech Republic and Poland, the rhetoric of these parties has a greater emphasis on domestic socio-economic issues pertaining to Ukraine, as opposed to international geopolitical concerns. With regard to Ukraine's accession to the EU, the majority of the analysed parties are opposed or do not

21

Funded by
the European Union

express unequivocal support. The political parties of Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia have expressed concerns that Ukraine's accession to the EU would place an additional economic strain on their respective countries and could potentially lead to an escalation in the ongoing conflict with Russia. Mi Haz dorp advocates for a referendum on the autonomy of Transcarpathia, a stance that directly contravenes Ukraine's territorial integrity. The SPD (Czech Republic) has asserted that Ukraine's accession to the EU could potentially result in their countries being engulfed in war. The People and Justice Union (Lithuania) is the only party that has not yet articulated a definitive stance on this matter. With regard to the issue of Russian aggression, a significant number of these parties adopt a position that exonerates the Kremlin's actions. The Bulgarian party "Revival" characterises the war as "a consequence of the coup in Kyiv in 2014" and advocates for peace negotiations with Russia, perceiving it as a "brotherly country". Hnutie Republika (Slovakia) has explicitly attributed the primary cause of the war to NATO's eastward expansion, aligning with the Russian narrative of "oppression of the Russian minority" in Donbas. SPD (Czech Republic) has highlighted that the West is "prolonging the conflict" and has expressed concerns over the dissemination of disinformation regarding the low level of support for the war among Ukrainians. Mi Haz dorp (Hungary) interprets the war as a global conflict between the US and Russia and sees no role for Hungary in its resolution. The majority of the analysed parties have expressed a strong opposition to military assistance to Ukraine. The SPD (Czech Republic), Hnutie Republika (Slovakia), Nowa Nadzieja (Poland), Mi Haz dorp (Hungary) and Vidrozhennia (Bulgaria) have advocated for an end to arms supplies, asserting that such actions merely "prolong the bloodshed". The SPD has characterised Ukraine as a "corrupt regime" and its government as undeserving of financial assistance. Concurrently, in Poland and the Czech Republic, a heightened focus on domestic issues pertaining to Ukrainian refugees is observed. In Poland, the political party Nowa Nadzieja (New Hope) has advocated for an end to social benefits for Ukrainian citizens and a prohibition on the import of Ukrainian products, aligning with the anti-immigration sentiments prevalent among the Polish right. SPD (Czech Republic) leader Tomio Okamura has advocated for the repatriation of Ukrainians, citing the purported rise in tuberculosis cases among them. With regard to the cessation of hostilities, all of the aforementioned parties advocate for the initiation of peace negotiations; however, a pro-Russian bias is evident in their respective interpretations of this matter. The Bulgarian political party "Revival" asserts that the prospect of peace is contingent upon the cessation of military assistance to Ukraine. SPD (Czech Republic) asserts that negotiations are imperative for all parties, but contends that they are not necessarily aligned with the interests of the "globalist elites" that wield power in the EU and the US. The political party Hnutie Republika (Slovakia) refuses to recognise the war as "unprovoked", instead calling it a consequence of NATO's policy. Mi Haz dorp (Hungary) emphasises that the West should "open up" to Russia, end sanctions and initiate a new dialogue. In general, these parties tend to accuse the West of instigating the war and rejecting Russia's responsibility.

In summary, the far-right parties in Western Europe are openly opposed to Ukraine's accession to the EU, sanctions policy and military aid. Their stance is characterised by either a diminution of Russia's culpability for the war or an accusation that the West is responsible for its continuation. The political party Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) has advocated for the re-establishment of collaborative ties with the Russian government, while the political party Reconquête! has advocated for the limitation of military support for Ukraine, citing national interests as a primary concern. In general, these parties do not perceive the war in Ukraine as a struggle for independence, but rather as a threat to their own economy. In Central and Eastern Europe, ESN parties adopt even more radical positions. These parties not only oppose Ukraine's European integration but also actively disseminate Russian narratives about "NATO provocations" and the "coup in Kyiv in 2014". A significant proportion of these parties refute Russia's culpability for the war, oppose the provision of arms, and regard any economic assistance to Ukraine as financially onerous for their respective nations. Some of these parties, including Mi Haz dorp, advocate for the autonomy of Transcarpathia, a stance that directly contravenes Ukraine's territorial integrity. A general overview of the political landscape reveals that the ESN of the European far right is predicated on a foundation of Euroscepticism, isolationism and pro-Russian sentiment. While Western European parties focus on economic arguments against sanctions and assistance to Ukraine, those in

Central and Eastern Europe utilise anti-Western rhetoric and outright disinformation more frequently. Furthermore, these parties seek to portray Ukrainian refugees as a burden to national economies. Consequently, the ESN has emerged as the most pro-Russian bloc within the European Parliament, seeking to weaken EU solidarity in support of Ukraine and persistently rejecting the notion of Russia as an aggressor.

11. Conclusions

It is evident that the newly constituted European Parliament is predominantly comprised of pro-Ukrainian and pro-European factions, thereby signifying the persistence of substantial political and financial backing for Ukraine within the European Union. Conversely, the rise of right-wing Eurosceptics poses a threat to the EU's long-term cohesion on sanctions policy and military assistance. The predominant pro-European political parties (EPP, EPP, ALDE, Greens) have expressed unequivocal support for Ukraine, its efforts in combating Russian aggression, and its future EU membership. Conservative parties (ECR) also generally support military assistance, but express caution on the issue of Ukraine's accession to the EU. The extreme left (PEL) emphasises diplomatic solutions to the war, whilst recognising Ukraine's territorial integrity and adopting a moderate position on Ukraine's accession to the EU. Among the extreme right-wing Eurosceptics (PfiE, ESN), there is significant division. Some condemn Russia's aggression but oppose military aid and EU enlargement, while others openly take a pro-Russian stance.

The parties from **Nordic countries** (Denmark, Sweden, Finland, and Ireland) have been identified as exhibiting the most consistent and pronounced anti-Russian stance, supporting the imposition of more stringent sanctions, the provision of military assistance, and the accelerated integration of Ukraine into the European Union. Conversely, **Central and Eastern Europe** (Poland, the Czech Republic, and partly Slovakia) and the Baltic states espouse a robustly pro-Ukrainian stance, regarding Ukraine's triumph as a strategic imperative for regional security. However, it is notable that there are substantial pro-Russian factions in Hungary and Bulgaria that are opposed to the imposition of sanctions and military assistance. **Western Europe**, comprising Germany, France, Belgium and the Netherlands, has a generally supportive stance towards Ukraine, though it is more cautious regarding military aid and sanctions policy. Some parties, notably nationalists and populists, have been known to voice disapproval regarding the economic implications of supporting Kyiv. Conversely, **Southern Europe** (Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece) has demonstrated the most restrained support for Ukraine, often emphasising the need for diplomacy and the avoidance of the "militarisation of the EU". However, certain Southern European political parties, such as the Brothers of Italy, advocate military assistance.

A further point of divergence is evident in the regional distribution of support for Ukraine's accession to the European Union. The Baltic states, Poland, Finland, Denmark, and certain parties in the Netherlands and Germany advocate for Ukraine's accession, contingent upon the fulfillment of all stipulated criteria. Conversely, Germany, France, Austria, Spain and Italy acknowledge the possibility of Ukraine's accession but underscore the imperative for EU-wide reform prior to any expansion. Conversely, far-right political parties in Western, Central, and Eastern Europe are either opposed to Ukraine's membership or have put forward conditions that make rapid integration unfeasible.

Attitudes towards the war and military aid also vary considerably. European political parties such as the EPP, PES, ALDE, Greens, and ECR (with the exception of some parties in Western and Southern Europe) have expressed unequivocal support for military assistance to Ukraine. The Baltic States, Poland and Northern Europe are the most active supporters of increasing military aid. Conversely, certain political parties in Germany, France, Spain and Italy have expressed a more nuanced stance, committing to financial support but not to military assistance. Conversely, far-right and nationalist groups in Western and Central Eastern Europe (ESN, part of the PfiE) have voiced unambiguous opposition, calling for the lifting of sanctions and negotiations with Russia.

The 2024 European Parliament elections have demonstrated that there are certain risks to the EU's continued support for Ukraine. The rise of Eurosceptic and pro-Russian parties could make it more difficult to decide on new sanctions and military assistance. Disagreements among pro-Ukrainian forces, including over military assistance, EU membership, and sanctions policy, may create difficulties in developing a common strategy. While the majority of parties advocate for Ukraine's accession to the EU, internal divisions among Western and Central and Eastern European countries have the potential to impede the enlargement process. The financial implications of providing aid to Ukraine are likely to become a contentious issue in future debates, particularly among Eurosceptics.

It is anticipated that the European Parliament will maintain a pro-Ukrainian majority following the 2024 elections, thereby ensuring the continuity of EU support for Ukraine in its efforts to counter Russian aggression. However, the rise of far-right Eurosceptics and nationalists poses challenges to EU unity, especially in the areas of sanctions, military aid, and EU enlargement. The most consistent allies of Ukraine are the countries of Northern and Central and Eastern Europe, while in Western and Southern Europe, support is more restrained and depends on domestic political calculations. The political landscape of the European Parliament in 2024 is characterised by a balance between maintaining support for Ukraine and shifting the focus to the EU's internal problems.

12. List of References

Austria

1. Elections in Austria. (n.d.). https://www.bmi.gv.at/412_english/start.aspx.
2. Europawahl 2024. (n.d.). https://www.bmi.gv.at/412/Europawahlen/Europawahl_2024/start.aspx
3. Welle, D. (2024, June 30). Hungary: Orban announces new far-right European alliance <https://www.dw.com/en/hungary-orban-announces-new-far-right-european-alliance/a-69517687>
4. Decision - 2023/2061 - EN - EUR-LEX. (n.d.). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2023/2061>.
5. 2024 European elections: National rules | Think Tank | European Parliament. (n.d.). [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)754620](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA(2023)754620)
6. National results Austria | 2024 Election results | 2024 European election results | European Parliament. 2024 European Election Results. <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/national-results/austria/2024-2029/>.
7. Kommunistische Partei Österreichs (KPÖ) (2024, October 26). KPÖ - Kommunistische Partei Österreichs. KPÖ. <https://www.kpoe.at/>.
8. Die Grünen (2024, 6 December). Startseite - Die Grünen. <https://gruene.at/>
9. SPÖ - Für ein gerechtes Österreich (2024, December 2). SPÖ. <https://www.spoe.at/>.
10. Neos. (2022, October 11). Bundesländer. Alle Informationen Zur Politischen Partei NEOS. <https://www.neos.eu/bundeslaender>
11. Volkspartei, D. (n.d.). Die Volkspartei. Die Volkspartei. <https://www.dievolkspartei.at/>.
12. Www.fpoe.at - Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs. (n.d.). <https://www.fpoe.at/>.

Belgium

1. PTB - Parti du Travail de Belgique (n.d.) (15 July 2024). <https://www.ptb.be/>
2. PTB/10 questions and answers à proposals for the peace process in Ukraine. <https://www.ptb.be/actualites/10-questions-et-reponses-propos-de-la-querre-en-ukraine>
3. Programme Européen. (n.d.). (15 July 2024). <https://www.ptb.be/programme-europeen>
4. PTB Belgique (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/ptbbelgique>.
5. PVDA - Partij Van De Arbeid van België (n.d.). <https://www.pvda.be/>.
6. PVDA Programme. (n.d.). Retrieved 15 July 2024, <https://www.pvda.be/programma>
7. Vrede. (n.d.). PVDA. <https://www.pvda.be/programma/vrede>.
8. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/pvdabelgie>.
9. Choisir un horizon. (n.d.). Ecolo. <https://ecolo.be/>.
10. Notre programme 2024. (n.d.). Ecolo. <https://ecolo.be/programme-2024/>.
11. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/Ecolo>.
12. Groen. (n.d.). Groen. <https://www.groen.be/>.
13. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/groen>.
14. Parti Socialiste. (n.d.). Parti Socialiste. <https://www.parti-socialiste.fr/>.
15. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/partisocialiste?lang=fr>.
16. vooruit.org/programme. (n.d.). <https://www.vooruit.org/programma-download>.
17. SP.nl. (n.d.). Www.sp.nl. <https://www.sp.nl/>.
18. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/SPnl>.

19. Accueil. (n.d.). MR. <https://www.mr.be/>.
20. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/MR_officiel.
21. Facebook. https://www.facebook.com/DavidClarinvalMR/posts/762394565697274?ref=embed_post
22. CSP Ostbelgien (Christlich Soziale Partei) | Ostbelgien. (n.d.). Csp-Dg. Retrieved 15 July 2024, from <https://www.csp-dg.be/>
23. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/CSPOstbelgien>.
24. Engagés, L. (n.d.). Les Engagés | Pour une société régénérée. Les Engagés. <https://www.lesengages.be/>.
25. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/LesEngages_be.
26. Engagés, L. (n.d.). Notre programme - Elections 2024 | Les Engagés. Les Engagés. <https://www.lesengages.be/notre-programme-elections-2024/>
27. Startpagina | Nieuw-Vlaamse Alliantie (N-VA). (n.d.). Www.n-va.be. <https://www.n-va.be/>.
28. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/de_NVA/.
29. X.com. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/jvanoverveldt>.
30. Welkom op de website. (n.d.). Vlaams Belang. <https://www.vlaamsbelang.org/>.
31. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/vlbelang>.
32. cd&v. (n.d.). Www.cdenv.be. <https://www.cdenv.be/>
33. CDENV/programme. (n.d.). https://www.cdenv.be/jongeren_voor_europa.

Bulgaria

1. FOR A DECENT BULGARIA IN A PEACEFUL EUROPE! PRE-ELECTION PLATFORM FOR THE ELECTION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2024 [BSP-PlatformEI-2024.pdf \(bsp.bg\)](#)
2. State Tax Service of Bulgaria - Manifesto for the State Tax Service. State Tax Service of Bulgaria - Beginning. URL: <https://www.dps.bg/izbori-2024/manifest-na-dps.html> (accessed 15.07.2024).
3. Priority GERB priorities [evrodeputati-.pdf \(gerb.bg\)](#) areas for the work of MEPs from the party
4. Parliament.bg. URL: <https://parliament.bg/bg/parliamentarygroups/3364> (accessed 15.07.2024). IMPORTANT: INTERNATIONAL ACTION AND THE EUROPEAN UNION
5. [Attention Required! | Cloudflare \(ppdb.bg\)](#)
6. [WHAT TO SAY AND HOW TO SAY IT \(vazrazhdane.bg\)](#)
7. You will be lost in Ukraine <https://vazrazhdane.bg/?s=україна> - Vrazhdanie. Vrazhdane. URL: <https://vazrazhdane.bg/?s=україна+https://vazrazhdane.bg/?s=україна+> (accessed 15.07.2024).

Croatia

1. Izborni programme - HDZ. HDZ - EU. <https://eu.hdz.hr/izborni-program/>
2. Možemo! <https://mozemo.hr/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/A4-program-2024-EU-Final.pdf>
3. PENAVA: NAORUŽANI VOJNICI ZARAČENIH STRANA NEMAJU ŠTO TRAŽITI NA TERITORIJU RH! | Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/share/v/NVZH6zoRwSr5tFJW/?mibextid=QwDbR1>
4. Political programme of the Domovinskog Pokreta. <https://dp.hr/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Politicki-pogram-Domovinskog-pokreta.pdf>
5. SDP - Socijaldemokratska partija Hrvatske. https://www.sdp.hr/wp/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/sdp_program_2024.pdf
6. The repercussions of the war in Ukraine on Croatia's Far Right - ECPS. <https://www.populismstudies.org/the-repercussions-of-the-war-in-ukraine-on-croatias-far-right/>
7. Sržić, A. (2024, 22 March). Svi su uz Ukrajinu, ali o Putinu uglavnom šute: Kako stranke dišu na temu rata koji drma Europeu. <https://www.tportal.hr/vijesti/clanak/svi-su-uz-ukrajinu-ali-o-putinu-uglavnom-sute-kako-stranke-disu-na-temu-rata-koji-drma-europu-foto-20240322>

Cyprus

1. Who is Fidias Panagiotou, the 24-year-old social media star turned Cyprus' 'third-largest party'?. in-cyprus.com | Latest News in Cyprus. URL: <https://in-cyprus.philenews.com/local/who-is-fidias-panagiotou-the-24-year-old-social-media-star-turned-cyprus-third-largest-party/> (date of access: 15.07.2024).
2. Wong, V. (2024, 10 June). Fidias Panagiotou: YouTube prankster from Cyprus elected as MEP. 3. BBC Home - Breaking News, World News, US News, Sports, Business, Innovation, Climate, Culture, Travel, Video & Audio. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c4nnnr72dqo>
3. APXIKH - Εθνικό Λαϊκό Μέτωπο (Ε.ΛΑ.Μ.). Εθνικό Λαϊκό Μέτωπο (Ε.ΛΑ.Μ.).
4. National Popular Front (ELAM). n.d. G. Gidis: "Neither with Russia nor with Ukraine - With the interests of Hellenism". Retrieved from <https://elamcy.com/>
5. 4.ΑΚΕΛ | Ανορθωτικό Κόμμα Εργαζομένου Λαού. (n.d.). European United Left/Nordic Green Left (GUE/NGL). Retrieved from <https://www.akeel.org.cy/en/category/european-united-left-nordic-green-left-gue/ngl/>
6. Democratic Rally. (n.d.). EpomeniMera_Manifesto_Final. Retrieved from https://www.disy.org.cy/EpomeniMera_Manifesto_Final
7. Democratic Party. (n.d.). Με Επίκεντρο Εσένα. Retrieved from <https://www.democraticparty.org.cy/>

Czech Republic

1. Ano. (2024). Česko pro tebe všeccko.
2. Kolář, O. [@ondrejkolartop09]. (2024, 28 May). Co s ruskými penězi v Evropě? Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7gPgugs361/>.

3. Okamura, T. [@tomio.cz]. (2024a, 8 March). In Ukraine and Russia, 13 % of students are in STEM/MARK programmes. The European share is 10 per cent. Přibližně třetina [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C4QFnqpo5aD/>.
4. Okamura, T. [@tomio.cz]. (2024b, 14 March). Je načase, aby se ukrajinští "uprchlíci" začali vracet domů. Počet lidí s tuberkulózou v Česku meziročně vzrostl o 64 případů [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C4f3AcqoVNw/>
5. Okamura, T. [@tomio.cz]. (2024c, 1 May). Ukrajinci odmítají bojovat za svoji vlast. Jen in Polsk se zákonné branné povinnosti na Ukrajině vyhýbá 235 tisíc ukrajinských mužů [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6cBkpBocT0/>
6. Okamura, T. [@tomio.cz]. (2024d, 3 May). French President Macron has made a call to Ukraine, as he has decided to open a new visa application to Ukraine. Stát by [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6gzPXsIX7n/>
7. Pirátská Strana. (2024a). Odvaha pro Evropu, Evropa pro tebe.
8. Pirátská Strana [@pirati.cz]. (2024b, 18 March). Přesně před deseti lety Rusko nezákonně anektovalo Krym. Je však stále nedílnou součástí Ukrajiny a nezmění to ani deset let [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C4qLSS4rXVU/>
9. Pirátská Strana (2024c, 28 March). V Praze vznikla meziparlamentní platforma dialogu se slovenskou opozicí. Jejím cílem je obrana demokracie. Hlavní web Pirati.cz. <https://www.pirati.cz/jak-pirati-pracuji/v-praze-vznikla-meziparlamentni-plattform-dialogu-se-slovenskou-opozici-jejim-cilem-je-obrana-demokracie/>
10. Pirátská Strana (2024d, 4 April). "Strategy je víc zbraní a munice, cíl je vítězství." Pirátská europoslankyně Gregorová přináší svědectví z Charkova. Hlavní web Pirati.cz. <https://www.pirati.cz/jak-pirati-pracuji/strategie-je-vic-zbrani-a-munice-cil-je-vitezstvi-piratska-europoslankyne-gregorova-prinasi-svedectvi-z-charkova/>.
11. Přísaha a. Motoristé. (2024). Memorandum. Koalice Přísaha a Motoristé. <https://www.prisahamotoriste.cz/memorandum>.
12. SPD a. Trikolora (2024). Programme SPD + Trikolora pro Evropské volby 2024.
13. Spolu. (2024a). Together for the European elections.
14. Spolu [@spolu koalice]. (2024b, 1 March). "Máme historickou zkušenost se sovětskou agresí v roce 1968. Podpora Ukrajiny v boji za svobodu z ní vychází a opírá [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3-j9SBsscX/>
15. Stačilo. (2024). Program.
16. Starostové a. nezávislí. (2024a, 22 April). To, že americký Kongres schválil pomoc Ukrajině, je dobrá zpráva. Evropa ale nemůže neustále spoléhat na pomoc Američanů. Je na [Video attached] [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=316492017928031&ref=sharing>
17. Starostové a. nezávislí. (2024b, 24 May). Ukrajinci do českého státního rozpočtu víc přispívají, než z něj čerpají. Pomoc je ale především o lidskosti, ne o penězích [Video attached] [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=1682539875889036&ref=sharing>
18. Starostové a. osobnosti pro Evropu. (2024). Volební programme.

Denmark

1. DANMARKSDEMOKRATERNE. URL: https://danmarksdemokraterne.dk/forside/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/EU_V4_low.pdf.
2. Europæisk samarbejde mellem selvstændige nationalstater - Det Konservative Folkeparti. Det Konservative Folkeparti. URL: <https://konservative.dk/politik/eu-2024-2029/>.
3. Forside - Moderaterne - Den fornuftige stemme. URL: https://moderaterne.dk/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/EuropapolitiskRamme_230923.pdf.
4. Frihed-Fred-Fremgang LAs EU-programme 2024. URL: <https://www.liberalalliance.dk/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Frihed-Fred-Fremgang-LAs-EU-program-2024.pdf>.
5. Hjem - Enhedslisten. URL: https://enhedslisten.dk/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/EP_Valgprogram_2024.pdf.
6. Programmet Radikale Venstres. URL: https://www.radikale.dk/media/nzrbor2j/europapolitisk_valgprogram_juni2023.pdf.
7. SF - Socialistisk Folkeparti. URL: <https://sf.dk/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/ep-valgprogram-vedtaget-020423.pdf>.
8. Socialdemokratiet. URL: <https://www.socialdemokratiet.dk/media/fl1fx1d/ep-valgprogram.pdf>.
9. Venstre Eu Programme 2024-2029. URL: <https://www.venstre.dk/Resources/Persistent/f/d/8/c/fd8ca0cb4b37c7245928896479b142c707493e5e/2023.12.14-Venstre%20Eu%20program-2024-2029-venstre.pdf>
10. Vores mærkesager i EU - Dansk Folkeparti - Danskerne Først. Dansk Folkeparti - Danmark skal være trygt. URL: <https://danskfolkeparti.dk/maerkesager/vores-maerkesager-i-eu/>.

Estonia

1. European Parliament. Election results Estonia <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/national-results/estonia/2024-2029/>
2. Isamaa. Euroopa Parlamendi valimised 2024. Isamaa erakonna valimisprogramm <https://isamaa.ee/ep24-programmi/>
3. Sotsiaaldemokraatlik Erakond. SOTSIAALDEMOKRAATLIKU ERAKONNA VALIMISPROGRAMM EUROOPA PARLAMENDI 2024 VALIMISTEKS <https://valimised.sotsid.ee/programm/>
4. Sotsiaaldemokraadid. Tanel KIIK: Ukraina presidendi visits aitab fookust hoida <https://www.sotsid.ee/tanel-kiik-ukraina-presidendi-visit-aitab-fookust-hoida/>
5. Sotsiaaldemokraadid. Raimond Kaljulaid: Eesti sõdurite saatmine Ukrainasse oleks plahvatusohtlik <https://www.sotsid.ee/raimond-kaljulaid-est-i-sodurite-saatmine-ukrainasse-oleks-plahvatusohtlik/>
6. Eesti Reformierakond. Manifest <https://reform.ee/euroopa-parlamendi-valimised-2024/manifest>

7. Reformierakond [@reformierakond]. (2024, 11 January) Peaminister Kaja Kallas rõhutas kohtumisel Ukraina president Volodõmõr Zelenskõiga, et Eesti usub Ukraina võitu [Photo] Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C1-Cj6gtruW/?hl=en>
8. Eesti Konservatiivne Rahvaerakond. "EESTI EEST EUROOPASI!" EKRE PROGRAMME 2024. AASTA EUROOPA LIIDU PARLAMENDI VALIMISTEKSTES <https://www.ekre.ee/eesti-eest-euroopas-ekre-programm-euroopa-liidu-parlamendi-valimisteks-2024/>
9. Eesti Konservatiivne Rahvaerakond [Eesti Konservatiivne Rahvaerakond]. Eesti Konservatiivse Rahvaerakonna esimees Martin Helme eesti poiste saatmisest Ukrainasse: "Poola presidendi Andrej Duda sõnul oli Pariisi kohtumisel 26.02 "kõige tulisem arutelu selle ümber, kas tuua Ukrainasse vägesid, ja "selles küsimuses ei jõutud kokkuleppele." Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/YvAivFSjDtxVa6M/>
10. Eesti Keskerakond. EESTI KESKERAKONNA EUROOPA PARLAMENDI VALIMISTE PLATVORM. <https://keskerakond.ee/et/45-hetkel-oluline/110-ep2024.html>

Finland

1. 2024 European elections: National rules | Think Tank | European Parliament. (n.d.). [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)754620](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA(2023)754620)
2. European Elections - Elections. (n.d.). Vaalit. <https://vaalit.fi/en/european-elections>.
3. Vaalit (En). (n.d.). <https://tulospalvelu.vaalit.fi/EPV-2024/en/index.html>.
4. National results Finland | 2024 Election results | 2024 European election results | European Parliament. 2024 European Election Results. <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/national-results/finland/2024-2029/>.
5. Europarlamentivaaliohjelma 2024 - Vasemmistoliitto. (n.d.). Vasemmistoliitto. <https://vasemmisto.fi/eurovaalit/eurovaaliohjelma/>.
6. Li Andersson on X: "Viime vuosien isot nullistukset koskevat erityisesti nuoriin: kuten korona ja Ukrainan sota sekä tulevaisuutta varjostavat luonto- ja ilmastokriisit. Siksi nyt on aika nostaa nuoret päätöksenteon keskiöön - tulevaisuudenuskon vahvistaminen on aikamme tärkeimpiä asioita. 3/3" / X. (2001, May 27). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/liandersson/status/1795052512581427522>
7. Vasemmistoliiton puheenjohtaja Li Andersson. . . - Vasemmistoliitto | Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/vasemmisto/posts/pfbid02ED8Z7DGsZGSyadPvAcSX16LfzydS8oU7ZAr8ri3212Rce6udsQd6fE2m9K42PUv6l?rvid=1UHFgjhLTNriLXrE#>.
8. Ulkomaalainen, äänestä Vihreitä Euroopan. . . - Vihreät - De Gröna | Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/vihreat/posts/pfbid02YWeqy9JfJnJybp2sZCtLdPjgqbH3HpdCEZVnD4FBbss4XULMxjLXNAaNSAgDLKzI?rvid=G19g2Fd76StgPm5o>.
9. Eurovaaliohjelma 2024 - Vihreät. (2024, May 3). Vihreät. <https://www.vihreat.fi/ohjelmat/eurovaaliohjelma-2024/>
10. Vihreät - De Gröna on X: "Kaikkein tärkein tavoitehan on, että Ukraina voittaa tämän sodan. Jos me olisimme ukrainalaisten asemassa, niin kyllä me toivoisimme, että muut maat tekisivät kaikki mahdolliset toimet, joilla voidaan hidastaa Putinia." - @VirtaSofia linjaa. #eurovaalit #vaalitentti" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/vihreat/status/1798780812810154489>
11. Vihreät - De Gröna on X: "Kenelle te annatte valtaa? Onko se laita- ja äärioikeisto? Vai onko se vaikka Vihreät, jotka ovat olleet aivan yhdenmukaisia Ukrainan tuen suhteen?" kysyy @VirtaSofia kokoomukselta, mutta jää ilman vastausta. #eurovaalit #vaalitentti" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/vihreat/status/1798790889474756689>
12. Sofia Virta on X: "Ukrainalaiset puolustavat koko Eurooppaa, myös meidän Suomeamme. Mitä tekee Orpon hallitus? Leikkaa vastaanottorahaa niiltä ukrainalaisilta, jotka ovat sotaa Suomeen paenneet ja joista monet ovat jo nyt leipäjonossa." / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VirtaSofia/status/1783539209199865947>
13. Sofia Virta on X: "Länsimaat ja EU ovat koko ajan asettaneet itselleen rajoja, miten Ukrainaa voidaan auttaa. On menty Putinin komennuksella ja pelätty eskalaatiota. Se on juuri sitä, mitä Putin on halunnut." Kiitos @VilleNiinisto painavasta viestistä. <https://t.co/sxnDEUe6pc> / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VirtaSofia/status/176643303678511430>
14. Ville Niinistö on X: "Toimittajat kyselevät pelkistävästi - hyvä niin. Yle kysyi pitäisikö EU-maiden lähettää sotilaita Ukrainaan, jos Venäjä uhkaa voittaa. Venäjä ei saa missään oloissa voittaa. Ei silti järkevää ennalta sanoa kaikkea. Kielto antaisi Venäjälle rohkaisua, myöntö varautumista." / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VilleNiinisto/status/1783435483457929468>
15. Ville Niinistö on X: "Tämä on se mittaluokka mitä Ukrainan auttamiseen aseellisesti on tehtävä, jotta sille on yhä mahdollista karkottaa Venäjän miehittäjä. Jos edes Suomessa ei ole valmiutta puhua tästä, olemme koko EU ongelmassa. USAn tuen hyytyminen ei ole etäinen skenaario vaan jopa odotettavaa." / X. (2001, May 22). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VilleNiinisto/status/1793162394111254671>
16. Ville Niinistö on X: "The time for half-measures has passed", says the letter demanding a total ban on Russian energy commodities in the EU initiated by the green lawmaker Ville Niinistö from Finland. A broad coalition of over 60 MEPs in a joint letter urging EU leaders: <https://t.co/UL33mmu6SJ>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VilleNiinisto/status/1763627501962543121>
17. Ville Niinistö on X: "Oksymoron. Sen sijaan että rakentaa maataloutta Venäjältä tulevien fossiileihin perustuvien lannoitteiden varaan kannattaisi kehittää kotimaista kiertotaloutta, kierrätyslannoitteita ja uudistavaa maataloutta maaperän laadun parantamiseksi. Ympäristö, vesistö, omavaraisuus 🍌" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/VilleNiinisto/status/1771650934659006576>
18. European elections 2024 - SDP. (n.d.). SDP. <https://www.sdp.fi/en/european-elections-2024/>.
19. Sosialidemokraatit on X: ". @AnttiLindtman: EU:n on tuettava Ukrainaa enemmän, jotta sota saadaan loppumaan ja jotta Venäjä ei saa tavoitteitaan läri. Ukrainan tulevaisuus on EU:ssa. #PystymmeParempaan" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/Demarit/status/1798026238575198591>

20. Sosialidemokraatit on X: ".@anttilindtman Meidän sukupolvemme tehtävä on pitää huolta siitä, että Ukraina voittaa. Meidän tehtävämme on antaa kaikki tarvittava resurssi Ukrainalle, eikä siirtää tätä päätöstä seuraaville sukupolville. #Vaalitentti #JoRiittää" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/Demarit/status/1798783724873732440>
21. Antti Lindtman ja Naton pääsihteeri Jens. . . - Sosialidemokraatit SDP | Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/sosialidemokraatit/posts/pfbid02FzS7LSNur9kBi3PUvkvBuHLcIFBnwNjcoV2tpxcrMhBQyFviBCCQ5n7UBqi22EjI?rddid=zMs4MpfFfR1Y91qr>.
22. Sosialidemokraatit on X: "Ukraine tarvitsee lisää tukea ja siihen tarvitaan EU:lta lisää varoja. Jos kaikelle sanoo pelkästään ei, niin silloin ei halua vahvistaa puolustusta. Meidän keino on EU:n omien varojen kehittäminen - ja kyllä ne Venäjän varat tarvitaan käyttöön. @AnttiLindtman #vaalitentti" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/Demarit/status/1795875582309269630>
23. Sosialidemokraatit on X: "Miten pakotteita pitäisi muuttaa, kysytään. @AnttiLindtman: Nyt täytyy iskeä sinne, mistä Putinin sotakassa täytyy. Venäjä kiertää kaasulle ja öljylle asetettuja pakotteita, tämä täytyy estää #Vaalitentti #JoRiittää" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/Demarit/status/1798780263876661727>
24. Suomen ja Ruotsin sosialidemokraatit. . . - Sosialidemokraatit SDP | Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/sosialidemokraatit/posts/pfbid0msAxHgn4jpnou9Bqmrh4vjHzVaBAHS8iNPtneCF2iH3Hk9aurVaWsJgvhMR4QpXSI?rddid=kYjBkZm5Ear9Jel#>
25. Antti Lindtman on X: "Nyt laitavoimat Euroopassa ja USA:ssa ovat pyrkineet heikentämään Ukrainalle annettavaa tukea ja pakotteita Venäjää vastaan. Tämä kehitys on pysäytettävä, tarvittaessa enemmistöpäätöksin." / X. (2001, May 18). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/AnttiLindtman/status/1791799180509274414>
26. Keskusta. (2024, May 14). Vaaliohjelmaa - Suomen keskusta. Suomen Keskusta. <https://keskusta.fi/politiikkamme/ohjelmia-ja-linjauksia/vaaliohjelmia/>
27. Video | Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=739079134822281&rddid=q8ANBmE3m6KdWLYL>
28. Elsi Katainen on X: "Tärkeä askel Ukrainan tukemisessa! ua Tänään julkistettu kahdenvälinen yhteistyösopimus takaa turvallisuusyhteistyön ja Suomen pitkäaikaisen tuen Ukrainalle, mikä on tukea koko Euroopalle. #SlavaUkraini <https://t.co/irbJQ0mxW3>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/ElsiKatainen/status/1775552950716301616>
29. Tuomas Vanhanen on X: "Neljä vuotta sitten 16.3.2020 hallitus totesi yhteistoiminnassa tasavallan presidentin kanssa Suomen olevan poikkeusoloissa koronavirustilanteen vuoksi. Edessä oli kovia aikoja monelle ja monella tavalla. Myös valtiontaloudelle. Kun eduskunta muuttamaa kuukautta ennen koronan" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/t_vanhanen/status/1769054871787864310
30. Hällfors, C. (2024, 13 March). Swedish People's Party in Finland's (SFP) European Election Programme 2024. European Elections 2024. <https://val.sfp.fi/en/sfp-eu-election-program-2024/>
31. Anders Adlercreutz on X: "Russia can lose. And it should lose, for the sake of the world - and for its own sake." <https://t.co/3zcA4GMxuh>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/adleande/status/1788474033958207749>
32. Speech by Minister Anders Adlercreutz at the Finnish Institute of International Affairs on 20 March 2024 - Finnish Government. (n.d.). Finnish Government. <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/en/-/10616/speech-by-minister-adlercreutz-at-the-finnish-institute-of-international-affairs-forum-19.-march-2024>
33. Pasi. (2024, May 23). National Coalition Party's EU election programme 2024 - kokoomus.fi. kokoomus.fi. <https://www.kokoomus.fi/national-coalition-partys-eu-election-program-2024/?lang=en>
34. Kokoomus on X: "@PetteriOrpo "Meidän täytyy tukea Ukrainaa, whatever it takes", @PetteriOrpo toteaa ua #kokoomus #SlavaUkraini #eurovaalit" / X. (2001, May 4). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/kokoomus/status/1786766517524222286>
35. Kokoomus on X: ""Nyt pitää tehdä se, että aseita, ammuksia ja välineitä saadaan Ukrainaan. Suomi on mukana Tšekin aloitteessa jolla haetaan valtava määrä ammuksia Ukrainaan", @PetteriOrpo toteaa Ukrainan tuestua 🇺🇸🇫🇮" / X. (2001, May 29). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/kokoomus/status/1795870232126394568>
36. Kokoomus on X: "@HennaVirkkunen "Nyt on autettava niin paljon, että Ukraina pystyy ajamaan Venäjän pois alueeltaan", @HennaVirkkunen linjaa. #kokoomus #eurovaalit" / X. (2001, June 5). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/kokoomus/status/1798418804831310138>
37. Kokoomus on X: "Tuuplaamalla puhtaan energian tuotanto varmistetaan omavarainen, kohtuuhintainen sähkö ja lämpö myös paukkupakkasilla. Putinin sotaa ei saa tukea: Euroopan on irtauduttava venäläisestä veröilystä ja -kaasusta. 🇺🇸🇫🇮" / X. (2001, June 5). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/kokoomus/status/1798376696283852866>
38. Ohjelmat | Kristillisdemokraatit. n.d. Kristillisdemokraatit. <https://www.kd.fi/tutustu/ohjelmat/>
39. Kristillisdemokraatit | KD on X: "2/X Eija-Riitta Korhola (MTV3): Ukrainaa pitää tukea kaikin tavoin. En kuulu niihin, jotka olisivat lähettämässä joukkoja. Katson, että silloin meidät tulkitaan sodan osapuoleksi. Se on merkittävä siirtymä, turvallisuusuhka. #KDpuolue #euro2024 @ER_Korhola" / X. (2001, June 5). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/KDpuolue/status/1798441061733253398>
40. Riitta Kuismanen on X: "Maailmanlaajuisesti on tuotteita, joita ei ole asetettu Venäjän pakotelistalle, esim. lannoitteet on katsottu ruokaturvan vuoksi kriittiseksi ja siksi niitä ei ole laitettu pakotteiden listalle. #eurovaalit @SariEssayah @KDpuolue <https://t.co/YJJIVyg6jX>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/RiittaKuismanen/status/1798780780149395797>
41. Eija-Riitta Korhola on X: "Se ulottuu paljon pitemmälle. Ei tuon olisi pitänyt tulla yllätyksenä päättäjille. Varoitin vuosia energievendestä juuri siksi että se tekee meistä kasvavasti riippuvaisia Venäjältä tuodusta energiasta. Tarvittu säätövoima otettiin Saksassa Venäjältä." / X. (2001, April 5). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/ER_Korhola/status/1776134097724703152
42. Ohjelmat - perussuomalaiset. (2024, July 18). Perussuomalaiset. <https://www.perussuomalaiset.fi/tietoa-meista/puolueohjelma/>
43. Perussuomalaiset on X: "Terveisiä maailmalta! Riikka Purra osallistuu Maailmanpankin ja Kansainvälisen valuuttarahaston (IMF) kevätkokouksiin. "Pidämme tärkeänä, että IMF ja Maailmanpankki jatkavat Ukrainan

- tukemista. Venäjän hyökkäyssota vaikuttaa laajasti maailmantalouteen, joten kokousten <https://t.co/tKXGPc4xEc> / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/persut/status/1781260953436172610>
44. Perussuomalaiset on X: "@ArtoLuukkanen 'Meillä on vieressä naapuri, joka on juonut imperialismishampanjaa eikä aio pysähtyä jollei sitä pysäytetä' #perussuomalaiset #venäjä <https://t.co/0moYlxHU1F>" / X. (2001, March 11). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://twitter.com/persut/status/1767221589181903202>
45. Riikka Purra on X: ""Ukrainan sodan kohdalla Euroopan yhteinen ja voimakas vastaus venäläiselle aggressiolle on ollut tärkeää. Sen sijaan taloudellisen yhteisvastuun hivuttaminen eteenpäin EU:ssa mm. käyttämällä ilmastopolitiikkaa tai valtiontukikilpailua tekosyynä, ei ole hyväksyttävää." 1/2 <https://t.co/t9ywxM5lir> / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/ir_rkp/status/1783123478775754776
46. Pohtiva - Liike nyt EU-vaaliohjelma 2024. (n.d.). <https://www.fsd.tuni.fi/pohtiva/ohjelmalistat/LIIK/1557>.

France

1. Programme partagé. (2024). Resource: Le programme, <https://programme.lafranceinsoumise.fr/programme-partage/chapitre-8/>
2. Melenchon, J.-L. [[@JLMelenchon](#)] (16 March, 2024). En Ukraine, il n'y a pas d'autre issue que la paix. La Russie est prête à un cessez-le-feu. Le Président [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/JLMelenchon/status/1769028847389823402>
3. Melenchon, J.-L. [[@JLMelenchon](#)]. (1 May, 2024). Nous voulons la paix en Europe. L'Ukraine and la Russie doivent négocier des garanties de sécurité mutuelles. Honte à ceux [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/JLMelenchon/status/1785669162364269023>
4. Melenchon, J.-L. [[@JLMelenchon](#)]. (4 June, 2024). Aider l'Ukraine à résister, oui. Entrer en guerre, non. La guerre humilie, blesse, détruit et fabrique l'esprit de revanche. Seule [Video attached]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/JLMelenchon/status/1798071318946156811>
5. Melenchon, J.-L. [[@JLMelenchon](#)]. (6 June, 2024). M. Macron autorise les Ukrainiens à frapper le territoire russe avec nos armes. C'est le début d'une escalade. Nous sommes prêts [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/JLMelenchon/status/1798788495684591797>
6. France Insoumise [[@FranceInsoumise](#)] (14 March 2024). "Je tiens à dire qu'intégrer l'Ukraine dans l'Union européenne, alors que le salaire minimum est aujourd'hui à moins de 200€ et]
7. Parti Socialiste. FAIRE BASCULER L'EUROPE Du néolibéralisme vers le socialisme écologique
8. Tondelier, M. [[@marinetondelier](#)]. (7 March, 2024). Ma déclaration, au nom des Écologistes, à la sortie de l'Élysée. Encore une fois, le Président ne semble pas écouter [Video attached]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/marinetondelier/status/1765752767455306185>
9. Tondelier, M. [[@marinetondelier](#)]. (4 June, 2024). L'Europe doit parler d'une voix unie face à la Russie. Une solution simple : taper Vladimir Poutine au porte-monnaie en [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/marinetondelier/status/1798035098522251611>
10. FAIRE BASCULER L'EUROPE Du néolibéralisme vers le socialisme écologique
11. Parti socialiste [[@partisocialiste](#)]. (21 May, 2024). J'ai vu en Géorgie, en Ukraine des gens prêts à mourir pour le drapeau européen [I see in Georgia, in Ukraine des gens prêts à mourir for the sake of the European Union]. Il est temps de montrer [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/partisocialiste/status/1792995981320982866>
12. Parti socialiste [[@partisocialiste](#)]. (26 May 2024). J'assume de dire qu'il faut l'élargissement de l'UE à l'Ukraine ! C'est un enjeu de stabilité et de sécurité immense pour [Dolueno video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/partisocialiste/status/1794687878427259144>
13. Parti socialiste [[@partisocialiste](#)]. (12 March 2024). Communiqué de presse Le PS votera pour l'accord de coopération en matière de sécurité avec l'Ukraine mais nous ne donnerons [Attached photo]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/partisocialiste/status/1767574545299288165>
14. Parti Socialiste [[@partisocialiste](#)] (14 March 2024). C'est précisément, pour éviter une confrontation militaire directe, que nous devons aujourd'hui livrer beaucoup plus d'armement au front [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/partisocialiste/status/1768366058652459442>
15. Parti Socialiste [[@partisocialiste](#)] (4 June 2024). "On a 206 milliards d'euros d'avoirs publics russes gelés dans nos banques, il faut les saisir et les affecter à [Video attached]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/partisocialiste/status/1798100035780923482>
16. Faure, O. [[@faureolivier](#)]. (7 April, 2024). Vladimir Poutine n'a jamais voulu négocier la paix en Ukraine. La seule langue qu'il comprend, c'est le rapport de force [Video attached]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/faureolivier/status/1777045768089510353>
17. Faure, O. [[@faureolivier](#)]. (31 May, 2024). Qui peut croire aujourd'hui que Poutine a l'intention de négocier la fin de la guerre en #Ukraine? Les véritables va-t-en-guerre, [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/faureolivier/status/1796527757691912427>
18. Renaissance [[@Renaissance](#)]. (7 May, 2024). Pour l'ua. Pour nos valeurs. For our security. #SlavaUkraini [Video]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C754sWeMSas>.
19. Hayer, V. [[@valeriehayer](#)]. (7 April, 2024). Si on ne crée pas les conditions d'une victory de l'Ukraine, le prix à payer sera bien plus important demain. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C5eKqmuMgcL/>
20. Hayer, V. [[@valeriehayer](#)]. (29 April, 2024). À Labège, l'avenir de l'industrie eu du drone s'écrit chez Delair. Un savoir-faire précieux au service de l'Europe : 100 drones. [Photo]. Instagram. https://www.instagram.com/p/C6WPIDhMjso/?img_index=1.
21. Renaissance [[@Renaissance](#)]. (6 June, 2024). "Très concrètement, demain, nous allons lancer une nouvelle coopération et une cession de Mirage 2000-5. Une décision qui permettra à [Attached video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/Renaissance/status/1798784033763000765>

22. Les Républicains (2024): Building a defensive Europe that guarantees peace and security. <https://republicains.fr/batir-une-europe-de-la-defense-qui-garantisse-la-paix-et-la-securite/>
23. Bellamy, F.-X. [@fxbellamy] (10 April, 2024). Nous proposons de structurer le statut d'État-associé pour permettre à l'Ukraine de s'arrimer à l'Europe, sans faire une fausse promesse [Attach video]. [Post]. X. <https://x.com/fxbellamy/status/1778162285904863543>
24. Quotidien avec Yann Barthé. (6 June, 2024) Cette question se pose de plus en plus. [Video]. [Post]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=833170078861710>
25. Bardella, J. [@J_Bardella] (22 March, 2024) I support the use of profits from Russian assets to finance the war effort in Ukraine: this is a measure [Video attached]. [Post]. X. https://x.com/J_Bardella/status/1771098528569250097
26. Bardella, J. [@J_Bardella] (30 May, 2024) Si demain l'Ukraine rentre dans l'Union européenne, c'est la mort de l'agriculture française. C'est le projet d'Emmanuel Macron! [Post]. X. https://x.com/J_Bardella/status/1796270647544312290
27. Bardella, J. [@J_Bardella] (30 May, 2024) Valérie Hayer fait campagne en instrumentalisant la guerre en Ukraine. Manon Aubry fait campagne en instrumentalisant la guerre israélo-palestinienne. [video attached]. [Post]. X. https://x.com/J_Bardella/status/1796281200270512152

Germany

1. Die Linke: Für Solidarität und soziale Gerechtigkeit! (n.d.). Die Linke. <https://www.die-linke.de/start/>
2. BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN. (n.d.). BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN. <https://www.gruene.de/>
3. Suche. (n.d.). Sozialdemokratische Partei Deutschlands (SPD). https://www.spd.de/suche?tx_kesearch_pi1%5Bsword%5D=Europawahl&tx_kesearch_pi1%5Bpage%5D=1&tx_kesearch_pi1%5Bfilter_2%5D=
4. Das Wahlprogramm der Freien Demokraten zur Europawahl 2024. (n.d.). FDP. <https://www.fdp.de/das-wahlprogramm-der-freien-demokraten-zur-europawahl-2024>
5. Oldenburg, A.- B. (n.d.). Wahlprogramme und Grundlagendokumente | Freie Wähler. Agentur77 - Bremen Oldenburg. <https://www.freiewaehler.eu/dokumente/grundlagen/>
6. CDU and CSU stellen ihr Wahlprogramm zu Europa vor. (n.d.). <https://www.cdu.de/artikel/freiheit-sicherheit-wohlstand>
7. Trem. (2023, November 17). Europawahlprogramm 2024 - Alternative für Deutschland. Alternative Für Deutschland. <https://www.afd.de/europawahlprogramm2024/>
8. Partei | Familien. (n.d.). Familien. <https://www.xn--whlefamilie-l8a.de/partei>
9. BSW Europawahl 2024. (n.d.). <https://bsw-vg.eu/>
10. Germany - How to vote. (n.d.). European Elections 2024: All You Need to Know. <https://elections.europa.eu/en/how-to-vote/de/>
11. Decision - 2023/2061 - EN - EUR-LEX. (n.d.). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2023/2061>
12. Officer, F. R. (n.d.). Political parties and candidates - The Federal Returning Officer. <https://www.bundeswahlleiterin.de/en/europawahlen/2024/wahlbewerber.html>
13. 2024 European elections: National rules | Think Tank | European Parliament. (n.d.). [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)754620](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_ATA(2023)754620)
14. Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community. (2024, May 29). Elections to the European Parliament. Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community. <https://www.bmi.bund.de/EN/topics/constitution/electoral-law/european-elections/european-elections-node.html>
15. Officer, F. R. (n.d.). Political parties and candidates - The Federal Returning Officer. <https://www.bundeswahlleiterin.de/en/europawahlen/2024/wahlbewerber.html>
16. Fabio De Masi on X: "Der Kanzler lehnt die Lieferung weitreichender Taurus Marschflugkörper an die Ukraine zu Recht ab. Auch die große Mehrheit der Bevölkerung ist klar dagegen. Taurus kann auch Ziele in Russland (wie zB Ministerien) treffen und somit den Ukraine-Krieg immer weiter ausweiten. Doch in" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/FabioDeMasi/status/1773591627761651914>
17. Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht on X: "Es braucht ein klares Nein zu Taurus-Lieferungen, ein klares NEIN zu einer deutschen Kriegsbeitragung und ein klares JA zu Diplomatie!" / X. (2021, March 5). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Buendnis_SahraW/status/1765018870442606628
18. Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht on X: "Ich finde es erschreckend, wie sehr sich in Deutschland die Grenzen in der öffentlichen Debatte über Krieg und Frieden verschoben haben. Als BSW fordern wir die Bundesregierung auf, alles in ihrer Macht stehende zu tun, um sich für einen Waffenstillstand zwischen Russland 2/6" / X. (2021, March 11). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Buendnis_SahraW/status/1767187742281052172
19. Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht on X: "Erlaubnis, russisches Territorium zu bombardieren? Wann kapierten es die Kriegsbesoffenen in Berlin, Brüssel und Washington endlich, was sie da riskieren?" <https://t.co/a7pswnptiQ> / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Buendnis_SahraW/status/1798263733313048978
20. Bündnis Sahra Wagenknecht on X: "Olaf Scholz geht einen weiteren Schritt Richtung Eskalation des Krieges. Die Freigabe mit deutschen Waffen nach Russland zu schießen, wird das Kriegsgeschehen nicht wesentlich beeinflussen, bringt aber eine hochgefährliche neue Dimension. Endlich raus aus der militärischen Logik!" <https://t.co/UpKCYmQciA> / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Buendnis_SahraW/status/1796518363566625123
21. Martin Schirdewan on X: "Wir brauchen Primat von Diplomatie & nicht von Aufrüstung. Statt immer mehr Waffen, von denen vor allem Rüstungskonzerne profitieren, sollte #EU Gewicht nutzen & gemeinsam mit Brics-Staaten diplomatische Initiativen starten, um Druck auf Putin auszuüben. <https://t.co/CilpdCp8Rg>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/schirdewan/status/1774104492981543299>
22. MdB Sören Pellmann on X: "Das ständige Überschreiten selbst formulierter roter Linien ist verantwortungslos. Wir spielen leichtfertig mit der Gefahr eines Weltkrieges anstatt uns endlich für eine friedliche Lösung des Konfliktes

30

Funded by
the European Union

- einsetzen. #russland #ukraine #rüstung #militär #biden" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/LINKEPELLI/status/1796447884004778316>
23. MdB Sören Pellmann on X: "Wenn in unserem Grundgesetz die Gewissensfreiheit verankert ist, jeden Militärdienst zu verweigern und es das Recht eines jeden ist, nicht zum Dienst an der Waffe gezwungen zu werden, dann gilt dies auch für Ukrainer, die bei uns Schutz suchen und ebenso für Desertierende und" / X. (2001, May 5). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/LINKEPELLI/status/1787037716204404801>
 24. Die Linke on X: "@Mark28246155 @schirdewan Unsere Haltung war und ist absolut klar: Russische Truppen raus aus der Ukraine. Allerdings sind wir davon überzeugt, dass es dafür großer internationale diplomatische Initiativen braucht. Den Glauben, diesen Krieg militärisch entscheiden zu können, teilen wir nicht." / X. (2001, May 30). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/dieLinke/status/1796455412210000185>
 25. BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN on X: "Wie steht es eigentlich um die #Inflation? Realtalk 🗨️🗨️ Fakt ist, die Inflation ist aufgrund des russischen Angriffskriegs auf die Ukraine stark angestiegen. Wir haben den Preisanstieg aber überwunden & heute ist die Inflationsrate so niedrig wie zuletzt im Juni 2021. <https://t.co/9JkucenRY4>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Die_Gruenen/status/1765756097699238290
 26. BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN on X: "We stärken die Europäische Union als Akteurin für Frieden und Sicherheit. We schützen sie, damit sie uns schützen kann. In sicherheitspolitischen Fragen wollen wir noch viel enger mit unseren europäischen Partnern zusammenarbeiten, um unsere Werte und Interessen zu vertreten. <https://t.co/eKSIP1O3c2>" / X. (2001, April 15). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Die_Gruenen/status/1779872212012482832
 27. BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN on X: "Der Stromanteil aus dreckiger Kohle ist allein im ersten Halbjahr 2023 um 23 % im Vergleich zum Vorjahr gesunken und lag damit unter dem Anteil von Windenergie. Außerdem sind wir jetzt unabhängig von russischem Gas und Öl - und so von Putin. 4/5" / X. (2001, April 9). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Die_Gruenen/status/1777668265218658318
 28. Terry Reintke on X: "Die Ukraine Teil gehört zu Europa und muss so schnell wie möglich Teil der EU werden. <https://t.co/2apggd1oJ6>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/TerryReintke/status/1771099223787794601>
 29. Terry Reintke on X: "Der Krieg in der Ukraine has gezeigt, wie wichtig Zusammenarbeit in der europäischen Union ist. We must with a common stance in the Auseinandersetzungen gehen, to protect our European values. Nur ein geeintes Europa ist ein sicheres Europa <https://t.co/XJfUJhkqR>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/TerryReintke/status/1763887160606724177>
 30. BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN on X: "'Wenn wir nicht weiter an der Seite der #Ukraine stehen, führt das dazu, dass Teile der Ukraine in einer Besatzung verharren. Deshalb stehen wir weiter klar an der Seite der Ukraine', so @TerryReintke im ZDF." / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/Die_Gruenen/status/1796250802270433764
 31. Terry Reintke on X: " We need to steer the European Union towards climate neutrality, away from authoritarian Russian dependence and towards the interests of European citizens. 🗨️🗨️ The elections are going to be our moment of truth. 🗨️🗨️ Let's fight for a democratic and value-oriented Europe. <https://t.co/7L5Urp0oc>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/TerryReintke/status/1782779853428715814>
 32. SPD (@spdde) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/spdde/reel/C4dXIYcNqLZ/>.
 33. SPD (@spdde) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C4gOQp4trN-/>.
 34. SPD (@spdde) - Instagram photo. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C50Q-chjTN/>.
 35. SPD (@spdde) - Instagram photo. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7mmHyuN24T/?e=fc2ce893-033e-4fdf-9379-3cdf4fd6691e&g=5#>
 36. Katarina Barley (@katarina.barley) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C7ofC1nNzkz/>.
 37. Katarina Barley (@katarina.barley) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C71LBS7NOQy/>.
 38. SPD (@spdde) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C74yy97tCZ9/>.
 39. Kevin Kühnert (@kuehnikey) - Instagram video Reels. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/reel/C5yb0tEtSOW/>.
 40. Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/freie.waehler.bundesvereinigung>.
 41. CDU Deutschlands on X: "Seit mehr als zwei Jahren führt Russland einen brutalen Angriffskrieg gegen die Ukraine. Unsere Botschaft ist klar: Europe must keep Ukraine in its mutual Abwehrkampf weiter unterstützen. Die Ukrainerinnen und Ukrainer verteidigen unser aller Freiheit. Danke für das Grußwort <https://t.co/TQPLhfaonc>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/CDU/status/1788180004351717757>
 42. Friedrich Merz on X: "'Der Krieg in der #Ukraine is nicht nur ein völkerrechtswidriger Angriff auf die territoriale Integrität dieses Landes. Er ist auch ein Konflikt zwischen den freien Gesellschaften und den autoritären Regimen auf der Welt, die wieder mit Gewalt Grenzen verschieben wollen.'" (tm) <https://t.co/WUFusUBTvY>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/_FriedrichMerz/status/1771245442170306705
 43. Friedrich Merz on X: "'Dass der #Bundeskanzler vor zwei Wochen beim #Ukraine-Gespräch schweigend sitzt, schweigend abreist und anschließend in Berlin eine verunglückte Pressekonferenz gibt, um zu erklären, warum er gegen diese weitere Ukraine-Hilfe steht, hat in Paris tiefe Spuren hinterlassen.'" (tm)" / X. (2001, March 13). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/_FriedrichMerz/status/1767821587120590991
 44. Friedrich Merz on X: "'Nach der Forderung von Rolf #Mützenich, darüber nachzudenken, wie man den Krieg gegen die #Ukraine 'einfrieren' könnte, vermerkt das Bundestagsprotokoll Beifall bei #SPD, #BSW, Linkspartei und Abgeordneten der #AfD. Da haben Sie sich ja in eine feine Gesellschaft begeben!'"(tm)" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/_FriedrichMerz/status/1770432749347750299
 45. Friedrich Merz on X: "'Wir als @cducusubt haben mehrfach gesagt, dass die Abhängigkeit von Gas aus #Russland falsch ist. Wir alle haben die Lage schon 2014 falsch eingeschätzt. Aber Gas als Brückentechnologie werden wir

- weiter brauchen - sogar Jürgen #Trittin hat das gesagt." (tm) #Merz #Habeck #Illner" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). https://x.com/_FriedrichMerz/status/1798794297212604794
46. AfD on X: "Die Deutschlandhasser von Ampel und Union treiben uns in den Krieg! #DeshalbAfD #AfD <https://t.co/yPIEXyo3J5>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/AfD/status/1765406165582622741>
47. AfD on X: "Wusstest Du, dass die #AfD sich gegen Kriegstreiber stellt? Die AfD setzt sich dafür ein, dass der Ukraine-Krieg am Verhandlungstisch beendet wird und lehnt die Waffenlieferungen ab. #DeshalbAfD Informiere Dich jetzt auf <https://t.co/mz4fgoWLX9>. . . über unsere Ziele für Europa! <https://t.co/RU3JtGKjML>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/AfD/status/178775432942999959>
48. Dr Maximilian Krah MdEP on X: "Bericht über eine Konferenz zur Lage in der #Ukraine von @davidpgoldman - weitere Eskalation oder Waffenstillstand? Goldmans Argumente halte ich für zwingen! <https://t.co/GKbAf2Y4Xj>" / X. (2024, March 3). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/KrahMax/status/1764299478780010983>
49. Dr Maximilian Krah MdEP on X: "Mal sehen, was unsere ganzen Supertransatlantiker so machen, wenn #Trump im November die Wahl gewinnt. All ihre Lieblingsprojekte - Ukraine-Krieg, Wokeismus, Klima-Voodoo - sind dann infrage gestellt. Ob sie dann wieder von "strategischer Autonomie" reden?" / X. (2001, March 17). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/KrahMax/status/1769465921674891682>
50. Giorgi Revishvili on X: "Putin: 'Now to negotiate just because they are running out of ammunition would be somehow absurd on our part. The Russian strategy has been the same for years or even centuries: ru will seek to grab as much land as possible and open negotiations on the rest of the territory. <https://t.co/LCbyxKzyyZ>" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/revishvilig/status/1767824406363975915>
51. FDP (@fdp) - Photos and videos on Instagram. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7UGEXftK0s/>.
52. FDP (@fdp) - Instagram photo. (n.d.). Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7guXcptbbH/>.
53. Marie-Agnes Strack-Zimmermann on X: "Weise Entscheidung. Ukraine sollte russische Raketen nicht nur auf eigenem Gebiet abwehren dürfen, sondern bereits Abschuss verhindern können - auch mit von uns gelieferten Waffen. Es ist bekannt, wo die Abschussrampen stehen, die täglich die UKR attackieren & Menschen umbringen." / X. (2001, May 31). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/MAStrackZi/status/1796477211916317018>
54. Marie-Agnes Strack-Zimmermann on X: "Zurecht spricht niemand davon, dass UK und USA mit Iran im Krieg sind. Es zeigt gleichzeitig, dass die Unterstützung der Ukraine eine Willensfrage ist. Wenn wir bzw. unsere Partner die israelische Luftwaffe bei Abwehr gegen iranische Angriffe unterstützen, geht das auch bei UKR." / X. (2001, April 16). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/MAStrackZi/status/1780169770223989122>
55. Marie-Agnes Strack-Zimmermann on X: ""Wir alle wollen Frieden. Aber dazu braucht es auf beiden Seiten Personen, die verhandeln wollen. Putin will das eindeutig nicht & Ukraine ganz einverleiben. Deshalb müssen wir die Ukraine im Kampf um Freiheit auch für Europa unterstützen." #wiegehteuropa #europawahl #zdf (TSZ)" / X. (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/MAStrackZi/status/1796259598187512027>

Greece

1. Syriza Webpage (24.07.2024) <https://syriza.gr>
2. [One moment, please... ΠΑΣΟΚ - Κίνηση Αλλαγής](https://pasok.gr/diakiryksi/). URL: <https://pasok.gr/diakiryksi/> (date of access: 15.07.2024).
3. European Parliament - the Greek solution (elliniki-lisi.gr)
4. [You were looking for Ukraine - The Greek Solution](http://elliniki-lisi.gr) (elliniki-lisi.gr)
5. [Fundamental Declaration - The Greek Solution](http://elliniki-lisi.gr) (elliniki-lisi.gr)
6. Κάλεσμα για τις Ευρωεκλογές. ΚΚΕ | Κομμουνιστικό Κόμμα Ελλάδας. URL: <https://www.kke.gr/article/Kalesma-gia-tis-Eyroekloges/> (accessed 15.07.2024).
7. A series of posts on the supply of weapons via the link to the official website: [KKE | Quest](http://kke.gr) (kke.gr)
8. Πρότυπά μας. Νεολαία ΝΙΚΗ. URL: <https://neolaia.nikh.gr/sxetika/ta-protypa-mas> (accessed 15.07.2024).

Hungary

1. DK-MSZP-P. (2024, 9 May). Az Európai Magyarország 15 pontja: Bemutatta programját az MSZP-DK-Párbeszéd koalíció. [mszp.hu](https://mszp.hu/hir/az-europai-magyarorszag-15-pontja-bemutatta-programjat-az-mszp-dk-parbeszed-koalicio). <https://mszp.hu/hir/az-europai-magyarorszag-15-pontja-bemutatta-programjat-az-mszp-dk-parbeszed-koalicio>
2. Dobrev Klára (2024). A szociáldemokrata Árnýékkormány programja.
3. Egyetérték a volt feleségemmel abban, hogyan működik ez az állam - mondta Magyar Péter a Klubrádióban. (2024, 12 April). NetrixLabs.com. <https://www.klubradio.hu/adasok/egyetertek-a-volt-felesegemmel-abban-hogyan-mukodik-ez-az-allam-mondta-magyar-peter-a-klubradioban-143395>.
4. Fidesz (2024a, 24 February). A kormány a háború kezdetétől a béke mellett van. [fidesz.hu](https://fidesz.hu/hirek/a-kormany-a-haboru-kezdetetol-a-beke-mellett-van) | Fidesz frakció. <https://fidesz.hu/hirek/a-kormany-a-haboru-kezdetetol-a-beke-mellett-van>
5. Fidesz (2024b, 3 March). Mindent meg kell tenni a NATO és Oroszország közötti konfliktus elkerüléséért. [fidesz.hu](https://fidesz.hu/hirek/mindent-meg-kell-tenni-a-nato-es-oroszorszag-kozotti-konfliktus-elkeruleseert_0303) | Fidesz frakció. https://fidesz.hu/hirek/mindent-meg-kell-tenni-a-nato-es-oroszorszag-kozotti-konfliktus-elkeruleseert_0303
6. Fidesz (2024c, 7 March). Magyar gazdák mindig számíthatnak a kormányra. [fidesz.hu](https://fidesz.hu/hirek/a-magyar-gazdak-mindig-szamithatnak-a-kormanyra) | Fidesz frakció. <https://fidesz.hu/hirek/a-magyar-gazdak-mindig-szamithatnak-a-kormanyra>.
7. Fidesz (2024d, 3 April). Újabb lépéseket tettünk a Magyarország és Ukrajna közötti kölcsönös bizalom érdekében. [fidesz.hu](https://fidesz.hu/hirek/ujabb-lepeseket-tettunk-a-magyarorszag-es-ukrajna-kozotti-kolcsonos-bizalom-erdekeben_0403) | Fidesz frakció. https://fidesz.hu/hirek/ujabb-lepeseket-tettunk-a-magyarorszag-es-ukrajna-kozotti-kolcsonos-bizalom-erdekeben_0403
8. Fidesz (2024e, 29 April). Egyre nő az ukrainai háború eszkalációjának veszélye. [fidesz.hu](https://www.fidesz.hu/hirek/egyre-no-az-ukrainai-haboru-eszkalaciojanak-veszelye) | Fidesz frakció. <https://www.fidesz.hu/hirek/egyre-no-az-ukrainai-haboru-eszkalaciojanak-veszelye>
9. KARD. (2024, 14 April). ÁPRILIS 11 - AMIKOR MAGYAR PÉTER REAGÁLÓ MÓDBA VÁLTOTT [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/eRHJjnCsxdHPiYk9/>.
10. Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. Mi Hazánk. Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. <https://mihazank.hu/?isPwa=true>.

11. Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. (2022). Parliamentary election programme of mi hazánk mozgalom. https://mihazank.hu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/20220527-Virradat_Program-EN-1.pdf?isPwa=true.
12. Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. (2024, 22 February). NEM Ukrajna EU-tagságára! - összefogtak az európai hazafias pártok - Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. Mi Hazánk Mozgalom. <https://mihazank.hu/nem-ukrajna-eu-tagsagara-osszefogtak-az-europai-hazafias-partok/?isPwa=true>.
13. Momentum. (2024). SZABADSÁG, JÖVŐ, EURÓPA. <https://momentum.hu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/momentum-ep-program-2024-web-1.pdf>
14. MSZP (2024). Magyarországról! Európáért! <https://mszp.hu/page/download?ct=doc&cid=674&dt=atch&did=1199>
15. Mszp. (2024). Önkormányzati választási programme 2024. <https://mszp.hu/page/download?ct=doc&cid=675&dt=atch&did=1200>
16. Tompos Márton [@MartonTompos]. (2024a, 28 February). Ukraine and Transcarpathian Hungarians however are closer to the EU and the West than ever before. Of course, Putin has [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://x.com/MartonTompos/status/1762881961175982291>
17. Tompos Márton [@MartonTompos] (2024b, 4 March). "Russia has no plans to attack Ukraine" - FM Sergey Lavrov, 28th of January, 2022 Putin wants to annihilate the Ukrainian [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://x.com/MartonTompos/status/1764632774030320039>
18. Tompos Márton [@MartonTompos]. (2024c, 23 April). FM Szijjártó's Ministry has welcomed the news that Gazprom, one of the main sponsors of the war, would invest in [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://x.com/MartonTompos/status/1782839988893192615>

Ireland

1. Fianna Fáil (2024). Europe matters - manifesto 2024. https://7358484.fs1.hubspotusercontent-na1.net/hubfs/7358484/Euro_Manifesto_May24-1.pdf
2. Fine Gael (2024). European election 2024. Manifesto. <https://www.finegae.ie/app/uploads/2024/05/Fine-Gael-European-Election-Manifesto-2024.pdf>
3. Independent Ireland. (2024). Tackling government waste, mismanagement and overspending. Independent Ireland. <https://www.independentireland.ie/>.
4. Labour Party (2024). A social Europe that works for all. <https://labour.ie/news/2024/05/30/a-social-europe-that-works-for-all-labour-publishes-european-election-manifesto-2024/>
5. McNamara, M. [@michaelmcnamaratd]. (2024a, 28 January). The Government is throwing money at providers of accommodation for asylum seekers (€1.88m/day), and Ukrainian beneficiaries of temporary protection (€3.3m/day) [Video]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2pqTMms3ol/>
6. McNamara, M. [@michaelmcnamaratd]. (2024b, 17 February). This will have major repercussions for Ireland and also other neutral EU member states. Seems von der Leyen thinks she's [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C3clqjMMk7s/>.
7. McNamara, M. [@michaelmcnamaratd]. (2024c, 11 April). €1 million per month was spent by the Government accommodating pets from Ukraine, on top of the €800k spent transporting [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C5nYy0aMzFv/>.
8. Ó Riordáin, A. (2024, 8 February). Irish MEPs have serious questions to answer over Russia vote in European Parliament - The Labour Party. The Labour Party. <https://labour.ie/news/2024/02/08/irish-meps-have-serious-questions-to-answer-over-russia-vote-in-european-parliament/>.
9. Sinn Féin (2024). Change starts here. European parliament manifesto 2024.

Italy

1. Alleanza Verdi e Sinistra. Programma. Il coraggio di osare.
2. Forza Italia [@forzaitaliaufficiale]. (2024, 7 May). Lo abbiamo sempre ribadito e continueremo a farlo, siamo dalla parte dell'Ucraina e del popolo ucraino, dalla parte della pace [Photo]. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6qrSXJNgMk/>
3. Forza Italia, & Noi Moderati. Con noi al centro dell'Europa.
4. Fratelli d'Italia. With Giorgia l'Italia cambio l'Europa.
5. Fratelli d'Italia. (2024a, 21 February). G7: 50 miliardi per solidarietà concreta all'Ukraine - FDI. FDI. <https://www.fratelli-italia.it/g7-dalla-puglia-solidarieta-concreta-allucraina/>.
6. Fratelli d'Italia. (2024b, 13 June). G7: 50 miliardi per solidarietà concreta all'Ukraine - FDI. FDI. <https://www.fratelli-italia.it/g7-dalla-puglia-solidarieta-concreta-allucraina/>.
7. Lega. Programme Elezioni Europee 2024.
8. Movimento 5. Stelle. Programme elettorale.
9. Movimento 5. Stelle [@movimento5stelle] (2024a, 5 March). "Le famiglie italiane non arrivano a fine mese ma per Meloni la priorità è finanziare le lobby delle armi" [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C4H83kGJag9/>
10. Movimento 5. Stelle [@movimento5stelle]. (2024b, 6 June). Al Parlamento europeo l'unica grande forza politica italiana coerentemente per la pace e contraria alla strategia bellicista a oltranza in [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C74MI9buZuu/>
11. Partito Democratico. L'europa che vogliamo.
12. Partito Democratico. (2024, 31 January). Provenzano (Pd) a Conte, Abbandonare Ukraine non porta la pace - Partito democratico. Partito democratico. <https://partitodemocratico.it/provenzano-pd-a-conte-abbandonare-ucraina-non-porta-la-pace/>.
13. Piro, E. (2024, 30 January). Ucraina. De Cristofaro: Interrompere forniture armi e avviare iniziativa diplomatica per la Pace - Alleanza Verdi e Sinistra - Reti civiche. Alleanza Verdi e Sinistra - Reti civiche. <https://verdisinistra.it/ucraina-de-cristofaro-interrompere-forniture-armi-e-avviare-iniziativa-diplomatica-per-la-pace/>

14. Salvini, M. [@matteosalviniofficial]. (2024a, 28 May). Trovo farneticanti e gravi le dichiarazioni di Borrell, socialista spagnolo e "ministro" degli Esteri dell'Unione Europea [Photo]. Instagram. https://www.instagram.com/p/C7gf5ozKjN_/
15. Salvini, M. [@matteosalviniofficial]. (2024b, 7 June). L'Italia non è in guerra con nessuno, non vogliamo rovesciare sui nostri figli la Terza Guerra Mondiale! [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C761nYlK-x5/>
16. Salvini, M. [@matteosalviniofficial]. (2024b, 8 June). Macron vuole trascinare tutta Europa in guerra? Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C79nza6qnzY/>
17. Sinistra Italiana [@sinistra.italiana]. (2024, 4 June). Negli ultimi 10 anni le spese militari in Europa sono aumentate del 40%, +50 miliardi solo nell'ultimo anno [Photo]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7zShsHt5T8/>
18. The Left. (2024, 4 July). The Left Welcomes Movimento 5 Stelle. The Left. <https://left.eu/the-left-welcomes-movimento-5-stelle/>

Latvia

1. European Parliament. Results Latvia <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/latvia/>
2. Jaunā Vienotība. Programme 14. Saeimas vēlēšanām <https://jaunavienotiba.lv/kompetenti-talredzigi-godpratigi/>
3. Jaunā Vienotība. Ārlietu ministre ANO Cilvēktiesību padomē: Krievijas Ukrainā pastrādātās zvērības var būt pielīdzināmas kara noziegumiem <https://jaunavienotiba.lv/arlietu-ministre-ano-cilvektiesibu-padome-krievijas-ukraina-pastradatas-zveribas-var-but-pielidzinamas-kara-noziegumiem/>
4. Jaunā Vienotība. Kalniete: Atbalstu Ukrainai izdevies līdzsvarot ar ES lauksaimnieku interesēm <https://jaunavienotiba.lv/kalniete-atbalstu-ukrainai-izdevies-lidzsvart-ar-es-lauksaimnieku-interesem/>
5. Nacionālā apvienība. Programme <https://nacionalaapvieniba.lv/programma/>
6. Nacionālā apvienība. [@nacionala_apvieniba] (2024, 7 June) Ināra Mūrniece, Saeimas deputāte, NA valdes locekle. Karš Ukrainā noteiks to, kāda būs drošības situācija Latvijā un Eiropā. Ukrainai ir jāuzvar, un Krievijai ir jāzaudē - tikai tā var būt ilgtspējīgs miers Eiropā. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C76zgNeqGud/?hl=en>
7. Latvian attitudes. Eiropas programme 2024-2029 <https://attistibai.lv/programma2024/>
8. Apvienotais saraksts. Programme <https://www.apvienotaisaraksts.lv/programma>
9. Apvienotais saraksts [@apvienotais_saraksts] (2024, 17 April) Eiropas Padomes Parlamentārā asambleja Strasbūrā, Francijā, vienbalsīgi apstiprinājusi rezolūciju par atbalstu Ukrainas rekonstrukcij. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C53Z1SQCPws/>
10. Progresīvie. Aizstāvam nākotni! <https://progresivie.lv/programma/>
11. Progresīvie. [@progresivie] (2024, 25 April) Laikā, kad Krievija uzbrūk Ukrainai, nogalina bērnus, sievietes un iznīcina pilsētas, Latvijā ždanokveidīgie un orbānveidīgie joprojām atkaņo Putina propagandas naratīvus, aicina draudzēties ar Krieviju, kā arī atklāti draud stāties ārā no Eiropas Savienības. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C6LelviL7-J/?hl=en>
12. Sociāldemokrātiskā partija "Saskaņa". Programme <https://saskana.eu/programma/>
13. Latvija pirmajā vietā. Programme <https://latvijapirmajavieta.lv/latvija-pirmaja-vieta-programma/>

Lithuania

1. DemokratA³ sĀjunga in Vardan Lietuvos - DemokratA³ sĀjunga in Vardan Lietuvos. URL: <https://www.demokratai.lt/Files/user/Strategija-GALUTNIS-10.pdf>
2. Electoral programme of the Home Union-Lithuanian Christian Democrats for the 2024 European Parliamentary elections - elpnariai.lt. URL: <https://elpnariai.lt/en/electoral-programme-of-the-homeland-union-2024/>
3. Europos Parlamento rinkimai - Liberalų sąjūdis. Liberalų sąjūdis -. URL: <https://liberalai.lt/europos-parlamento-rinkimai-2/>
4. LLRA-KŠS. LLRA-KŠS. URL: <http://www.awpl.lt/?lang=lt>
5. LSDP Europos Parlamento rinkimų programma. LSDP rinkimų programme. URL: <https://rinkimai.lsdp.lt/programma/>
6. Pagrindinis - Laisvės partija. URL: <https://laisvespartija.lt/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/EP-programa-lengvai-suprantama-kalba.pdf>
7. Programme - LVŽS - Lietuvos valstiečių ir žaliųjų sąjunga. LVŽS - Lietuvos valstiečių ir žaliųjų sąjunga. URL: <https://www.lvzs.lt/lt/šešėlinė-vyriausybė/programa>
8. Programme. TTS. URL: <https://tautateisingumas.lt/programma/>
9. x.com. X (formerly Twitter). URL: <https://x.com/EveDobrovolska/status/1804149441449828715>
10. V. Tomashevsky: It is necessary to stop inciting ethnic hatred. BNS Spaudos centras. URL: <https://sc.bns.lt/view/item/418543>

Luxembourg

1. CSV (2024). CSV BROCHURE. <https://europawalen24.csv.lu/brochure/>
2. DP (2024). Election programme. DP, Demokratesch Partei. <https://www.demokrateschpartei.lu/en>
3. Déi Gréng (2024). European election manifesto 2024. https://grenglokal.lu/content/uploads/sites/51/2024/04/2024_manifesto_eu_EN.pdf
4. LSAP (2024). LSAP: OUR PROGRAMME FOR A STRONG #HEARTOFEUROPE. https://lsap.lu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/LSAP_Europa24_Wahlprogramm_ENG_LANG_FINAL.pdf
5. ADR (2024). FIR E STAARKT LÉTZEBUERG AN EUROPA. <https://adr.lu/europawalen-2024/>

Malta

Funded by
the European Union

1. Partit Nazzjonalista (2024). Electoral Manifesto European Parliament elections 2024. <https://cdn-others.timesofmalta.com/b80e6902ee1dd64ed67663a0758610445ed39bb1.pdf>
2. Stivala. 'Serve Peace Not War': Meet Labour MEP Candidate Daniel Attard. Lovin Malta. <https://lovinmalta.com/ewropei-2024/serve-peace-not-war-meet-labour-mep-candidate-daniel-attard/>.
3. Partit Nazzjonalista (2024, June 8). Għalik. Partit Nazzjonalista. <https://pn.org.mt/?r3d=programm-elettorali>.
4. European Parliament (2024, May 9). President Metsola in Ukraine on Europe Day. European Parliament News. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240508IPR21422/president-metsola-in-ukraine-on-europe-day>.
5. Lovin Malta (2022, 27 February). Malta Should Open Doors Wide Open To Ukrainian Refugees, MEP David Casa Urges At PN Rally. <https://lovinmalta.com/news/election-2022/malta-should-open-doors-widen-open-to-ukrainian-refugees-mep-david-casa-urges-at-pn-rally/>.
6. Newsbook Malta (2022, 25 March). Iltqajt ma' nies li qaluli l-Ukreni jmisshom iċedu.... https://newsbook.com.mt/blog/iltqajt-ma-nies-li-qaluli-l-ukreni-jmisshom-icedu/?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAR3H-mkZzWC2OzrzqIqCqA_2WmxccEpoBHUUOHwi7Dugq5St98L1wProBU-0_aem_8BrkEL84eKln7x-rbtGW4g

Netherlands

1. Christian Unie (2023). Nieuwe verbondenheid verkiezingsprogramma 2023-2028. https://www.christenunie.nl/library/download/urn:uuid:7bf0e12a-89bf-4afd-9d36-ec15297f9c6b/christenunie+verkiezingsprogramma+2023-2028+nieuwe+verbondenheid.pdf?format=save_to_disk
2. BBB. BBB BoerBurgerBeweging. <https://boerbürgerbeweging.nl/>.
3. BBB (2024). Er staat veel op het spel Verkiezingsprogramma Europees Parlement 2024 - 2029. https://boerbürgerbeweging.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/BBB-Verkiezingsprogramma-EU_INDEX-20240522.pdf
4. CDA. Een fatsoenlijk land CDA. <https://www.cda.nl/>
5. CDA. (2023). RECHT doen. Een hoopvolle agenda voor heel Nederland. verkiezingsprogramma 2023-2027. <https://d14uo0i7wmc99w.cloudfront.net/CDA%20Verkiezingsprogramma.pdf>
6. D66. (b.d.). D66 - Nederland verdient beter. Er is een alternatief. <https://d66.nl/>
7. D66. (2024). Nieuwe energie voor Europa. Europees Verkiezingsprogramma 2024. https://d66.nl/europa/wp-content/uploads/sites/434/2024/07/2024_28juni_VKP-EP-2024.pdf.
8. GroenLinks-PvdA (2024a). Internationale veiligheid | GroenLinks-PvdA. <https://groenlinkspvda.nl/standpunten/internationale-veiligheid/>
9. GroenLinks-PvdA (2024b). Migratie | GroenLinks-PvdA. <https://groenlinkspvda.nl/standpunten/migratie/>
10. GroenLinks-PvdA. (2024c). STERKER MET ELKAAR VOOR EEN HOOPVOLLE TOEKOMST IN EEN GROEN EN SOCIAAL EUROPA. <https://groenlinkspvda.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/vkep2024definitief.pdf>
11. Nieuw Sociaal Contract. Home | Nieuw Sociaal Contract. Nieuw Sociaal Contract. <https://partijnieuwsociaalcontract.nl/>
12. Nieuw Sociaal Contract. (2024). Beperk en versterk. verkiezingsprogramma europa 2024. <https://europa.partijnieuwsociaalcontract.nl/files/downloads/252/Verkiezingsprogramma%20NSC%20Europa%202024.pdf>
13. Nsc. (2024). Tijd voor herstel verkiezingsprogramma 2023 vertrouwen, zekerheid, perspectief. https://storage.googleapis.com/groep-pieter-website/media/NSC_verkiezingsprogramma_2023.pdf
14. Partij for Dieren. Partij voor de Dieren. Partij voor de Dieren. <https://www.partijvoordedieren.nl/>
15. Partij voor de Dieren. (2024). Een plan van wereldbelang. programmema verkiezingen europees parlement 2024. <https://assets.partijvoordedieren.nl/assets/algemeen/2.-Documenten/Verkiezingsprogrammas/Verkiezingsprogrammas-EU-24/Verkiezingsprogramma-Europese-Parlementsverkiezingen-2024-Partij-voor-de-Dieren.pdf>
16. PVV. (2023). VERKIEZINGSPROGRAMMA 2023. <https://www.pvv.nl/images/2023/PVV-Verkiezingsprogramma-2023.pdf>
17. PVV. (2024). Verkiezingsprogramma-EP. <https://www.pvv.nl/images/2024/EP/PVV-Verkiezingsprogramma-EP-2024.pdf>.
18. SGP (2024). VERKIEZINGSPROGRAMMA. https://sgp.nl/download?docID=a9b121e206dd4794bd9cf0c5324fb22665c046b9&name=Verkiezingsprogramma_SGP_EP2024.pdf
19. Volt. Volt - De enige echte Europese partij. Volt Nederland. <https://voltnederland.org/>
20. Volt. (2024). Electoral moonshot programme. [https://volteuropa.org/storage/pdf/eu-elections-2024/volt-eur-electoral-moonshot-program_v5-final-\(1\).pdf](https://volteuropa.org/storage/pdf/eu-elections-2024/volt-eur-electoral-moonshot-program_v5-final-(1).pdf)
21. VVD. (2023). Keuzes voor een optimistische toekomst. Verkiezingsprogramma VVD 2023. <https://www.vvd.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Verkiezingsprogramma-VVD-2023-2027-1.pdf>
22. VVD. (2024). Standpunten. VVD Europe. <https://europa.vvd.nl/standpunten/>.

Poland

1. European Parliament. Results Poland <https://results.elections.europa.eu/en/poland/>
2. Koalicja Obywatelska. 100 konkretow <https://100konkretow.pl/>
3. Platforma Obywatelska. PLAN FOR STABILISATION OF POLISH-UKRAINIAN RELATIONS <https://platforma.org/aktualnosci/plan-stabilizacji-relacji-polsko-ukrainskich>
4. Platforma Obywatelska [@PlatformaObywatelska] Polish powinna być pastwem najbardziej zaangażowanym w odbudowę Ukrainy. X. https://x.com/Platforma_org/status/1706583732021346665?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw%7Ctwcamp%5Etweetembed%7Ct

- [wterm%5E1706583732021346665%7Ctwgr%5E4b9256d81788966c75d21b7381c279009065bf7%7Ctwcon%5Es1&ref_url=https%3A%2F%2Fplatforma.org%2Faktualnosci%2Fplan-stabilizacji-relacji-polsko-ukrainskich](https://www.konfederacja.pl/ukraina-przygotowuje-sie-do-wejscia-do-ue-bruksela-woli-o-tym-nie-mowic/)
- Platforma Obywatelska [@PlatformaObywatelska]. Będziemy dalej namawiać naszych sojuszników, aby ta ścieżka, ta droga dojścia zarówno do Unii Europejskiej, jak i do NATO była dla Ukrainy jak najszybsza. X. https://x.com/Platforma_org/status/1810281733532664197?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw%7Ctwcamp%5Etweetembed%7Cwterm%5E1810281733532664197%7Ctwgr%5E858367f4de3d5ab0d52286b0101982fb6b260e70%7Ctwcon%5Es1&ref_url=https%3A%2F%2Fplatforma.org%2Faktualnosci%2Fporozumienie-ws-bezpieczenstwa-miedzy-polska-a-ukraina
 - Prawo and Sprawiedliwość. BEZPIECZNA PRZYSZŁOŚĆ POLAKÓW <https://pis.org.pl/dokumenty>
 - Konfederacja. Aktualności. Ukraine przygotowuje się do wejścia do UE. Bruksela woli o tym nie mówić! <https://konfederacja.pl/ukraina-przygotowuje-sie-do-wejscia-do-ue-bruksela-woli-o-tym-nie-mowic/>
 - Konfederacja. Aktualności. Popzedni rząd mówił, że są sługami narodu ukraińskiego. And ten rząd mówi to samo
 - Confederation of Wolność and Niepodległość. Polska dla Ciebie
 - Trzecia Droga. 12 gwarancji Trzeciej Drogi <https://polska2050.pl/trzecia-droga/12-gwarancji-trzeciej-drogi/>
 - Lewica. PROGRAMME WYBORCZY KW NOWA LEWICA <https://lewica.org.pl/program/program-wyborczy-kw-nowa-lewica>
 - Lewica. USTAWA O POMOCY OBYWATELOM UKRAINY <https://lewica.org.pl/aktualnosci/10796-ustawa-o-pomocy-obywatelom-ukrainy-klub-lewicy-bedzie-za-przyjeciem-tej-ustawy>

Portugal

- Aliança Democrática. (2024). Voz na Europa.
- Bloco de Esquerda. (2024a). Europa por ti.
- Bloco de Esquerda [@blocoesquerdaoficial]. (2024b, 29 May). Uma Europa para a paz e a cooperação [Photo]. Instagram. https://www.instagram.com/p/C7JFDM2MdDe/?img_index=3.
- Chega. (2024). Limpar Portugal.
- CHEGA TV. (2024, 12 April). A UE tem de lutar para que os crimes de guerra na Ucrânia sejam julgados [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E8l6m6TFB-s>.
- Claudino, H. M. (2024, 14 May). Europeias: Candidato do Chega defende "uma espécie de cooperação reforçada" entre Ucrânia e Rússia "em que os russos se sintam confortáveis". CNN Portugal. <https://cnnportugal.iol.pt/amp/tanger-correia/ucrania/europeias-candidato-do-chega-defende-uma-especie-de-cooperacao-reforcada-entre-ucrania-e-russia-em-que-os-russos-se-sintam-confortaveis/20240514/6643de4bd34ebf9bbb3d8918>
- CNN Portugal (11 March 2024). Ventura admite tropas portuguesas na Ucrânia e tem uma posição clara sobre Putin. CNN Portugal. <https://cnnportugal.iol.pt/videos/ventura-admite-tropas-portuguesas-na-ucrania-e-tem-uma-posicao-clara-sobre-putin/65ef79c30cf2c4edbc0e258c>.
- Coligação Democrática Unitária. (2024). Sempre contigo para o que der e vier.
- Cotrim de Figueiredo, J. [@liberalpt]. (2024, 21 May). A DEFESA DO MUNDO LIVRE [Video]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7PLiwMsGY/>.
- Iniciativa Liberal. (2024). Por um Portugal com Futuro. Programmea Eleitoral. Legislativas 2024.
- Oliveira, J. [@pcp.pt]. (2024, 29 May). Quem é que aqui vai assumir a responsabilidade dos seus filhos serem empurrados para a guerra? Quem vai parar esta [Video]. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C7hzkEdoClh/>.
- Partido Socialista. (2024). O Futuro de Portugal na Europa.
- The Presidential Office of Ukraine. (2024, 28 May). Ukraine Has Signed a Bilateral Security Agreement with Portugal. The Presidential Office of Ukraine. <https://www.president.gov.ua/en/news/ukrayina-uklala-dvostoronnyu-bezpekovu-ugodu-z-portugaliyeyu-91193>.

Romania

- A Romanian senator of the Slovak Republic said: Ukraine has lost its mouth and gardens and will give us a new world in the future (2024, 25 February). RT Balkan. https://rt.rs/opinion/kristina-lalic-spirkovic/77704-rumunskaposlanica-srpskoq-porekla/?fbclid=IwZXh0bG9hZWMCMTAAR1k2Pr2RqHcxM9xua3MsroTxOeG-4m6WfYq7OCrX0XqusBJ2-Ot6Qs379o_aem_qhsVq20uQ3qRzVhBJxIXWA
- European Union (2024). Programmeul partidului politic alianța pentru unirea românilor. https://partidulaur.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Program-AUR_final_cu-numerotare.pdf.
- Extraordinary Congress of the AUR to adopt two resolutions: "Reintegration of the national economy in Romania" and "Independence of the energy sector in Romania and the respective agendas of the European Union" (2022, 27 March). News.ro. <https://www.news.ro/politic-intern/congresul-extraordinar-al-aur-a-adoptat-doua-rezolutili-reintregirea-nationala-a-romaniei-si-independenta-energetica-a-romaniei-si-respingerea-agresiunii-federatiei-ruse-asupra-europei-1922401727002022031520652932>.
- Dreapta Unită. (n.d.). Cele 12 priorități ale dreptei unite. dreaptaunita.eu. <https://dreaptaunita.eu/prioritati>.
- Europarlamentarul Daniel Buda: Reprezentantii Uniunii Europene au ajuns la un acord crucial pentru extinderea măsurilor de liberalizare a comerțului cu Ucraina - PNL media. (2024, 21 March). PNL media. <https://media.pnl.ro/europarlamentarul-daniel-buda-reprezentantii-uniunii-europene-au-ajuns-la-un-acord-crucial-pentru-extinderea-masurilor-de-liberalizare-a-comertului-cu-ucraina/>.
- Europarlamentarul Siegfried Muresan: Noi, instituțiile Uniunii Europene, trebuie să ne implicăm mai activ în a ajuta țările candidate, ca Republica Moldova și Ucraina, să îndeplinească criteriile de aderare - PNL media. (2024, 13 March). PNL media. <https://media.pnl.ro/europarlamentarul-siegfried-muresan-noi-institutiile-uniunii-europene->

- [trebuie-sa-ne-implicam-mai-activ-in-a-ajuta-tarile-candidate-ca-republica-moldova-si-ucraina-sa-indeplineasca-criteriile-de-a/](#).
- Nicolae Ionel Ciucă (2024, 6 March). The Liberal National Party supports the nomination of Ursula von der Leyen for the candidacy for a new mandate at [Attached image] [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/IonelNicolaeCiuca/posts/pfbid02VW4cGydWqyyp16hmGKh9d91aTcSyGaeDKtyFHJFgjkHyQe3WXXK12cHrmfscxYdl?rclid=IijqKVFLMsivevkg>.
 - Reper. (2022). Manifest politics. <http://partidulreper.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/manifest-politic.pdf>.
 - Reper. (2024). Partidul REPER. Partidul REPER. <https://partidulreper.ro/>.
 - Rmdsz. (b.d.). Prioritásaink. <https://junius9.rmdsz.ro/>. <https://junius9.rmdsz.ro/prioritasaink>
 - S.o.s Romania. (2024a). Romania programme politic. SOSRO. <https://sosro.ro/program/>.
 - S.o.s Romania. (2024b, 27 March). România aruncată în război împotriva voinței națiunii. SOSRO. https://sosro.ro/romania-aruncata-in-razboi-impotriva-voinei-natiunii?fbclid=IwZXh0bG9hZDZ0CMTEAAR3_4_XC_Dpn4ebdGYuU_ozkHaAqJMkav0lx12_o6A6Jog3cVPZ-7WR9Yxo_aem_JCNibkccGSdsxo34yrukA.
 - Uniunea Democrată Maghiară Din România. (2021). Coaliția pentru reziliență, dezvoltare și prosperitate/ programme de guvernare 2021 - 2024. <https://s.iw.ro/gateway/g/ZmlsZVNvdXJjZT1odHRwJTbnJtJGJtJGJc3RvcnFnZTA0dHJhbnNjb2Rlci5yY3MtcmRzLnJvJjJGc3RvcnFnZSUyRjltwMjEiMkYxMSUyRjltJjJGJmTQxOTE4Nj8xNDE5MTQ2X1BHLUZJTkFMLVBOTC1QU0QtVURN/Ui1GSU5BTC5wZGYmaGFzaD1hZDEyNmNh/Zik2ZWU3MdBmYzBhOWNIOWYzN2U2YicwOQ==.pdf>.
 - Vincze Loránt (2024, 27 June). Common sense is returning to Brussels. From tomorrow, the EU will impose protective duty on Ukrainian eggs and sugar [Status update]. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/23FRRbvenbawLJGb/>.
 - Winkler Gyula. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/winkler.gyula>.

Slovakia

- S&D (2023, 12 October). S&D Group to suspend Slovak MEPs. S&D. <https://www.socialistsanddemocrats.eu/newsroom/sd-group-suspend-slovak-meps>.
- Eunews (2024, July 10). There is another group in the EU Parliament, even further to the right than the Patriots: It is "Europe of Sovereign Nations". <https://www.eunews.it/en/2024/07/10/there-is-another-group-in-the-eu-parliament-even-further-to-the-right-than-the-patriots-it-is-europe-of-sovereign-nations/>.
- Strana SMER (2024). ZA MIER V EURÓPE! Strana SMER - Slovenská očiálna Demokracia. <https://www.eunews.it/en/2024/07/10/there-is-another-group-in-the-eu-parliament-even-further-to-the-right-than-the-patriots-it-is-europe-of-sovereign-nations/>.
- Ondruš, B. (2024, June 4). Váčšina Ukrajincov už nechce bojovať. Braňo Ondruš - Poslanec EuróPskeho Parlamentu. <https://branoondrus.sk/2024/06/04/vacsina-ukrajincov-uz-nechce-bojovat/>.
- Hnutí REPUBLIKA (2024). Our názory a postoje. Hnutí REPUBLIKA. <https://www.hnutie-republika.sk/nazory/#postoj-k-zapadu-usa>
- Progresívne Slovensko (2024). PS. Progresívne Slovensko. https://progresivne.sk/program/?_cf_chl_tk=LINI0q9MR3hHNeRauUK823TUOEmTa.o3_VHwjhMUGSS-1721320845-0.0.1.1-4094
- KDH (2024). Silné Slovensko v bezpečnej Európe. KDH, Kresťanskodemokratické Hnutie. <https://kdh.sk/eurovolby-program/>.

Slovenia

- Golob, R. [@_robertgolob_]. (2024, 24 February). Ob drugi obletnici ruske invazije na Ukrajino [Photo]. Instagram. https://www.instagram.com/p/C3ux_RnIC1w/?img_index=1.
- Nova Slovenija. (2024). Blizu našim ljudem. <https://nsi.si/novica/evropa-blizu-nasim-ljudem-programska-izhodisca-za-evropske-volitve-2024/>
- Prebilič, V. (2024). Programme izhodišča za nastop Vesne na volitvah v Evropski parlament 2024. <https://www.vesnazelenastranka.si/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/VESNA-EU24-PROGRAM-v01.pdf>
- Sds. (2024). Preudarno. <https://www.sds.si/eu-volitve-2024>
- Socialni Demokrati (2024). Evropa Slovenija. <https://socialnidemokrati.si/mocna-evropa-mocna-slovenija-2024/>
- Svoboda. (2024). V Evropi s svojo glavo. https://www.gibanjesvoboda.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/GS_program_daljsa.pdf

Spain

- Militarnyi (2024, 27 May). Spain has allocated a billion-dollar military aid package to Ukraine. <https://mil.in.ua/uk/news/ispaniya-vydilya-milyardnyj-paket-vijskovoyi-dopomogy-ukrayini/>.
- Ahora Repúblicas (2024). Por la democracia, los derechos y las libertades, ahora repúblicas.
- CEUS. (2024). Indar Berria European. Tu voz importa.
- Conde, A. (2024, 21 May). El PP saca adelante su iniciativa para ampliar la ayuda militar a Ukraine en el marco de la UE. Inicio | Partido Popular. https://www.pp.es/sites/default/files/documentos/20240621_titulares_agustin_conde_-_apoyo_ucrania.pdf
- EH Bildu [@ehbildu] (2024, 2 June). Los países que han enviado armamento a Ucrania están publicitando su permiso a emplear sus armas y bombas en territorio [Tweet]. Twitter. <https://x.com/ehbildu/status/1797229935146246623?s=46&mt=E2boBfmKaEOsZAHgyfJFw>

6. Esquerra Republicana. (2024, 24 February). Avui fa dos anys que va començar la guerra a Ucraïna. Dos anys de patiment, d'angoixa i de por [Attached image] [Post]. <https://t.me/esquerrarepublicana/2120>
7. Europa Press National. (2024, 27 May). Vox apoya la ayuda a Ucrania pero critica a Sánchez por reconocer el derecho de Kyiv a defenderse y no el de Israel. europapress.es. <https://www.europapress.es/nacional/noticia-vox-apoya-ayuda-ucrania-critica-sanchez-reconocer-derecho-kiev-defenderse-no-israel-20240527123638.html>
8. Floriano, C. (2024, 13 March). El GPP logra aprobar la iniciativa de condena a la invasión de Ukraine y que pide el 2% del PIB en Defensa. Partido Popular. <https://www.pp.es/actualidad-noticia/gpp-logra-aprobar-iniciativa-condena-invasion-ucrania-que-pide-2-pib-defensa>
9. Junts EU. (2024). Programma Electoral 2024 Eleccions Al Parlament Europeu.
10. Pérez, A. (2024, 25 January). La bolsa china (CSI 300) se ha DERRUMBADO un 54% desde el inicio de su crisis [Post_verbos]. <https://t.me/Alviseperez/9362>
11. Podemos (2024a). Por un futuro de paz y derechos.
12. Podemos. (2024b, 13 May). Estas próximas elecciones europeas nos jugamos si queremos ser una Europa de PAZ o una Europa de GUERRA [Attached video] [Post]. <https://t.me/ahorapodemos/2075>
13. PSOE (2024). Más Europa.
14. Sumar. (2024). Un programme que marca el rumbo en Europa.

Sweden

1. Ett Sverige för alla - inte bara för de rikaste. (n.d.). Vänsterpartiet. <https://www.vansterpartiet.se/>
2. Partiprogram. (n.d.). Vänsterpartiet. <https://www.vansterpartiet.se/resursbank/partiprogram/>
3. Vänsterpartiet (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/vansterpartiet>
4. Vänsterpartiet, Facebook. (n.d.). <https://www.facebook.com/vansterpartiet>
5. Jonas Sjöstedt @jsjostedt (n.d.). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/jsjostedt>
6. Miljöpartiet (n.d.). Miljöpartiet. <https://www.mp.se/>
7. Partiprogram. (n.d.). Miljöpartiet. <https://www.mp.se/om/partiprogram/>
8. MP: Regeringen göder Putins krigskassa | Miljöpartiet. (n.d.). Miljöpartiet. <https://www.mp.se/orebro-lan/just-nu/mp-regeringen-goder-putins-krigskassa/>
9. Valmanifest till Europaparlamentsvalet 2024. (n.d.). Miljöpartiet. <https://www.mp.se/valmanifest-till-eu-valet-2024/>
10. Miljöpartiet @miljopartiet (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/miljopartiet>
11. Kompensera UkrainaförEU:sFossilberoe (<https://www.mp.se/just-nu/kompensera-ukraina-for-eus-fossilberoende/>)
12. Socialdemokraterna. (n.d.). <https://www.socialdemokraterna.se/>
13. Partiprogram och riktlinjer. (2022, June 1). <https://www.socialdemokraterna.se/var-politik/partiprogram-och-riktlinjer>
14. Säkerhet, sammanhållning och demokrati. (n.d.). Socialdemokraterna. <https://www.socialdemokraterna.se/eu-val/var-politik-i-eu-valet/sakerhet-sammanhallning-och-demokrati>
15. X.com. (n.d.-b). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/magdandersson>
16. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/socialdemokrat>
17. S krav: Regeringen måste agera för mer svensk ammunition till Ukraina. (2024, May 28). Socialdemokraterna. <https://www.socialdemokraterna.se/nyheter/nyheter/2024-05-28-s-krav-regeringen-maste-agera-for-mer-svensk-ammunition-till-ukraina>
18. ValManifest EU-Valet 2024. (2024, June 7). Socialdemokraterna. <https://www.socialdemokraterna.se/eu-val/var-politik-i-eu-valet/valmanifest-eu-valet-2024>
19. <https://www.centerpartiet.se/>
20. Ukraina. (n.d.). Centrepartiet. <https://www.centerpartiet.se/var-politik/a-o-om-eu/politik-a-o/u/ukraina>
21. Centrepartiet/Utvidgning (<https://www.centerpartiet.se/var-politik/a-o-om-eu/politik-a-o/u/utvidgning>)
22. Centerpartiet. Manifesto. <https://www.centerpartiet.se/download/18.546951f618cf66a0eefb8a1d1706810963962/Centerpartiets%20valplattform%20%C3%B6r%20EU-valet%202024.pdf>
23. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/Centerpartiet>
24. Liberalerna - Frihet måste försvaras. (n.d.). Liberalerna. <https://www.liberalerna.se/>
25. Programme och rapporter. (n.d.). Liberalerna. <https://www.liberalerna.se/program-och-rapporter>
26. Valmanifest (<https://www.liberalerna.se/wp-content/uploads/liberalernas-valmanifest-2024-1.pdf>)
27. X.com. (n.d.-c). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/JohanPehrson>
28. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/Liberalerna>
29. Nu får vi ordning på Sverige. (n.d.). Moderaterna. <https://moderaterna.se/>
30. Vårt idéprogramme - frihet och ansvar. (n.d.). Moderaterna. Retrieved 15 July 2024, from <https://moderaterna.se/ideprogram/>
31. @PLJonson (https://x.com/PLJonson?t=gpCR_ZeSIDpKglOM7_qzXQ&s=09)
32. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/moderaterna>
33. Välkommen till Kristdemokraterna - För ett samhälle där alla tar ansvar. (n.d.). Kristdemokraterna. <https://kristdemokraterna.se/>
34. Ideologi och principprogram. (n.d.). Kristdemokraterna. <https://kristdemokraterna.se/var-politik/ideologi-och-principprogram/>
35. x.com. (2024). X (Formerly Twitter). <https://x.com/kdriks>
36. KD-dagarna (KD-dagarna 2024 - tal av partiledare Ebba Busch.pdf)
37. Sveriges snabbast växande folkrörelse. (n.d.). Sverigedemokraterna. <https://sd.se/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/valmanifest2024.pdf>

